

HOW THE LEADERSHIP FUNCTIONS INFLUENCE THE
GIG WORKERS ENGAGEMENT IN THE UK
RESTAURANT SECTOR.

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Declaration

I, Ahmed Seif El Islam Kerdali, certify that this research is a result of my proper work, and no part of it has been submitted for any other awards and degrees, to the best of my knowledge, and the original work is mine except where it is referenced.

Abstract

The employee engagement definition has been cryptic amid both practitioners and academic researchers for several decades. The gig economy, on the other hand, has grown drastically in the last decade, developing a new era of employment in the restaurant sector and attracting more gig workers regularly, notably with the emergence of the food delivery and hiring agency apps that have made employees just one click away from their next gig. Despite the gig workers' emergence, little is known regarding how businesses and management can efficiently rely on gig workers to enhance their business performance.

Drawing on relevant literature regarding the drivers of employee engagement, various drivers were reviewed with an assorted of them related to leadership roles and functions. This research aims to study the leadership functions as drivers that can be opted by the front-line management as approaches and methods to engage the gig workers.

This study relied on the qualitative method (interviews) to understand the front-line management point of view. At the same time, the quantitative approach (questionnaire) was appreciated to understand the gig workers angle regarding the engagement with the gig perception and strengthen the qualitative data. The empirical finding shows a positive correlation between the gig workers engagement among the leadership functions principally with communication, motivation and teamwork development.

This study outcome will help future studies aiming to explore gig workers from a managerial perspective, predominately in the engagement field. In addition to that, the research will assist front-line managers on how efficiently employing their functions as drivers can boost the gig workers engagement allowing restaurants to perform in a better dynamic course.

key words: Gig economy, Gig workers engagement, Leadership functions, Employee engagement drivers.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

The start of this chapter includes a contextual exploration of the research background, involving a thorough review of relevant literature and a brief description of the research problem. Following this, the chapter presents key components, namely the gig workers' engagement, leadership roles, and the gig economy, along with an explanation of how COVID-19 and the increased migration of unskilled workers have boosted the emergence of the gig economy. This provides a basic understanding of their interrelationships within the scope of this research. The research rationale is clarified simultaneously, providing insights into justifications and motivations that underpin this research. This was followed by a coherent articulation of the objectives and aim of this study, outlining the intended direction and expected results. The chosen methodology and the adopted theories will be elaborated in the subsequent section. Finally, the last part of the chapter will present the overall structure that will govern the study exploration.

1.2 Research background

Over the last decade, the gig economy has tremendously grown in the restaurant industry, transforming how business functions, including sales, human resource management, and operational management, are conducted (Horney, 2016). Furthermore, online platforms have revolutionized the labour market by challenging traditional jobs, where individuals spend their whole lives working for the same company on a daily 9 to 5 basis (Huws et al., 2016). The number of people using those platforms to secure their source of income has grown dramatically in the last few years, particularly with the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic, causing many white and blue-collar job positions to vanish and driving many more employees to rely on app-based platforms as an additional or even primary source of income during the unprecedented situation (Cameron et al., 2021). The current phenomenon is called the gig economy, referring to employees (gig workers) performing one-time work (gigs) for a period related to the task required by a company (Abraham et al., 2017).

Due to the dramatic changes in how jobs are done nowadays, fostering the gig economy is becoming necessary for many businesses to sustain and compete in the new era of business. Also, many more individuals are embracing the new way of working, undoubtedly creating a new future for the labour market and business operations (Oldekop et al., 2020). It is anticipated that the gig economy will continue to grow post-pandemic. This necessitates business leaders and managers

to strategize new approaches for conducting business operations, adapting to the inevitable shift in employment traditions. This adaptation is crucial for securing the long-term viability of the gig economy (Stiglitz et al., 2020). The gig economy's impact extends across various businesses, industries and functions. However, the hospitality sector is particularly affected by this phenomenon, given the significant number of job opportunities it offers to the gig workers in the restaurant sector. This enables businesses to efficiently staff their establishments with few clicks, while gig workers can easily find new employment with just a few touches on their phones (Woodcock & Graham, 2019).

The gig economy has effectively addressed the shrinking labour pool in the restaurant sector, ushering in a new era for gig workers. They now have the opportunity to secure jobs with just a few clicks on their screens (Hiray & Kalsekar, 2019). Gig workers can choose the type of jobs they prefer and determine their work hours, offering flexibility that has resonated with many millennials. This flexibility has led them to consider the gig economy as an additional or even primary source of income (Schwellnus et al., 2019).

The restaurant sector stands as one of the largest and fastest-growing industries in the UK, boasting nearly three million employees and over 45,000 locations throughout the country (Ntounis et al., 2021). Historically, the dining-out concept prevailed as the dominant model. However, the emergence of the gig economy has brought about significant changes. Restaurants now face intense competition from app-based delivery platforms, which have evolved into primary sources of ready-to-eat meals in recent years (Hirschberg et al., 2016). This shift has been further accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic and associated stay-home orders, making these apps the preferred choice for consumers to order their favourite food from preferred restaurants without leaving their homes or workplaces (Dube et al., 2021).

This gig economy has significantly transformed the restaurant industry, creating more job opportunities and establishing a new revenue stream for restaurants. The surge in sales attributed to the gig economy compels restaurants to expend their workforce to ensure smooth operations and meet the escalating demands of consumers (Bakker and Twining, 2018). Notably, the restaurant industry has one of the highest employee turnover rates. According to Birkin (2019), the annual turnover rate in the UK hospitality sector exceeds 30%, signifying that 3 in 10 workers leave their positions within the first year of employment (Bajrami et al., 2021). Those figures are double the United Kingdom average. Retaining employees in this sector has long been a formidable challenge for managers and shop owners, influenced by various industry-specific factors. These challenges include the lack of career prospects, low wages and benefits, and the

unsociable long working hours (Yan et al., 2021). In addition, over 55% of employees in the restaurant sector engage in the job for short periods or as an additional source of income; this aspect has heightened the difficulty for managers, not only in retaining existing staff against competition but also in attracting and retaining talented employees (Walmsley et al., 2018).

The predominantly part-time nature of restaurant employees poses a significant challenge for managers striving to optimize available workforce resources amidst labour shortages and heightened customer demands, driven in part by the gig economy (Boella & Goss-Turner, 2019). The advent of app-based delivery services and hiring agencies has further complicated retaining restaurant workers. The allure of the gig economy, with its enticing benefits such as substantial flexibility in choosing working hours and competitive pay, has made it increasingly challenging for restaurants to retain their employees. The improved working conditions offered by the gig economy have resulted in a notable shift, with many employees opting to leave the traditional restaurant industry (Duggan et al., 2020). Furthermore, Brexit is anticipated to exacerbate the challenges restaurants face in securing talented individuals, stemming from new employment rules and a notable shift of employees toward the gig economy (Tiwasing, 2021). While recruiting agencies traditionally served as key sources for supplying restaurant employees, the landscape is evolving with the emergence of app-based agencies. Those modern agencies, operating in a more practical manner compared to the traditional office model, have streamlined the employment process for restaurants (Barratt et al., 2020).

The gig option for securing and hiring individuals with expertise to fill vacant positions appears practical for restaurants. This approach can reduce expenses by allowing establishments to employ workers only, when necessary, without the obligation to meet minimum requirements such as low wages, holidays and sick pay (Adeosun and Ohiani, 2020).

However, in the long run, this approach may prove detrimental to the overall restaurant operations, which is evident from various perspectives. Challenges include a lack of understanding of the qualities of gig workers. There is difficulty in fostering teamwork between gig workers and full-time employees and various other managerial hurdles. This study will explore those challenges, exploring motivation, communication, training and more (Jacobson, 2021). While employing gig workers can initially seem appealing to restaurant management due to the enormous benefits associated with the phenomenon, addressing the potential drawbacks for sustained operational success is essential.

The employment of gig workers comes with certain issues, notably a lack of engagement in the business, which can hinder companies from operating efficiently and achieving their set goals

(Kurin, 2016). Employee engagement is crucial and reflects the extent to which the workers are involved in the performance of their jobs, encompassing behavioural, cognitive and emotional aspects – considered the holy grail of workplace performance (Pereira et al., 2022).

The new employment model often perceives gig workers as less connected and interactive with their workplace. This has intensified the need for businesses to develop new strategies to improve employee engagement, a goal that can be accomplished by efficiently implementing leadership functions (Coetzer et al., 2017).

Several research studies, such as (Kahn, 1992, as cited in Bakker et al., 2014 and Saks, 2006, as cited in Rai & Maheshwari, 2020) consistently highlight that engaged employees demonstrate higher profitability, accuracy and productivity levels. Conversely, employee disengagement is associated with reduced productivity, lower performance and increased staff turnover, leading to significant financial losses (Hejjas et al., 2019). Therefore, maintaining a high level of employee engagement is vital and very challenging for management. Both practitioners and academic researchers have recognized the significance of this issue, ranking it as a top priority for organisations to cultivate engaged employees (Nazir and Islam, 2017).

While employee engagement has long been a focus of researchers and practitioners, the advent of the new gig employment model introduces fresh challenges for front-line management. Ensuring gig workers' mental and emotional engagement alongside their physical presence has become a critical concern (Ahmed, 2020). The engagement of gig workers has emerged as a pivotal driver in the gig economy, significantly impacting business operations and the morale and the productivity of both in-house employees and gig workers (Duggan et al., 2020). Highly engaged employees are pivotal for the seamless operation of restaurants, contributing to the delivery of better products and services. On the contrary, the disengagement of employees poses a significant risk to businesses, resulting in substantial losses attributed to low productivity, high employee turnover and increased absenteeism. In response, restaurant management must proactively seek opportunities to formulate new strategies to boost gig workers' engagement. This involves understanding the key drivers that can improve engagement and identifying potential challenges that may arise (Behl et al., 2021). Additionally, as highlighted by Elewa (2016), leadership plays a direct and indirect role in influencing employee engagement.

Leaders can adopt various strategies to improve subordinate engagement (Carasco-Saul et al., 2015). Those roles include setting a clear vision and goals, developing efficient teams, providing motivation and inspiration, effectively delegating tasks, fostering autonomy, ensuring efficient communication, and cultivating trust. Mastering those roles enables leaders to communicate a clear

vision for employees' value within the company, ultimately enhancing their engagement (Jha & Kumar 2016; Andres et al., 2015; Robbins & Judge 2015). The existing literature reveals a notable gap in linking the leadership functions to engaging gig workers within the restaurant industry. Addressing this gap, this study aims to identify the most efficient drivers that the front-line management can employ to enhance engagement among gig workers. The JD-R and SET models are employed to understand the behaviour of front-line management toward gig workers. The SET is there to comprehend the interaction among restaurant individuals, including permanent employees, front-line management and gig workers (Tan et al., 2020).

1.3 Leadership functions, gig economy and employee engagement

In this universal competitive environment, efficient leadership is indispensable to slow down the rate of attrition and to accomplish the organisational goals and objectives productively (Eagly and Carli, 2018). According to Putra and Cho (2019), leadership is one of the most crucial business functions to help businesses and individuals achieve their best (Putra & Cho, 2019). In addition, Ni (2016) stated that employees' productivity, performance and engagement can be primarily affected by the leadership styles employed by managers and how efficiently the business leaders and managers are mastering their functions (Mehrad et al., 2020).

A dynamic leader inspires followers to achieve sought-after goals and objectives while enhancing the organisation's overall performance and efficiency (Praneshet et al., 2017). The leadership's social influence seeks the subordinate's voluntary contribution to achieve the organisation's goals. Leaders influence and empower others to achieve objectives (Mourão, 2018). Leadership in the restaurant sector is critical due to its constant and continuous role in being part of the actions that lead to running the operations smoothly within the restaurant. Due to the rapidly changing global environment, it has never been more critical for organisations to have influential leaders who can fully comprehend the complexities surrounding the industry in which they operate.

A good relationship between leaders and employees can lead to employees' effective participation in solving and achieving the requested tasks by being part of the problem-solving process (Osborne & Hammoud, 2017). Different leaders have different styles and approaches. Yet, the best leaders are deemed to be those who have a variety of different styles, skills and techniques with the ability and the flexibility to switch from one to another smoothly depending on different situations to keep their employees as motivated as possible and to achieve the organisation's set goals and objectives

(Iqbal et al., 2015). The leadership approach is more effective in restaurants than bossy managers, as leaders build teams that can operate as one body to accomplish 'restaurant goals (Shakil,2020). Moreover, leaders can motivate employees to give their best and enhance their engagement by boosting their confidence to work as smoothly and efficiently as possible.

Leadership is one of the most critical factors that determine the success of restaurants due to its multiple responsibilities and roles, which makes the leadership style chosen by managers affect various aspects within restaurants (Fahlevi et al., 2019). The employees' engagement, productivity, and commitment, as well as the overall outcome of restaurants, can primarily be affected by how efficiently managers perform their leadership functions. Managers must opt for an efficient leadership style and efficiently utilise their functions to cope with and solve restaurant issues and enhance employee engagement (Popli & Rizvi, 2016). In addition, the effective employment of the leadership functions will allow managers to efficiently delegate some responsibilities and tasks, which will improve the overall operation of restaurants, as well as build confidence among team members which will allow employees to perform and act responsibly throughout the business functions that will lead to better business performance (Srivastava & Dhar, 2016).

Leaders need to build a team that can face restaurant challenges and operate as a single body to run restaurant operations efficiently and work toward accomplishing the business goals and objectives. Moreover, leaders are required to efficiently motivate and train employees to work as effectively as possible toward achieving the company's goals and smoothly running the restaurant functions, eventually making employees more engaged (Shakil,2020). Moreover, leaders are needed on the floor, which will boost the employees' confidence and increase the knowledge of leaders in terms of team members' strengths and weaknesses, allowing managers to inspire and delegate tasks to workers accurately (Dike et al., 2015). In addition, leaders can often communicate with the employees to increase their awareness of their circumstances, which will help business leaders manage efficiently, make employees feel more valuable, help to decrease restaurant' turnover and improve workforce engagement in the business (Needham, 2019). The rise of the gig economy in the restaurant industry has been a warning for many business functions to be adjusted and reshaped to cope with the phenomenon's emergence.

The number of gig workers is increasing drastically, particularly with the hit of the COVID-19 pandemic that has accelerated the shift of employees toward the gig economy occupying a large part of the restaurant sector workforce due to the vast opportunities offered by the gig economy in the industry either by the food delivery app companies or hiring agency apps (Lobel, 2020). While many business areas have been majorly affected by the gig economy, the employment market is

undoubtedly among the most hit areas, as the number of businesses relying on gig workers to fill their vacant positions is increasing dramatically, which has set the efficient management of the gig workers as a priority for enterprises to succeed (Roy-Mukherjee & Harrison, 2020). Engaging employees in businesses has been challenging for many managers due to the complexity of understanding the ideal approach that can reach the nerve of employees' engagement. With the appearance of the gig phenomenon, it has become even more challenging for management due to the nature of gig workers' employment and mentality based on less commitment toward businesses and more on being flexible, independent and getting the gig done (Liu et al., 2020). While business leaders could be among the few in business management that have direct contact with gig workers, the efficient implementation of the leadership functions could save businesses to enhance the engagement of gig workers in the operations, which will help companies to operate more efficiently achieving their set goals and objectives (Choi et al., 2015).

Gig workers seek the more flexible and beneficial option to secure their jobs and be their own bosses. Agencies are using technological tools such as apps to offer the services of the available gig job seekers to restaurants to fill temporary positions. According to the restaurant industry, businesses are suffering to keep their employees from moving to the gig market, where they are offered better salaries and flexibility (Yildirmaz et al., 2020). This has developed a challenge for managers and leaders to keep up with the needs and demands of employees. Business managers smoothly plan and run operations that will help to sustain businesses by meeting their goals and objectives and achieving the company's vision. Employees are the core sources for restaurants to run their day-to-day activities while enabling businesses to deliver the necessary food and services to meet the consumer's expectations and build repeat customers that can help them compete and sustain in the industry (Lai et al., 2020). The high employee turnover rate in the restaurant industry has driven managers to rely on gig workers to fill empty shifts, which has developed managerial challenges, including how to enhance employee engagement in restaurants (Marrone & Finotto, 2019).

1.3.1 COVID-19 and the gig economy

The economic downturn triggered by the COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted several sectors and industries (Joo & Shawl, 2021). Notably, the hospitality domain experienced a substantial transformation, primarily driven by the surge in online food delivery services facilitated by app-based platforms. The pandemic, marked by government-imposed stay-at-home and social distancing orders, spurred a considerable increase in sales for food delivery platforms (Umar et al.,

2021). To adhere to these measures and sustain themselves in the industry, numerous restaurants swiftly embraced partnerships with online food delivery platforms, aiming to boost sales and navigate the challenges posed by the pandemic. Conversely, the pandemic forced many restaurants to close permanently, while others had to lay off their workforce temporarily, leading to widespread closures in the restaurant industry (Joo & Shawl, 2021). These circumstances left many well-trained individuals unemployed, creating a pool of talent available to transition immediately into gig work to survive the economic downturn. For those restaurants that managed to weather the pandemic, participation in food delivery platforms and being located in residential areas, where people were working from home or on furlough, increased sales (Herrera et al., 2020). Simultaneously, the surge in restaurant partnerships placed a substantial workload on food delivery platforms, driven by the heightened demand for their services amid the COVID-19 restrictions; the surge has significantly elevated the contribution of gig workers to the operations of food delivery platforms, impacting not only consumers but also food suppliers (Katta et al., 2020). Consequently, restaurants have been compelled to re-evaluate and reformulate their strategies concerning human resources to navigate and cope effectively with the negative impact of the pandemic. Furthermore, restaurants have been incentivized to engage gig workers as a strategic measure to reduce the cost flexibility of nonessential labour and navigate the challenges posed by the pandemic (Li et al., 2023). Despite the widespread negative impact of the pandemic on numerous businesses, the food delivery platform industry has experienced dynamic equilibrium growth, showcasing remarkable resilience and sustainability. Various sources have recognized and labelled this phenomenon, including the food winners in the COVID-19 outbreak, such as the food navigator as one of the only winners in the COVID-19 outbreak (Umar et al., 2021). Food delivery platforms demonstrated an impressive surge in revenue and user numbers. For instance, Deliveroo, a prominent online Delivery platform, reported a doubling of orders and sales in the first quarter of 2020, along with a 25% increase in restaurant partners in the same year (Herrera et al., 2020). This growth fostered a broader cooperative relationship between society and restaurants. The economic structure of supply and demand strongly supported the surge in food delivery platforms during the pandemic. Platforms responded to increased demand by expanding their employment and food delivery capacity. Notably, the number of gig workers surged by 150% in the US, contributing nearly 1 trillion to its economy (Li et al., 2023).

The gig economy continues to experience continuous growth after the pandemic, driven by the rapid societal shift in employee attitudes toward informal employment in the restaurant sector; there has been a notable workforce transition from full-time positions to self-employment. The pandemic has played a pivotal role in accelerating the growth of food delivery platforms and, concurrently, increasing the number of gig workers in the restaurant industry (Joo and Shawl, 2021).

1.2.3 Unskilled worker migrants and the gig economy

In the conventional labour market, migrant labourers frequently encounter suboptimal working conditions and face limitations on their employment arrangements attributed to residency and visa constraints (Williams et al., 2022). Employing migrant workers as self-employed individuals or independent contractors in the gig economy has fundamentally altered migrant workers' limitations, allowing the subverting of income earnings. However, all the challenges migrant employees encounter in the traditional labour market are being demolished due to the exploitative cycle of employment models adopted by the app-based platforms (Crouch, 2019). There is a significant distinction between contractors and employees. At the same time, workers are vested with minimum wage assurances and employment rights; the independent contractors do not benefit from this package of rights.

Digital intermediary platforms, such as uber and Deliveroo, reinforce the ideology of capitalism, where achieving a positive income is firmly attached to perseverance and hard work (Newlands, 2022). This marketing strategy has attracted workers fairly relegated to the labour pool, such as migrants, individuals with a low level of education and young people. There are a limited number of studies that have tried to comprehend the degree of migrant workers' involvement in the gig economy; those studies have highlighted the structural conditions that have led migrant workers to be primarily attracted to the gig economy, such as education level, language barriers, and residency status in which app-based platforms have overcome all those issues through implementing an easier form of onboarding allowing migrant workers to secure their source of income instantly (Anwar & Graham, 2020). Immigrant workers make up the most significant part of the on-demand gig economy workforce due to their visa working status, leaving the app-based platforms one of the only options that allow migrant employees to work freely whether they are illegal workers or migrants with limited work hours able to extend their working hours. The migration influx of low-skilled workers, characterized by limited educational qualifications and language proficiency, combined with permissive labour regulations in the United Kingdom, has

significantly contributed to the expansion of the gig economy. This growth is particularly evident due to the minimal constraints on hiring unskilled labour on app-based platforms (Williams et al., 2022). Furthermore, as exemplified by the food delivery and hiring applications, the gig economy's operational model emphasizes granting employees the autonomy to determine their work hours, attracting a substantial number of unskilled immigrants (Whiteside, 2021). These immigrants are motivated to join the gig economy with the prospect of securing their livelihoods and relishing the freedom to earn substantial income with fewer restrictions and hindrances. Notably, the app-based platforms are characterized by autonomy and flexibility not commonly offered by UK competitors, sectors or industries. This unique proposition has resonated strongly with unskilled immigrants willing to exert considerable effort to achieve financial stability (Crouch, 2019).

Moreover, it is noteworthy that the employment conditions offered by these app-based companies may not align with the standards acceptable to UK residents. Concerns primarily revolve around the absence of guaranteed minimum wage and fair working conditions (Whiteside, 2021). Paradoxically, unskilled immigrants may find these conditions acceptable, given their eagerness for integration and perceived lack of better alternatives. As a result, they may be less inclined to seek alternative employment options, thus perpetuating a scenario where suboptimal working conditions persist within the gig economy (Anwar & Graham, 2020).

1.4 Research rationale

The gig economy continues to surge, showing no signs of slowing, especially in the aftermath of the pandemic. The global health crisis has transformed gig work from a privilege to a necessity, massively shaking consumer habits and individual lifestyles, including a substantial shift toward remote work, whether total or partial (Umar and Mirza, 2021). While the ascent of the gig economy has delivered numerous advantages for businesses, it has also brought to light various challenges that management must navigate to leverage this phenomenon efficiently. The hospitality sector, in particular, has faced significant repercussions due to the gig economy, compounded by social distance measures and work-from-home orders implemented by the government to control the pandemic (Law et al., 2018).

The widespread job losses during the pandemic prompted many employees to use app-based delivery platforms for gig positions to meet their financial needs. Simultaneously, the hiring agency system, known for efficiently connecting employees and employers, played a crucial role in providing effective solutions for both parties (Gandini, 2019). The furloughing of many

employees placed immense pressure on restaurants to secure staffing, further elevating the role of hiring agencies that offered flexible solutions to employees and employers. This shift resulted in increased flexibility for employees, allowing them to secure their source of income. Simultaneously, employers benefited by being able to staff their businesses as needed, maintaining control over the hiring and training costs. This flexibility has proven valuable for navigating the business environment's uncertainties (Duggan et al., 2020). The emergence of the gig economy has significantly transformed several business functions, including human resource management, sales, operational management, marketing, and leadership. As the gig economy continues to evolve rapidly, it has become necessary for businesses to adapt to compete in the new market. Companies have few options but to develop the essential skills and tools to influence the business environment efficiently (Roy & Shrivastava, 2020). In addition, most studies, such as Montgomery and Baglioni (2021), Tassinari and Maccarrone (2020), El Hajal and Rowson (2021) and Dazzi (2019), conducted on the gig economy focus on how the overall dining out concept is changing, as well as how the consumer habit of ordering food has shifted drastically from eating out to ordering ready-to-eat food to be delivered to their doorstep. In addition, there are a variety of studies on employee engagement, such as Kahn (1992 as cited in Bakker et al., 2014) and Saks (2006, as cited in Rai and Maheshwari, 2020), which were all interested in understanding the importance of employees' engagement and how it can be possibly reached (Krishnaveni & Monica, 2016).

However, all the studies targeted in-house employees and not gig workers. On the other hand, several researchers tried to investigate factors and drivers of employees' engagement (Mani, 2011; Seijit, 2006; Wallace et al., 2006; Towers Watson, 2009; Hewitt, 2004; Bhatla, 2011 as cited in Tadesse, 2019). A handful of studies tried to explore the role of leadership as a driver of employee' engagement. For instance, IES (2004, as cited in Tsourvakas and Yfantidou, 2018) set leadership as a factor driving employee engagement (Sharafizad et al., 2020). Meanwhile, other studies suggested some leadership functions as factors (Bhatla, 2011; IES, 2005 as cited in Tadesse, 2019) that stated communication as a prominent driver for engaging employees. In addition, Karumuri (2017) identified the motivation as a driver and Tampubolon (2017) the interpersonal relationship as a driver. However, all those studies were concerned with regular employees, and none studied gig workers (Tadesse, 2019). The employment market is the focus of many studies and research on how the gig era reshapes the job market. This is developing a new understanding of the work concept, which offers more flexibility, allowing employees to reach the desired life balance that could have never been achieved in the restaurant industry (Cappelli & Eldor, 2021). While the employment market and sales are the most noticeable affected areas in the gig era, gig workers'

engagement is barely covered in previous research, leaving a large gap on how the issue can be targeted through the reliance on one of the core business functions, leadership. Leadership is a very crucial business function that used to rely on specific styles to lead permanent employees, which, with a bit of expertise from leaders, can permit them to conduct their role efficiently while motivating, communicating, training and many other leadership functions (Kramer et al., 2019). The gig economy has developed a new challenge for leaders due to the employment system based on hiring individuals to conduct specific tasks. This employment model has designed further objections to leaders on leading gig workers, including training, communication and motivation, and efficiently developing teamwork between gig workers and permanent employees (Horney, 2016). This will lead to gig workers' engagement, increasing their performance and productivity and allowing businesses to achieve their goals and objectives, permitting a smooth run of their operations. The gig economy, together with many other social aspects, has enhanced the new gig employment system, categorised in the app delivery driver, and the gig workers that use tradition and app hiring agencies to gig, moving from one company to another (De Stefano, 2015). Those new employment models have urged leaders to develop more flexible leadership styles to reduce employee turnover and attract and motivate gig workers and permanent employees to improve their engagement in the company (Wakabi, 2016). While the gig economy is increasing drastically and continuously affecting every single aspect of businesses, this research aims to enhance the understanding of how leadership functions can be employed efficiently to improve gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector (Book et al., 2019). Despite the several studies done by many researchers (Kahn, 1992 as cited in Bakker et al., 2014; Saks, 2006, as cited in Rai & Maheshwari, 2020), this study will contribute by enhancing the knowledge challenges developed by the gig economy regarding gig workers' engagement and how the leadership functions can be factors in tackling and improving gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant industry (Book et al., 2019).

The current research aims to provide extra strands of knowledge to the prior attempts to form a better comprehension of the gig economy's impact on the restaurant sector. This research covers the role of leadership functions in enhancing gig economy employees' engagement in the UK's restaurant sector. Furthermore, this work will attempt to look at research that covers the gig economy and employee engagement by demonstrating how leadership functions can efficiently be utilised to enhance the engagement of gig workers (Book et al., 2019). Restaurants and businesses know that the more employees are engaged, the more productive they become. Therefore, companies should prioritise exploring the factors, drivers and challenges

facing management to encourage the engagement of gig workers. Several factors and drivers of gig workers' engagement have been discussed in prior studies (Saks, 2006, as cited in Rai & Maheshwari, 2020; Tadesse, 2019). Yet, this paper discusses core leadership functions such as communication, motivation and teamwork as drivers. While various business functions can amplify business performance, leadership is a significant function of employee performance and engagement (Book et al., 2019). According to Saks (2019), the existing literature shows a deficiency of academic studies regarding the leadership role in employees' engagement (Saks, 2019). Further, many studies (Bhatla, 2011; IES, 2005 as cited in Tadesse, 2019) have suggested leadership functions, such as communication and motivation, as individual drivers of employee engagement. However, they were not related to leadership, which in this study will clarify how business management can help increase employee engagement (Lee et al., 2017).

The business world is changing dramatically, introducing new ways of conducting business functions and developing new challenges to companies where continuous development to improve their performance is becoming necessary for them to sustain themselves in the market. Studying gig workers' engagement has significantly become one of the most critical areas in management (Gaur, 2020). Employee engagement can help develop an assertive attitude among employees toward their workplace, which can lead to better performance. The results of this research will contribute to future research. Given that the gig economy is developing continuously, attracting dramatically more gig workers, this has meant engaged employees are an influential element in the productivity of businesses. For the researcher, this work has unveiled the critical role of leadership functions in facilitating gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant industry, thereby providing future publications with ideas regarding the efficient utilisation of the leadership function to boost gig workers' engagement (Book et al., 2019). Moreover, this research will be a significant venture in promoting the role of leadership in engaging gig workers and its importance in the company's overall performance and the development of a better environment in the workplace. In addition, it will be beneficial for future researchers and students willing to study employee engagement, particularly gig workers and the leadership (Sharafizad et al., 2020).

The empirical findings in this study are an extension of the previous outcomes related to the gig economy in the restaurant industry, employee engagement, leadership and hiring employment agencies. The current research strives to promote the current views of the gig economy in the UK restaurant sector, attempting to seek more knowledge regarding the impact of the phenomena on employee engagement, explaining how the leadership function can be the ultimate solution to boost gig workers' engagement (Book et al., 2019). This study's fundamental contribution will

come about through its response to the gaps discovered in the literature, for instance, how the gig economy affects employee engagement and how the leadership can help gig workers to be more engaged in the UK restaurant sector (Roy & Shrivastava, 2020).

1.5 Research questions and objectives

Employee engagement has been the focus of many businesses as a promising strategy to boost productivity and enhance retention. Yet, with the emergence of the gig economy introducing a new employment system, academics and practitioners are urged to intensify their roles in the evolution of engagement strategies due to the increased importance of engagement in gig employment (Gaur, 2020). While several studies have defined the drivers of employee engagement, including the leadership and many other drivers that come under the core leadership functions such as motivation, communication and teamwork development, little research was conducted on how efficiently the front-line management in the restaurant industry opt for the core leadership functions as drivers to gig workers' engagement. This knowledge gap has developed the impulse for further research to facilitate gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector while relying on core leadership functions (Book et al., 2019).

This research seeks to identify the core leadership functions used as an employee engagement driver. The engagement drivers related to the leadership functions will be studied as drivers of gig workers' engagement that can be opted for by the front-line management in the UK restaurant sector. In addition, it applauds the need to understand the challenges that can be faced by the management, highlighting the ideal drivers that can be used efficiently to overcome those challenges and accomplish gig workers' engagement (Sharafizad et al., 2020). To be more specific, the research objectives are:

- To review the literature on the gig economy, gig workers, employee engagement and leadership in the UK restaurant sector.
- To identify the core responsibility front-line management exercised in the UK restaurant sector.
- To explore the specific leadership function-related drivers that can enhance the engagement of gig workers in the UK restaurant sector.
- To understand the managers' challenges to boost the gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector.

- To provide recommendations to the restaurant industry on improving gig workers' engagement by relying on the right factors and overcoming the challenges.

1.5.1 Research questions

This study focuses on the employee engagement drivers concerning the leadership functions that can be opted for by the front-line restaurant management to enhance gig workers' engagement. To accomplish validated outcomes regarding the above aim, the following questions will be addressed in this research:

- To what extent has the gig economy reshaped the labour market in the UK restaurant sector?
- Which core responsibilities are employed by the frontline management within the restaurant sector?
- What specific leadership functions serve as critical drivers for employee engagement?
- What challenges do management encounter when engaging gig workers in the UK restaurant sector?
- How can frontline management leverage their core functions to enhance gig workers' engagement and efficiently address their challenges?

1.5.2 Research aim

This research aims to identify the core leadership functions that can be employed by the front-line management in the UK restaurant sector as drivers for gig workers' engagement.

1.6 Research design and analytical method

This research adopts a pragmatic paradigm, chosen for its effectiveness in guiding mixed methods studies that incorporate both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Pragmatism is known for its openness to diverse methods, prioritizing practical solutions and flexibility. Given the complexity of the research questions, the researcher adopted the pragmatic stance to address those questions by integrating qualitative and quantitative data, which will devote valuable insight to practice and theory. Exploratory interviews were conducted in this research targeting managerial positions within the restaurant sector, including head chefs, managers, owners and supervisors. These interviews played a crucial role in enhancing the knowledge gathered from the existing literature,

offering valuable managerial perspectives on the phenomenon. The insights gained from these interviews contributed to refining the research constructs and conceptual framework.

Moreover, the data collected significantly influenced the development of the questionnaire measures. They bolstered the validation of the findings and the conclusion content due to the unclear impact and role of leadership functions in boosting gig workers' engagement and the lack of determination of the best leadership functions that motivate gig workers. Thus, Churchill (1979) will be valuably adopted in this study due to its effectiveness in integrating the qualitative paradigm in the data generation process in the first step of this study. After that, the literature will be reviewed to assess the instrument design and the scale validity through the engagement of in-depth interviews with key information (i.e., shop owners, managers and supervisors in the restaurant industry). NVivo software was used in this study in the qualitative data analysis to extract and code the gathered information for interviews. The researcher has adopted the mixed method approach to allow the data that have not been paid attention to, that are unknown, or that lack comprehension in prior research to be tested. Accordingly, the quantitative method will be employed in the next phase of this research to examine the research elements and their scale validation. The scale purifying process will include the quantitative and qualitative questionnaire assessment. The validity of content measurement. A group of participants in managerial positions will be devoted to the apprise the items gathered from interviews. Their input and feedback will assist the researcher in illuminating the extra measures and ensuring that the items represent the scale domain.

To evaluate the leadership functions influencing gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector, a self-administered questionnaire will be handed out to gig workers in the UK restaurant sector, a seven-point Likert scale questionnaire ranging from 1 to 7, gradually increasing from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”. This approach's option distribution will allow participants to pick the responses that ideally satisfy their opinions. This research targeted all gig workers, including those using app-based delivery apps working as delivery drivers and those using app-based hiring apps working in-house as gig workers. In different positions, this will allow the research to explore in-depth data regarding the gig workers' point of view on engagement and how and what leadership functions can enhance their engagement as gig workers. The questionnaires were handled by different restaurant and gig workers working in various positions and companies, and a total of 336 questionnaires were gathered for this research.

The statistical package for social science (SPSS) will be opted for this research to efficiently accomplish the descriptive statistics of the sample gathered in this study. According to Churchill (1979), exploratory factor analysis (EFA) alongside the coefficient alpha technique is the ideal tool to assess the scale validity and diminish the total observed research indicators (Field, 2013).

The structural equation model will be adopted to determine the measurement model quality through the utilization of analysis of moment structure (AMOS) 25, which will allow the assessment of the causal relationship between the constructs of this research. Structure equation modelling (SEM) is a fundamental approach to evaluating managerial theories and will assist in developing a solid modelling technique. This research will opt for a two-stage process introduced by Anderson and Garbing (1982). The confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) will be employed in the first stage, allowing the development of the Uni-dimensionality with strict evaluation. After that, the measurement models will assess every item subset to validate constructs. The second stage will use goodness-of-fit to test structural model fit.

1.7 The thesis structure

This part will outline the fundamental research, which consists of seven chapters as stated below:

Chapter 1: This chapter provides a background of the research, starting with an introduction to the current study. After that, the research rationale is delineated, followed by an intensive explanation of the gig economy, leadership functions and gig workers' engagement in the restaurant sector. Subsequently, the research methodology is explained.

Chapter 2: This chapter covers the literature related to the gig economy, leadership functions and gig workers' engagement while understanding how and what leadership functions influence the engagement of gig workers in the restaurant sector, followed by the conceptual framework of this research.

Chapter 3: This chapter discusses the research methodology and design that the researcher chose in this study, illustrating the methodological choices and approaches and highlighting and explaining the techniques utilised to analyse the gathered data. Subsequently, an illustration of the statistical tools used in this study to underlie the assumption is presented in this chapter.

Chapter 4: This chapter will report the findings of the qualitative research, discuss the qualitative data collection, and provide an analysis of the content of the interviews, which will back the quantitative findings in the next chapter.

Chapter 5: This chapter will express the outcome of the quantitative findings, covering the presentation of the scale development and purification results. This includes data simplification, data cleaning and structural equation modelling.

Chapter 6: The discussion chapter presents the findings from the qualitative and the quantitative studies, discussing the relevant procedures and the steps of the data analysis together with the results related to the research questions.

Chapter 7: This chapter will summarise the outcome of this study, addressing the implication and the importance of the findings and highlighting the research limitations. Future research will provide some directions and suggestions on the areas that can be developed based on the current study findings. After that, appendices and references are presented.

Chapter 2: Literature review

2.1 Introduction

The gig economy is rapidly expanding, influencing businesses across various sectors globally and catalysing a transformation in all facets of business operations (Vallas and Schor, 2020). The employment concept is a central domain where a comprehensive shift has occurred, permanently altering the traditional notions of jobs and workplaces (Guoguang, 2020). Notably, as highlighted by Broderick (2018), the gig economy has significantly impacted the restaurant domain, leading to a profound redefinition of the employment concept. In the restaurant industry, the gig economy has reshaped multiple aspects, including the employment market, food delivery dynamics and the overall idea of eating out. The gig economy's impact is notably observed in the rise of food delivery apps, which are revolutionizing the traditional methods of obtaining ready-to-eat food and introducing a flexible employment system (Wu et al., 2019). Dazzi (2019) notes that the employment of gig workers has indirectly influenced several areas in the restaurant industry. Encompassing aspects include gig workers' management and their engagement in business operations. This extends the critical role of leadership in enhancing the engagement of gig workers (Dazzi, 2019). The restaurant sector, known for its historically high employee turnover, has consistently pressured management to adopt exemplary leadership approaches and styles. These efforts aim to attract, motivate and retain employees, ultimately fostering a more stable and efficient work environment (Xiong, 2020).

The gig economy has ushered in a new era of employment, offering employees increased flexibility to work wherever and whenever they choose (Anwar & Graham, 2021). This newfound flexibility presents leaders with the challenge of attracting gig workers, leading them efficiently and enhancing their engagement with the business. Moreover, the gig economy has pressured restaurant leaders to update their leadership styles and adeptly perform their roles and functions to navigate the phenomena successfully. This proactive approach is essential to prevent employees from transitioning to the gig economy and encourage increased workplace engagement (Horney, 2016). Furthermore, with the business environment's inherent instability and the changes hitting the labour market, it is more necessary than ever to have engaged employees who could help businesses sustain themselves and succeed through these difficult times (Healy et al., 2017).

Employee engagement has increased remarkably in recent years (Christy, 2019), particularly with the changes occurring in the business environment and the introduction of new employment

concepts such as freelance, gig workers and work from home, which have become more familiar since the start of the pandemic (Lobel, 2020). The nature of the new employees has made it even more challenging for management to engage their workforce (Shambi, 2021). Securing employee engagement will eventually positively affect businesses and employees (Cappelli & Eldor, 2021). A lack of consistency and clarity regarding the employee engagement literature has divided practitioners and academics (Motyka, 2018). This leaves a large pool of articles and researchers to discuss the concept, while there is no universal agreement on the exact meaning, which makes it hard to measure in action. According to several pieces of literature (Al Maktoum, 2015; Bratton & Gold, 2007; Buckingham & Coffman, 2016; Simha & Vardhan, 2015), employees' engagements were described as a psychological state, a communication strategy and a motivation exercise (Healy et al., 2017). There was no standard approach to employee engagement regarding its drivers, challenges, tools and ways to achieve it. The emergence of the gig economy, bringing the new employment system, has made it even more challenging and vital for business management to explore and employ the necessary tools and skills to achieve it (Cappelli & Eldor, 2021).

There is an extensive literature review regarding the gig economy's impact on the restaurant sector, leadership and employee engagement. Yet there is a lack of literature in terms of relating the emergence of the gig economy causing the reluctance of employees and its impact on gig workers' engagement, as well as the rise of challenges for leaders and managers to practise their roles and functions efficiently to engage gig workers (Fest et al., 2021). This research studies how employee engagement can be achieved in the gig era through the efficient employment of the leadership with its functions and roles, which are mainly based on training, motivating, developing teamwork and communicating alongside many other tasks in the restaurant sector (Johnston & Land-Kazlauskas, 2018).

This chapter aims to trace the emergence of the gig economy as one of the main reasons behind the dramatic changes in the restaurant labour market. Furthermore, a discussion of the gig economy and how it has changed the employment market will be conducted, including an understanding of the gig economy and how it is becoming necessary for both employees and employers. This will be followed by comprehending how its elements have been revolutionary, such as the food delivery and hiring apps that have helped reshape the restaurant sector's labour market. After that, frontline management roles with gig workers' engagement are discussed, followed by a deep understanding of employee engagement, including its importance and drivers. Leadership in the gig economy and the restaurant sector is discussed, followed by the leadership functions and their relation to the gig

workers' engagement. Furthermore, this study covers management's challenges in engaging gig workers. Ultimately, this research will cover the conceptual framework and the research theories used.

2.2 The gig economy

2.2.1 Overview of the gig economy

The term 'gig economy' is increasingly prominent, particularly in employment disputes. It characterizes a labour market structure involving short-term contracts and freelance work, offering flexible employment hours but with minimal work protection (Wilson, 2017). As Waring (2018) outlined, the gig economy signifies significant departures from traditional foundations in the global economy, which have been in place since the Industrial Revolution and centred around enduring employment (MacDonald & Giazitzoglu, 2019). Moreover, the gig economy represents a novel economic model wherein companies and businesses heavily rely on independent workers engaged in short-term contracts. In this respect, the 'gig' is a one-time task an individual is paid to accomplish whenever needed (Wilson, 2017).

Margaret Rose referred to the gig economy as a free-market system that commonly relies on independent employees to temporarily fulfil the organisation's positions through short-term engagements (Warning, 2018). In short, the gig economy is a set of collected markets that introduce consumers and providers to each other on a gig basis through on-demand commerce (Vyas, 2021). This model is based on setting a formal agreement between gig employees and on-demand businesses to deliver services to the company's customers (Donovan et al., 2016). Clients can request those services through smartphone applications or internet-based platforms, allowing them to look for service providers that meet their needs (Schiek & Gideon, 2018). On the other hand, the gig workers engage with the on-demand company to provide the requested services they will be compensated for (Warning, 2018).

Although household and driver services are the best known in the market, provided by uber and taskrabbit, for example the gig economy operates in multiple other services such as business, delivery and medical care (Kitching et al., 2019). Different tech platforms use business models based on the needs of the related brand (Croxon et al., 2021). While some brands leave it to the service providers to set the prices and select the jobs, other companies control costs and assignment decisions. In addition, some companies operate locally while others work globally (Graham &

Anwar, 2019). Often, on-demand companies view service providers as independent contractors using their platforms to transact with customers rather than employees, which can be more explicit in the formal agreements explaining the company and provider relationship (Kitching et al., 2019). In addition, many on-demand companies provide some flexibility for providers, such as accepting or refusing jobs, setting the level and hours of participation, and monitoring some parts of their employment (van der Burg et al., 2019). It can be seen that the gig economy is an expansion of the traditional freelance work that was based on the self-employed accomplishing a series of jobs and projects to generate their income (Ostoj, 2019). Yet, there are few differences between gig and traditional freelance jobs. Due to the reduced entry cost provided by tech-platform companies to providers, many employees with different skills and career characteristics will be attracted (Ly, 2020). Furthermore, unlike traditional freelancers, gig workers do not invest money to establish and market their companies to consumers. This will reduce the operating costs and allow the participant workers to be more transitory in the gig market, not to mention the provider and company relationship characteristics that, when put together with other aspects, separate the traditional freelance and gig workers' models from each other (Chen et al., 2019).

In recent years, the role of the gig economy has gained increasing significance for both employees and employers, a trend amplified by the widespread use of smartphones, laptops, apps and the internet. These technological tools empower individuals to secure gig opportunities swiftly enabling employers to staff their establishments with just a few clicks (Ostoj, 2019). Many individuals are embracing freelance work and joining the gig economy, departing from traditional work environments. This shift provides them with the opportunity to swiftly earn a living immediately in ways that once demanded considerable time and effort to enter (Zaman, 2019).

The rapid migration of traditional employees to the gig economy has brought various benefits for employees and employers, albeit with accompanying drawbacks. nonetheless, this significant shift appears to be more advantageous than risky, as discussed by Mulcahy (2016). According to Balaram et al. (2017), employees are listed at the top regarding the employers' expenses; this makes employers contract employees rather than traditionally employing workers to reduce costs. Furthermore, this can help employers avoid the associated cost of hiring, which includes the fee of interviews and the investment in talented employees that may not fit the company's long-term objectives; this has meant gig workers are a better option for employers due to their ability to accomplish the requested job in a cost-efficient way (Oranburg, 2018).

Schwellnus (2019) affirmed that hiring gig workers would help employers lower the cost of employing full-time and new employees and reduce all the benefits. Gig workers are mostly paid only for the job and the time requested to accomplish it, which lowers the cost for employers without providing the equipment to the gig workers (Broughton et al., 2018). Furthermore, employers usually spend a lot of money on training their new employees and developing the skills of the current worker. By hiring gig workers, companies can reduce all those costs. In addition, using gig workers will reduce the extra costs employers provide to employees, such as sick pay and holidays (Collier et al., 2017). Balaram et al. (2017) argued that employing gig workers saves time and money for businesses by reducing their expenses on developing human resource programmes and healthcare and guiding their focus to hiring the ideal freelancers for a specific job and limited period. Alongside lowering the cost while employing gig workers, reducing time while hiring and looking after the regular worker has pushed companies to hire freelancers and consider them the key to boosting their business (Broughton et al., 2018).

Another valuable benefit for employers, highlighted by Collier (2017), is the ability of businesses to hire gig workers from a diverse pool of flexible workers in the market, allowing employers to select from a wide range of employees with different capacities and characteristics. In addition, gig workers work flexible hours that make accomplishing a task outside of regular business hours more likely, providing more flexibility to employers. Furthermore, due to the varied gig workers' backgrounds, skills and experiences, more creativity and ideas will be brought to the company (Roy & Shrivastava, 2020). Along the same line, the gig workers pool is increasing dramatically due to the benefits offered by the gig economy that have facilitated the gig economy to be a successful concept where the supply and demand are high from both employers and the employees (De Groen et al., 2018).

Unlike traditional employees, gig workers are flexible in choosing the type of work they want to do, including the desired hours of work, the place they want to work and many other options that they can choose from to carry out their jobs (De Groen et al., 2018). Furthermore, Friedman (2014) agreed that flexibility allows workers to work at their convenience, which offers them the opportunity to achieve a better life balance than the traditional employment concept, where life balance is hard to achieve, mainly in the restaurant sector. Thus, flexibility is a significant benefit that encourages traditional workers to move to the gig sector and will enhance their creativity (Friedman, 2014). In addition to the flexibility, freelancers may have a variety of jobs to complete for various businesses; those multitasking conducted regularly provide gig economy employees with more experience and make their jobs more interesting (Collier et al., 2017). Furthermore, this

will help gig workers be more creative and productive while working on different daily tasks and in different restaurants (Jacobson, 2021).

Despite the many benefits that have encouraged both employers and employees to be part of the gig economy, several drawbacks can prevent particular categories of individuals and businesses from participating in the gig economy. According to Deng et al. (2016), having less reliable employees is one of the disadvantages highlighted in many studies due to working under less pressure and less complex environment is set to be among the core reasons for the shift of traditional employees to the gig economy. This can develop less engaged, involved and productive employees who may have a massive impact on the business performance if it is not dealt with by the management (De Groen et al., 2018).

Along the same line, various drawbacks can be faced by employees and can prevent them from moving to the gig economy, causing a shortage that may affect restaurants that rely heavily on gig workers to source their vacant positions. According to Kuhn and Galloway (2019), one of the worst things gig workers should be aware of is the lack of benefits in most gig jobs, as they are not considered part of the package offered to gig employees. Usually, full-time employees are offered various benefits such as guaranteeing the minimum wage, holiday pay, sick pay and many other benefits that make employees feel secure. However, most are exempt from all those benefits due to the lack of a law that can guarantee those benefits for employees (Balaram et al., 2017).

Another drawback that most gig workers consider while participating in the gig economy is the stress the phenomenon can bring. Chen et al. (2019) stated that gig economy workers are more anxious due to the nature of their work and the conditions. Gig workers must constantly look for their next job to avoid being jobless. This can lead to more stress for gig economy workers. In addition, while full-time employees feel a little secure, most gig economy workers do not, which puts massive pressure on them, not to mention that gig workers are continually facing changes in jobs and salaries that can create stress for them. Not being familiar with the workplace and the environment can create more stress for gig workers, possibly affecting their performance (Chen et al., 2019).

2.2.2 The emergence of the gig economy

In recent years, the gig economy has emerged dramatically, entering almost every scope in our lives and transforming our work environment. Naidu et al. (2019) predicts that by 2024, the number of gig workers will surpass that of traditional employees. While the gig economy has gained recent popularity, it has roots extending over a century. Its growing influence has become so significant

that legislative bodies are enacting new laws to address its impact (Schiek & Gideon, 2018). Projections indicated that by the end of 2022, approximately 7.25 million Brits were expected to be part of the gig workforce, encouraging companies to invest billions in developing gig works (Abraham et al., 2019). Jazz musicians introduced the term 'gig' in 1915, referring to live performances. However, its usage expanded, and the term was increasingly used in the job market with the rise of temporary agencies and positions (Vatsa et al., 2022). In the digital era, the gig economy developed a new market. In 1996, Craig Newmark launched an email newsletter called *San Francisco Events* (Ostoj, 2021). The company started listing followers, and as the list increased, the company went beyond local events to list various jobs and apartments. In 2005, Amazon began recruiting gig employees to conduct complex tasks such as surgery answering and many others (Ostoj, 2019). At the beginning of the 20th century, apps emerged, encouraging many companies to develop their applications and enter markets with better values and services (Stallkamp & Schotter, 2021). In 2008, Airbnb was the first app in the sharing economy to make renting more affordable; after just ten years, the company was worth 38 billion dollars (Moreno-Izquierdo et al., 2018). Alongside Airbnb, many app companies entered the app markets to allow individuals to provide consumer services, such as Uber and TaskRabbit (Riggs et al., 2019). More than 30% of Americans and 10% of British people are freelancers. In addition, 8 out of 10 Brits use cell phones, which is all they need to start making their living and develop new sources of income (Demir et al., 2022). Yet, gig workers do not have certain working conditions such as steady income, sick pay, and many others compared to traditional work (Bajwa et al., 2018). One of the most significant milestones of the gig economy journey was the pandemic, which was undoubtedly the reason behind its emergence in recent years, tempting employees from various sectors to participate. This will be discussed in more detail below.

COVID-19 developed a new era for the gig economy as it developed new need for gig work in various sectors. Future roles will be different due to the emergence of the blended workforce. According to Mahato et al. (2021), the UK emphasizes the increasing trend of a combined workforce in the post-COVID era, with rising confidence in remote working and expanding on-demand jobs. The pandemic impact will probably result in meaningful collaboration between full-time workers and independent contributors, allowing companies to hire talented pinch hitters for tasks without having to spend a significant amount of money on salaries and bonuses, resulting in the emergence of a unique workplace environment that is defined as the gig economy (Joo & Shawl, 2021). With various current difficulties such as health issues, increasing population

expansion and increased movement of people, the COVID-19 pandemic is swiftly spreading over the globe (Nkengasong & Mankoula, 2020). In such circumstances, many employees have shifted from various industries and positions to the restaurant sector where gig workers were offered increased opportunities by the food delivery apps and restaurants due to the large increase in demand. Joo and Shawl (2021) stated that despite a large part of the restaurant workforce having been furloughed, many restaurants have become busier, particularly with the emergence of food delivery apps and the "eat out to help out" scheme that allowed restaurants to be bustling at specific times and days. According to Umar et al. (2021), this has popularized the gig workers concept that is based on hiring individuals only when they are needed without worrying much about the cost accompanied by the process, including training costs, contract issues and many other issues connected to the operation of hiring permanent employees paving the way for additional short-term jobs to be created through third-party web-based and mobile platforms. These platforms are proprietary applications (apps) that users download and utilize (Healy et al., 2017); this makes it easier to construct a triangle partnership, a new economic model in which producers and users can exchange goods and services through a digital intermediary (Stewart & Stanford, 2017). This is because the increased reliance on gig workers to home-delivery necessities to consumers' participation in the gig economy has developed fast. It has expanded enormously since the start of the coronavirus pandemic.

Moreover, Cao et al. (2020) stated that the crisis had thrown the usual 9-5 working world into disarray, prompting many blue- and white-collar workers to seek gig work for extra – or perhaps primary – income in these unusual times. Many full-time employees have been forced to enter the gig economy out of need since COVID-19. According to Jeon and Ostrovsky (2020), to preserve the gig economy's long-term viability, talent executives must plan for this inevitable transformation and develop new methods to support workers as the world begins to fully embrace this new way of working, which will likely continue to grow post-pandemic. While the gig economy is known to apply in most sectors, the restaurant industry is the most touched by the phenomenon.

2.3 The gig economy in the restaurant sector

Restaurants have been more than a place where people buy (ready-to-eat) food in the last century, as people have chosen those places to be meeting spots where they can socialize, meet friends and even family over coffee, lunch or dinner (Belanche et al., 2021). Busy life has added extra reasons

for individuals to pop into restaurants and cafes to enjoy a short break between their workplaces and homes, adding them to their daily schedules and activities (Gupta, 2019). According to Khan (2020), The world has been dramatically affected by the emergence of technology and algorithmic platforms, which have changed almost every daily activity in our lives, such as shopping, travelling and many others. Restaurants are no exception and have been affected by this phenomenon in various ways, such as the emergence of delivery apps platforms, the increase of gig workers and hiring-app agencies. Yet, the change in people's habits, the busy life of individuals and the lack of life balance has encouraged employees to move to the gig economy to fulfil their financial and social needs (Warren, 2021). The busy life of employees has put their daily diet at risk, where having a proper lunch break started to become a privilege and accomplishment if it can be done more than once a week (Khan, 2020).

In addition, coming after a long shift and cooking for the family has not become fun anymore due to the sociological changes, which have affected our lives and forced people to work long hours to meet their financial needs (Thompson, 2018). The gig economy came up with a creative solution that has provided individuals with more flexibility through developing the app-based food delivery concept which has allowed people to have their favourite cuisine and food delivered at a convenient time and place (Chopra et al., 2018). On the other hand, this concept has created more jobs, and enhanced the freelance idea, which has provided employees with more ability and money (Veluchamy et al., 2021). Miroso and Bremer (2020) stated that app-based delivery platforms have helped many restaurants to compete in the new era. Yet, it has developed new challenges to the industry by reshaping almost every business function, requiring a new approach to be efficiently accomplished (Duggan et al., 2020).

The rise of hiring-app agencies has helped restaurants cope with a significant shift of traditional workers replaced by gig workers who could be hired with a few clicks; having all the necessary information regarding the available employees made the hiring process even more accessible (Suciu et al., 2019). In addition, the tech-reliant way of working has encouraged more businesses and employees to opt for the hiring system for convenience (Williams et al., 2021). Also, the increased reliance on digital technologies in our daily activities has enhanced the growth of food delivery platforms that have saved thousands of businesses from closing, developing a new source of income for many individuals (Sharma, 2020). All those factors have enhanced the importance of the gig economy among employees and employers, making it a necessity more than a privilege (Allon et al., 2018).

2.4 The gig economy and the workforce in the UK restaurant sector

The restaurant sector is one of the most significant sectors in employee turnover, putting managers and restaurants in a difficult position where they must constantly look for individuals to fill their vacant positions. The rapid growth of the gig economy has developed a new source of restaurant employees, who can be hired with a few clicks to perform a specific task at a particular time (Hyers & Kovacova, 2018).

This sounds like a great deal for employers due to its benefits, such as no holiday pay, no training fees, no sick pay and many other benefits. But according to a study conducted by Shin et al. (2021), this phenomenon has also created a new challenge for restaurants and managers to keep their employees from moving to the gig economy due to the enormous benefits offered to gig workers such as more flexibility, good pay, no bosses and many others.

Although employees are shifting from all sectors, according to Broderick (2018), the restaurant sector is one of the biggest industries witnessing employees move to the gig economy due to several conditions surrounding the industry, such as low wages, unsocial hours, no straightforward programme and vision for development and many other aspects. All those points have improved the gig economy by attracting employees to join the fast-growing phenomenon (Lobel, 2017). Consumers' shift to the so-called gig economy has allowed food delivery apps to continuously ask for more gig workers to fulfil the growing demand and usage of consumers on app-based delivery platforms, together with the rise of the freelance jobs offered by the hiring work agencies that provide employees with more flexibility to do the job they like at a convenient times and place (Vallas & Schor, 2020). Despite the several drawbacks of this phenomenon, such as no life insurance, no job benefits and many other limits, it seems that flexibility attracts many restaurant employees regularly (Watson et al., 2021).

2.4.1 Food delivery apps and the restaurant labour market

Food delivery apps are, without a doubt, one of the biggest revolutions the restaurant sector has witnessed in decades, significantly affecting the stakeholders of the industry: consumers, employees and businesses (Goods et al., 2019). These new algorithmic management platforms have linked three contributors to a single place where consumers choose the restaurant and the

food they want on their tables. Meanwhile, app-based companies find available gig workers to deliver the food after it is accepted and prepared by restaurants (Rani & Furrer, 2021). According to Bi et al. (2021), the apps offer gig workers ample flexibility to accept or decline the order and gig whenever is convenient for them. The high level of flexibility provided by food delivery apps has shaken up the employment market in the restaurant industry by attracting a wide range of restaurant employees looking for a more flexible source of income either as a main or extra job (Chetan et al., 2019).

The restaurant industry is set to be one of the most significant sectors regarding employee turnover due to various reasons, such as low wages and unsociable working hours. On top of this, many other rationales are causing restaurants an enormous distraction and increasing their operational expenses, accompanied by hiring and training procedures (Bi et al., 2021).

Although the staff turnover in restaurants has been around for a long time and has developed a continuous challenge for managers and business owners to reduce the turnover and keep their employees from moving away, undoubtedly, the emergence of food delivery apps such as Uber Eats, Deliveroo and Eat has made the situation even worse for restaurants (Cha & Seo, 2020). While restaurants are busier in coping with the increase in food demand caused by the delivery platforms, it is tough for them to keep up with the employee shortage in the industry (Laitinen, 2021). The emergence of delivery apps has set new employment norms that have raised employee expectations toward businesses and managers.

Altenried (2021) stated that the restaurant sector has faced various challenges lately. However, reducing employee turnover and competing with the delivery apps to attract gig workers are some of the most significant objections in the market due to the rapid immigration of employees in the restaurant sector as well as the dramatic sign-in of gig workers to so-called gig economy apps (Altenried, 2021). On the other hand, restaurants are going through one of the most challenging moments due to a set of reasons, including Brexit, the pandemic and the dramatic increase of competition in the market, as well as many other aspects that made it bleak for business to keep up with the employee's expectations.

Managers are expected to be more flexible and to develop a strategy to cope with the phenomena as it is happening rapidly and seems set to be the norm in the coming years (Hong et al., 2021). Finn (2020) agreed that there are a set of strategies that managers can adopt to deal with phenomena such as being more flexible with the rota schedules (leaving empty shifts that

employees can fill), increasing the contribution of employees in the restaurants that will enhance their engagement in the business, work on motivating employees, so they feel more valuable to companies. In addition, frontline management can be more flexible regarding their styles and approaches, attracting more employees (Shet & Pereira, 2021).

Food delivery platforms have helped businesses remain operational throughout the pandemic lockdowns by providing a convenient alternative for individuals who were asked not to leave their homes. The platforms offered consumers a better option where their chosen food can be delivered to their doorstep with just a few clicks on their phones. Consumers' shift to food apps has developed new job positions filled by gig workers and employees who lost jobs due to the pandemic (Parwez & Ranjan, 2021).

According to Goods et al. (2019), the way the world eats has changed drastically in recent years, notably with the emergence of the on-demand food delivery model and the restrictions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has enormously boosted the phenomenon. Changes in consumer habits, expectations and dining restrictions have fuelled the global food delivery market surge (Hong et al., 2021). Even though the food platforms charge a significant stake, they could be seen as rescuers who helped restaurants survive the pandemic lockdowns and allowed them to remain operational after this difficult time.

2.4.2 Recruitment agencies and restaurant employment market

Recruitment agencies refer to third-party intermediaries connecting temporary job seekers to employers to fill empty business positions, taking responsibility for hiring and paying workers (Kuhn, 2021). Employees looking for temporary or permanent positions connect with agencies, providing their availability schedules that match the jobs from different businesses. According to Bhattarai (2018), the equation seems to keep all parties happy, while businesses always keep their positions filled. Employees can work at their convenience, having the flexibility to accept and refuse jobs. Technology has completely changed all the traditional ways of doing things. As for recruitment agencies, apps and websites have replaced the old-fashioned recruiting offices (Charlton & Castillo, 2021).

Lehdonvirta (2018) agreed that flexibility has become an essential element for employees in recent years, particularly in the secondary labour market where the work environment shows a lack of life balance, poor conditions and low wages; this has put a large portion of workers off pursuing

full-time jobs where they are stuck to a single place with no career vision nor job promotions. Along the same line, the changes in employees' needs and work expectations, together with the emergence of gig opportunities, and the ease of securing crowd work, have encouraged many employees to rely on traditional agencies or mostly on app-based agencies such as Adecco, Reed, Hays and many others (Elias et al., 2016). This is where they can work at their convenience and places with an easy process to select a suitable time and place to gig (Gandhi et al., 2018). Staffing restaurants has always been challenging for managers and restaurant owners due to the high turnover in the industry, caused by a variety of reasons. Yet, with the emergence of hiring apps, attracting temporary workers and keeping the restaurants' full-time employees is becoming even more challenging.

The front-of-house and the behind-the-scenes workforce are as important in the success of restaurants as good menus, locations and reasonable prices (Barratt et al., 2020). This puts the management under constant pressure to be more efficient and flexible with the full-time employees to avoid the consequences of their migration, such as training time conception and cost. In addition, managers need to be more flexible in dealing with gig workers as the nature of their employment require less interaction which can drive the gig workers to be less committed to their work and managing them can be tricky, particularly with the review option offered by the apps that can interfere with future attempts to hire the same gigger or attract new gig workers (Duggan et al., 2021).

Repeatable experience for gig workers and managers can be ideal for both, with the slight privilege to managers as it reduces the time and the cost of training as well as increases the operation's running efficiency while enjoying the flexibility of filling positions at the most necessary times (Williams et al., 2021). On the other hand, employees may feel more comfortable being around the same workplace while still enjoying full autonomy with no commitment.

Recruiting apps have grown significantly in recent years, transforming the labour market in the restaurant sector by reshaping the traditional way of hiring and managing employees. This phenomenon is increasing at rapid pace and does not seem to be slowing down due to various sociological reasons. Managers and business owners are urged now more than ever to develop new flexible strategies and plans to cope with significant changes in the labour market that can ultimately affect their long-term suitability plans (Tepayakul & Rinthaisong, 2018).

2.5 The restaurant sector's core roles of front-line management in the gig economy

To advance gig worker engagement in the restaurant industry, this research aims to comprehend talent management approaches for permanent and gig employees. The techniques are primarily based on the employee perception or 'psychological contract', which can take two distinct forms in employment relations. According to Savarimuthu and Rachel (2017), there are two types of contracts: the transactional psychological contract (short-term and focuses on individuals' reciprocal exchange agreements with their employers), and the relational psychological contract (long-term and involves socio-emotional exchanges, mutual trust, and loyalty, such as job security and career development) (Agarwal & Gupta, 2018)

Psychological contract satisfaction has been shown in studies to improve task performance and engagement for all gig employees, regardless of their employment with the organisation (Liu et al., 2020). Furthermore, Sharma et al. (2016) stated that a positive employee perception could influence a blended workforce in a work atmosphere that is becoming increasingly turbulent. Collaboration, performance management, learning and development, rewards and recognition, motivation, efficient communication and whether or not an employee is organisation-fit have all become highly essential, pushing firms to reconsider their talent management strategies post-COVID-19.

2.5.1 Collaboration in the restaurant sector

In essence, structured teamwork boosts any company's production, making full-time employee collaboration a critical aspect of its success. It permits all members of the team to generate ideas and ask questions to increase efficient communication (Paulas & Kenworthy, 2019). New ideas and perspectives emerge when people from many sectors collaborate (cross-functional collaboration). These varied perspectives make problem-solving more accessible, encouraging in-house innovation to speed up solution implementation (Elikwu, 2019; Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020).

EY (2020) stated that the collaboration between gig workers, front-line management and permanent employees enables shared leadership through the socially connected flow of information, which builds commitment, trust and cohesion among the participants (Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020). Furthermore, it allows restaurants to listen to the best ideas presented for

executing the company's operations via the efficient communication developed throughout the restaurant collaboration (Ruggieri et al., 2016). EY (2020) affirmed that control and trust are the two criteria for measuring collaboration, which frequently fails because of the inefficient management of a globally dispersed workforce. In addition, front-line management in the restaurant industry has begun to reevaluate their management strategies in light of the current state of uncertainty, taking initiatives such as gig workers' feedback for better collaboration and data collection from gig workers' reviews in the hiring apps (EY, 2020).

These improvements have prompted the proposition of a blended workforce structure, in which gig economy workers and full-time employees in a single team can collaborate from various perspectives. In a blended workforce, the mix of both employees' experiences can benefit restaurants. Experience and skillsets, as well as the distributed expertise of gig workers, can serve as a conduit for crucial support among these workers (Anderson & Sanga, 2019). In addition, Brown and Portman (2018) stated that teamwork communications and chats are critical for enabling engagement across mixed teams to create an atmosphere that not only supports their collective team goals but also harnesses their creativity, resulting in economic benefit for the restaurants (Ruggieri et al., 2016).

2.5.2 Teamwork and gig workers in the restaurant sector

Developing a teamwork environment is one of the most critical focuses for leaders and managers aiming to increase the performance of employees and businesses equally. According to Guchait et al. (2016), creating teamwork is one of the significant leadership functions that help individuals in the company to work and collaborate to achieve higher performance. Furthermore, building efficient teamwork will enable employees to be more productive by sharing the workload and facilitating ideas generation and creativity that will lead to the creation of practical solutions (Goodman et al., 2013). In the same line, teamwork tends to build trust among employees which can boost their motivation and morale, which in turn helps them to relieve their stress and make the work more fun (Guchait et al., 2016). Eventually, working as a team will improve customer service as well as the overall business performance, meaning teamwork is essential for restaurants due to the type of business operations that are efficiently performed by the correlation of the front of house and behind the scenes workforce (Sulistiyani & Ferdinand, 2018).

Senani (2016) stressed that working as a team in the restaurant sector will increase employees' productivity by decreasing work stress and reducing mistakes, which will improve the restaurant's

overall performance (Senani, 2016). In addition, while the gig economy has dramatically affected every business function in the restaurant industry, undoubtedly, the employment market has seen the most prominent challenges due to changes at all levels caused by the emergence of gig employment (Vogler et al., 2018). Furthermore, employing a gig worker has many benefits and drawbacks for employees and employers, which were discussed earlier in the study. Yet, leading and managing gig workers develops new challenges for managers and employees. One of the challenges both parties can face is the development of efficient teamwork by the front-line management among the gig workers and in-house employees (Vogler et al., 2018).

The front-line leaders and managers follow mostly predictable steps to develop a team with members well known to them in terms of capabilities, interpersonal skills and personal circumstances; this has facilitated the process of creating efficient teamwork (Senani, 2016). Yet, with the new gig economy employment in the restaurant sector, the front-line management has a lack of knowledge regarding gig workers' skills and capabilities as well as the type of employment that does not encourage employees to try to be part of the team due to the limited jobs or shifts are conducting to the employer together with lack of motivation which all can develop obstacles for the management to create team among gig worker and in-house employees. (Vogler et al., 2018)

Accordingly, developing efficient teamwork is very important for better performance of restaurants and customer service (Vanikj & Zendeli, 2019). Yet, with the emergence of the gig economy and the new work phenomena, it seems that it is more challenging than ever for front-line leaders and managers to enable teamwork between gig workers and permanent employees (Ab-Latif et al., 2020; Vogler et al., 2018). Furthermore, restaurants have found it very challenging to devise solutions to teamwork issues as they affect the overall performance of employees and restaurants.

According to Ab-Latif et al. (2020), front-line managers and leaders used to apply the same methods to lead employees efficiently. The dramatic changes occurring in the industry have led to widespread impacts on the process and put more pressure on front-line management to cope with those changes and come up with a flourishing solution which will help both employees and gig workers to team up together and operate adequately toward achieving restaurants' goals and objectives as well as to achieve higher performance and provide a better service (Guchait et al., 2016). The front-line management needs to give efficient help to gig workers and permanent

employees to encourage them to work together for the good of the business (Hanners & Malvini, 2021).

2.5.3 Communication and gig workers in the restaurant sector

Guay et al. (2020) stated that communication is one of the most critical managerial functions due to its importance in the organisation's success through talking employees through the business vision, goals and objectives. Furthermore, communication is an essential part of all business stakeholders as it sets where everyone stands in the company's success plan (Duggan et al., 2020). According to Li (2020), business communications refer to how the employees and management interact efficiently to achieve a high level of productivity and maintain a strong working connection at all business levels. Front-line management should invest more energy and time into delivering clear communication lines that will help employees to develop strong trust and relationships among the team, which will generally lead to a rise in output, morale and productivity (Li, 2020). Therefore, good communicators are an excellent asset for businesses due to their importance in smoothing business operations and playing a valuable role in the company's success (Kaine & Josserand, 2019).

Gross et al. (2018) stated that efficient communication has several benefits, such as: building a strong team, increasing employees' contribution, developing solid management and boosting employees' productivity. Therefore, all those benefits mentioned and many others set communication to be among the most crucial business functions managers need to take seriously to develop a happy environment that will reduce employee turnover and increase productivity (Smith, 2021).

On the other hand, poor communication can drown business in serious issues such as developing a distracted culture within the company and unmotivated staff, which can lead to a high turnover rate among employees. In addition, productivity can be at its lowest level when poor communication occurs in the workplace, leading to poor performance within businesses (Carasco et al., 2015).

The restaurant sector is one of the most prominent industries facing high employee turnover and on-demand services where communication is necessary to efficiently and run restaurant operations smoothly (Davis et al., 2020). Furthermore, an efficient communication plan is essential for leaders to develop a thriving teamwork environment where employees put their effort into achieving the

restaurant's vision. Undoubtedly, the emergence of the gig concept based on hiring temporary workers to fill specific shifts has developed new objections for leaders to efficiently implement their communication strategies due to the nature of the gig workers' environment (Kaine & Josserand, 2019). Furthermore, front-line managers and leaders must find new channels and methods to facilitate communication between the in-house workers and gig workers to achieve the ultimate productivity and run operations smoothly and efficiently (Smith, 2021).

In the same line, leaders affirmed that communication is essential in workplaces as it brings up a large set of benefits to businesses such as the creation of job satisfaction, more minor conflicts, a rise in productivity, formation of relationships and many other benefits that boost the overall performance of restaurants. Moreover, front-line managers and leaders have opted for the same methods and channels to circulate communication through all business stakeholders efficiently (Davis et al., 2020). However, the gig economy, the emergence of technology, and several sociological changes in the job market have put leaders under new pressure to develop new strategies and theories to communicate with all stakeholders (Smith, 2021) effectively.

Developing the algorithmic platform approach has created new channels for leaders to communicate their strategies, the company's goals and objectives and the necessary messages to employees, particularly gig workers which have less contact and knowledge with the in-house employees, leaders and the work environment. According to Gross et al. (2018), hiring apps can be utilised by leaders as the first contact channel to communicate the necessary messages, rules and guidance with gig workers which allows the pre-knowledge of the job tasks to be clear to gig workers and will help them to reduce the time for adaptation to the work environment (Kaine & Josserand, 2019). In addition, leaders can use permanent employees to help keep the communication fluid among gig workers, increasing their productivity and satisfaction and developing a reputable experience (Istrate & Harris, 2017). Furthermore, technology has affected how our daily communications proceed and has given a better alternative for leaders to efficiently and rapidly communicate with gig workers and in-house employees. With new communications channels arriving continuously, leaders are advised to be updated on the most efficient channels to send the necessary guidance to the appropriate audience (Gross et al., 2018).

2.5.4 Management of performance in the restaurant sector

According to Sarangal et al. (2020), performance management refers to the continuous communication between a supervisor and an employee throughout the year in support of the

organisation's strategic objectives. Furthermore, a well-designed and documented performance management process, in theory, can be rewarding for both managers and employees: however, in practice, it often has unintended consequences, such as high costs of performance management activities, employees and even managers despise the performance management requirements that their organisations impose, and the information gathered from this formal documentation is often untrustworthy (Mueller-Hanson & Pulakos, 2018). In most situations, performance management in the gig economy is accomplished in the present arrangement by setting performance levels and using recruiting agencies' input to grade gig worker performance (Meijerink & Keegan, 2019). Despite the changing organisational attitude, the same approach cannot fully justify their short-term performance management objectives when applied to gig workers. Therefore, according to Majid et al. (2019), the method's effectiveness is brought into doubt because they are people who desire more versatility and have a high level of self-efficacy for pursuing tasks that require more work, establishing higher goals, and generating better tactics (Sarangal et al., 2020). For example, hiring agencies use a rating system in which previous employers are asked to rate their experiences on a five-star scale. Performance-oriented managers can appraise effectively in an organisational setting. Still, they fail to provide efficient ratings and feedback, putting gig employees at a disadvantage when monitoring their performance (Myung et al., 2020).

Given the aforementioned considerations, global economic competitiveness is generating new ties between breadwinners, and these new links necessitate new and more flexible approaches to controlling performance. On the contrary, Majid et al. (2019) stated that owing to the limited contact that gig employees have with their bosses, these performance measurement elements are frequently accelerated to result-based metrics. Furthermore, gig workers in a blended team can focus on the business value while recognizing their excellence if they are given an equal opportunity to define individualized business goals (Myung et al., 2020). For the entire team, real-time scoring may be established, allowing the front-line management to monitor their work efficiently. Gig workers can be given short-term ratings, providing them with the opportunity to improve their performance in the upcoming evaluation. In addition, two-way feedback should be fostered among the blended team, using real-time feedback methods such as daily evaluations, one-on-one performance conversations, and resolving specific concerns and grievances (Meijerink & Keegan, 2019).

2.5.5 Learning and development in the restaurant sector

According to Lives (2017), human capital is the most critical asset that distinguishes an excellent firm from a good one in the twenty-first-century worldwide market, making it critical to keep employees' skills and knowledge up to date. The disparity between the skills that organisations wish for and the skills that their workforce possesses has the potential to harm firm-level productivity and increase average labour costs, as workers are more likely to be less productive when there are significant skill gaps, necessitating training (McGuinness & Ortiz, 2015).

In the same line, just-in-time learning is another type that responds to fast-changing needs by providing workers with immediate training before they are required (Wilkie, 2013). Furthermore, most restaurants improve these learning approaches by employing cross-functional workshops to deliver high-quality products or services while also generating a culture of rapid progress (Fiscor, 2018). In addition, gig workers, on the other hand, often perceive learning and development as their duty and do not receive the same amount of investment in their knowledge and abilities as full-time employees. However, they must usually pay for self-improvement to keep up with skills and expertise (Tucker, 2017).

According to Kulkarni (2019), new learning models such as e-learning, AI-based learning, and microlearning, available remotely and in flexible formats, help bridge this gap. The gig workforce's ability to access e-learning modules on their systems and devices allows them to access anything from remote education to computerized electronic learning, Internet learning, and more (Kulkarni, 2019). In addition, bite-sized learning opportunities in consumable hour-long courses (microlearning) allow users to learn according to their preferences and flexible work schedules (Kulkarni, 2019).

2.5.6 Motivation and gig workers in the restaurant sector

According to DiRomualdo et al. (2018), liberalization and globalization have set workers as a compelling competitive advantage for businesses with the ability to propel and flourish with their performance. Employees are set to be among the essential assets for any business, allowing them to succeed or fail. This has put leadership and management functions amid the essential ones affecting business performance (PJ et al., 2020). Furthermore, the restaurant industry is one of the tightest markets. It has the highest turnover in terms of employees, which makes keeping talented

employees and developing their loyalty undoubtedly crucial and challenging for leaders and managers (Knott & Scragg, 2016).

The restaurant sector is one of the highest industries for employee turnover due to several reasons, such as the nature of employees, primarily students and temporary workers (Jabagi et al., 2019). Furthermore, the working conditions struggle to achieve a balance due to the industry's unsociable hours and salaries that are primarily minimum wage. Hence, all those aspects have put leaders under more pressure to prevent employees from leaving restaurants, which can cause operational and financial issues to businesses, such as training costs, hiring costs and time for the new employee to achieve high productivity (Ryan & Deci, 2020).

Accordingly, with all the changes occurring in the restaurant industry and the emergence of the gig economy which has changed the work market for good, front-line leaders and managers are urged more than ever to act urgently by setting efficient strategies to retain their talent workforce. One of the resources that managers can utilize to keep their employees satisfied is motivation (Pereira et al., 2020). According to Karlsson and Wranne (2019), motivation refers to the set of actions that are put together to satisfy employees' demands and needs to achieve the company's goals and objectives. Furthermore, there are a variety of motivation theories and frameworks, such as Herzberg's motivation-hygiene and Maslow's need hierarchy theories. Yet, there is no doubt that the emergence of the job opportunities offered by the gig economy has shifted the traditional employees' needs and demands. In addition, that has increased their expectations, which has put management under a continuous challenge to develop innovative motivation methods to keep up with the new era of employment created by the gig economy (Viorel et al., 2009).

Jabagi et al. (2019) stated that the basic traditional ways of motivation used to be limited and known to managers due to high awareness of employees' circumstances and capabilities as well as the type of employees' full-time situations, goals and objectives together with a lot of other information that helped front line management to motivate employees efficiently. Furthermore, gig workers' motives differ from permanent employees due to the two different work approaches and natures. According to Burbano (2021), gig workers' approach to work is based on the flexibility of gigging at the most convenient time as well as working with no boss, no commitments, career goals and objectives in the workplace; all those aspects draw no clue for leaders on what motivate gig workers. On the other hand, full-time employees' motives are more

likely recognizable by front-line management due to their regular interaction, as well as the high and close awareness of their needs and wants (Karlsson & Wranne, 2019).

2.6 Employee engagement in the gig economy

2.6.1 Evolution of employee engagement

According to (Kahn, 1990, as cited in Iqbal et al., 2017), employee engagement can be traced back to the study by Erving Goffman (1961), in which he claimed that employees dedicate three aspects to performing their jobs: emotional attributes, cognitive behaviour, and physical energies. He added that those three functions reflect personal engagement. If they are not present, it can indicate the disengagement of the individuals (Kahn 1990, as cited in Karumuri, 2016). The work of Goffman was the start of the employee engagement studies, and his research still influences many recent studies despite the passage of time.

Furthermore, when talking more about the idea from an organisational perspective, we go back to Kahn (1990), who introduced Goffman's ideas into a more practical context focusing on understanding the influence of personal disengagement and engagement on performance (Welch, 2011, as cited in Ruck et al., 2017). According to Ruck et al. (2017), the necessity of the employees to be engaged in the organisation was behind the foundation of Kahn's work, defining work engagement as the exploitation of the employees to their job functions, adding that engaged employees express and employ themselves while performing their roles cognitively, emotionally and physically. The ethnographic research of Kahn (1990, as cited in Iqbal et al., 2017) was the first qualitative study done regarding employees' engagement, developing the three-dimensional engagement theory that has become a reference for almost all studies done on engagement of employees, where at least one of his developed aspects would be included in the research. Most engagement literature still relies on the relevant findings of Kahn's work, which had moved away from Goffman's work by using the term personal engagement rather than the three-dimensional job functionality that was used by Goffman (1961). This can be noticed in the conceptual framework used in Kahn's study, which was stated as personal engagement and disengagement (Ruck et al., 2017).

2.6.2 Importance of employee engagement in the gig economy

The term engagement can be traced back to Kahn (1990), defining it as the mobilization of employees to their roles in the company, including their cognitive, emotional and physical involvement in their job performance (Rothmann, 2016). Furthermore, other practical approaches to employee engagement have described the phenomenon as the level of the workers' involvement and commitment toward their company by being aware of their goals and objectives and working with available means to achieve them. Employees' engagement has gained particular attention from business management in recent years, identifying its efficiency in improving the overall performance of businesses if it is well mastered (Motyka, 2018). Furthermore, the gig economy has enhanced the importance of engagement due to the nature of the employees that are related to the company for a particular time or work. With the popularity of engagement increasing dramatically among businesses, several studies have been generated by academics and practitioners to determine where the concept stands in the gig era (Iddagoda & Opatha, 2017; Shuck et al., 2017; Mencl et al., 2016). While both academic and practitioner approaches are concerned with different outcomes, it can be said that the practitioner community sees the concept as a method to increase sales, performance, customer loyalty, productivity and commitment.

On the other hand, academics focus on work engagement from the psychological concept by exploring the factors that can enhance work engagement and the challenges facing implementing strategies to achieve it (Shuck et al., 2017). Recently, several studies have emerged concerning employees' engagement (Sasuck et al., 2017; Garg & Kumar, 2012; Mencl et al., 2016), which have developed a more comprehensive understanding of work engagement. Yet, there is still a lack of agreement on a standard definition of engagement as well as common factors. Therefore, it can be said that employee engagement is a complex concept with no broadly conventional description (Shuck et al., 2017). However, there is an increasing harmony among academics that the construct is perceptible from complementary concepts in management such as job involvement, leadership, communication, motivation, commitment and job satisfaction. This can be based on the two-way relationship between employees and employers. Since employee engagement has been acknowledged as a complex concept, employers and academics can foster it differently, exploring the factors affecting the phenomenon from their perspectives (Ruck et al., 2017).

The gig economy has developed more reasons for academics and practitioners to study employee engagement due to the emergence of one-time jobs, particularly with the hit of the pandemic. As a result, this has caused millions of individuals to lose their careers and has enhanced the gig

workers market where employees seek jobs through hiring agencies platforms that can allow them to work for several businesses in one week (Meyer & Schneider, 2021). On the one hand, it is becoming more challenging and more necessary than ever for management to utilize all their available tools and functions to enhance the engagement of their employees and the performance of their businesses, while studies have shown that employees' engagement is based on three constructed dimensions: behavioural, cognitive and emotional (Mencl et al., 2016).

2.6.3 Definition of employee engagement

According to Sojan (2021), the term employee engagement has seen a variety of differences throughout the development of ideas regarding its constructs, predictors, concepts and outcomes. Furthermore, the engagement was investigated and debated by two groups: the academic community and the consultancy firms. The two groups have been researching the topic from two various points of view, which has developed different conceptual adjustments that led to further explorations in the research (Bailey et al., 2017).

There are two perspectives. Although various authors from both parties have sought to define engagement, it emerged as the first to originate the term 'engagement' (Kahn 1990, as cited in Karumuri, 2016). Literature on burnout (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018; Maslach & Leiter, 2017; Leiter & Maslach, 2016) characterized engagement as the opposite of burnout's negative state, which may occur as a result of the exhaustion of job resources. He explained how people might employ varying degrees of their selves in job role performances, physically, intellectually and emotionally. Moreover, other academics have written about engagement utilizing various conceptual frameworks for well-being (Bakker & Leiter, 2017; Schaufeli & Bakker, 2003 as cited in Bakker & Albrecht, 2018), burnout (Maslach & Leiter, 2017), job involvement (Gopinath, 2020) and passion (Zigarmi et al., 2018).

According to well-being research (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2003 as cited in Bakker and Albrecht, 2018; Tayama et al., 2019; Bliese et al., 2017), engagement is a pleasant, gratifying work-related state of mind marked by zeal, commitment, and immersion. Even though Kahn (1990) is recognized for coining the phrase 'engagement', the notion itself is not novel. Before the 1990s, authors took a more pragmatic approach, referring to engagement within the organisational behavioural environment as a flow as 'the holistic sensation' or 'the fire in the belly' those employees experience when they perform with whole involvement (Mousa & Chaouali, 2022).

Flow condition occurs when there is a slight separation between the self and the environment. Individuals in a 'flow state' require a small amount of conscious control over their actions. As a result, an employee in a 'flow state' is aware of the business context and collaborates with co-workers to improve job performance for the organisation's interest.

Organisations must seek to cultivate and grow engagement, which necessitates a two-way relationship between the employer and the employee. In a similar vein, engagement was defined as an energetic state of connection in personally fulfilling activities to improve one's sense of professional competence (Getahun Asfaw & Chang, 2019).

Following Kahn's (Kahn 1990, as cited in Iqbal et al., 2017) rationale, job-involvement researchers defined engagement as how people engage and expend themselves physically, mentally and emotionally during a role performance. The Gallup Organisation was the first to advocate for commercial engagement among practitioners. Buckingham and Coffman (2016) noted that Gallup invested a significant effort in perfecting a series of survey questions (the Gallup Workplace Audit) that linked employee engagement to efficiency, revenue, retention and customer retention service.

According to Chandani et al. (2016), the definitions of employee engagement presented in the literature are based on academic research and commercial consulting firms. Academics tended to correlate engagement with phrases like job, role and self-expression in a role, whilst commercial organisations were inclined toward linking engagement with terms like organisational commitment, ethics and vision. While the notion of employee engagement has become increasingly popular, it has experienced substantial evolution in terms of definition, measurement and conceptualization, whereas academic research has lagged (Meyer & Schneider, 2021)

As practitioners searched the academic literature for tactics and frameworks for cultivating an engaged workforce, they encountered a paucity of studies on the concept (Saks, 2019). As a result of the vacuum produced by the practitioner community's demand for answers and the concept's increasing presence in academic schools of thinking, two distinct perspectives emerged: the practitioner approach and the academic approach (Zigarmi et al., 2018).

This has occurred owing to each study that evaluated employee engagement under a particular methodology and setting and the prevalence of different definitions in academic and practitioner communities that made it challenging to define engagement. Furthermore, the concept of engagement is a complex construct in and of itself, making it harder to define (Kahn 1990, as cited

in Iqbal et al., 2017). As a result, employee engagement is a complicated term with no widely accepted definition (Al Mehrzi & Singh, 2016)

Nonetheless, academics are coming to a consensus that this idea may be distinguished from other management concepts, including job engagement, job involvement, organisational citizenship behaviour, job satisfaction and commitment (Al Mehrzi & Singh, 2016). On the other hand, employee engagement is founded on the idea that it depicts the two-way transfer of efforts between employees and employers. Hence, its connotations are stretched beyond the previous conceptions (Saks, 2019). However, it is also recognized that employee engagement is a complicated notion with numerous issues influencing engagement at various levels. As a result, different organisations can support engagement in multiple ways; thus, there is no 'one fits all' solution. Since each Corporation may define employee engagement differently, the most effective engagement will be determined by the adaptability of the most appropriate method for that particular institution. For example, a firm may assess a best practice (the customer is always right) and then associate it with a potential workplace consequence (increased sales) (Rothmann, 2016).

In terms of intent and outcome, the practitioner and academic methodologies are vastly different (Al Mehrzi & Singh, 2016). The practitioner method, for example, is more concerned with the construct's usability and actionable consequences such as increased retention, commitment and productivity levels and focuses more on gathering data at the macro or group level to improve workgroup functionality (Rothmann, 2016). While this approach provides a valuable perspective on the subject, it frequently conflates employee engagement with other related organisational concepts such as fulfilment or dedication, and there is little validity or reliability of estimated data presently offered among practitioner metrics (Saks, 2019)

On the other hand, the academic approach concentrates on specifying and confirming the psychological notion itself and is more focused on the micro or individual level (Bailey et al., 2017) to comprehend better antecedent characteristics that affect the effectiveness of engagement. In the scholarly literature, the academic method is a relatively new phenomenon (Saks, 2019). Its study's aim is scholarly; hence, this literature survey is dedicated to scholarly publications that enrich the research topics under consideration.

2.6.4 Employee engagement drivers

The literature has recently witnessed an increase in the popularity of the term 'employee engagement drivers'. This emergence is due to the rise of interest in human resource personnel and consultancy firms, according to Iddagoda and Opatha (2017). A driver refers to the tools that handle the behaviour of individuals. Various studies conducted to explore what drives engagement have shown no difference in the definition of the phenomena which differ from one organisation, culture and individual to another. Following Hofstede's cultural dimensions, a society's culture influences its members' behaviour and values (Ruck et al., 2017). Thus, the cultural differences need to be considered by researchers due to their importance among the factors akin to an exact behaviour in a specific social context (The Hofstede Centre, 2017). Using this example to the engagement of employees raises attention regarding what drives the engagement majorly in one context, which can be less influential in another.

Furthermore, the employee engagement drivers are interrelated and vary appreciably from one place to another (Mmako & Schultz, 2016). However, the literature showed an area of agreement on factors eliciting engaged employees. In addition, a variety of research works attempt to identify the drivers of employee engagement to define the factors embellishing employees' engagement in different contexts and organisations (Chandani et al., 2016). Corporations have shown an increased interest in exploring the engagement of employees' drivers to create the necessary policies to efficiently enhance their employees' engagement.

Furthermore, according to Al Senani (2016), there is an astronomical number of drivers that improve the engagement of employees. Thus, it is favourable to classify those drivers into a predominant classification to allow organisations to concentrate fundamentally on the most important ones to develop an engagement strategy efficiently. According to compelling research on the employee engagement drivers by Iqbal et al. (2017), the factors enhancing engagement were categorised into influential bands: personal attributes and situational factors. Furthermore, this work shows that researchers largely ignored personal factors while most research focuses on situational factors. At the end of the study, a conclusion was drawn that personal factors are as crucial as situational factors when it comes to attributes of employee engagement (Kumar & Giri 2007; Sharma & Mohapatra, 2009). Organisational leadership is one of the drivers highlighted by various research to be a strategic driver to engage employees.

Furthermore, much research pointed out that leaders must fixate on developing strategies to enhance employee engagement (Al Maktoum, 2015; Simha & Vardhan, 2015). In addition, according to Elewa (2013), leadership indirectly and directly influences employee engagement and leaders can play several roles in improving their subordinate's engagement. Those roles are setting a clear vision and goals developing efficient teams, motivating, inspiring, delegating tasks, developing autonomy, communicating effectively and spreading trust. Through mastering those roles, leaders will set a clear vision for the employees about their value in the company and eventually enhance their engagement (Jha & Kumar, 2016; Andres et al., 2015; Robbins & Judge, 2015).

The relationship between employees and leaders is one of the dimensions influencing engagement. To add more intensity to this, Markos and Sridevi (2010) refer to the vital connection between employees and managers as one of the most critical factors that drive the engagement of employees. More specifically, strong employee engagement reflects the strength of the relationship between employees and leaders (Al Maktoum, 2015; Truss et al., 2013). Al Maktoum (2015) points out that employees see their leaders as role models to enhance their engagement with the employees. Furthermore, employees tend to imitate their leaders, which shows that leaders are required to be effective and competent, not to mention their roles to demonstrate moralistic attributes to their subordinates such as justice, transparency and integrity (Hough et al., 2015; Jenkins and Delbridge, 2013). Following this claim, the employees are more inclined to be engaged when their leaders set a virtuous model within the organisation. This was encouraged by Anitha's (2014) claim, which believes that inspiring leaders consistently enhance employee engagement.

Valuing and involving the employees is set to be a booster of the engagement of employees. According to Iqbal et al. (2017), leaders aiming to boost employees' value and involvement can encourage them to be part of the decision-making and to share their concerns and ideas independently (Park et al., 2020; Rothmann, 2016). In this same line, empowering employees is believed to be a pivotal enhancer to engaging employees; according to Al Maktoum (2015), this can be done similarly by allowing employees to contribute toward the process of decision-making within the organisation and facilitating their contribution by backing them through an efficient management policy and counselling (Iqbal et al., 2017).

According to Jha and Kumar (2016), organisational leadership is linked to various engagement aspects and key drivers that have enhanced engagement advancement in organisations. This has

highlighted leaders' role in comprehending and upholding their followers to determine the engagement enhancers and help companies cope with development emerging in the current business world.

Effective communication has been determined to be one of the main fundamental factors boosting employee engagement (Gupta, 2015; Jha & Kumar, 2016; Simha & Vardhan, 2015). According to Al Maktoum (2015), communication should be a two-way process allowing employees to communicate openly with managers and vice versa. Communication is a process in which information ought to flow in a dual channel to raise the procedure of decision-making, involvement and feedback if it is efficient, according to Mishra et al. (2014).

Another study, conducted by Watson (2003) regarding communication, stated that efficient communication enhances the performance of organisations (Gupta, 2015). Leaders communicating efficiently can be one of the leading factors that boost employees' engagement by encouraging them to share their views and feedback with their leaders (CIPD, 2006; Kapoor & Meachem, 2012). In addition, efficient communication helps employees access the required data to accomplish their job competently (Al Maktoum, 2015). For communication to enhance engagement efficiently, it must be constant and precise (Saks, 2017).

A piece of work conducted by Mishra et al. (2014) to investigate the equivalence between communication and the engagement of employees showed that communication is crucial in developing a disclosure atmosphere between subordinates and leadership as well as broadening the engagement of employees (Gupta, 2015).

According to various studies (Bhuvanaiah & Raya, 2015; Gupta, 2015), there are a variety of positive outcomes that can be influenced by the impact of communication on the firm's performance, such as the level of employee engagement, loyalty, productivity, revenue and customer satisfaction.

Training and professional development are factors that can dynamically achieve the engagement of employees within corporations. Various studies (Gupta, 2015; Jha & Kumar, 2016; Mishra & Mohanty, 2016; Dessler, 2013; Simha & Vardhan, 2015) have recognised training as a significant driver that can help employees to be engaged. In addition, Dessler (2013) stated that professional development positively influences employee engagement.

Employees are keen on their career growth, making it one of the main drivers boosting engagement. Hughes (2013) listed various factors influencing the employee retention rate, with career development among the most important. Providing employees with the necessary skills and tools to ease the process of accomplishing their tasks will encourage them to be more attached to the organisation (Cheallaigh, 2015). Organisations offering a potential road for the employees to grow, learn and develop tend to enhance the employees' engagement. In addition, training and career development boost the level of effort given by employees toward accomplishing their goals and objectives (Hughes, 2013).

On the other hand, the lack of professional development can develop a high employee turnover in organisations (Ahmadi et al., 2012), which highlights the importance of career development in enhancing the sense of belonging of employees to their workplaces, enhancing their engagement, motivation and confidence (Anitha, 2014).

One of the other employee engagement key predictors is the reward and recognition that can be implemented by adopting an efficient scheme to reward effective employees, which can be in the form of benefits, honouring and pay (Kapoor & Meachem, 2012). This can lead to a high level of engaged employees. This was concluded by various studies (Al Maktoum, 2015; Bratton & Gold, 2007; Buckingham & Coffman, 2016; Simha & Vardhan, 2015). According to Hanaysha (2016), significant factors that boost the engagement of employees are nonfinancial, with the author adding that motivation can never be achieved by money alone. The rewards need to be accomplished by relying on financial and non-financial methods that enhance recognition to be among the fundamental factors in employee engagement (Anitha, 2014). Appreciating, valuing and praising employees for their achievements will boost their engagement level (Lartey & Randall, 2021). Organisations implementing an efficient system of appreciation, benefits and salaries tend to attract more employees to join their workplace. Furthermore, they naturally enhance employees' engagement toward helping organisations accomplish their goals and objectives. Thus, organisations must implement an efficient recognition scheme and connect it to their objectives (Al Maktoum, 2015, p. 42).

In the same line, different studies (Kapoor & Meachem, 2012; Mishra & Mohanty, 2016; Susi & Jawaharrani, 2011) discussed work-life balance as one of the core strategic drivers of engaging employees. The phenomena refer to the balance between the job tasks and the employees' commitment outside the workplace. In this respect, studies have set various factors for work-life

balance (Mishra & Mohanty, 2016). However, the most discussed one was family support, which, according to various studies, has shown a positive relation to the engagement of employees. According to Mishra and Mohanty (2016), the performance of an employee can be influenced dramatically by the family due to its role in providing encouragement and support to the job. Furthermore, another study by Kapoor and Meachem (2012) stated that employees belonging to their workplace will be enhanced when the family gathers, which will urge them to work harder to participate in the organisation blossoming. In addition, families can be a good source of material and emotional protection as they help individuals surpass their work stress during hard times (Elewa, 2013).

Following the same path, Shuck et al. (2017) investigated the issue and stated that the lack of work-life balance would boost dissatisfaction and disappointment among employees due to the absence of family time. Furthermore, a study by Dibben et al. (2011) stated that motivation, employee engagement and employee retention are positively impacted by work-life balance achievement. In addition, work-life balance enhances the employee's self-confidence, support and attachment to their workplaces. Work-life balance can also be developed to efficiently utilise personal resources in order to control work demands (Wang & Seifert, 2017)

It can be summarised that work-life balance is one of the factors that can help employees accomplish a high level of engagement. However, according to Elewa (2013), the amount of work-life balance is hard to define. He added that employers need to explore their employees' convenience more to draw a plan that can include the employees' families and provide more time for their workforce when it is necessary with their loved ones (Wang & Seifert, 2017).

The firm's image has emerged as one factor driving employee engagement in numerous studies (Al Maktoum, 2015; Simha & Vardhan, 2015). The company's attractive and positive image can enhance employees' engagement levels. In addition, involving employees in the activities of organisations can help develop a positive organisational image (Simha & Vardhan, 2015)

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) was linked to employee engagement in various studies. The work of Gupta and Sharma (2016) aimed to understand the impact of CSR on achieving a high level of employee engagement. The findings show that employees' engagement to enhance firms' performance is influenced by internal and external CSR. Therefore, opting for an efficient CSR scheme that aims to bring both employees and social benefits will help firms develop the engagement level of their employees. Teamwork and co-worker relationship is set to be one of the

core drivers of employees' engagement; this can be accomplished through creating efficient teamwork that has precise tasks, goals and objectives together with the development of an effective relationship among colleagues (Anitha, 2014; Al Maktoum, 2015).

According to Gibbons (2006, cited in Sahoo and Mohanty's (2019) work on studying the employee engagement drivers), several drivers were highlighted, such as honesty, confidence and the efficient connection between employees and managers. In the same line, research by Delbridge (2013) stated that employees' engagement could be accomplished through the reliance on the job features, workers' voices, social connections and values of organisations.

According to the research findings summarising Bhuvanaiah and Raya's (2015) study on employee engagement drivers, the drivers were mainly organisational factors covering the authority of decision-making, growth and development opportunities, leadership, fair treatment and empowerment. Moreover, creativity, leisure events, workers' autonomy, motivation schemes, innovation, ethical standards and many other factors were listed by various studies (Bhuvanaiah & Raya, 2015; Gupta, 2015; Mishra et al., 2014; Truss et al., 2013).

On the opposite side, according to work by Shuck et al. (2017), it can be said that there are various ways to enhance the engagement of employees varying from one firm to another, with no one model that can fit all. Different sectors and businesses must explore unique factors that can enhance engagement within their organisations. This can be achieved through investing more time and resources to investigate the employee engagement drivers that fit their circumstances and contexts. This will help them to be ahead of achieving better productivity, efficiency and organisational development (Sahoo & Mohanty, 2019).

2.7 Leadership

2.7.1 Defining the leadership roles and functions.

Since McClelland's work in the 1960s, debating what made an effective manager, the leadership skills framework has gained interest. The leadership functions and roles have become an undeniable economic aspect, particularly concerning human capital. There are a variety of leadership styles in the scientific literature that tend to influence employee involvement, performance or work-related attitude (Shamim et al., 2019).

According to Robescu et al. (2020), knowledge is also a significant aspect of gaining a competitive advantage, and by implementing an extensive learning curriculum, a theoretical knowledge-

sharing model will enhance the performance of businesses (Robescu et al., 2020). Furthermore, Leadership is the art of mobilizing others to fight for common goals (Kouzes & Posner, 2010).

Efforts to define and evaluate leadership skills continue to be essential to a more significant movement towards a competency management culture. (Boyatzis, 1982 as cited in Velu and Manxhari, 2017) produced one of the earliest LDC models, which included 19 competencies and showed five clusters: goal and action management, leadership, human resource management, emphasis on others and direct subordinates. Sparrow researched and defined good managers' managerial and behavioural skills in 1997.

While these two conceptualized models focus on individual abilities, Sparrow et al. (2016) added organisational or strategic competency, emphasizing practices that contribute to innovation. LDCs must actively capture the new paradigm because of globalization and rapid technological advances. Fowler, Zigarmi, Roberts, and Shuck published a novel LDC model (Sparrow et al., 2016) based on self-determination theory in 2018, suggesting that leaders who enable autonomy are less likely to respond or utilize pressure. They distinguish between efficient and ineffective managerial behaviours for sustaining success by promoting relationships and encouraging subordinates to do their part for the team by enhancing the connection (Robescu et al., 2020). In addition, these behaviours emerge the feeling of competence among employees, emboldening their skills to be shown and inspiring them to perform and develop. Also, providing positive feedback regarding the accomplished tasks is one of the leadership competencies (Shamim et al., 2019).

Sparrow et al. (2016) defined LD organisational competency as a quality based on an employee's behaviours rather than individual ability. Various models can be utilised to determine the competencies, such as the LDC strata plex, which refers to a multi-level model and covers layered (strata) and segmented (plex) requirements of skill. The following leadership skills are included in the model: interpersonal skills – the ability to influence others and convey effective social interactions; business skills – the ability to perform operations analyses and manage resources; and strategic skills – the ability to solve organisational problems, also known as solution appraisal and objective evaluation skills.

As a result, context is crucial in identifying which competencies are the most relevant. The most recent leadership competence school combines all previous schools, treating qualities, behaviour and emotional intelligence as abilities and proposing that competency profiling suits various contexts and competencies.

The management team's employee impression is crucial, as adopting appropriate leadership behaviour can result in the ideal work attitude (House, 1971 as cited in Nickels & Ford, 2017). As a result, the 360-feedback model is regarded as a valuable instrument for evaluating leadership abilities. Some of the tool's benefits are increasing self-awareness, clarifying behaviours and discovering possibilities for promotion, accountability and responsibility. Several studies were conducted to determine how different employees view leadership. The goal was to determine the management team's competency gaps and development needs at the RTM company. The evaluation was based on a 360-feedback paradigm (Nickels & Ford, 2017; Fleenor, 2019), utilising a questionnaire prepared to measure 15 competencies, which were classified into three main categories: interpersonal competencies, job-related competencies and personal competencies (Fleenor, 2019). The LDC models acknowledge the complexities of organisational life and how situational and personal differences factors can reduce or boost efficacy on various levels. Plus, the design and conceptualize applying science-based evidence. As defined by Mumford, Campion, and Morgeson (2018), competency is a set of knowledge, abilities, skills, experiences, and behaviours that lead to a compelling performance. Furthermore, leadership competency is pointed to as the capability to serve as a role model for designing the LDC model, including empowering human resources selection, recruiting procedures, employee engagement assessments, training and development plans. The goal of this analysis was to comprehend better-associated competencies, as well as personal and interpersonal competencies (Nickels & Ford, 2017).

These suggestions are arranged around a model of 360-feedback features similar to Fleenor's approach from 2019. "The model concerns the quality and nature of 360-feedback given to feedback recipients and their organisations" (Fleenor, 2019). Presently, the recommended approach entails: (a) determining the competencies to be evaluated; (b) being conscious of the feedback (e.g., respondents' viewpoints and impressions); (c) accepting the feedback (discussion of research findings); and (d) being accountable for acting on the feedback (conclusions). According to Nickels and Ford (2017), the management effectiveness profile system can be utilised to determine and define those leadership competencies. The table below will illustrate the competencies derived together with their definitions.

Table 1: Leadership competencies

<i>1. Job related competencies</i>	
Problem solving	Ability to predict and surmount barriers or challenges faced in present work by correctly diagnosing problems, creating proper ways to solve them from the standpoint of the entire organisation, and accepting accountability for actions and decisions taken, both personally and as a subordinated staff manager (Burke et al., 2018).
Time management	The ability to efficiently utilize one's own working time to accomplish delineated goals, to set aside time for team management, and to maintain positive relationships with superiors, subordinates, and peers in the organisation, as well as with other business partners (Lestari et al., 2021).
Objectives settings and prioritization	Setting SMART work targets for subordinates' staff and emphasizing the importance of teamwork and teams. Allot enough time to the activities that contribute the most to the attainment of the company's strategic goals and urge the coordinated team/teams to do the same (Déry et al., 2019).
Performant leadership	Acquisition of good, specialized knowledge and management abilities; the capacity to develop and track particular performance parameters to enable continuous attainment of objectives and continuous advancement of performance at the coordinated team/teams. Ability to recognize potential risks related to actions and devise strategies to mitigate or remove them. At a cross-departmental level, fostering a collaborative working space (Paiuc, 2021).
Organisation	Task allocation that is balanced and equal among the members of the led team, as well as task allocation that is relevant to each member's expertise and experience. The team's structure emphasizes each member's aptitude and ability, fostering a sense of progress among personnel (Niswaty et al., 2019).
<i>2. Interpersonal competencies</i>	
Team development	Motivating, encouraging, and continuously enabling subordinate employees so that they can improve the abilities required for high professional performance; knowing the aspirations of the members of the coordinated team, promoting their career progression, providing an environment appropriate to advancement, and a confident attitude in their capability for improvement; acknowledgment of merits and cultivation of employee performance; readiness to offer support through coaching and mentoring to attain positive results for the team and the organisation. Establishing and maintaining a company culture

	that values constant progress and evolution, as well as learning from previous mistakes, disagreements, and differing viewpoints (Lacerenza et al., 2018).
Delegation	Ability and concern for effectively delegating duties to team members/lead teams. deputation of both regular and complicated decisions or tasks, with the necessary conditions in place for the delegates to do them properly. Monitoring and assisting with the completion of delegated duties. taking accountability for delegated tasks (Hidayat et al., 2021).
Contribution	An open, positive, and proactive attitude toward co-workers, work, and advancement in general is demonstrated. Participation in and support of ongoing activities and projects of the organisation, as demonstrated by personal example, in order to realize the organisation's strategic objectives. To enhance outcomes, identify and promote innovations and change efforts at the organisational level (Titareva, 2021).
Feedback	Allot enough time to discuss subordinate employees' tasks, initiatives, or behaviours in order to learn from them and enhance performance. Providing honest and balanced positive and constructive feedback to led team members on a regular basis, based on specific facts and results. Genuine acknowledgement of subordinates' merits, enjoyment of team accomplishments, and public acknowledgement of exceptional merits. Specifically, offering constructive input and keeping anonymity regarding the topics raised. Obtaining input from others on one's own activity, outcomes and behaviour and applying that feedback for professional and personal improvement (Sexton et al., 2018).
Respect for team/employees/company	Respect in all interpersonal connections, with all types of individuals, under all circumstances. The ability to comprehend and analyse opposing perspectives in arguments or confrontations, to counter-argue without insulting the individual, and to maintain self-control. Encouraging an inclusive culture by recognizing and appreciating all forms of diversity. Promoting staff awareness of the company's mission and their individual responsibilities to clients, community health and environmental protection (Rogers, 2018).
<i>3. Personal competencies</i>	
Stress management	The ability to deal with working responsibilities without expending extra emotional energy, without negatively impacting one's personal health or the work environment of others. The ability to maintain self-control, calmness and inner balance in tension, crisis or conflict situations, which enables effective management of those circumstances (Joy, 2020).
Integrity	Consistent behaviour that earns people' trust. All actions should be conducted in a responsible and professional manner, in accordance with the organisation's values, strategy, and mission. Organisational compliance with appropriate legislation, regulations, working processes and standards. Promoting and maintaining a company culture that punishes immoral, unlawful, or abusive behaviour (Hughes, 2018).

Communication	Ability and confidence to voice pertinent views, to say things by name, to properly manage disagreements, and to surpass communication barriers in order to foster an environment that encourages free debate and real dialogue. Ability to support clear, succinct, and captivating written and oral communications for a variety of audiences. The ability to actively listen to interlocutors in order to establish common grounds of agreement in the event of a disagreement or to find the best solutions to difficulties encountered (Odin, 2021).
Personal engagement	The ability to instil enthusiasm and dedication in others in order to attain the organisation's strategic goals. The ability to inculcate confidence in coordinated team members for the future, as well as their continued motivation and team performance (Engelmann & Tomasello, 2018).
Motivation	The ability to empower individuals to accomplish a high level of performance thorough overcoming all their barriers, achieving the set goals and objectives. Motivation can drive the behaviour of human individuals to higher levels of accomplishment using their inter hidden energy (Werdhiastutie et al., 2020).

Source: Researcher from different literature

2.7.2 Leadership in the restaurant sector

Shi (2018) stated that leadership refers to the approach opted by leaders and managers while selecting, training, equipping and influencing individuals with diverse skills and abilities and motivating them to concentrate on the companies' goals and objectives. Leaders have diverse styles depending on their characteristic behaviours while motivating, guiding and managing employees toward accomplishing the companies' goals and objectives (Fleming & Head, 2021). Leaders encourage followers to enthusiastically and willingly ante up physical and spiritual energy in a concerted effort to accomplish the organisation's mission and goals (Poon, 2019). Furthermore, leaders need to have a clear future vision that helps them influence followers to believe and comprehend their role in the current action steps. There are a variety of leadership styles – including autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, transformational, transactional and transformational – which have been used for several centuries by a variety of leaders (Shi, 2018). Although all leadership styles have benefits and drawbacks, leaders' characteristics drop into those types when efficiently leading employees. The restaurant industry has one of the highest staff turnovers, which has been proven to lead to poor performance; this means leaders are among the most critical assets of any restaurant due to their importance in training, retaining and inspiring employees while cost-efficiently operating restaurants to achieve their vision and objectives (Zhang & Jenkins, 2021). The restaurant sector is one of the most affected by the rise of the gig economy, introducing a new source of income and a new employment norm based on hiring freelancers to run business operations. With the high employee turnover, employing gig workers

seems to be the most efficient solution for leaders to cope with the phenomena (Adams et al., 2018). However, this new method of employment has developed new challenges for restaurants as well as for leaders since the traditional styles of motivating, inspiring, training and guiding employees might not be efficient in the new era of employment where workers are more flexible and are used to the new autonomy employment system (Shi, 2018). In addition, the emergence of the gig economy, particularly the app-based delivery companies, has created a new source of income for employees and has enhanced the migration of employees from traditional full-time employment while providing good flexibility and money in the gig sector (Anwar & Graham, 2020). While leaders used to have more flexibility in selecting their leadership styles, the emergence of the gig economy has limited their options due to the changes occurring in the labour market and the job opportunities offered by the gig economy, either by the food delivery apps or the hiring agencies (Bryant, 2020).

2.7.3 Leadership in the gig economy

The gig economy has redefined the employment models developing new approaches for employees and employers. For decades, employees used to stick to one job, coping with all conditions and working hard to keep their jobs. With the growth of the digital economy, employees are free to move from one workplace to another with a single click on their phones (Sibanda et al., 2021). The flexibility developed by the phenomenon has created enormous pressure on leaders to adjust to the new job market and develop new styles that can show efficiency with the new employees' mentality (Zhang & Jenkins, 2021). Leaders encounter two types of employees: those who are working for food delivery apps and those who are freelancers and using hiring apps to work flexibly with restaurants. Each of the two models has developed a variety of challenges for leaders to function efficiently (Sibanda et al., 2021). Leadership is based on mastering a set of functions to operate businesses and employees efficiently. However, the most crucial functions are training and motivating employees and developing excellent communication and teamwork among workers. (Zhang & Jenkins, 2021). Although all those functions have taken the same approach for decades, depending on the leadership styles, recently, and with the emergence of the gig phenomena changing employment models, and the development of new aspects such as gig workers and food delivery apps, leaders are required to come up with new approaches and styles to cope with the changes in the work environment (Sibanda et al., 2021). Traditional workers and gig workers are ultimately different in terms of their work motives, aims and objectives, which puts more pressure on leaders to develop an efficient approach to lead each of the employees,

defining methods to motivate, communicate and train them so they work with each other productively (Duggan et al., 2020).

2.7.4 Leadership functions and employee engagement

The leadership concept is one of the critical topics most researched when it comes to employee engagement and management science over the last decade. However, previous studies have not investigated the relationship between employee engagement and leadership (Bao & Zhao, 2018). According to the preceding research results, businesses are spending more resources to hire talented individuals and develop, retain and engage them to operate their businesses more efficiently. Businesses adopting the earlier strategy must collaborate with positive leaders and efficiently employ and inform them on how to positively instil energy in their followers (Carasco et al., 2015).

Despite the extensive studies conducted on employee engagement and leadership, there is still a gap in the research on how leadership functions. Styles and behaviours could impact employee engagement, as well as the most crucial functions that can enhance the engagement level among gig workers (Gupta et al., 2017). There are a variety of leadership qualities that are related to the engagement of employees. According to Gupta et al. (2017), leadership is one of the significant factors that should be considered wisely nowadays due to the challenging situations the economy is going through, particularly with the emergence of the pandemic, the gig economy, Brexit and many other aspects that lead the economy to be more challenging than ever for businesses (Smith, 2021).

In the past, control and command shaped leadership. According to Breevaart et al. (2016), that is in the past, and the kind of leadership based on command and control no longer secures engaged employees (Smith, 2021). Elewa (2013) pointed out that the leadership role in engaging employees is vital during economic uncertainty. He added that leadership could also indirectly affect employees' engagement through its influence on the organisation's performance. Moreover (Bao & Zhao, 2018) stated that a good role model of engagement from leaders will encourage the subordinates to follow. There are a variety of theories regarding leadership that were developed over the last decades, such as the trait, behavioural, contingency and transformational leadership theories which have studied leadership from different perspectives developing a variety of characteristics, factors and aspects in defining effective leadership (Carasco et al., 2015). According to Gupta et al. (2017), leadership reflects the effort of leaders to influence subordinates

to comprehend and concede on what should be done and how it should be done, together with the process that could facilitate the effort of individuals to achieve the set goals and objectives. Furthermore, leadership can be defined as an individual's actions to influence a team of people to accomplish the set goals (Smith, 2021).

Going through the definitions mentioned above, it can be said that the leadership definitions highlighted several components that had shown contradictions to the early theories of leadership: for instance, the trait theory suggested that leadership is a trait that individuals are born with (Gupta et al., 2017). In addition, recent years have shown an increasing interest in employee engagement from both scholars and practitioners, which has enhanced the emergence of several factors causing the rise of engagement, and leadership is set to be one of those factors. According to Prochazka et al. (2017) and much other research regarding engagement, engaged employees are more likely to be happy about their bosses and organisations, which will boost their contribution toward the development of a positive brand in their organisations. It also encourages them to remain in the company, which will reduce the overall employee turnover and boost the employees' efforts, which will ultimately influence productivity, customer satisfaction, sales and service quality. According to Smith (2021). Many employees tend to leave their workplace due to unhappiness with their bosses. On the other hand, Xanthopoulou et al. (2011) stated that the constant variation of leadership could enhance employees' self-belief in their work experiences.

To sum up, it can be seen that employees are remarkably influenced by their leaders' actions, negatively or positively, which shows that the relationship between followers and leaders can draw the outcome of all levels, including organisational, individual and group.

According to the assumptions stated above, it can be said that leadership is one of the core antecedents of employee engagement (Bao & Zhao, 2018). That can lead to a gratifying corollary enhancing employees' well-being and business performance.

A variety of other scholars have investigated leadership and employee engagement, such as Gupta et al. (2017), who studied the possible impact of the supervisor's leadership styles on the work engagement of their followers. This research found a strong relationship between the level of engagement and self-efficacy, optimism and transformational leadership (Gupta et al., 2017).

Furthermore, a study conducted by Zhu et al. (2009, cited in Gupta et al., 2017) examined two statements, the connection between the engagement of the followers and transformational

leadership as well as the strength of the leadership engagement and its relation to the positive characteristics of the followers. This piece of work concluded that employee engagement showed negative relation to transformational leadership as well as to the self-rated characteristic of employees. Furthermore, Aryee and Walumbwa (2012) performed a study to determine the extent to which employee engagement is influenced by transformational leadership. The study was staged in China, covering 193 supervisor and subordinate employee participants. The results showed an indirect impact on employee engagement from transformational leadership (Gupta et al., 2017).

Along the same line, Salanova et al. (2011, as cited in Bao and Zhao, 2018) investigated the relationship between extra-role performance and the transformational leadership of supervisors, including their engagement and self-efficacy. The study was conducted in Portugal, covering 297 nurses. The data analysis showed a partial relation among the studied phenomena, highlighting work engagement as a factor enhancing and facilitating the impact of transformational leadership on extra-role performance (Bao & Zhao, 2018). Furthermore, various other research has been conducted about leadership and employee engagement, which has shown evidence that employees' behaviour and attitude could be enhanced by authentic leadership, which can show a positive work outcome such as job commitment, engagement, satisfaction and creativity (Dan et al., 2013).

According to the results of Dan et al. (2013), the statement above regarding authentic leadership can be supported, as the analysis shows a strong correlation between the engagement of employees and the most traditional concepts of management. Furthermore, employee trust and engagement were positively correlated to authentic leadership (Iszatt-White & Kempster, 2019). Tourish (2005, as cited in Gupta et al., 2017) has conducted related research, setting effective communication to be among the most efficient ways that can be opted by leaders to boost the engagement of employees (Karanges et al., 2015). In support of Tourish's (2005) assumption, Elewa (2013) debated that efficient communication is required at all levels for engagement to be achieved. Furthermore, the work of Gupta et al. (2017) has drawn further development to the study of Tourish by concluding that the research reports showed that efficient communication could lead to up to 4.5 times higher level of engagement compared to companies operating with low communication strategies (Osborne & Hammoud, 2017).

In addition, many studies have set efficient communication as a strategy and tool that can be used in economic recessions to challenge the negative accoutrements of the economic crisis (Brockett, 2009 as cited in Zala, 2021). Furthermore, Elewa (2013) has highlighted in a different study that

branding is one factor that can help engage employees. In support of this argument, Zala (2021) stated that the image of a company is part of employee engagement (Chandani et al., 2016). Going through all the findings generated from the previous research on leadership, it can be suggested that leadership influences employee engagement to an immense extent (Hsieh & Wang, 2015). However, it is essential to observe that being a good leader or having the traits of good leadership can be learned and earned through experiences, individuals' life stories and many other sources rather than something that one can be born with (Caulfield & Senger, 2017).

The researcher has briefly discussed in the section above a few leadership attributes and how they can influence the engagement of employees. However, according to MacLeod and Clarke's study, employee engagement consists of 50 definitions that will require significant time to examine and investigate the various conceptualisations of employee engagement (Allan et al., 2019). This will give the researcher a premium insight into the approach to construct a practical conceptual framework that will highlight the antecedent to employee engagement based on the core leadership functions (Breevaart & Bakker, 2018).

2.7.5 Communication as a driver of gig workers engagement

According to previous literature, employee engagement is critical regarding worker turnover, profitability and consumer relations, which has put pressure on organisations and leaders to work hard on enhancing employee engagement. Communication is an essential tool that allows the smooth transmission of organisational information, support and activities to employees (Mone & London, 2018). According to Reissner and Pagan (2013), communication is one of the most efficient channels that can be utilised as a medium between organisational hierarchy layers to foster direct engagement akin to prospect and social relationships. Many Organisations are developing a culture and an environment where two-way communication and management behaviours are adopted efficiently to enhance employee engagement (Reissner & Pagan, 2003, as cited in Heide and Simonsson, 2018). Welch's study (2011) has allowed the formulation of an employee engagement model from the communication context that demonstrated that organisational communication could influence employee engagement (Ruck et al., 2017).

According to Kahn (1990) cited in Welsh's (2011), workers' engagement consists of three psychological antecedents: safety, availability and meaningfulness. Kahn argued those three conditions are crucial for employee engagement (Iqbal et al., 2017). Furthermore, according to Welsh, integrated commitment is one of the employee engagement antecedents based on the study

performed by Meyer et al. (2010, as cited in Megha, 2016). The psychological conditions that Kahn determined by safety, commitment, meaningfulness and availability need to be met for the physiological dimensions to emerge, allowing employee engagement to take place in organisations. Kahn's physiological dimensions are cognitive, emotional and physical engagement (Bailey et al., 2017). In the same line, a study by Schaufeli and Bakker (2004) has defined three engagement characteristics: vigour, absorption and dedication. Engagement was defined by Schaufeli and Bakker (2009) as a "positive work-related state of mind" which is represented by absorption, dedication and vigor" (Adiarani, 2019), while absorption depicts the flow of employees, effortless focus and concentrated attention. Vigour and dedication are believed to be at the substance of engagement (Decuyper & Schaufeli, 2020).

Welsh (2011) refers to communication as a core part of the engagement antecedents and promotes physiological engagement dimensions. Furthermore, the work of Welsh stated that senior leadership communication is set to be an integral factor of engagement. He added that communication is considered one of the psychological needs of employees that organisations should meet to develop and maintain employee engagement (p. 340) (Welsh, 2013, as cited in Moletsane et al., 2019). The Welch model has positioned organisation communication among the most important functions that enhance engagement, through boosting the sense of affiliation and commitment, as well as subsequent outcomes of engagement, such as comprehension and awareness (Soares & Mosquera, 2019). Moreover, Welch suggested the creation of physiological engagement conditions can be achieved through the efficient application of corporate and leadership communication which will emerge in the development of the physiological dimensions of engagement that will enhance organisational effectiveness, competitiveness and innovation, according to the Welch (2011) model (Moletsane et al., 2019).

Communication was referred to by Reissner & Pagan (2013) as the ideal way to promote engagement among employees in organisations. However, a limited number of studies have been conducted on the fundamental role of communication in enhancing engagement. Furthermore, creating an engagement culture within organisations seems to be helping the development of a culture and environment that improves the engagement of employees (Osborne & Hammoud, 2017). This can be done through management behaviours and two-way communication (Kang & Sung, 2017).

Communication has shown efficiency in facilitating the process of engaging employees, which can be achieved through management communication of the operational and strategic procedures with

employees and encouraging employees to communicate back with their managers (Karanges et al., 2015). In addition, a study conducted by Macleod and Clark (2009) has suggested that engagement activities developed by organisations are the key to motivated employees, which will develop more opportunities for employees to connect with their managers, organisations and colleagues (Okpuand Kpakol, 2018). Furthermore, employee engagement reflects the procedure of developing opportunities for employees to comprehend the organisational disorder that could be referred to as sense-making. According to Weick et al. (2005), sense-making is defined as the iterative exertion of employees to clarify their insight framework in order to represent the reality effectively, and which will eventually enable them to act efficiently (Rofcanin et al., 2017).

Furthermore, communication is seen as a core segment of sense-making. Thus, boosting internal communication is the key to enhancing sense-making among employees, ultimately improving job satisfaction and employee engagement (Kulachai et al., 2018). In the same line as Welch (2001), Weick (2001) disputed that managers should help their employees select the interpretation that suits the interest of the organisation (Weick, 2001; Welch, 2011). Reissner and Pagan (2013) have researched the impact of communication on employee engagement (Reissner & Pagan, 2013, as cited in Lemon and Palenchar, 2018).

The qualitative study covered 24 individuals and 3 group interviews, including employees and frontline managers working for a company in the UK that had freshly introduced new communication ventures aiming to boost the engagement of employees. The company's communication activities included team meetings, newsletters and organisation-wide events to boost shared understanding. In addition, managers were emboldened to communicate more strategic and operational resources with employees, including business actions (Barhite, 2017). The research aimed to ascertain whether employee engagement was improved by introducing the new communication scheme; in this matter, employees were asked about the engagement activities and the engagement relationship with their managers (Barhite, 2017). The findings of this work showed that employees dignified the expanded interaction opportunities implemented by managers and the company together with the rise in discursive communication and discussion that enhanced employees to comprehend their organisation better (Lemon & Palenchar, 2018). In addition, the rise in two-way communication boosted employees' engagement and involvement in the organisation (Lemon & Palenchar, 2018). The research findings emphasised the importance of organisational communication activities and their connection to employee engagement. In the same line, the Rainbow Trust Children's Charity, named among the Top 100 Employers by the

Sunday Times, conducted another study to determine how to engage employees. The organisation surveyed its employees with focus groups and worked on boosting employee engagement through developing activities. The first action pointed out by the focus groups and the survey used various channels to communicate continuously, including employee stories, newsletters and the formulation of performance conversations between employees and managers (Bone & Baeck, 2016). The study conducted by The Rainbow Trust Children's Charity in 2008 aimed to develop an environment within the company where honest and open communication was endorsed. According to Powis (2012), within the four years of conducting the research and after the company had implemented the communication schemes, the Rainbow Trust Children's Charity won the award in employee engagement (Barhite, 2017).

To sum up, according to the publication of the Corporate Communication International Organisation in 2013, there is a revived intensity on the role of communication in the engagement of employees (Heide & Simonsson, 2018). Furthermore, the report stated that building employee engagement and positive corporate culture were substantially emphasised by organisations to resilient the emerging conditions of the global economy, the changing business and media environments and networked enterprise (Altehbah et al., 2019). Employees play a crucial role in a networked organisation that enhances the need to improve employees' morale. Therefore, leadership and corporate communication can play a crucial role in the engagement of employees (Altehbah et al., 2019).

2.7.6 Motivation as a core driver to gig workers' engagement.

Going back to the origin of the word motivation will take us back to the Latin word *motivus* which means "to move". From an organisational point of view, motivated employees are those willing and ready to move the business toward achieving its goals and objectives, while unmotivated workers are those who show no interest in being part of the business's success (Suharno & Despinur, 2017). Ryan and Deci (2020) refer to motivated individuals as engrossed in contributing eagerly to whatever they can do. Contrarily, the unmotivated show no interest in taking action toward an end. Employee motivation is one of the most studied organisational behaviours by researchers, exceeding 250 studies seeking to determine what are the bottom-line motives for employees (Suharno & Despinur, 2017).

Harvard Psychological Clinic in Boston was among the most distinguished studies developing a helpful scale for motivation by 27 associates (Murray, 1938, cited in Sanford, 2017). This could

be seen as the measurement of motivation together with the Thematic Apperception Test that McClelland later categorised into three broad classes: the need for affiliation, power and achievement. Employee motivation has increasingly become one of the most researched concerns in organisational studies, helping organisations to put employee motivation into their priorities to address their issues (Baron, 1991; Abah & Nwokwu, 2016).

Katz and Kahn (1978, as cited in Davis et al., 2020) set motivation as the tool that should be adopted efficiently by organisations in order to function at their best. Hiring motivated employees is one of the most critical steps for organisations through targeting people whose interest is far more than joining the company (Sanford, 2017). They are also willing to contribute to the company's success and development by being more reliable and dependable while performing their jobs, as well as willing to go the extra mile and do more than their obligatory roles (Abah & Nwokwu, 2016). Kahn (1990) developed his ideology regarding the engagement concept by relying on the recent assertion of Katz and Kahn. However, it is necessary and beneficial to go through the motivation conceptualisations before inspecting the similarities and differences between employee motivation and employee engagement (Anthony-McMann et al., 2017).

In the same line, Jabagi et al. (2019) have identified the motivation of employees to be among the most crucial issues that managers in organisations could face. Likewise, Nohria et al. (cited by Ye, 2018) agreed that learning to satisfy the fundamental needs of humans is the key for managers aiming to efficiently motivate their employees (Jabagi et al., 2019). The four human fundamental needs are bond, acquire, comprehend and defend, which allow individuals to have social status, connect with others, satisfy their curiosity and be protected.

External and internal factors reflect the fundamental and essential forms of motivation. According to Pereira et al. (2022), motivation refers to psychological action that encourages the perseverance and guidance of voluntary activities toward the goal. This perceives motivation as an emotional behaviour and activity deliberately provided by the employees under supervision (Soares & Mosquera, 2019). Another study related to motivation and employee engagement was conducted by Pinder (2008); this characterised motivation as a number of factors that can enhance behaviours related to work in organisations and define its direction, duration, intensity and structure (Latta & Fait, 2016).

Therefore, engagement and motivation can be linked to an employee's spontaneous behaviour. Following the above argument, another study, performed by Edger (2009), suggested that

managers can play a huge role in increasing employee motivation by providing them with the necessary tools such as the authority and the power to complete their jobs (Jabagi et al., 2019). On the other hand, a variety of other studies have different thoughts, such as the CIPD (2012), which believes that communication is the critical factor for employee motivation. In addition, employers should share the business challenges and realities they face to enhance employees' involvement and motivation to share their ideas to be part of the problem-solving process and contribute toward achieving the companies' goals and objectives (McManus & Mosca, 2015). Furthermore, communication can efficiently play a crucial role in sustaining employees' dedication when the reward system fails to do so, which will help the organisation to operate more efficiently (CIPD, 2012; McManus & Mosca, 2015).

Guay et al. (2020) refer to motivation as the justifications underlying the actions and behaviour of employees. By way of explanation, the designed motivational programme can determine how employees act in the organisation. This means the better the programme is, the more motivated are employees (Suharno & Despinur, 2017). Butschek et al. (2022) defined motivation as the characteristic part of employees that allows them to perform a specific action. In addition, the definition of Prabowo et al. (2019) highlighted two aspects that need to be met while talking about motivation: the individual level and the organisational level. In their statement, motivation reflects how ready employees are to work toward achieving the company's goals and objectives, while still being able to satisfy their needs (Altehbah et al., 2019). Management is responsible for developing goals that can be achieved while at the same time drawing a platform where employees' desires can be satisfied (Sanford, 2017). In the same line, Karlsson and Wranne (2019) agreed that motivation represents the determined processes an individual is willing to perform to convert their resources into possible actions. Furthermore, motivation was defined as a mixture of forces determining individual behaviours (Wright & Noe 1996, cited by Nicolaidis, 2020).

Similarly, another study suggested that motivation reflects employees' behavioural phenomena based on their individual needs, which managers can use efficiently to attain the company's goals (Barhite, 2017). According to a survey conducted by Nohira et al. (2008), including 400 participants, the motivational indicators for employees can be categorised into four sections: reward system, performance management and resource allocation, development of teamwork culture and meaningful job concept (Abah & Nwokwu, 2016).

2.7.7 Motivation forms for gig workers (intrinsic and extrinsic)

The two most considered types of motivation are extrinsic and intrinsic. However, they have seen differences in educational and developmental practices (Ryan & Deci, 2020). Herzberg (1959, cited by LaBombard, 2022) distinguished the two types of motivation by stating that employees always have motivation expectations at work, which, if not met, can lead to demotivation. Thus, this was debated by Herzberg stating that they are two independent factors influencing the satisfaction and the dissatisfaction of individuals, which are hygiene and motivation factors (Nicolaidis, 2020).

The theory of the two factors presumes that job dissatisfaction and satisfaction differ; this is why they should be separated. Management must define the workplace's demotivational factors to allow employees to be motivated efficiently by the motivators that are put in place (LaBombard, 2022). Lai and Gelb (2018) argued that the satisfiers, the motivational factors, are intrinsically rewarding for employees. Those satisfiers are responsibilities, growth, a sense of achievement and recognition. However, hygiene factors represent the fundamental factors that enhance motivation in organisations and lead to short-term satisfaction. To be more specific, the hygiene factors are the job environment factors that prevent employees from being dissatisfied in the workplace (Altehbah et al., 2019).

Various factors come under the hygiene factors, such as interpersonal relations, security salary, working conditions and organisational supervision; those factors are expected to meet the physiological needs of employees. On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is related mainly to tangible or intangible rewards, such as bonuses, benefits and pay raises (Latta & Fait, 2016). Extrinsic factors refer to the external factors as they are implanted and controlled outside the work environment. Furthermore, this system of reward is one of the earliest forms that guarantee the fundamental reward aspects that can attract employees in the first place to organisations (Suharno & Despinur, 2017). Undoubtedly, the financial aspects are the first to be considered when accepting a job. However, other significant intrinsic rewards can develop satisfaction at any job that can be considered a motivator for employees and determination to join businesses; this type of motivation is firmly connected to the engagement of employees (Nicolaidis, 2020). Therefore, intrinsic motivation is an activity performed to satisfy its genetics rather than other breakable results. Intrinsically motivated employees will deliberately and enjoyably react to a challenge rather than respond to external factors such as rewards and pressure (Fishbach & Woolley, 2022)

The intrinsic motivation phenomenon was first acknowledged in experimental studies conducted on the behaviour of animals, showing that even in the absence of benefits and rewards, animals were still engaging in curiosity and exploratory-driven behaviours (Rode et al., 2015). In the same line, Deci et al. (2000) have taken this study further and suggested that employees displaying intrinsically motivated behaviours conduct their work to satisfy their basic psychological needs for autonomy. On the other hand, extrinsically motivated employees perform their job based on external non-related consequences (Soares & Mosquera, 2019). According to Thomas (2009, as cited in Alhassan & Greene, 2020), four intrinsic rewards can enhance employees' engagement in their workplaces, which are:

The sense of choice: Employees are more engaged when they feel free to perform their activities under their judgment and accomplish the required task. The feeling of ownership of their jobs will enhance their confidence in taking all responsibilities to accomplish the job in the best ways possible (Thomas, 2009, as cited in Alhassan & Greene, 2020).

The sense of progress: Employees can achieve it through seeing the results of their actions and efforts. Enhancing their feeling toward going in the right direction and achieving the requested tasks will boost their confidence in their choice and allow them to be more engaged in the future (Victor & Hoole, 2017).

The sense of competence: How employees handle their jobs will increase their sense of competence. Performing the job efficiently could exceed organisational expectations and will develop a sense of satisfaction among individuals and augment their feelings regarding their competence, which could allow them to improve their performance (Alhassan & Greene, 2020).

The sense of meaningfulness: This can be used to reward the involvement of employees by highlighting the importance of what they are performing. Employees feeling that there is a meaningful result to their performance will make them feel more valued in terms of the time, the energy and the effort they are providing, which will engage them more in the organisational activities (Victor & Hoole, 2017).

Various theories have emerged to define the influencers of employees' motivation, which shows that some of the theories are marginally related to the engagement of employees. There are two types of theories: process and content theories. Content theories cover Douglas McGregor's theories X and Y, Fredrick Herzberg's theory, Maslow's hierarchy of needs, and the theory of

motivation. On the other hand, the process theories include the cognitive theories of motivation, Derived or Reinforcement theories and instinctive theories of motivation (Fishbach & Woolley, 2022). Maslow's hierarchy of needs is arguably one of the most influential content theories. It is categorised into five distinguished groups of individual needs for safety and security, self-esteem, physiological needs, social needs and self-actualisation. Recognising the needs of individuals for behavioural motivation is one of the critical strengths of Maslow's theory (De Vito et al., 2018). Managers can employ their skills to determine the discontented needs of employees to motivate them efficiently. Furthermore, managers can collect data from employees on what motivates them to develop an effective motivation programme within organisations (McManus & Mosca, 2015).

In the same line, Wiley (1997) argued that asking employees is the best way to acknowledge what motivates them, stating that past studies noted that employees are the ideal source to define what motivates them. Also, managers are advised to communicate more with employees to be aware of their motivations (Latta & Fait, 2016). Furthermore, positive feedback has been recognised as an efficient tool for employees' motivation which can also enhance their self-image. Maslow's theory rationale is based on centralising the successor level of need while satisfying the lesser need. This will divert the employees' focus toward achieving the highest need in the hierarchy (De Vito et al., 2018). Regarding the self-actualisation need, Maslow has argued that it might never be reached due to the physiological character of individuals who keep looking for the unsatisfied need to motivate their behaviours which can only be found in the leading need (Soares & Mosquera, 2019). Organisations are very familiar with Maslow's theory due to its frequent usage. However, it has been criticised mainly due to the diverse priorities of employees as well as its inflexibility, which has pushed Maslow to believe that it is unrealistic for individuals to move constantly and progressively to the top of the pyramid as each react differently based on their needs (De Vito et al., 2018).

2.7.8 Frederick Herzberg's two-factors theory

Hertzberg developed this theory after a study conducted on engineers and accountants to determine their dissatisfaction and satisfaction. The research saw a strong correlation between employee performance and the jobs they are rewarded for, such as promotions, achievement, professional acknowledgement and the nature of the work. On the other hand, the unsatisfied part was related to salary, management and work conditions (Bevins, 2018). Hertzberg considers motivation as the key to enhancing work performance through the motivational factor process that will reflect the

precise work performed by employees. The factors reflect the imperative circumstances for work action implementation. However, the theory was criticised for not efficiently evaluating the connection between performance and action (Sanjeev & Surya, 2016).

2.7.9 Douglas McGregor Theory X and Theory Y

This theory is one of the leading motivation theories. Work conducted by McGregor (1960) categorised employees into two groups (the X and Y employees) (Hattangadi, 2015). X employees represent the category of employees who neglect their duties, lacking ambitions and avoiding as much work and responsibility as possible. This category of employees has shown no interest in organisational desires and apathy towards change (Prottas & Nummelin, 2018). For this reason, X employees should be punished, controlled and penalised in order for them to develop an interest in achieving the company's goals and objectives (Alam, 2015).

On the other hand, Y employees are ones who believe that putting in intellectual and physical effort at work is part of their job, taking responsibility for performing various assignments at their best while still considering rewards as a motivational factor. Y employees deliberately attain high performance with no outside pressure and force as their work environment majorly motivates them (Hattangadi, 2015). Alongside the motivational theories mentioned above, there are various action theories. While the content theories are based on the aspirations and necessities as factors to motivate employees. The process theories concentrate on processes, such as the psychological forces influencing motivation (Soares & Mosquera, 2019). The starting point is where employees are willing to act positively and gather expectations. Managers looking at implementing motivational techniques that can be realised on the ground are advised to opt for the cognitive and the process theories rather than the content theories. There is a variety of process theories, however, the best-known ones are expectancy theory, equity theory and goal-setting (Osabiya, 2015).

2.7.10 The goal-setting theory

Lotham and Locke (1979) have developed this theory, arguing that performance and motivation are higher when individuals have more difficult objectives in place that they are given feedback about (Audenaert et al., 2019). Developing organisational objectives is one of the significant roles of human resource specialists. Allowing employees to participate in setting the organisational goals will enhance their feeling of belonging, which approves higher targets through

comprehending the consequences and the processes. This can be performed efficiently by sharing feedback that will motivate employees to achieve higher targets (Nurun Nabi & Dip, 2017).

2.7.11 The equity and justice theory

This theory suggests that treating employees fairly would enhance their motivation; on the contrary, employees with no equity will be less motivated. This can be seen as important at the moral and ethical levels. When the theory was first introduced, it was trying to understand how the treatment of employees has an impact on their response to various situations (Biermann & Kalfagianni, 2020). Examining inequitable comparisons of employees' attitudes using the equity theory was expected to reflect the disagreement and the inequity influence on compensating and adjusting the behaviour. This theory puts the treatment of individuals among the strong factors that can influence the motivation and demotivation of employees (Osabiya, 2015). Equal treatment of employees is set to be the key to their motivation. In contrast, any unfair treatment of employees can cause demotivation among employees in the organisation. The theory of equity was studied in various contexts and by different authors covering education, gender, pay and other inequitable treatment within the organisation (Lee & Raschke, 2016).

2.7.12 The expectancy theory

The only possible way to achieve motivation is to relate work performance and the results meant to satisfy a specific need. This theory argues that motivation consists of three constructs: valence, expectancy and instrumentality (Lloyd & Mertens, 2018). The expectancy theory of motivation has been adopted in various studies, explaining the behaviour of employees toward their jobs. This theory was developed by Porter and Lawler (1968) to relate the expectancies and the motivation of employees. The expectancy theory elements were incorporated with the need for accomplishment and goal setting. A study conducted by Monge et al. (1992) explored the impact of group and information communication and the three motivational variables on innovation in the company. This work showed that employees' involvement is strongly related to the level of motivation forces (Nimri et al., 2015).

2.7.13 Cognitive theory

Cognitive theory has a close relation to the engagement theory developed by Kahn. The concept of this theory is based on the anticipations, beliefs and expectations of employees toward a future

event. Therefore, the behaviour is persistent and goal-oriented (Steers & Porter, 1991). Toman (1932) and Kahn (1990) have agreed that changes mainly influence engagement and positive behaviours in environmental beliefs rather than previous habits. Furthermore, other theories refer to motivation as unconscious behaviour rather than rational such as the instinct theory (Ozyilmaz et al., 2018).

There are various studies connecting motivation to engagement. However, there is a notable sensitivity between the two concepts. According to James (2002), engagement and motivation can have the same definition. However, there is still a difference between the two. While engagement amounts to involvement and learning, motivation is based on control and manipulation (Schoen, 2015).

On the other hand, organisations will control motivation through incentives, rewards and other benefits. Furthermore, he suggests that engaging will enhance the cordial connection among colleagues. At the same time, the engaged employee will perform and participate in the job without anticipating rewards from employers. Similarly, Armstrong (2009) stated that attaining a reward or something desired is the primary key and the only motive for employees to be motivated, whilst the case of employees' engagement is different (Mansaray, 2019). According to Smith (2012), there are a few distinctions when it comes to the concept of engagement and motivation; engagement is a state that can be achieved through avoiding a set of issues that enhance the employee's disengagement, such as unclear expectations, favouritism and the organisational hypocrisy (Suharno and Despinur, 2017). According to Smith, avoiding the mentioned problems will enhance the engagement of employees regardless of the reward system opted for by organisations. However, the motivation is related to the rewards opted for by organisations, such as benefits and bonuses, which ultimately might not boost engagement. CIPD (2012) has debated the phenomenon, arguing that engaged employees go far beyond job satisfaction and motivation (McManus & Mosca, 2015). At the same time, it can be addressed as a commitment toward the colleague and organisation. In addition, motivation is seen as a one-way concept from the point of view of organisations looking for methods to motivate their employees; employee engagement is seen as a psychological contract between employees and the organisation that represents the obligations between the two parts (McManus & Mosca, 2015).

Lee and Lee (2012), of the Aston University Business School, stated that the level of employees' engagement is not necessarily related to their motivation, and the level of employees' motivation

does not represent their engagement in the organisation (Latta & Fait, 2016). In the case of employee engagement, the motivation level can vary from one employee to another. At the same time, their type of motivation and their orientation can be different. This distinction is not covered by engagement theories (Osabiya, 2015). It can be said that intrinsic motivation is the closest to engagement. in which employees share the enjoyment and the inherent in performing jobs.

On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is based on actions meant to lead to different outcomes, such as a performance bonus that is different to the theories of engagement. Engagement and intrinsic motivation share various similarities, such as that the concept is based on creating an engaging environment to enhance employees' enjoyment while performing their jobs (Okpu & Kpakol, 2018). However, this may not always be the case, as organisations can provide the right environment and features that boost the employees' motivation. However, employees may still not feel motivated or engaged in the organisation's activities (Abah & Nwokwu, 2016). For extrinsic motivation, employees could be willing to perform their jobs due to the anticipation of a reward. More specifically, extrinsic employees could be seen as not engaged as, according to Elewa (2013, p. 37), motivation could be connected to engagement on individual expectancy and satisfaction parameters (Victor & Hoole, 2017).

2.8 Gig workers' engagement challenges

Engaging gig workers has been defined by various researchers and practitioners as a beneficial concept that can help businesses enhance the overall performance of the business as well as boost individual involvement and satisfaction with the company, which will decrease turnover, increase productivity and many other benefits for both employees and employers (Dey et al., 2022). On the other hand, management may face several challenges in engaging the gig workers, which are crucial to be determined by the front-line management to surpass those challenges and facilitate the engagement of gig workers (Kuhn et al., 2021). When identifying the factors that drive gig workers' engagement to promote organisational performance, the multifaceted, broad and complicated idea of engagement poses numerous difficulties for researchers and practitioners (Roy & Shrivastava, 2020). The amount of effort that employees choose to make depends on how they interpret work relationships within the context of personal significance, which is stated as "having a purpose and striving towards a goal or goals" and "making sense, order, or coherence out of one's existence". Outside forces or points of engagement include the following.

2.8.1 Lack of understanding of engagement

The front-line management contribution to fostering a healthy workplace culture is essential, and research has shown that managers have the most significant influence on employees' attitudes and behaviours (Huo et al., 2020). Nonetheless, managers' efforts appear to have been focused on the wrong places without knowing the "locus of engagement" or what workers are involved with (Rockmann et al., 2018). Notably, the nature of gig workers' employment limits contact between gig workers and the management, leaving very little information for management regarding the gig workers, which may not be enough for them to draw a clear picture of how to engage them efficiently (Kuhn et al., 2021). Furthermore, issues occur because, as Manion (2005) emphasises, managers find it much harder to motivate employees when their attention is diverted to needs unrelated to their jobs. This may prevent the front-line management from having a clear understanding and approach to engaging gig workers (Huo et al., 2020).

2.8.2 Understanding gig worker disengagement

Employee disengagement, specifically the physical, cognitive or emotional retreat of workers throughout role performances, has been conceptualised by Kahn (1990) as a separation from work duties (Lemon & Palenchar, 2018). According to Allam (2017), employee disengagement is the act of employees showing an absence of passion, dedication or attention at work. The revolutionary writings of Kahn (1990), who differentiated disengagement from his viewpoint, serve as the foundation for the idea of disengagement (Allam, 2017). When personally disengaged, such workers become preoccupied with withdrawing from others and defending their ideal selves. They also display disconnected behaviours, such as emotional, physical and cognitive retreat and passivity when playing roles (Lemon & Palenchar, 2018). While engagement is regarded as a management technique, it aspires to drive people to go above and beyond in their performance in their roles and their interactions with others (Rofcanin et al., 2017). Employee disengagement can take many different forms, as shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Employee disengagement indicators

Unwillingness to be part of the problem-solving process
Shows lack of attitude to the values of the business
Shows lack of loyalty to the business
Shows lack of interest in improving productivity

Does not go the extra mile beyond the stipulated organisational standards
Spends the minimum possible effort to accomplish tasks
Shows no enthusiasm or interest for the job with lack of commitment
Lacks connection to management, colleagues and organisation
Has a high level of absenteeism and presenteeism
Shows willingness to leave the company

Sources: Aslam et al. (2018), Allam (2017), Govindarajo et al. (2014).

Table 2 lists the signs of employees' disengagement. As per Allam (2017), disengaged employees detach from the company with a solid inclination to quit. Following Shuck et al. (2011), disengaged workers commonly exhibit attitudes and behaviours that negatively affect providing good customer service (2019). Based on Aslam et al. (2018), managerial activities such as unjust acts, actions that go above and beyond the call of duty, high workload and organisational inequity are among the leading causes of employee disengagement (Aslam et al., 2018). According to Shuck et al. (2011), unfavourable environmental and individual factors cause workers to disengage. The environment is regarded to incorporate people, physical area and organisational climate, whereas personal variables involve one's character, physical features, and emotions. Employee disengagement occurs when the components mentioned in these factors are unfavourable (Lee et al., 2020). The pressures of the twenty-first century are tremendous, and the nature of employment is changing quickly. As seen by reports, the dilemma for HRM practice is exacerbating due to technological progressions and elevated competition, which has significantly impacted how work is arranged (ILO, 2019; Hayter, 2015; Stone & Deadrick, 2015). Employment and work have become more unstable (Robinson et al., 2019; Hyman & Grumbell-McCormick, 2017). When an organisation is under stress, employee disengagement may worsen. However, the HRM field cannot afford to lose its emphasis on people (Marchington, 2015).

The problems identified by Blessing White (2008) as being of the most significant concern throughout the entire study are that managers are ineffective in recognising and rewarding accomplishments and in stimulating the use of employees' abilities (Beltrán-Martín & Boullusar, 2018). This supports the claim made by Robinson et al. (2007) that line management may not directly affect levels of engagement but instead functions as a sub-driver impacting variables like feeling cherished that immediately affect levels of perceived engagement (Lee et al., 2020).

Managers perform an essential role in cultivating engagement by allowing employees to feel engaged and appreciated in their work while providing them with liberty and assistance. This is

further discussed in the research of Saks (2008), who used the demands–resource approach (Demourouti et al., 2001) to analyse the factors that influence involvement (McManus & Mosca, 2015). As shown by Saks, employees are most involved at work when job expectations are minimal (such as job security and non-demanding workloads) and job resources are provided (i.e., elements that support work aspirations and encourage personal growth) (Jabagi et al., 2019). Defective managerial strategies that result in heavy workload, job insecurity and role vagueness operate as obstacles to engagement, whilst factors like autonomy, assistance from managers and co-workers, and insightful feedback enhance engagement (McManus & Mosca, 2015).

Another aspect claimed to affect disengagement is a person's availability at work. Engagement declines as access increases. According to research by May et al. (2004), time invested engaging in activities apart from work is a predictor of reduced availability scores. They contend that because people can only dedicate so much of themselves to their numerous responsibilities, those with many obligations outside of work may find it more difficult to be engaged than other workers (Anthony-McMann et al., 2017).

Evidence showing a connection between day-level engagement and proactive behaviour and how well employees recuperate from their previous day's work over break favours this focus on scarce resources (Ouyang et al., 2019). Workers who do not occasionally "unwind" tend to find indulging harder and harder. In order for workers to be capable of integrating their work to the utmost, it is crucial to ensure that they have a sensible work-life equilibrium and are in good health.

Gig workers' degree of involvement is affected by the nature of their employment, which is consistent with several interpretations of engagement. Employment that is tough, diversified and uses both old and new talents has been emphasized in many writings (Latta & Fait, 2016). For the employee, the task must be considered inventive and thrilling. Additionally, workers need to believe that the effort they are conducting matters to them and others. This is an essential factor that is mentioned in both academic and professional literature (Altehbah et al., 2019).

2.9 The conceptual framework and research theories

Most studies regarding employee engagement have focused on traditional employees (Bakker & Schuafeli, 2008; MayetaI, 2004; Saks, 2006). Shuck (2010) stated that not all businesses could come under a single system of management of an organisation. Furthermore, he argued that the business level of interaction among business members and the size of businesses could determine

the complexity and the variation of the organisational activities (Pepra-Mensah & Kyeremeh, 2018). This research is based on targeting engagement among the gig workers, presuming that the engagement is a social exchange outcome in the restaurant sector (Aktar & Pangil, 2017). Despite a large number of studies investigating the drivers of employee engagement in various sectors, businesses and countries, at the present time, limited studies have been conducted on gig workers and the restaurant sector, areas considered highly uncertain, and employees are less committed, involved and engaged. Although the gig economy is growing dramatically in the restaurant sector, there is still a constant increase in demand to investigate the issues highlighted by the emergence of the gig economy, including organisational, covering productivity and engagement alongside many other managerial functions (Pepra-Mensah & Kyeremeh, 2018). While no prior studies focus on gig workers' engagement in the restaurant sector, this research, to the researcher's knowledge, is the first to explore the leadership functions driving gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector (Aktar & Pangil, 2017).

2.9.1 Research theories

2.9.1.1 Job demands and resources: an engagement perspective.

The study findings stated that the JD-R is a valuable model that can be utilised to comprehend engagement and its fundamental motivational procedures. The JD-R model is one of researchers' most cited and famous models for exploring engagement. The JD-R model was first developed to overcome the deficiency of the job-control-support models and the demand-control models. Furthermore, this model has covered personal and relational resources, including leadership (Schaufeli, 2017). Therefore, the JD-R model was developed to overreach models with various occupations and risks.

Furthermore, this model aims to construct job characteristics into job demands and resources to define the basic health breakage procedure that drives burnout and motivation to drive engagement (Borst et al., 2019). According to Demerouti and Bakker (2011), job demands refer to the aspects that instruct psychological or physical skills and effort related to psychological costs. On the other hand, job resources refer to the aspects that enhance the accomplishment of job goals, inspire personal development and decrease the potential cost of job demands (Schaufeli, 2017). According to Bakker et al. (2007), various social, organisational, physical and psychological aspects are covered under job demands and resources. Furthermore, the job resources are related to the employees' intrinsic motivation, meeting their basic needs of competence and autonomy (Metin et

al., 2016). Accordingly, the JD-R model is a method that allows the organisation of the motivational procedure.

Moreover, if the job resources have motivational potential, excellent performance and high work engagement can be accomplished. To be more specific, job resources can play an intrinsic motivational role through promoting the growth of employees, learning and development and an extrinsic role through accomplishing the job goals. Furthermore, the model has included personal resources to support work engagement (Borst et al., 2019).

The JD-R model has grown in popularity among researchers. However, various drawbacks are associated with the application of the model. De Braine and Roodt (2011) stated that oversimplifying the health impairment process and motivation are among the drawbacks of the model. In addition, not considering the neutral impact is seen as one of the failures of the JD-R model (Metin et al., 2016).

The application of the J-DR model to research

The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) theory, initially introduced by Demerouti et al. (2001), offers a robust conceptual framework for understanding the intricacies of employee engagement within the gig economy, particularly in the restaurant industry. This theory posits that factors influencing work-related well-being and engagement can be comprehensively understood through the interaction of two pivotal categories: job demands and job resources (Borst et al., 2019).

Job demands

For gig workers in the restaurant industry, job demands encompass unique characteristics such as irregular working hours, high task variability, and potential job insecurity. These specific demands associated with gig employment can significantly affect employees' engagement and well-being (Bakker et al., 2007). The JD-R theory provides a framework for analysing how these demands may exert a negative impact on the engagement of gig workers, offering insights into the dynamics between job demands and employee well-being within the context of the gig economy (Metin et al., 2016).

Job resources

On the other hand, job resources for gig workers in the restaurant industry may include opportunities for skill development, accessibility to training programs, and managerial support. According to the JD-R theory, managers can positively influence the engagement levels of gig workers and foster a more fulfilling and productive work environment by recognizing and

optimizing these resources. Identifying and enhancing job resources can contribute to the overall well-being and engagement of gig workers within the gig economy context (Schaufeli, 2017).

Leadership functions as resources

The JD-R framework provides a lens through which we can view leadership functions such as motivation, communication, and collaboration as essential resources. Efficient communication and collaboration function as social and organizational resources, while motivation serves as a positive psychological resource. Frontline management, aiming to enhance gig workers' engagement, can strategically leverage these resources according to the JD-R theory. By recognizing the significance of these leadership functions as resources, management can create a work environment that fosters higher engagement levels among gig workers in the restaurant industry (Demerouti and Bakker, 2011),.

Motivation as a driver

Motivation, as a pivotal leadership function, aligns well with the JD-R theory by acting as a resource to alleviate job demands and enhance engagement. The inherent challenges of gig employment can be mitigated by offering acknowledgment, intrinsic rewards, and a sense of purpose to motivate workers, ultimately contributing to increased staff engagement. This integration of motivational strategies within the JD-R framework provides a comprehensive approach for frontline management in the restaurant industry to address the unique demands of gig workers and foster a more engaged workforce (Borst et al., 2019).

Communication as a resources

Effective communication, as an additional leadership function, functions as a resource within the JD-R theory, facilitating a sense of connection and clarifying job expectations. Recognizing the significance of communication as a resource that acts as a buffer against job demands, the JD-R framework emphasizes its role in enhancing job satisfaction and engagement among gig workers. This underscores the critical role of communication strategies employed by frontline management in creating a supportive work environment for gig workers in the restaurant industry (Schaufeli, 2017).

Collaboration as a resource

Within the JD-R framework, collaboration serves as an organizational resource and a collaborative leadership function. By fostering teamwork and collaboration among gig workers, frontline management can create a positive work environment that functions as a resource, helping to mitigate the challenges inherent in the episodic nature of gig work. This underscores the

importance of collaborative efforts in enhancing the engagement and well-being of gig workers within the restaurant industry (Schaufeli, 2017).

Benefits of using JD-R Theory

The primary advantage of employing the JD-R theory in studies on the engagement of gig workers lies in its comprehensive and dual-focused methodology. This theory provides a detailed examination of the work environment by systematically identifying both job demands and resources. Such a holistic approach allows for targeted interventions aimed at optimizing engagement levels. The application of JD-R theory offers valuable insights into crafting strategies that find a balance between resources that enhance workers' well-being and the unique demands associated with gig employment

Limitations of JD-R Theory

However, it's crucial to acknowledge the limitations of the JD-R theory. The framework has the potential to oversimplify the intricate dynamics of gig labour, potentially overlooking subtle nuances that are particularly relevant to the restaurant sector. Additionally, it may not fully capture the evolving nature of gig employment and the rapid impact of technology on the industry (Schaufeli, 2017).

Justification for JD-R in gig workers' engagement

The empirical robustness and applicability of the JD-R theory to contemporary organizational contexts serve as the basis for its implementation. Restaurant gig labour presents unique opportunities and challenges, and the JD-R theory's focus on maintaining a balance between demands and resources aligns well with the multifaceted nature of gig work. Its capacity to guide practical interventions for frontline management to enhance engagement in this specific employment context emphasizes its relevance (Borst et al., 2019).

In conclusion, the Job Demands-Resources theory offers a valuable framework for researching and understanding the engagement of gig workers in the restaurant industry. Frontline management can effectively address the challenges presented by gig employment and cultivate an environment that promotes greater engagement and well-being by utilizing leadership functions as resources, specifically motivation, communication, and collaboration. The JD-R theory provides a strong foundation for empirical research and practical ideas to optimize the engagement of gig workers in the restaurant sector, even with its acknowledged limitations (Metin et al., 2016).

2.9.1.2 Social Exchange Theory

This theory aims to explore the intrinsic and extrinsic rewards that are received by individuals in return for accomplishing a requested job or service (Emerson, 1981, cited in Nunkoo, 2016). The two rewards can differ in their forms as an intrinsic reward is related to gratitude, love and pride. While extrinsic rewards come in the form of physical, performance or financial (Paraskevaidis & Andriotis, 2017). In the same line, Ritzer (2010) affirms that social exchange is based on one providing a beneficial act in return for a reward or compensation. Furthermore, Nunkoo (2016) asserts that the outcome is strongly related to the exchange process that increases the valued results and decreases the antagonistic outcomes (Cook, Molm, & Yamagishi, 1993, cited in Nunkoo, 2016).

Social Exchange Theory (SET) is linked to the JD-R model, highlighting the importance of the necessary resources for the employees to accomplish their jobs no matter how much they were paid to get the job done. According to Nunkoo (2016), support from management is necessary for both extrinsic and intrinsic individuals to accomplish the job. Therefore, not paying employees well enough will negatively impact their motivation with the essential resources for employees to be more productive and accomplish their tasks (Borst et al., 2019).

The scholar community briefly explored the implication of the social exchange relationship on employees' engagement (Macey & Schiender, 2008; Saks, 2006; Zigrani, 2009). According to the outcomes gathered from the research of Saks (2006), there are various predictor variables, such as fairness and job characteristics, that can enhance engagement development leading to higher commitment and involvement (Nunkoo, 2016).

Various conceptual and theoretical spaces were reviewed in the literature studies, including several employee engagement facets. Various scholars have contributed to the development of a variety of theories, such as Kahn (1990), Maslach et al. (2001), Schaufeli and Bakker (2003) and Saks (2006). However, this research was in the same line as the Saks approach of engagement, highlighting the human beings' multifaceted experiences, considering the behaviours, thoughts and emotions that influence the result of gig workers at restaurants (Sun & Bunchapattanasakda, 2016).

In the same line, clear comprehension of the SET can help the development of a theoretical foundation for the all-engagement models, such as the drivers of the engagement challenges based on an exchange of socio-emotional and economic resources about the rules of SET. Therefore, restaurants providing those resources to gig workers will enhance the urge among the gig workers

to repay. The lack of those resources can enhance disengagement among the gig workers allowing them to withdraw (Cropanzano et al., 2017). Therefore, the socio-emotional resources are strongly contingent on the amount of the emotional, behavioural and intellectual resources (Jung & Takeuchi, 2019). This model examined gig workers in the UK restaurant sector. In terms of the study, the research explored gig workers' drivers related to the leadership functions, which the front-line management can use to enhance gig workers' engagement. The outcomes derived from the research highlighted various leadership functions that showed the front-line management employed positive results to engage gig workers. The framework consists of nine focal constructs derived from the research questions and the literature review (Engen & Magnusson, 2015).

The application of the SET theory in the research

The Social Exchange Theory (SET), originating from the work of Homans (1958) and further developed by Blau (1964), serves as an effective framework for understanding the social dynamics and interactions within job relationships. In the context of gig workers in the restaurant industry, applying SET to analyse the reciprocal exchanges between employees and managers underscores the benefits for both parties and the impact on employee engagement (Engen & Magnusson, 2015).

Reciprocal exchanges

In accordance with the Social Exchange Theory, individuals engage in social exchanges with the expectation of receiving something in return. Within the gig economy, factors such as contributions, rewards, and perceived fairness play pivotal roles in the exchanges between gig workers and restaurant managers. Understanding and enhancing engagement necessitate a thorough comprehension of these reciprocal interactions (Engen & Magnusson, 2015).

Leadership functions as exchanges

Within the Social Exchange Theory (SET) framework, social exchanges involve the integration of leadership functions such as motivation, communication, and collaboration. The engagement levels of gig workers are influenced by managers who effectively motivate, engage in open communication, and promote collaboration. These leadership functions are perceived as contributing positively to the social exchange, thereby impacting the engagement of gig workers (Cropanzano et al., 2017).

Motivation as exchange currency

Within the Social Exchange Theory (SET), motivation functions as a form of currency in social exchanges. Managers' contributions to the exchange are perceived as motivational leadership functions, such as providing recognition and intrinsic rewards. When gig workers observe these

motivational initiatives, they tend to respond by increasing their engagement. This establishes a positive cycle of reciprocity within the social exchange (Jung & Takeuchi, 2019).

Communication as Information Exchange

In the framework of the Social Exchange Theory (SET), effective communication is regarded as an information exchange. Managers who communicate clearly and openly contribute to a positive social exchange, fostering commitment and trust between gig workers. Conversely, insufficient communication may lead to the breakdown of the exchange, potentially impacting engagement (Sun & Bunchapattanasakda, 2016).

Collaboration as cooperative exchange

Within the Social Exchange Theory (SET), collaboration is considered a cooperative exchange. Managers who promote collaboration and teamwork contribute to the development of a sense of community and shared goals, fostering a positive social exchange. Engaged gig workers are more likely to actively participate in collaborative efforts, thereby enhancing organizational success (Nunkoo, 2016).

Benefits of using SET

There are several advantages to utilizing Social Exchange Theory in studies focusing on the engagement of gig workers. It offers a sophisticated perspective on the social dynamics occurring between managers and gig workers, emphasizing the significance of reciprocal exchanges in fostering engagement. The quality of social exchanges is the focal point of SET, providing valuable insights into managerial practices that may enhance engagement ties (Nunkoo, 2016).

Limitations of SET:

The presumption of rational decision-making and the potential oversimplification of the complexity of social exchanges constitute two limitations of SET. Conventional SET may not adequately capture the intricacies presented by the gig economy, given its unique challenges and transient nature. Furthermore, the emotional and subjective aspects of engagement may not align seamlessly with the theory's emphasis on logic (Saks, 2006).

Justification for SET in the engagement of gig workers

The utilization of Social Exchange Theory is warranted by its ability to illuminate the reciprocal interactions and social dynamics inherent in engagements within the gig economy. The restaurant industry, characterized by short-term commitments and unique job structures, aligns well with SET's focus on the interplay between rewards and contributions. Through the application of SET,

the study identifies intricate social exchanges that enhance engagement and informs practical interventions (Borst et al., 2019).

In conclusion, Social Exchange Theory offers an insightful perspective for analyzing and enhancing the engagement of gig workers in the restaurant industry. Motivation, communication, and collaboration emerge as pivotal elements in the reciprocal exchanges between gig workers and managers. While SET presents both advantages and limitations, it furnishes valuable insights into the social dynamics shaping engagement, thereby advancing our understanding of the gig economy workforce in the restaurant sector (Paraskevaïdis & Andriotis, 2017)

2.9.2 The conceptual framework

Figure 1: The conceptual framework

Sources: developed by the researcher

The gig economy and the labour market

The characteristics of the labour market in the restaurant industry have undergone significant changes with the emergence of the gig economy, presenting both opportunities and obstacles. Historically characterised by stable, long-term employment, the restaurant industry has observed a discernible trend towards gig-based arrangements facilitated by online platforms (Shin et al, 2021). The increasing popularity of food delivery applications and virtual marketplaces connecting consumers with nearby eateries and freelance delivery personnel exemplifies this transformation.

In this context, the gig economy has provided individuals with an alternative means of participating in the restaurant industry without adhering to conventional full-time employment (Lobel, 2017). Recruiting practices within the restaurant sector are significantly influenced by the gig economy procedures, marking a noteworthy impact on the labour market. Restaurants increasingly rely on gig workers for food transportation, allowing them to reach a broader customer base without the financial burden of maintaining an expensive delivery fleet (Watson et al., 2021). These shifts in recruitment strategies contribute to a more adaptable and readily available workforce, aligning with the evolving demands of both employees and consumers in the digital age. However, despite the advantages of cost efficiency and flexibility offered by the gig economy, it introduces drawbacks such as job insecurity, inadequate benefits and the potential exploitation of gig workers. The trend toward gig-based employment arrangements replacing traditional employment relationships, which are supported by regulatory frameworks and employee protections, raises concerns about the overall well-being of workers in the restaurant industry (Broderick, 2018). Academics and decision-makers grapple with understanding the broader implications of the gig economy as it continues to redefine the dynamics of work within the restaurant industry. This field of study scrutinises its impact on workers' rights, the value of employment and the overall stability of the labour market in restaurants (Vallas & Schor, 2020). Scholars contribute crucial insights into job protocols, regulatory frameworks and the potential trajectory of employment in the dynamic restaurant business by conducting thorough analyses of the interplay between the gig economy and the restaurant sector (Goods et al., 2019).

Hiring and food delivery apps and gig workers' engagement

The dynamics of how gig workers engage with employment in the restaurant industry have undergone significant changes due to the integration of food delivery and recruitment applications within the gig economy (Rani & Furrer, 2021). Acting as intermediaries, these online marketplaces play a crucial role in connecting patrons and eateries. In addition to transforming the employment process, the accessibility and user-friendly nature of these applications have profoundly influenced the perspective and participation of gig workers (Chetan et al., 2019).

A more convenient and effective method for gig workers to secure employment is through staffing applications in the food industry. Traditional recruiting processes have been surpassed by digital methods, granting gig workers immediate access to a broader range of job listings, the capacity to negotiate terms and the opportunity to find employment swiftly (Bi et al., 2021). This increased

accessibility positively influences gig workers' levels of engagement, concurrently enhancing their sense of empowerment and professional fulfilment (Cha & Seo, 2020).

The impact on gig workers' engagement has been exacerbated by food delivery applications, a substantial element of gig economy platforms in the restaurant industry. These applications facilitate direct communication between gig workers and clients, allowing real-time interaction and feedback (Laitinen, 2021). The flexibility to choose delivery tasks and the immediacy of engagement enhance gig workers' sense of independence and control, consequently fostering their dedication to the gig and overall job satisfaction (Altenried, 2021).

Despite their advantages, these applications have a nuanced impact on gig workers' engagement. The gig economy, centred around short, task-based engagements, may induce feelings of insecurity and unpredictability among labourers (Finn, 2020). The fluctuating nature of gig workers' participation is influenced by the continual need to secure new engagements and the absence of traditional job security. Additionally, the reliance on user feedback and ratings in these applications introduces performance-oriented elements that could affect gig workers' overall job satisfaction and engagement (Lehdonvirta, 2018).

In conclusion, the gig economy within the restaurant industry encompasses both recruiting and food delivery applications, exerting a substantial impact on the engagement of gig workers. Scholars and industry stakeholders are tasked with conducting thorough investigations into the intricate influence on gig workers' perspectives on work and formulating measures to enhance overall involvement in the expanding gig economy. This remains a crucial endeavour, even as these applications offer unparalleled convenience and flexibility (Shet & Pereira, 2021).

The gig economy and hiring and food delivery apps.

The gig economy, recruiting and food delivery applications are interconnected elements, mutually influencing and bolstering each other's ascent in the dynamic contemporary labour market (Kuhn, 2021). The rapid and flexible labour arrangements emblematic of the gig economy have experienced significant growth, with staffing and food delivery apps playing pivotal roles in fostering the evolution and expansion of this economic model (Charlton & Castillo, 2021). Within the gig economy, hiring apps have emerged as efficient tools for connecting job seekers and recruiters across various industries, including the restaurant sector (Elias et al., 2016). These platforms enable companies to identify and engage with gig workers more expeditiously by simplifying the hiring process (Gandhi et al., 2018). The accessibility and immediacy of these

applications' availability benefit the gig economy by facilitating the rapid matching of job opportunities with a diverse pool of gig workers, thereby creating a more adaptable and responsive labour market (Barratt et al., 2020).

Conversely, the emergence of the gig economy has paved the way for the development and widespread adoption of food delivery applications, establishing a symbiotic relationship between the two (Duggan et al., 2021). Food delivery services leverage a vast network of independent contractors to fulfil customers' orders, capitalising on the flexible and on-demand nature of gig work. The gig economy provides an essential labour force for delivering prompt and efficient food services through these apps (Williams et al., 2021). This mutually beneficial association contributes to the continual advancement of both food delivery applications and the gig economy (Berg & Kim, 2018). Moreover, the fusion of food delivery and employment applications has not only fuelled the expansion of the gig economy but also transformed the dynamics of the traditional employer–employee relationship. Facilitated by these applications, the gig economy advocates for an autonomous, digitally connected job framework that challenges conventional notions of work arrangements (Tepayakul & Rinthaisong, 2018). Through these platforms, gig workers are engaged as independent contractors benefiting from the autonomy and flexibility inherent in gig economy work. Their reliance on the digital infrastructure provided by food delivery and hiring apps further exemplifies the evolving nature of contemporary employment (Williams et al., 2021).

To sum up, the gig economy and food delivery and hiring apps share a symbiotic relationship marked by reciprocal enhancement of each other's progress. These digital platforms are reshaping the foundations of employment and the labour market, likely exerting a significant influence on the evolution of the gig economy in the years ahead and shaping how individuals engage with and impact the broader economy (Kuhn, 2021).

Hiring and food delivery apps and the labour market

The landscape of employment trends has undergone a profound transformation with the emergence and widespread adoption of recruiting and food delivery apps, significantly reshaping the dynamics of the labour market within the restaurant industry. Conventional full-time jobs in the food business have experienced a notable shift as an increasing number of workers opt to leverage gig opportunities facilitated by these digital platforms (Williams et al., 2021). With the proliferation of applications such as Just Eat, Deliveroo and Uber Eats, individuals now have an

alternative to traditional job arrangements allowing them to choose when, where and how much they work (Berg & Kim, 2018).

Restaurants can now access a broader pool of qualified employees, thanks to the streamlining of the recruiting process facilitated by hiring applications. These platforms provide businesses with a straightforward and efficient means to connect with gig workers, addressing their short-term staffing needs and adapting to fluctuating demand. Gig workers benefit by having more employment opportunities and the chance to engage with various platforms, thereby expanding their sources of income (Chetan et al., 2019).

Workplace dynamics have undergone a transformation due to mutually advantageous connections among food delivery apps, hiring platforms and the labour market. Driven by the freedom and independence offered by these platforms, a considerable number of traditional full-time restaurant staff have transitioned to gig labour (Rani & Furrer, 2021). Consequently, the gig economy has become a crucial element of the broader labour market landscape, disrupting conventional job structures and fostering a more flexible and decentralised approach to work (Bi et al., 2021). However, challenges accompany this shift. Employees may experience job insecurity due to the gig economy's focus on temporary, task-based engagements facilitated through applications. Concerns about the long-term sustainability and well-being of gig workers arise from an absence of stable job benefits such as healthcare and pensions. Additionally, discussions around fair wages, labour rights and the necessity for legal frameworks to protect workers in this evolving environment have been prompted by the surge in gig employment through applications (Cha & Seo, 2020).

In conclusion, recruiting and food delivery apps have fundamentally altered the landscape of the labour market in the restaurant industry, influencing choices made by both employees and employers. While these applications offer convenience and flexibility, concerns related to job security and workers' rights underscore the necessity for ongoing discussions and regulatory measures to ensure a fair and sustainable gig economy within the restaurant sector (Berg & Kim, 2018).

Front-line management and gig workers' engagement

Front-line management plays a crucial role in efficiently engaging gig workers in the restaurant industry, emphasising key areas such as, communication, motivation, learning and development and collaboration (Savarimuthu & Rachel, 2017). Given the dynamic nature of gig employment,

front-line managers must be proactive and adaptable to cultivate a positive and efficient working environment (Agarwal & Gupta, 2018).

The ability of front-line managers to engage gig workers is heavily reliant on effective communication. Clear and transparent communication channels facilitate the transmission of tasks, expectations and performance evaluations (Liu et al., 2020). Front-line managers should leverage digital tools and platforms to facilitate smooth discourse, ensuring that gig workers are well-informed and aligned with company objectives (Sharma et al., 2016). Open channels of communication, consistent updates and real-time feedback contribute to gig workers feeling understood and valued within the team (Paulas & Kenworthy, 2019).

Motivation is another crucial strategy employed by front-line management to enhance the engagement of gig workers. Recognising and valuing the contributions made by gig workers can significantly boost morale and increase job satisfaction (EY, 2020). Front-line managers should employ performance-based rewards, acknowledge achievement and cultivate a positive work environment that specifically recognises the efforts of gig workers as motivational techniques tailored to the gig economy (Poortman, 2018). This approach contributes to a more motivated and satisfied gig workforce.

Front-line management roles in the restaurant industry should offer opportunities for learning and development (Ruggieri et al., 2016). Providing avenues for skill development and professional advancement can enhance the overall job satisfaction of gig workers, even in temporary engagements. Through training programmes, workshops and resources, front-line managers can support ongoing education, enabling gig workers to grow professionally and acquire new skills (Lives, 2017). This investment in their development not only benefits the individual gig worker but also contributes to a more skilled and motivated workforce within the gig economy (Wilkie, 2013).

Collaboration plays a significant role in the engagement of gig workers and is a crucial element of front-line management. Despite the temporary nature of their assignments, front-line managers must foster a spirit of cooperation and teamwork among gig workers (Ruck et al., 2017). Encouraging gig workers to see themselves as integral parts of the larger team by creating a welcoming and inclusive work environment promotes engagement and contributes to a positive work culture (Paulas & Kenworthy, 2019). This sense of belonging can enhance the overall experience for gig workers and positively impact their motivation and commitment EY (2020).

In summary, front-line management in the restaurant industry plays a critical role in effectively engaging gig workers. By prioritising collaboration, learning and development opportunities, motivation and clear communication, front-line managers can cultivate a work environment that enhances the engagement and satisfaction of gig workers. This approach proves beneficial for both the workers and the restaurant businesses (Ruggieri et al., 2016).

Core leadership functions and gig workers' engagement

Leadership functions play a significant role in shaping the engagement of gig workers in the restaurant industry. Core leadership functions, including effective communication, motivation and equitable treatment of in-house and gig workers, have a profound impact on the level of engagement within the workforce (Mone & London, 2018).

Communication stands out as a crucial leadership function with a direct impact on the engagement of gig workers (Welch, 2011). Leaders must establish clear and open channels of communication to convey expectations, provide guidance and foster a sense of community among gig workers. Leveraging digital platforms and tools for real-time updates and feedback enhances the effectiveness of communication (Kahn, 1990). The engagement of gig workers tends to be positively influenced when they feel well-informed and connected to the organisation's goals (Moletsane et al., 2019).

Motivation is another essential leadership function crucial for engaging gig workers. Leaders should adopt strategies that acknowledge and value the unique contributions made by gig workers (Kang & Sung, 2017). Establishing a healthy work atmosphere, providing performance incentives and acknowledging achievement all contribute to engaging gig workers. Effective motivational leadership ensures that gig workers are not only motivated to deliver their best work but also find satisfaction in their roles (Karanges et al., 2015).

Equitable treatment of both gig and in-house employees is a crucial leadership function that promotes diversity and fairness (Okpu & Kpakol, 2018). Leaders should establish procedures and policies ensuring impartial treatment for all, regardless of their work status. This includes providing both internal and external gig workers equal access to opportunities, benefits and recognition. Leaders demonstrating a commitment to equity cultivate a positive workplace and enhance employee engagement (Kulachai et al., 2018).

In summary, core leadership functions such as motivation, communication and fair treatment of both gig workers and in-house employees are critical factors that influence gig workers' engagement in the restaurant industry. Leaders prioritising these aspects cultivate a welcoming and inspiring workplace, ultimately enhancing employee and gig worker engagement and job satisfaction (Barhite, 2017).

Gig workers' perspectives on engagement

Due to the distinctive features of gig economy employment, gig workers bring a unique perspective to their engagement in the restaurant industry. Their perception of engagement revolves around job satisfaction, contentment and the ability to balance their personal and professional lives (Lobel, 2017), often seeking flexibility and independence. Gig workers commonly have the autonomy to determine their own work schedules and locations, a factor that can impact their willingness to engage in the restaurant industry, distinguishing it from typical full-time employment (Broderick, 2018).

Engagement among gig workers is closely tied to the nature of their employment and the level of autonomy they possess. In the gig economy, workers can accept multiple gigs simultaneously, granting them access to various opportunities and experiences (Shin et al, 2021). This autonomy contributes to their overall engagement and professional satisfaction. However, as gig workers may prioritise optimising earnings and achieving personal goals, they may exhibit less dedication to a single employer causing them to be less engaged while transitioning between jobs (Lobel, 2017).

The gig workers' willingness to engage is influenced by various factors such as equitable pay, transparent communication and a positive work environment. Gig workers often seek opportunities that align with their interests, skills and financial considerations. Restaurants are more likely to attract and retain engaged gig workers if they offer fair compensation, clear expectations and a work environment conducive to the gig workers (Mone & London, 2018).

The gig economy's employment structure, characterised by temporary engagement and limited job security, can impact gig workers' overall levels of engagement. While the flexibility is enticing, concerns about irregular income and a lack of benefits may make them less inclined to remain with a specific restaurant or job. Restaurants that address these issues and prioritise the well-being of gig workers tend to foster greater levels of engagement and loyalty (Kulachai et al., 2018).

In conclusion, gig workers' perspectives on engagement in the restaurant industry are multifaceted and influenced by factors such as the nature of their gigs, the level of flexibility and the overall

workplace environment. Restaurants can enhance engagement and cultivate positive relationships by being attentive and responsive to their specific needs and preferences. Understanding the complexities of the gig economy and addressing the unique considerations of gig workers can contribute to a more mutually beneficial relationship between restaurants and the gig workforce (Kang & Sung, 2017).

Challenges of gig workers engagement

Engaging gig workers into the restaurant industry poses various challenges due to the characteristics of gig labour and the management methods. One notable challenge is that gig workers may not exhibit the same level engagement (Kuhn et al., 2021). Given the temporary and flexible nature of gig work, employees might perceive their roles as transient, potentially leading to a lack of dedication compared to regular full-time positions (Dey et al., 2022). It becomes the management's responsibility to underscore the significance of gig workers' contributions to the overall performance of the restaurant and to assist them in developing a sense of purpose and commitment (Roy & Shrivastava, 2020).

Management can also face various challenges in establishing a coherent work environment for gig workers who are more autonomous while operating (Huo et al., 2020). Gig workers may find it more difficult to create lasting relationships due to the absence of regular engagement and team-building activities that are typically common in traditional employment environments. Creative management techniques can be adopted to address the challenges by fostering a sense of community among gig workers through digital communication platforms, frequent check-ins and virtual team-building exercises (Allam, 2017). Furthermore, the gig economy poses challenges for employees in the form of income unpredictability, a lack of benefits and an unclear professional trajectory (Rofcanin et al., 2017). These challenges may contribute to decreased engagement levels among gig workers. Addressing these concerns by offering competitive compensation, providing access to benefits and creating opportunities for professional growth and skill development can significantly enhance the engagement of gig workers (Robinson et al., 2019). Providing tangible support in these areas can contribute to a more positive and committed gig workforce in the restaurant industry (ILO, 2019). In summary, engaging gig workers in the restaurant industry comes with challenges related to both management practices and inherent characteristics of gig labour. To foster meaningful engagement in this dynamic and evolving employment landscape, a comprehensive approach is essential. This approach should encompass efficient management strategies, an understanding of the unique needs of gig workers and efforts to improve the overall gig work experience in order to address these challenges (Marchington, 2015).

Gig workers' engagement development

Boosting the engagement of gig workers in the restaurant industry requires a comprehensive strategy that addresses the aforementioned challenges. One crucial tactic is improving communication between management and gig workers (Kang & Sung, 2017). Candid and regular communication can help bridge the knowledge gap created by the decentralised nature of gig employment, ensuring that gig workers are well-informed about their responsibilities, expectations and the restaurant's ultimate goals. Regular virtual check-ins, feedback sessions and communication through digital platforms can foster a sense of community and purpose (Moletsane et al., 2019).

To maintain the engagement of gig workers, motivation is crucial and effective managers should strive to create an environment that fosters intrinsic motivation. Gig workers can feel more dedicated and prouder of their contributions when their efforts are acknowledged, even in temporary roles (Barhite, 2017). Managers can implement both monetary and non-monetary reward systems to recognise exceptional work and encourage sustained commitment. This approach, aligned with the notion of treating gig and in-house employees equally by promoting an inclusive atmosphere and celebrating shared achievements (Wilkie, 2013).

Opportunities for learning and development are crucial for gig workers to feel committed to their roles and motivated to positively impact the restaurant's performance. Management can facilitate ongoing learning by offering workshops on skill development, training programmes and online resources (Paulas & Kenworthy, 2019). By supporting the professional development of gig workers, managers not only enhance their skill sets but also demonstrate a commitment to their long-term growth, potentially fostering a more devoted and engaged gig workforce (ILO, 2019). Employing virtual team-building exercises and forums can foster collaboration even in decentralised gig employment situations (Huo et al., 2020). These initiatives provide gig workers with opportunities to connect with their peers, share experiences and collaborate to achieve the restaurant's objectives. Whether in a virtual or physical setting, cultivating a sense of community among gig workers reduces their feelings of isolation and enhances their commitment to the goals and values of the restaurant (Moletsane et al., 2019).

In conclusion, improving communication, encouraging intrinsic motivation, providing opportunities for learning and development and promoting teamwork are all crucial elements in enhancing the engagement of gig workers. By addressing these aspects, management can create an environment that attracts gig workers and encourages their sustained engagement, ultimately

contributing to the resilience and growth of the restaurant industry within the gig economy (Agarwal & Gupta, 2018)

2.10 Conclusion

In summary, this chapter has provided an overview of the historical evolution of the gig economy within the restaurant industry, tracing its emergence and dominance while reshaping the labour market in this sector and increasing its significance. Following this, the research delved into the crucial roles played by front-line management in the restaurant industry, recognizing their pivotal position in navigating the complexities of a gig-based workforce. Subsequently, the review explored the nuances of employee engagement within the context of the gig economy, emphasizing the drivers, which can be categorized under leadership functions, to enhance gig workers' engagement. The chapter also highlighted challenges encountered in implementing engagement among gig workers in the restaurant sector. As the narrative transitions from historical and managerial perspectives to the theoretical framework, it establishes that leadership functions can serve as instrumental drivers for boosting the engagement of gig workers, laying the foundation for the conceptual framework that incorporates related concepts and theories discussed in this chapter. The literature review chapter extensively explored various information sources to establish the foundation for this research. It considered previous literature alongside the current research aim, objectives, and questions to identify the most relevant literature. The chapter began by defining the gig economy, highlighting its major aspects, and outlining its impact on various sectors and industries. The transformation of the labour market due to the gig economy was discussed, emphasizing how traditional employment structures were disrupted. As the gig economy became the norm, it brought about significant changes and challenges for management across different industries. The restaurant sector, in particular, experienced a shift in the nature of employees and work conduct. This transformation posed new challenges for frontline management, who serve as the initial point of contact with gig workers. The roles and functions of frontline management gained increased importance, and this aspect was thoroughly explored in the literature covered in this chapter. The literature also delved into the realm of employee engagement and its drivers. Various sources were examined to identify the drivers of employee engagement, with a specific focus on leadership and its functions. Functions such as communication, motivation, and collaboration were discussed in detail, highlighting their crucial role in fostering employee engagement. Furthermore, the challenges associated with engaging gig

workers were explored, providing insights into the complexities faced by frontline management in this process. The literature review then transitioned to theories and the conceptual framework shaping the study, offering an in-depth discussion of these theoretical foundations. At the conclusion of this chapter, the research presented the conceptual framework, incorporating the theories employed in the study. The upcoming chapter will provide a detailed account of the methodology used for data collection in this research. These concepts contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics between the gig economy, hiring and food delivery apps, the labor market, leadership, and gig worker engagement, addressing the unique challenges posed by these phenomena. This understanding aims to facilitate the development of a comprehensive and effective approach for front-line management to engage gig workers in the restaurant sector.

Chapter 3: Research methodology

3.1 Introduction

The methodology is a research strategy aiming to set forth the ideal way to undertake research. It contains philosophical presumptions and a system of values, which help to form a comprehensive tolerance of the research questions and underpin the research methods selected (Singh, 2006). The research methodology is a necessary part of a thesis that aids the researcher in establishing consistency between the underlying philosophy and the selected techniques and tools (Chawla & Sodhi, 2011). Research methodology can be constructed in a variety of ways.

The research methodology commences by describing the main philosophy, the selected methods, approaches and strategies together with outlining the data collection methods, and sampling, which will be followed by the main procedures and techniques of gathering and analysing data (Novikov, 2013). The concept of the research methodology is based on calling attention to the series of actions that will be adopted and utilised to effectively analyse the research and acquire a trustworthy outcome (Baker, 2000). This chapter of the research aims to justify and elucidate the methodological foundation and the research design applied in response to the research questions of this study, as well as to experimentally endorse the proposed model (Jonker & Pennink, 2010).

3.1.1 Research Questions

Concerning the gaps in the literature discussed in Chapter 2, this research's key objective is to investigate how the emergence of the gig economy has developed a whole gig employment system that has challenged the management to apply their leadership functions to engage gig workers in the restaurant sector. Therefore, this research aims to answer five questions to get a clear overview of the highlighted research problem. The main research question is divided into detailed questions that will permit the researcher to study the causes and circumstances that have caused the main problem. The researcher has firstly reviewed the literature regarding the gig workers, gig economy, employee engagement, leadership and its functions that are considered drivers of gig workers' engagement in the restaurant sector, followed by understanding the core roles and functions that can drive and enhance employee engagement. Furthermore, to have more details regarding what enhances the engagement of employees, the researcher investigated the drivers for employees to engage with the challenges the managers faced while enhancing gig workers' engagement.

Ultimately, this research suggests and recommends to managers ways to improve their gig workers' engagement.

3.1.2 Introductory question

Question one: To what extent has the gig economy reshaped the labour market in the UK restaurant sector?

This question aims to explore the role of the gig economy and its elements such as gig workers, hiring and food delivery apps alongside many other aspects that have accompanied the phenomena and how they have influenced the labour market in the UK restaurant sector.

Question two: Which specific core responsibilities are employed by front-line management within the restaurant sector?

While the gig economy has been emerging rapidly in recent years, it has existed for some time impacting various businesses, sectors and functions in different ways. The restaurant sector is one of the most challenging sectors for front-line management due to the nature of the employees and the circumstances surrounding the industry. This question aims to explore the roles employed by front-line management in the restaurant sector.

Question three: What specific leadership functions serve as key drivers for employee engagement?

This question explores the drivers of employee engagement alongside the leadership functions while identifying which of these functions can be adopted as drivers to enhance gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector.

Question four: What challenges do management encounter when engaging gig workers in the UK restaurant sector?

The researcher introduced this question to examine the challenges facing leaders and managers while operating their functions in engaging gig workers.

Question five: How can front-line management leverage their core functions to enhance gig workers' engagement and efficiently address the challenges they face?

Regardless, the studies link many drivers to employee engagement. The researcher urges that leadership, and its roles and functions are the least covered by those research studies that have enhanced the choice of the research topic. It illustrates how the efficient usage of those functions will allow the restaurant management to get the best out of the gig workers who will work their magic in enhancing the overall operation and success of the business.

3.2 The research philosophy

Research philosophy, as defined by Bryman (2012), encompasses a set of beliefs that guides the investigation of reality. In addition, it can be seen as the underlying illustration of knowledge's nature. Research philosophies vary from one research study to another, deepening goals and objectives of the research as well as how effectively they can be deployed to accomplish those goals (Goddard & Melville, 2004). Selecting the appropriate research philosophy hinges on the type of knowledge being investigated in the study, which will assist the researcher in illustrating the research process assumptions and how efficiently will fit the opted methodology (Holden & Lynch, 2004). Saunders noted that research philosophy is an integral part of the research methodology due to its crucial role in creating and pointing out the most beneficial and suitable research methods that need to be fostered by the researcher. Additionally, research philosophy plays a crucial role in supporting researchers throughout the data collection process (Crossan, 2003). Furthermore, the research philosophy tools up researchers with a comprehensive set of methodologies, enabling them to select the most related ones; meanwhile, it assists researchers in designing their research approach (Mkansi & Acheampong, 2012).

3.2.1 Epistemology

According to Richards (2003), this area of philosophy generally refers to the assumptions made by the researcher regarding the nature and kind of knowledge through developing possible ways to discover the world. Crotty (1998) has seen epistemology as the ideal way to look at the world and make sense of it, which includes knowledge and what it entails, as well as its nature, legitimacy, possibility and scope. Likewise, with specific contrasts regarding the path of studying the social and the natural world. Bryman (2008) delineates epistemology as a matter related to the question of what is defined as possible knowledge in a discipline. Furthermore, Cohen et al. (2007) defined epistemology as assumptions about the very bases of knowledge and nature; on top of this, how this knowledge can be obtained and efficiently communicated to other individuals. For

instance, this study focuses on determining what leadership functions qualify as possible drivers of gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector. Moreover, the authors unveil how the nature of epistemological assumptions made or held regarding specific knowledge deeply leverages the way the social behaviour knowledge will be uncovered. The authors here refer to the decisions made by researchers while opting for the ideal methods for the research by relying on their epistemological assumptions. The researcher underscores how the suggested assumptions regarding the leadership function profoundly shape knowledge discovery about the behaviours and roles of front-line management in boosting the engagement of gig workers; this has influenced the methodological choices of the researcher (Al-Saadi, 2014). The researcher needs to play an observer role while developing natural science methods such as measuring and testing if the knowledge is seen as tangible, challenging and objective. On the other hand, if the knowledge is viewed as subjective, unique and personal, the researcher will not accept the procedures adopted by natural science and the greater involvement with their subjects (Grüne et al., 2010).

This branch of philosophy grapples with the fundamental questions of what acceptable knowledge is and how it can be achieved. To be more specific, it is based on responding to the questions starting with 'what' and 'how'. The current study is concerned with adopting this philosophy as the research questions all use what and how conditions, as per epistemology, many traits are considered as means of knowledge, such as faith, reason, perception, sensation and intuition (Williams, 2001). Three philosophical stances are often related to epistemology: critical realism, interpretivism and positivism. The research will go through each one of them to better understand epistemology (Al-Saadi, 2014).

Positivism and objectivism

Positivism is considered an epistemological position covering the significance of objectivity and evidence in finding the truth. According to Snape and Spencer (2003), the values and facts in positivism are very much independent, which allows researchers to conduct a free-value and objective enquiry. In other words, the researcher should avoid interfering with the research findings. In addition, positivist epistemology sees that all objects consist of meaningful realities and meaning, which are awaited to be determined by researchers (Crotty, 1998). This point of view simply means that meanings always exist along objectives. However, they are discovered alongside the recognition of those objectives. Also, the positivist paradigm always sees the truth as objective and static, which is objectified where people are studied. However, it can be discovered if it is approached optimally (Clarke, 2009). Discovering knowledge needs to be

approached properly, such as careful direct observation, which was proposed by a variety of positivist writers such as Francis Bacon and Isaac Newton. On the other hand, deduction from an abstract proposition is not considered by many writers as the best way to discover knowledge (Ormston et al., 2014). More specifically, objectivism originated from the consent of natural science as a paradigm to investigate human knowledge alongside employing similar means and methods in data collection and interpretations to those utilised in natural science, such as causal explanations, construct testing and modelling. To sum up, most knowledge about the world originates from experiences that will be derived through the senses. This led to considering phenomena that the sense can confirm as a piece of genuine knowledge (Bryman, 2008; Ormston et al., 2014; Wellington, 2000). Wellington (2000) stated that positivist knowledge is deemed value-free, objective, replicable and generalisable, which often allows positivism to be perceived as equivalent to the scientific method. Nevertheless, positivism has been subject to criticism for decades due to several drawbacks accompanied by the utilisation of this philosophy. The rejection of this epistemological position was based on the grounds that relying on observation as the only way to set rules and laws can be objected to by the fact that some onward observations can develop an exception to the current rules and laws (Ormston et al., 2014). This has developed another version of positivism that is known as post-positivism. This new version argues that testing propositions can be the right way to produce practical knowledge of the world rather than relying entirely on observation. In addition, the constructs should be generated initially from theories and then tested empirically against observations that refer to deductive reasoning. The post-positivist approach states that reality is an approximate determinant. At the same time, positivism sees that reality is accompanied by absolute accuracy (Ryan, 2018).

Interpretivism and constructionism

Many authors see interpretivism and constructionism as the opposite of what positivists and objectivists believe regarding knowledge and discovering the world. According to Bryman (2008), there are several methods to discover more about the world, such as our perceptions and interpretations rather than direct observation. Individuals' perceptions can be utilised efficiently to interpret what their senses tell them. Likewise, understanding can be a great source to learn more about the knowledge of the world which is derived from our reflections on events alongside but not only our experiences (Ormston et al., 2014). In clear opposition to the positivist tradition, the interpretivist approach asserts that understanding and exploring the social world of individuals involved in the study can be the ideal way to produce knowledge while concentrating on their interpretations and meanings (Hasan, 2016). For instance, social actors can socially construct

meanings that will help researchers develop a firm ground on which the research will be designed, and the methods used to gather data. The positivist tradition states that the research process will not have an impact on reality and that researchers need to be distanced from findings.

Interpretivism claims that researchers rely on participants' meanings and interpretations to develop their own (Hay, 2011). Moreover, the research process is mainly inductive, where researchers intend to use the gathered data to generate theories rather than testing existing ones. The interpretivism approach differs from constructionism, as the first believes that value-free research can be efficiently conducted as the values and facts are objectives (Parsons, 2010). More specifically, the researcher is seen as a part of the research and fully engaged, allowing their values and perspectives to influence their findings. To sum it up, according to Cohen et al. (2007), interpretivism is not an excellent way to study natural sciences. However, it is a suitable approach to studying the social world as social reality cannot be captured accurately due to various perceptions of reality (Ormston et al., 2014). It can be seen that both paradigms have their benefits and critics. However, selecting the most appropriate epistemology is mainly enhanced by the nature of the research, such as the research objectives and questions (Saunders et al., 2005).

Pragmatism

Pragmatism in research philosophy is based on the idea that research methods and knowledge value lies in their practical applicability (Legg & Hookway, 2008). It highlights the importance of choosing the most efficient approaches for research aiming to address particular, issues and objectives. In a management context, the pragmatist research philosophy is valuable where real-world application is important alongside the practical implications of the pragmatic philosophy (Shusterman, 2016).

The pragmatic viewpoint highlights how the study has practical applications. The research intends to offer actionable suggestions for corporate leaders aiming to improve their functions and increase the involvement of gig workers by fusing qualitative tales with quantitative data (James, 2020). This methodology corresponds with pragmatic philosophy's focus on generating practical understanding that may guide decisions in real-world situations (Bacon, 2012)

To conclude, the application of a pragmatic research philosophy provides a versatile and useful strategy in the investigation of leadership roles and the involvement of gig workers through the use of both qualitative and quantitative approaches. It enables researchers to produce insightful findings, fully comprehend the phenomenon, and add useful information to the domain (Simpson, 2018). Table 4 concludes the epistemological beliefs adopted by the researcher while conducting this study.

Table 3: Epistemological beliefs of the research

<i>Epistemological basis</i>	<i>Application to the study</i>
The researcher is quite familiar with the world, which also consists of an observable phenomena.	The effects of managers' and leaders' functions on enhancing gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector can be observed from the external realities.
Explore the impact of the managerial functions on enhancing the gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector.	This study attempts to figure out the relationships between the efficient utilisation of managerial functions and gig workers' engagement.
The process of understanding how GE has influenced the labour market in the restaurant sector and employee engagement. The gig workers' leadership-related functions will be included in the study.	The study is based on existing theories of GE and its impact on the labour market, the restaurant sector, the leadership functions and employee engagement which will be the starting point to conduct the research.

Source: developed by the researcher

Looking at Table 3, it can be seen that this research relies heavily on a pragmatist stance. However, the researcher believes that ontology, which is how nature and social reality are seen, can widely influence knowledge regarding social reality, known as epistemology (Fleetwood, 2005). As a result, it is crucially important to examine the ontological assumptions of this research.

3.2.2 Ontology

Ontology, as elucidated by Snape and Spencer (2003), delves into the fundamental nature of "what is" while exploring the essence of "being". This philosophical stance seeks to unravel what can be learned about the world, the structure of reality, and the nature of existence (Crotty, 1998). According to the SAGE online dictionary, ontology is defined as the concept of studying the existence of and analysing the relationship among various social aspects such as cultural norms and social structure. Also, the dictionary defines ontological issues as questions concerned about the existence of sorts of things in society.

Richards (2003) further refines the definition of ontology, framing it as the formulation of assumptions about the nature of reality and the entities that exist. In addition, ontology was defined

by Snape and Spencer (2003) as what knowledge we have about the world as well as its nature. Moreover, Bryman describes social ontology as the part of research where philosophy is considered while studying the nature of social entities. For instance, this can be used to learn more about the objectivity of the entities that can be developed free from social factors.

Applying ontology to the specific context of this study, which is the leadership functions driving the engagement of the gig workers in the UK restaurant sector with the pragmatic stance adopted by the researcher, we navigate realism and constructivism as the two prominent perspectives (Shusterman, 2016). Pragmatism as a research paradigm seeks functional usefulness and affirms the use of procedures that work to address a real-world problem, which is the engagement of gig workers in UK restaurants within pragmatism; the focus is on the usefulness and efficiency of knowledge (James, 2020).

Altering the mentioned ontological perspective to the field of the restaurant sector in the UK and focusing on the functions of leadership to drive the engagement of gig workers, the pragmatic stance underscores the need for practical elucidation (Legg & Hookway, 2008). From the pragmatic point of view, the priority is on choosing leadership functions and strategies that yield tangible outcomes in boosting the engagement of gig workers. The selection of leadership functions should not be limited to theoretical considerations but should be impelled by their real-world impact on gig workers' engagement in the restaurant sector (Bacon, 2012).

In essence, opting for a pragmatic stance while investigating gig workers' engagement and leadership functions in the UK restaurant sector is a problem-solving and flexible approach encouraging the researcher to investigate and gadget leadership functions that prove efficient in the practical and dynamic context of gig workers' engagement with the restaurant sector (Stuhr, 2015). On the other hand, they can be built up from individual interpretations, perceptions and actions in society. The ontology is seen by Ormston et al. (2014) as the ideal answer to whether human conceptions and interpretation can independently develop a social reality and if a shared social reality exists. To be more specific, ontology is related to the beliefs regarding nature, the social world and reality (Smith, 2003).

There are two significant perspectives regarding ontological assumptions: constructivism and realism. According to Archer et al. (1998), realism includes the existence of an external reality such as figures and material objectives. Realism consists of two significant sub-groups: critical realism and naïve realism. While critical realism states that there is no such thing as interpretation

or theory-neutral observation, naïve realism accepts that the efficient use of the appropriate methods can lead to a comprehensive understanding of reality (Cameron, 2008).

This can conclude that reality is not natural as it can influence behaviours and be influenced. Individuals, existing knowledge and ideas can influence the reality that can be interpreted, described and observed through the use of the senses and the knowledge of the observer (Cocchiarella, 2007). The observer, through those observations, will eventually take the most suitable actions. Therefore, it can be said that reality has several consequences. According to Fleetwood (2005), for an entity to be accurate, it has to have a remarkable impact on behaviour, make a difference and have original efficacy . In addition, the entity can exist independently of our knowledge of it. On the other hand, constructivists state that theories can be generalised rather than relying on reality to be formalised. According to Guba and Lincoln (1994), constructivism states that reality is socially developed (Mäki, 2008).

Table 4: The difference between the two assumptions drawn from the ontology.

	Constructivism	Realism
Nature of observed reality	Socially assembled	Biased yet rigid
Manager's role	Contexts' originator, actor.	Reactor, information processor
The strategic choice's nature	Hypothetical process of sub-organisational concern troop	Realistic, response to possibilities
Organisational identity	Diversified, numerous, disintegrated.	Obvious, unique.
Theories of measurement	Framework as essential to perspective.	Reproduction is a way to certainty.

Source: developed by the researcher

It can be seen from the information shown in Table 4 that constructivism and realism consist of one major distinction that is based on the nature of reality. The researcher will summarise the ontological beliefs that will be opted for this study in Table 5.

Table 5: The ontological beliefs of this research

Ontological principles	Application of the study
The knowledge of an entity can independently develop it (Danemark, 2002).	Front-line leadership functions drive employee engagement, although, it is not yet conceptualised and theoretically known in the context of gig workers in the restaurant sector.
The social phenomena of reality can be easily understood (Bhaskar, 1978; Patomaki & Wight, 2000).	Investigating gig workers' engagement in the restaurant sector includes making sense of the entire phenomenon together with learning the cause-effect relationship.
The theory has an impact on actions and forms of diversity (Fleetwood, 2005).	Examining the theory of employee engagement, and how the management and leaders functions in the restaurant industry affect it, as well as how those functions drive the engagement of gig workers.

Source: developed by the researcher

In this research, the gig economy, including gig workers, is set to be an external reality that occurs together with various other realities in the social world. These realities can be seen as outcomes and drivers of the core phenomena under study, for instance, employee engagement (Cruickshank, 2007). This study aims to comprehend the connection between the engagement of gig workers in the restaurant sector and leadership functions as drivers of engagement. This will consider the importance of making sense of the phenomena (leadership functions and gig workers' engagement) (Cocchiarella, 2007). To sum up, the researcher will adopt critical realism as an underlying ontological assumption for this study.

3.2.3 Justification of the chosen philosophy

The focus of this research is based on exploring the leadership functions driving the engagement of gig workers in the UK restaurant sector. The researcher adopted pragmatism and critical realism as research philosophies aiming to comprehend the dynamic and complex nature of the investigated phenomena of this study (Legg & Hookway, 2008).

Critical realism regarding the ontological assumptions is assigned for the investigation of both the underlying structures and observable surface and mechanisms that affect the leadership functions and how they can be employed efficiently as drivers by the front-line management (Rawwas et al., 2013). In the restaurant sector, the engagement of gig workers is affected by various factors that broaden beyond immediate observations. Furthermore, the use of critical realism in explaining the social reality through acknowledging the existence and the reality of the social phenomena as independent human perception (Lamy, 2023) aligns with the objective of this research to uncover the most efficient leadership functions that can enhance gig workers' engagement which goes beyond superficial manifestations (Sułkowski, 2010). The adoption of the pragmatic stance by the researcher was mainly based on furnishing a balanced approach, allowing the researcher to assimilate both subjective interpretations and objective observations (Lamy, 2023). In this study context, exploring the leadership functions together with comprehending their practical implications in driving the engagement of gig workers constrains a holistic approach. Moreover, the pragmatic stance tends to show positivity with a problem-solving orientation which led this study toward the determination of efficient leadership functions. Also, it enhances the integration of various perspectives and methods, establishing that the outcomes of the research are practically applicable to front-line management in the UK restaurant sector (Kim & Donaldson, 2018).

Pragmatism and critical realism enhance one another, providing an inclusive point of view to effectively comprehend the research problem. While pragmatism focuses on establishing findings that are actionable and related to real-world scenarios, critical realism offers theoretical and in-depth grounding. Furthermore, opting for the pragmatic stance in this research provided the researchers with better flexibility while choosing methods, considering their suitability for addressing this research question (Legg & Hookway, 2008). Flexibility is very important in this research due to its nature in investigating the leadership functions and gig workers' engagement drivers where various phenomena are involved requiring diverse analytical approaches and data sources (Shusterman, 2016). The selected philosophies resonate efficiently with the nature of the research that focuses on the UK restaurant sector, leadership functions and employee engagement characterised by a dynamic and varied workforce (James, 2020). Pragmatism and critical realism accommodate the complexities of sector studies, enabling research that takes a step forward in theoretical thought to provide actionable insights for managerial practices (Bacon, 2012).

To sum up, pragmatism and critical realism are adopted as research philosophies in this study aiming to capture the leadership functions and intricacies influencing the engagement of gig

workers in the UK restaurant sector while considering the practical stance for front-line management. These philosophies offer a robust foundation for uncovering both the actionable awareness needed and the underlying structures for efficiently using the leadership function in the context of gig workers' engagement (Stuhr, 2015).

3.3 Research approach

The research approach is a core element that is considered by researchers seeking more details about the knowledge. The research approach consists of two types: inductive and deductive. The deductive concept strengthens the theories' validity, and calculations using existing theories which will allow the formulation of the research approach and testing (Silverman, 2013). This approach will be most suitably used where the research study examines whether the previous research's outcomes and the observed phenomena match each other (Wiles et al., 2011). The deductive and positivist approaches can be beneficially suited and used together, which allows the formulation of an acceptable level of profitability regarding the statistical testing of expected results and the formation of suppositions (Snieder & Larner, 2009). However, the qualitative research techniques and the deductive approach can be used advantageously together as, in many cases, the pre-existing expectations will be formed differently from the ones from the construct testing (Saunders et al., 2007). The deductive approach is best described as advancing from the general to the particular (Kothari, 2004). On the other hand, the inductive approach is best depicted as moving from the specific to the general (Bryman & Bell, 2011). This approach concept involves new theories' developments together with generalisations. The starting point for the researcher in this approach is the observations, and the data usually include patterns (Beiske, 2007). Whatever the research's scope is, the debate on research paths should be a fundamental part of a scientific treaty (Saunders et al., 2007). The Table 6 illustrates the core differences between the inductive and the deductive approaches.

Table 6: The core differences between the inductive and the deductive approaches.

Inductive approach	Deductive approach
Attaining a comprehension of the meanings.	Scientific principles
Individuals are connected to events.	Running from theory to data

A direct perception of the study context	A causal connection among variables needs to be illustrated
Qualitative data collection	Quantitative data collection
The structure is more adaptable which allows correction of research emphasis while the research is in process.	The approach is highly structured. The operationalisation of concepts to ensure clarity of definition. Controls need to be applied to validate data
The researcher takes part in the research procedures.	The researcher is not involved in the research.
The importance of generalising is a minor.	A sufficient size of samples is required to generalise conclusions.

Source: (Graue, 2015)

Despite the clear differentiation between the inductive and the deductive approaches in the literature, it is widespread to combine both approaches (Saunders et al., 2005).

Research is based on various successive steps, including developing the theory and reviewing it through collecting, analysing and interpreting the data. In turn, the interpreted data contributes to the development of the theory (Bryman & Bell, 2007).

According to Kaplan (1964), the data is generally gathered upon the theoretical foundation and rarely from scratch. However, the theoretical basis can be sometimes *primaeval*. Thus, the research often includes a process of fitful theory building and data collection. This comes in favour of the arguments supporting combining the inductive and inductive approaches (Graue, 2015). The researcher's beliefs in this research regarding the approaches will be summarised in Table 7.

Table 7: The research approach and application

Principles of research approach	Application of the research
The search illustrates the connection.	This study aims to clarify the cause-effect correlation between gig workers' engagement and leadership functions.
The approach is highly structured.	This includes the creation of theories, causes and consequences of gig workers' engagement in the restaurant sector.

Facts are measured qualitatively.	The gig economy is reshaping the restaurant sector which can be proved through a qualitative study. This will permit quantitative measurement to study the level of impact of leadership functions on gig worker engagement.
Close comprehension of context.	This research is specifically involved with the implication of gig workers' engagement in a particular context (i.e., leadership functions).

Source: The researcher

3.3.1 Justification for using this approach.

The pragmatic philosophy opted by the researcher enhances the selection of the most efficient methods to address the study questions. To comprehensively examine the phenomenon, this research uses combined deductive and inductive approaches, lending empirical observations and theoretical insights (Fereday & Muir-Cochrane, 2006).

The adoption of the deduction approach allows the established leadership functions and gig workers' engagement theories to be tested through a theoretical framework. This is affiliated with critical realism, giving prominence to the significance of determining underlying mechanisms (Hammoudeh, 2009). On the other hand, the induction approach will help the researcher explore fresh insights and patterns from the emerging data. From the pragmatic stance, the induction approach assists the generation of original theories and the adjustment of the current ones relying on empirical observations (Greco, 2001). Furthermore, the flexibility offered by the pragmatism in the research design, encourages the researcher to use inductive and the deductive approaches in the context of the leadership functions and gig workers' engagement in the restaurant industry, ensuring that the research is contextually applicable and relevant. Moreover, using both approaches help the appropriate formation of methodological triangulation, converging the derived outcomes and enhancing the validity of the research (Liu, 2016).

Despite the advantages surrounding the combination usage of deductive and inductive approaches, various limitations can be encountered by the researcher such as complexity and resource-intensiveness that put more pressure on the researcher to efficiently interplay between the two approaches (Dornes, 2013). Furthermore, the researcher encounters the risk of overlooking aspects related to the gig workers' engagement or leadership functions which enhances the importance of

inclusive examination. Also, the researcher should integrate findings cohesively by employing robust strategies due to the challenges that may be faced in the data analysis process while merging the deductive and inductive insights (Azungah, 2018). Considering that the gig worker engagement concept has been theoretically grounded in the literature, based on the actual gig workers' engagement theory, this research intends to study the application of the same concept in the restaurant sector, covering the leadership functions of drivers (Pandey, 2019). Accordingly, the theory anticipated data gathering in the primary stage of the study. In addition, the deduction approach's unique distinguishing feature is applied in this research. However, even though the gig economy has been around for a long time and is a well-established construct, it has lately been growing in the restaurant industry context. In this respect, the researcher used semi-structured interviews, and a questionnaire (qualitative data) was gathered through this study to have a more comprehensive picture of the context of the restaurant sector (Overmars & VerBurg, 2007).

At this level, the qualitative data was efficiently utilised to establish theories and themes regarding gig workers' engagement in the restaurant sector, in particular, the leadership functions and the labour market enhanced by the developments that developed the emergence of delivery and hiring apps (induction characteristic). The researcher tested the developed theories qualitatively to prove the well-structured research design that is followed in this study (Azungah, 2018).

To sum up, it is seen that this research included a procedure of cyclical theory building and data collection throughout the research stages. Deduction has been chosen as the core approach of this research. The context of gig workers' engagement and management functions in the restaurant sector needs to be understood through qualitative research. Given the particularities of this context (Alase, 2017), Combining both the inductive and the deductive approaches within this research framework, which is based on the critical realism and pragmatism, enhances affluent expedition of the leadership functions and gig workers' engagement. Yet, the researcher needs to consider the potential tensions and the complexities brought to light by the adaption of both approaches to guarantee the relevance and rigour of the research.

3.4 Research strategies

This part of the research aims to draw the researcher's plans and methods to gather the necessary data for the research. The research strategy refers to the comprehensive plan for handling a study that will take the researcher through the process of planning, accomplishing and observing the study (Bryman et al., 2012). The research strategy needs to be complemented with the ideal

research methods, such as questionnaires, to accomplish the most efficient outcomes in terms of the data collected. There are a variety of research strategies which will allow the researcher to select the most suitable one based on the goals, needs and characteristics of the study being undertaken (Bajwa et al., 2016). The ideal research strategy helps the researcher to answer the research questions in the most efficient way possible by meeting the appropriate specific measures of the research. Moreover, the research strategy needs to be feasible from a practical standpoint, which covers the researcher's accessibility to data sources, such as documents, places and individuals (England, 2006). In addition, the researcher needs to consider the most sufficient and least time-consuming method to be more effective while collecting data for the study. The researcher should also ensure that the chosen strategy can be pursued in an ethically responsible way, such as protecting the participants' identity, as well as informing the respondents about their rights and role in the research and that the gathered data will only be utilised to conduct the study (Aurini et al., 2016). Several methods can be employed to collect data, such as case study, action research, grounded theory, survey, experiment, archival research and ethnology. The researcher can select more than one method to conduct the research based on the need explained in the research (Johnson, 1998), the researcher is adopting an experimental survey as a strategy to conduct this research due to its effectiveness in helping the researcher gather the needed data to answer the main research questions. The use of the experimental survey will increase the understanding and awareness of the researcher regarding the phenomena being investigated in this study. Three common approaches can be adopted by researchers while conducting research: qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods. The selection of the most efficient approach depends on the research questions and the type of data required to answer those questions (Baker, 2000). The research questions can encourage researchers to study the data needed to respond to the research questions and assess what will aid them in selecting the most appropriate approach for the study. Research can be analysed through the gathered textual data, numerical data or a mixture of the two. Based on this evaluation, the researcher determines one of those aforementioned approaches to engage in research (Pepper & Wildy, 2009). In addition, the type of data required to conduct the research is one of the significant assessments that can enhance the researcher's decision. For instance, typically, researchers utilise the qualitative approach to answer questions requiring textual data, the quantitative approach for questions requiring numerical data and mixed approaches to respond to questions where textual and numerical data are needed. This research will study all methods and select the most suitable one to conduct this research together with an explanation of the chosen approach (Pathak et al., 2013).

3.4.1 Quantitative research approach

Quantitative research first emerged among investigators to quantify data, which Western countries have used as the ideal research method for developing new knowledge and creating data. The research design consists of numerical and statistical approaches that led to quantitative research, which, according to Leedy (2001), is specifically designed to fit experimentation and surveying as it is derived from existing theories. Also, the quantitative research methodology sustains themes of an empiricist paradigm (Creswell, 2003). The researcher and the research are considered to be two independent elements that will result in data being utilised to evaluate reality and develop meaning impartially. Researchers opt for quantitative research to efficiently answer research questions that consist of variables where researchers are looking for predictions and explanations which can be produced for different places and persons; this will help to set up, affirm or approve relationships and create generalisations devoted to theory (Leedy & Ormrod, 2001, p. 102).

Quantitative research can be classified into three broad types: experimental, descriptive or causal comparative. The most basic method is the descriptive research approach, which evaluates the current state of a situation; this starts by identifying and observing the phenomena's attributes and correlating between a few phenomena (Bahari, 2010). Researchers can use experimental research to explore and measure the treatment outcome of the intervention of the study group. This quantitative research approach consists of three types: pre-experimental, true-experimental and quasi-experimental. Each type has different perspectives, such as a higher degree of validity and control, validity, independent variables and many others. Those are the main determinants that researchers rely on while selecting the most appropriate approaches which allow them to conduct adequate research (Pepper & Wildy, 2009). Researchers can apply comparative research to examine dependent variables that can affect the independent ones. This will help researchers to inspect the interaction and the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variables. There are several research methods to conduct quantitative research, such as observation studies, surveys and correlational (Walter & Andersen, 2013).

An initial exploratory study was conducted to determine the research question. The researcher was optimistic about the lack of knowledge regarding gig workers' engagement from the usage of the leadership function perspective. Therefore, the researcher opted to use Churchill's (1979) procedures to create an efficient scale to cover the gap in the field. The initial exploratory study was applied to effectively comprehend the field of the research (Churchill, 1979). Developing

insights toward the gig economy, gig workers' engagement labour market and leadership functions have allowed the researcher to formulate research questions and themes and purify the measures of the questionnaire (Cuomo et al., 2021).

The phenomenon was produced through gaining ideas and insights from the involvement of individuals' judgment samples, which many scholars regarding the exploratory studies suggested. In addition, this research started on a wide scale going through reviewing stages, including literature and interviews, to measure gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector.

3.4.2 Qualitative research approach.

Qualitative research refers to a holistic approach which covers discovery. Qualitative research is defined as an unfolding model that arises naturally, aiming to allow researchers to explore an efficient level of data relying on their considerable interference in authentic experiments (Creswell, 2005). Also, qualitative research is seen as the point of view of participants regarding the investigated social phenomenon. Several research design types utilise qualitative research methods to shape the research approach that will dramatically affect the strategies explored in the research. Qualitative research is established through efficiently explaining, interpreting and then describing the data gathered by the researcher. According to Creswell (2003),

Qualitative research can be efficiently handled through a poststructuralist paradigm that covers several areas such as case studies, phenomenological studies, grounded theory studies, content analysis and ethnography studies (Conroy et al., 2008). Those areas represent the research that evolved from associated methodologies and inductive reasoning. Qualitative research depends on inductive reasoning rather than deductive as the researcher attempts to explain the posed observational elements where a strong correlation between the data and the observer is developed (Yu, 2006). Qualitative research can be conducted through various methods such as case studies, ethnography, grounded theory, content analysis and phenomenology. The researcher can select the most efficient method based on what the research aims to achieve (Silverman, 2020). According to Creswell (2003), different methods can be utilised to meet different needs. For example, grounded and case studies are required where the researcher is aiming to examine activities, processes and events. On the other hand, ethnographic research is adopted by researchers seeking to analyse broad cultural-sharing behaviours of groups or individuals.

3.4.2.1 Planning, management and data interpretation

The themes developed by the researcher will be tested through a coding test created from the conceptual framework. The researcher relied on the gig economy, gig workers' engagement, leadership functions and the labour market to develop the scope to analyse and code the data. The codes will reflect the variables identified by the researcher in this study (Harvey & Alston, 2011). Open codes were the first step to determining the constructs by the literature review. The list of codes will have been derived from research questions, problems and critical variables that have formatted the conceptual framework (Miles et al., 2013). The researcher has noted all transcripts of interviews before coding the transcript, which will facilitate the qualitative analysis (Ozdemir et al., 2020). The data can be easily collected through descriptive codes, which will enhance the visibility of the gathered data. The three coding stages increase the emergent data trustworthiness. Three coding stages were used in this research to boost the trustworthiness of the data. The open codes were at the primary stages for the second data analysis, represented by the axial coding, while the last stage of coding was the selective coding to merge the themes developed in this research. QSR NVivo software was used to administrate the data and attain the results, as well as to draw diagrams to allow the immediate appearance of the inter-relationships codes. (Bryman, 2016). Furthermore, various other benefits enhance the usage of the NVIVO, such as retrieving the stored data, managing the qualitative data and verifying the themes for equilibrium which will allow the analysis process to be more accurate. In addition, the validity and reliability can be tested through this software, not to mention its ability to assist in the analysis of the qualitative data delivering a more accurate, reliable and transparent analysis of the collected data (Gupta, 2010). The coding reliability was verified by analysing the repetitiveness of the code through several researchers acquiring more agreeability on theme identification. The researcher utilised a system of coding that tested the interviewee's words and phrases, going through the process of determining the phenomenon while considering the previous development codes.

The qualitative findings can be analysed through various approaches, whereas several literatures have thoroughly discussed them (Harvey & Alston, 2011; Miles et al., 2013; Ozdemir et al., 2020; Bryman, 2016; Silverman, 2015). The researcher employed grounded theory to conduct the qualitative study and tested the findings. The coding process for qualitative data was guided by the conceptual framework derived from the literature. Codes were developed by the researcher based on measures related to gig workers' engagement and leadership functions, drawing on the concepts of employee engagement studied in earlier research. This methodological approach allowed for a systematic and in-depth analysis of the qualitative data, ensuring alignment with established

theoretical frameworks and contributing to the rigor of the study. such as (Saks, 2006; Gupta, 2010) Together with the drivers highlighted and determined in those studies, this research specifically focuses on the leadership functions-related drivers that can enhance the engagement of gig workers. This has expanded the scope for coding and analysing the findings. Additionally, the researcher determined in this study that codes should address the research questions, areas of issues, and key variables highlighted by the authors (Miles et al., 2013; Palmer, 2011). A careful methodology was employed by the researcher to experimentally investigate the research questions and ensure a systematic and thorough examination of the data.

In the initial stages, the narrative coding relied on the process of open coding, followed by the identification of constructs through the literature review. The list of codes focused on questions of the research, areas of the issue, conceptual framework, and variables developed by the researcher. Every interview transcript was carefully reviewed by the researcher before coding. The coding of the data assisted in comparing the level of the search to identify the required patterns for supplementary research. The coding of data procedures in the interview transcripts is one of the primary steps in qualitative analysis. (Harvey & Alston, 2011; Miles et al., 2013) The descriptive codes facilitated the data collection process, which was then followed by the emergence of a thematic method that shared similar content.

Patton (2014) asserts that it is crucial to design rules that can be utilized to justify the admittance of the remaining assigned data, aiding replicability tests. The adoption of this method qualifies the outcomes of the coding to systematically appear in the data. The analysis of the codes can be conducted through three coding steps: selective, axial, and open, which tend to increase the trustworthiness of the emergent data. The qualitative data coding for this study was based on Malhotra et al. (2017). The generation of open codes constitutes the initial step in data analysis. This stage involves interpreting open codes as distinct concepts that allow for the emergence of fundamental categories.

The open coding process commences with the individual review of each text (interview transcripts), phrase-by-phrase and sentence-by-sentence. Passages containing keywords such as leadership functions, front-line management, communication, collaboration, motivation, equal treatment, gig workers, gig economy, labor market, employee engagement, and restaurant sector were coded. The researcher then deliberated on the positions these codes would be classified in the top or bottom of the open codes' lists (Harvey & Alston, 2011). Subsequently, each transcript underwent a thorough double-check to identify patterns related to the literature. This intensive and continuous comparison allowed the researcher to scrutinize each sentence in relation to its

preceding open codes. Codes were open coded for differences and similarities, and when codes matched, the researcher categorized them as identical. Codes that did not match were assigned different labels by the researcher (Silverman, 2015). The primary objective of open coding is to transcribe all findings, whether they exhibit different or similar patterns to the related literature review. Utilizing open coding for each transcript of interviews enabled the researcher to accumulate a substantial number of memos and comments. These annotations proved instrumental in developing a highly rigorous analysis, facilitating the creation of axial codes (Bryman, 2016)

The second stage of data analysis involved axial coding, aiming to establish connections and relationships between principal categories and sub-categories to enhance the description of patterns in the interview transcripts. The systematic axial coding began after the open coding, providing an advantage in considering the entire set of open codes in an individual case (Bryman, 2016; Silverman, 2015). This approach avoids misleading data analysis and is beneficial in reflecting on the entire group of open codes during the continuous comparison process. The axial coding process was generated from the interview responses during open coding, considering differences and similarities through a continuous comparison procedure (Bryman, 2016). All open codes were initially compared to each other before comparing them to the axial codes in a subsequent step. This process facilitated the creation of new axial codes, modifications, and the merging of existing axial codes (Gupta, 2010).

The final stage of coding is selective coding, aimed at integrating the emerging theory. This stage is considered the most complex in grounded theory analysis, requiring a conscientious expression of incidents to generate a theory that effectively fits the data. Selective coding involves shifting towards a higher level of abstraction with the created paradigmatic constructs, establishing connections, and presenting a construct or fundamental category in a way that allows other constructs and categories to revolve, enabling them to be related to each other (Sacks, 2006). The initiation of selective coding is linked to the axial coding stage where the linkage among all axial codes was initiated. Clarifying the phenomenon of the study is associated with this stage of grounded theory analysis, making it the most crucial and complex stage of the coding process (Silverman, 2015).

In addition to the conventional coding procedures based on asking questions, comparison, and writing memos, the researcher employed further techniques. These included reconsidering open codes and raw data while comparing axial codes, reviewing the study questions as a general guideline, and discussing the codes with managers and experts to check the fitness and relationship between codes. The clarification of the data review helped the researcher identify dimensions of

gig workers' engagement alongside the leadership functions, its drivers, and its outcomes (Bryman, 2016). The collected data underwent a thorough purification, interpretation, and synthesis process through the application of the QSR NVivo software (version 12). This software facilitated the administration and extraction of data. A notable advantage of using this software was the support it provided to the researcher in visualizing entire texts and creating diagrammatic drawings, allowing interrelated codes to emerge promptly. Additionally, NVivo was instrumental in storing and retrieving data. Data verification involved extracting node content, which could interfere with inter-relationship thematic ideas, ensuring balance and consistency in searching through qualitative data analysis (Miles et al., 2013).

The NVivo software enabled the researcher to interrogate the data at a specific scale and address the reliability and validity of the research results. Furthermore, it facilitated the analytical process in a meticulous, thorough, and highly efficient manner through the effective application of software tools. These tools permitted the researcher to store data, record and link ideas, retrieve information, and explore the interpretation and data patterns. The simplicity and accuracy of these tools contributed to their efficiency and reliability (Harvey & Alston, 2011). The NVivo software assists the qualitative data analysis through providing an accurate, reliable, transparent and easy data analysis together with manipulating and analysing the data in better facilitated manner. The reliability of the coding was ensured through content analysis, wherein the code development process was carried out repeatedly by a different researcher. This iterative approach aimed to achieve consensus on the identification of themes and enhance the overall reliability of the coding process (Ozdemir et al., 2020)

Content analysis is a research technique employed to derive replicable and valid inferences from data and its meaning. Uncovering themes, categories, and patterns is a pivotal step in the researcher's endeavor to analyze qualitative data, emphasizing the selection of the most meaningful and significant data. This process requires careful consideration by the researcher to ensure the extraction of relevant insights from the collected information (Silverman, 2015). The coding system was employed by the researcher to assess the generated phrases and words that potentially convey significant meaning as perceived by the interviewees. Subsequently, the researcher attempted to identify the phenomenon using the gathered data, along with the indicators defining the start and end of the phenomenon, employing a research-driven code development approach. The researcher employed the verbatim transcripts of all interviews to gather rich data, facilitating the development of suitable information for examining the scale development (Silverman, 2015). This approach ensured uniformity and consistency in terminology compared to previous research.

Ultimately, the data was interpreted based on the established research framework. The quality of data holds paramount importance in social science, influencing philosophical and methodological approaches that are inherently diverse in studying human activity (Bryman, 2016). Reliability and validity serve as pivotal factors in shaping research, analysing findings, and forming judgments about the study's quality. However, a common definition for these factors in qualitative studies is still lacking. Research reliability can be affirmed through a trustworthiness assessment, wherein the trustworthiness opinion substantiates the concept of truth through measures of reliability and validity (Silverman, 2015).

Reliability and validity stand at the core of the conventionally discussed issues concerning the trustworthiness of a research report. The researcher opted for a theoretical sample over a randomly selected statistical sample, acknowledging its role in maximizing opportunities for comparing concepts and their properties (Gupta, 2010). This approach aids in delineating differences and similarities, assisting the researcher in the process of defining categories, specifying their variability range, and differentiating between them. According to Denzin and Lincoln (2017), the existence of reliability is strongly associated with the existence of validity, making the expression of the former sufficient to establish the latter (Saks, 2019). The accuracy of research techniques and methods is achieved through reliability to promote data validity as the study's outcome. Perceptions in qualitative research can influence the levels of both reliability and validity. Subsequently, the triangulation method will be employed to enhance the research's trustworthiness and eliminate bias. Triangulation involves seeking convergence among various information sources to develop research categories and themes (Silverman, 2015). Furthermore, the triangulation method improves the validity, reliability, and evaluation of findings in a study. Therefore, reliability, validity, and triangulation are interconnected study concepts. The techniques employed in this research to enhance trustworthiness will be illustrated in the table below:

The researcher employed content analysis to verify the reliability of the coding after various content coding ensured stability. Furthermore, for assessing reliability concerning potential categories of gig worker engagement using leadership functions as drivers, only an independent coder (an expert in qualitative studies) was utilized. This individual was not familiar with the study (Saks, 2019).

Table 8: Meeting the trustworthiness' criteria.

Traditional criteria	Trustworthiness criteria	Techniques employed to ensure trustworthiness
Internal validity	Credibility	Quality access (the researcher was provided with an office desk, computer, access to company intranet, email address, freedom of talking to and interviewing anybody, freedom of getting any company documents, including lots of confidential strategic documents.) and extensive engagement in the field. Multiple triangulations Peer debriefing Constant comparison
External validity	Transferability	Detailed description of the research setting Multiple cases and cross-case comparison
Reliability	Dependability	Purposive and theoretical sampling Cases and informant's confidentiality protected Rigorous multiple stages of coding
Objectivity	Confirmability	Separately presenting the exemplar open and axial codes. Word-by-word interview transcription Accurate records of contacts and interviews Writing research journal Carefully keeping notes of observation Regularly keeping notes of emergent theoretical and methodological ideas

Source: Based on Creswell (2013)

3.4.2.2 The argument for methodological triangulation

According to Olsen (2004), each approach has a variety of limitations that make the combination of both approaches very beneficial for the study as it strengthens the weaknesses of each of the methods (Jick, 1979; Lyon et al., 2000; Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003). The researcher will use various methods to study a single phenomenon by combining the quantitative and qualitative methods, called methodological triangulation. To conclusively understand the research problem while addressing a phenomenon from several perspectives, the researcher can adopt methodological triangulation. Methodological triangulation processes can be formed in a different structure. However, the principle of combining both methods will remain the same. The research approach and questions are the main elements that the researcher relies on while choosing the most efficient procedure. This research was conducted in two core phases. Part of this study used the quantitative method to study some aspects of gig workers, such as the kind of people doing such jobs, whether gig workers are entirely relying on gig work as the only source of income and many other aspects. Questionnaires were utilised as a source to gather such data. On the other hand, the researcher used qualitative methods to gather data that helped to investigate the research questions and problems. Interviews were used to gather qualitative data. The findings from both methods were integrated into the interpretation process.

3.5 Data collection methods

3.5.1 Time-horizon

The time frame varies from one study to another depending on the accessibility of the data as well as the number of variables being investigated (Sahay, 2016). There are two types of time horizons: cross-sectional and longitudinal. The cross-sectional time horizon refers to the research where the time of the data collection process is already pre-set and established (Flick, 2011). This time horizon can be utilised to investigate a study with a specific phenomenon at a specific period. On the other hand, the longitudinal time horizon represents the data repeatedly collected over an extended extent of time, such as following an individual reaction at different seasons or ages throughout the year (Melnikovas, 2018). This type can be used in studies aiming to examine the changes of a crucial factor over a specific time and study changes and development of an element that will help to control the investigated variables. The research approach and methodology will not affect the chosen time horizon by the researcher (Saunders et al., 2007). The researcher is adopting the cross-sectional time horizon as the time for data collection is already set by the researcher. The researcher will collect data over an intensive period of six weeks (Gog, 2015). The data collection process is based on questionnaires and interviews. This research is collecting data based on the participants' current or previous experiences, and it is not interested in studying variables over time, making the cross-sectional type, the most appropriate time horizon to conduct this research. (Jafarzadeh et al., 2015).

3.5.2 Qualitative aspect

3.5.2.1 Interview

To achieve the study's objectives, the researcher conducted interviews to operationalize and pinpoint the crucial components required for quantifying the implication of the leadership functions in engaging gig workers in the UK restaurant sector. In-depth interviews were conducted with individuals holding various managerial positions in the UK restaurant sector including owners, managers, supervisors and head chefs. These interviews significantly enhanced the researcher's comprehension of the topic and enabled the collection of attitudinal and behavioural data (Alshenqeeti, 2014; Jain, 2021; Harrell & Bradley, 2009). The research utilised a subject manual as the foundation for the interview guide, aiding in the organisation of leadership functions chosen by the front-line management as drivers for gig workers' engagement. This manual aligned

the main themes with the interview questions, thereby facilitating a cohesive and insightful discussion flow. Due to the limitations imposed by the pandemic, all interviews were conducted via video conversations on platforms such as Skype or WhatsApp. This approach was chosen to ensure a clear understanding of the participants' perspectives and to gather the necessary information for the study's objectives (Churchill, 1999). The scheduling of interviews took into consideration the preferred method of communication and availability aligning with their desired interview times (Griffie, 2005). In line with Gill et al. (2008), the majority of the interviews lasted over 30 minutes. To enhance credibility, the researcher recorded and transcribed each interview. The method employed for these in-depth interviews was semi-structured, direct, open, and conducted in a private setting to uncover the core beliefs, motivations and emotions of the participants. To ensure comprehensive coverage of relevant topics, a question sheet was created by the researcher. According to Crowe and Sheppard (2010), the researcher adhered to the expert dress code and positioned themselves as a DBA researcher rather than a student. Various strategies were employed to establish rapport with the respondents, aiming to create an environment conducive to delving deeper into the subject matter. Bertrand and Bourdeau (2010) suggest that in-depth interviews provide opportunities to uncover new information, reveal fresh perspectives, and obtain vivid, truthful, inclusive stories, grounded in first-hand experience. The flexibility of in-depth interviews allows researchers to enquire about a wide range of complex issues (Luo & Wildemuth, 2009). Perception, value and attitude are outcomes derived from non-qualified data, with qualitative research providing support in this regard. According to Fishbein and Ajzen (1975), attitude is a crucial concept that commonly aids in comprehending and forecasting people's responses to changes or objects. Additionally, it serves as a method for assessing the management point of view regarding the emerging phenomenon and understanding how gig workers engaged (Mingers et al., 2013). This allows interview subjects to appraise and analyse reputational characteristics and communication-related elements. The data obtained is deemed "more credible because the replies are restricted to the substitutions indicated" (Janghorban et al., 2014). Balmer (2011) advocates for giving greater weight to exploratory studies, starting with a situational analysis conducted through manager interviews (Gupta et al., 2010). When addressing profound issues in a less structured manner and exploring the opinions, experiences and feelings of respondents, the qualitative method is adopted (Malhotra et al., 2017). The qualitative investigation aims to gather more detailed data to achieve a deeper understanding of the idea of gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector and how the leadership functions can be

employed by the front-line management to effectively drive the engagement in the UK restaurant sector (Bampton & Cowton, 2002).

Why the personal interview technique?

Saunders et al. (2003) stated that the most advantageous technique for research involving explanatory alongside the exploratory elements is interviewing. The researcher used interviews as an efficient technique to gather data due to the exploratory nature of this level of research. Moreover, the explanatory nature of the research enhances the application of interviews as they allow the inference of causal relationships among variables (Harrell & Bradley, 2009). The researcher is adopting qualitative interviews to gather participants' points of view. Interviews allow the researcher to gather more detailed information due to the flexibility provided by such techniques that most other forms of data collection do not offer (Musselwhite et al., 2007). In addition, these techniques will also permit the researcher to ask open-ended and follow-up questions. This will allow further information to be discovered and help the researcher gain detailed and rich information on how the gig economy is affecting the restaurant sector, in particular, the leadership functions and their roles in enhancing gig workers' engagement (Bampton & Cowton, 2002). Personal interviews allow the researcher to measure the atmosphere of the investigated setting socially by considering the sets of non-verbal communication, including the body language, the behaviour and the attitude of the interviewee. Also, the researcher will be enabled to feel familiar with the research context (Janghorban et al., 2014). Interviews will be utilised by the researcher to figure out how the gig economy concept is reshaping restaurants covering the leadership styles, job market and operational management. The gathered information will build a basis for the investigation of the impact of the gig economy on the restaurant sector (Robinson, 2014).

Why specifically key informant semi-structured interviews?

Concerning the respondents of the interviews, the researcher selected them carefully based on their knowledge and expertise to efficiently target the issues investigated (Newcomer et al., 2015). This approach is particularly fruitful in the sort of research aiming to determine the main characteristics of critical concepts depending on the participants' understanding and experience (Whiting, 2008), how the gig economy concept is well known, familiar and elucidated practically with a specific organisation in the chosen industry (the restaurant industry).

The concept needs to be investigated from the perspective of managers, gig workers and restaurant employees who are believed to be fully aware of and knowledgeable about the different aspects accompanied by the emergence of the gig economy that occurred in the restaurant industry, as well as the specific areas that were mostly hit and affected by this concept (Rabionet, 2011). Notably, this research has selected critical informant semi-structured interviews as the most suitable and efficient for this research. From this point of view, the research used a clear focus to begin the investigation, allowing more particular issues to be addressed (Bryman & Bell, 2007). The researcher used the topic's guide to create the interview guide; this has widely condensed the gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector as the topic of interest. Twenty-five individuals with managerial positions in the UK restaurant industry were contacted by the researcher using his network in the industry. The researcher targeted candidates through a straightforward approach seeking their ability to be part of the study. Only 22 participants showed interest in being part of this research, while the rest declined the invitation for different reasons. Therefore, the researcher interviewed 22 individuals from different positions and restaurants. The interviews were performed through several methods, including face-to-face and video calls. Interview times varied from one interviewee to another. Most of the interviewees had a previous direct or indirect relationship with the researcher that facilitated the introductory phase and allowed the interviews to run smoothly.

The researcher targeted several related topics focusing on gig worker engagement and leadership functions (Malhotra et al., 2017). In addition, the researcher enabled the interviewees to evaluate and assess the reputation attributes, which made the data more reliable (Mingers et al., 2013). The interviews were mostly done through face-to-face meetings with a few over the phone. The online process was conducted through the usage of online meeting platforms such as Skype and WhatsApp, depending on the need; each interview took around 45 minutes to conduct.

Table 9: Interviewee information

Number of interviewees	Position/role	Nature of business	location	Method of interview	code
1	Manager	Coffee shop	Knightsbridge	Face-to-Face	Manager 1
2	Manager	Fast food	Dalston	Face-to-Face	Manager 2
3	Manager	Restaurant	Leyton	Face-to-Face	Manager 3
4	Manager	Restaurant	Norwich	WhatsApp	Manager 4
5	Manager	Fast food	Leyton	Face-to-Face	Manager 5
6	Manager	Coffee shop	Wanstead	Face-to-Face	Manager 6
7	Manager	Pizza shop	Shoreditch	Face-to-Face	Manager 7
8	Manager	Coffee shop	Leytonstone	Face-to-Face	Manager 8
9	Manager	Restaurant	Walthamstow	Face-to-Face	Manager 9

10	Manager	Restaurant	Blackhorse	Face-to-Face	Manager10
11	Manager	Bakery	Walthamstow	Face-to-Face	Manager11
12	Owner	Bakery	Hampstead	WhatsApp	Owner 1
13	Owner	Coffee shop	Northfield	Face-to-Face	Owner 2
14	Owner	Fast food	Leytonstone	Face-to-Face	Owner 3
15	Owner	Coffee shop	Hackney	Face-to-Face	Owner 4
16	Owner	Restaurant	Norwich	Zoom	Owner 5
17	Owner	Coffee shop	Leytonstone	Face-to-Face	Owner 6
18	Owner	Kebab shop	Walthamstow	Face-to-Face	Owner 7
19	Owner	Fish & chips	Essex	Skype	Owner 8
20	Owner	Restaurant	South end	Face-to-Face	Owner 9
21	Head chef	Pizza shop	Walthamstow	Face-to-Face	Head chef 1
22	Supervisor	Restaurant	Piccadilly	Face-to-Face	Supervisor 1

Source: developed by the researcher

3.5.2 Quantitative aspect

3.5.2.1 Design of questionnaire

To understand the core leadership functions that can be used by the front-line management to engage gig workers in the UK restaurant sector, the survey was evaluated by the respondents based on their personal experiences in the gig economy in the restaurant sector involving their experience of front-line management and what can be defined as an ideal driver of their engagement (Yaddanapudi & Yaddanapudi, 2019). Interviews play a vital role in identifying the notion of drivers that are related to leadership functions and their efficiency can be investigated and evaluated through the questionnaire. The Likert scale, a commonly used tool in research for assessing respondents' levels of agreement or disagreement, was utilised to measure participants' attitudes toward gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector (Crowe & Sheppard, 2010). Attitude measures serve to characterise an individual's emotions, perceptions and beliefs. These measures of attitudes extend to oneself, others and various situations and activities. Krosnick (2018) proposes replacing the five-point Likert scale with a seven-point Likert scale to enhance construct variance and reduce measurement error variation. Shiu et al. (2009) documented the response pattern of gig workers in the UK restaurant sector using a Likert-type scale with the following scores: 1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = Somewhat disagree, 4 = Neutral, 5 = Somewhat agree, 6 = Agree, and 7 = Strongly agree (Lietz, 2010).

Understanding the gig economy in the UK restaurant sector and how it has impacted the labour market will successfully participate in the process of understanding the increase of gig workers in the restaurant sector. The front-line management is facing gig workers' emergence in the UK restaurant sector which makes it more challenging than ever to understand what drives their

engagement in the UK restaurant sector. Thus, it makes sense to focus on the leadership functions related to drivers to boost the engagement of gig workers in the restaurant sector. The introductory section of the questionnaire considers the background of the gig economy and gig workers to assess the emergence elements of the phenomena in the UK restaurant sector. To ensure respondents could easily answer the questions, the survey's queries are designed with a clear structure, format and visual appeal (Fakhreddin et al., 2021). Questions about the respondents' attitudes toward the leadership functions and their usage by the front line management as drivers to engage gig workers were associated with the statement. Additionally, the respondents were asked to define which of the functions are the most efficient drivers of the engagement. Respondents needed to carefully consider their responses to accurately understand and answer the attitude scales. The survey for this research spanned six pages, including a cover letter to enhance the response rate. The accompanying letter, along with ensuring participants' confidentiality, outlined the key guidelines for the investigation (Pesudovs et al., 2007).

3.5.2.2 Targeted respondents

According to Bryman and Bell (2007), the population is defined as the whole assortment of cases from where the sample will be generated. The population in this research is the gig economy in the UK restaurant sector, investigating the consequences of the rapid emergence of the gig economy on the restaurant sector (Rowley, 2014). Gig worker engagement, leadership functions and human resource management such as hiring, employee management and many other managerial areas have increasingly influenced gig worker engagement. Hence, these restaurants perceive the gig economy, particularly gig workers' engagement, as an essential tool to attract talented employees and engage them in the business (Edwards et al., 2009). However, they need to cope with the consequences following the employment of gig workers. The researcher aims to gather sufficient data to have a clear view regarding gig workers' engagement in the restaurant sector, relying on the leadership functions as drivers, including the targeting of gig workers as well as individuals of different managerial positions to take part in this study.

This includes restaurant workers and managers, delivery drivers, gig workers in restaurants and agency workers. In addition, the researcher is interested in gathering data regarding some gig economy tools and their impact on participants, such as delivery app companies, apps-based hiring companies and agencies (Saris & Gallhofer, 2014). Due to the emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic, some of the interviews could not be done face to face; for that reason, the researcher relied on calls and emails to conduct some interviews. 346 questionnaires were sent by email or

given by hand to participants and collected at different times. The researcher's position as a restaurant worker and the extensive network in the industry provided easy access to various gig workers throughout the industry. The researcher gave away 120 questionnaires to delivery drivers who were regularly operating in the area, given that they have worked at different gig positions, which were dropped back later. 180 questionnaires were given to 12 restaurants using gig workers to fill their vacant positions. The questionnaires were given to the available gig workers at different times by restaurants. The researcher used his close contacts to deliver and collect the questionnaires (Pesudovs et al., 2007). The researcher also used other contacts to deliver 46 questionnaires to freelancers in restaurant positions, such as chefs, baristas, pastry chefs, sous chefs, supervisors and kitchen porters. The researcher used the latter questionnaires to gather more data regarding their previous experiences and thoughts about the engagement (Dörnyei & Taguchi, 2009). The researcher handed questionnaires to participants through the usage of the appropriate contacts in the industry, which allowed a large number of participants (346), particularly with the current situation forced by the pandemic where contact with individuals was limited. Among all the questionnaires distributed, only 10 questionnaires were excluded, for different reasons, including questions that were not all answered and some of the questionnaires were not returned.

3.5.2.3 The appropriate number of participants

In this section, the researcher discusses the commonly used methods for determining the appropriate sample size. Determining the right number of participants for sample size is considered challenging and intricate. The primary method is associated with data analysis procedures. Five factors can influence sample size in structural equation modelling (SEM) to obtain accurate estimations (Field, 2009; Hair et al., 1998). Firstly, the ratio of respondents to parameters should be higher especially when the data is non-normal according to the multivariate distribution. Therefore, when the data distribution deviates from the multivariate assumption of normality, having at least five respondents per parameter is considered an appropriate quantity to minimise the difficulty of deviation from normality.

Secondly, if the greatest maximum likelihood approach is being used, the sample size needs to range from 150 to 400 replies. When the sample size surpasses 400 participants, which is not the case in this research, the maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) method becomes delicate, resulting in poorer quality goodness-of-fit scores (Hair et al., 2013).

Thirdly, the sample size is considered moderate given the paradigm complexity if the SEM comprises five or fewer constructs, each construct has three or more measures and the item

communalities exceed 0.6. For instance, a sample size ranging from 100 and 150 is regarded as small. Conversely, a sample size of 200 is required if one of the commonalities is moderate (0.45 to 0.55) or if the construct has fewer than three measures (Shiu, 2009).

Fourthly, if more than 10% of the data is deemed to be missing, the sample size should be expanded. Finally, a large sample size is warranted if the average error variance of the indicator is less than 0.5 for the construct's commonalities.

Ritchie et al. (2003) provide fundamental guidelines for determining an appropriate sample size. For most research, a sample size exceeding 30 and fewer than 500 respondents is considered suitable. If multivariate analysis is employed, a sample size of at least ten times the number of variables in the study is necessary. Comrey and Lee (1992) assert that a sample size of 100 is inadequate, 300 is good and 500 is exceptionally good. Hence, existing research indicates a lack of definitive or precise guidance on determining sample size in the literature. Additionally, there is a scarcity of rigorous empirical studies thoroughly documenting gig workers' perceptions of engagement and the most efficient leadership functions that can be opted for by the front-line management to implement in the UK restaurant sector. This study represents the most comprehensive and rigorous analysis of the relationship between research constructs to date. Employing Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) in this analysis requires an empirical ratio of at least five observations for every estimated parameter (Green et al., 1989), with commonalities greater than 0.5. Therefore, the sample size under consideration for examination is 336 respondents.

3.6 Sampling

The samples for the qualitative research are generally purposive rather than informants due to the core aim of qualitative studies, which is based on generating an in-depth analysis rather than emphasising generalisability (Collis & Hussey, 2013; Bryman & Bell, 2007). The representativeness issues are less critical than understanding the investigated theme's in-depth problems. Thus, qualitative studies favour purposeful sampling over probability sampling (Etikan & Bala, 2017). The researcher utilises the key informant interviews to conduct this study while drawing on purposeful sampling as the most effective technique. The researcher selected information-rich cases while adopting the purposive sampling form, which is known to be the most efficient sample to fulfil the research question (Robinson, 2014).

Purposeful sampling consists of a variety of strategies. However, the researcher adopted theoretical sampling as a strategy to conduct this research due to its effectiveness in qualitative research. Also,

it authorises a theoretical coverage of the conceptual framework of the research (Marshall, 1996). It can be understood that sample selection and theory building are progressing simultaneously. The development of theory is shaped by collecting and analysing the primary data. Subsequently, the results of the analysis will enhance the gathering of additional information through the utilisation of new samples that will result in additional illustrations of the theory (Taherdoost, 2016).

Based on the sequential design adopted, this research is mainly based on the qualitative principle, which will focus on refining the ideas and developing a sample size that suits the study's aim and objective. According to Saunders et al. (2003), the qualitative researcher does not require large samples in quantitative research. Moreover, qualitative studies have no rules informing the ideal sample size (Oppong, 2013). The theoretical sampling adopted in this research aims to generate information covering all aspects of the study framework. The quality of the information gathered from the participants will become evident in the theories studied in this research and the newly emerging themes generated from the gathered data (Taherdoost, 2016).

The qualitative study will be conducted on the UK restaurant sector due to the dramatic emergence of the gig economy in the United Kingdom, specifically the restaurant sector. The restaurant industry is taking a significant portion of the gig economy which undoubtedly affects most of its business functions such as staffing, management and many other parts of the restaurants. In particular, restaurants that are adopting the gig economy tools to run their businesses, such as the hiring apps and food delivery apps, as well as the gig workers, occupy a significant stake in the labour force in the UK (Hennink, 2020). It can be seen that restaurants adopting applications to hire gig workers and mobile-based apps to sell and deliver food to consumers are actively engaged in the gig economy (Mohajan, 2018). A few considerations need to be taken into account by the researcher to gain reliability while adopting SME. Those considerations include the multivariate data distribution, the employment of the maximum likelihood estimation method, the model complexity, the missing data and the average error variance of indicators. The researcher has considered all those aspects while conducting this research, keeping the sample size between 150 and 500, as is ideal. Furthermore, it lacks missing data and other aspects such as the lack of absolute sample size and systematic empirical research. In addition, the researcher limited the estimated parameter number of empirical ratio observations to a minimum of five with higher commonalities than the minimum of 0.5.

3.7 The scale development and the research instruments

This part of the research is about developing a valid and reliable measure concerning the theoretical constructs relying on the qualitative study and the literature. The first phase of this process allowed the generation of several items, some of which were repeatable, encouraging the researcher to exclude them for parsimony reasons. Several experts have reviewed the generated items from the qualitative research, which allowed them to exclude the unnecessary measures to secure the relevance of the items to the scale and their accuracy. The researcher will demonstrate the information development process in the upcoming section.

3.7.1 The domain of construct determination

The content of the domain was developed mainly depending on the qualitative research and the literature that can be represented in the questionnaire development process. This research aims to cover the gap related to the gig workers' engagement relying on the drivers related to the leadership functions, as when it comes to the gig economy era those issues were not targeted by any previous studies. The researcher followed Churchill's (1979) paradigm to foster efficient measures allowing items to be produced. The literature and the interviews were the main sources in the process of developing focal constructs.

Table 10: The study constructs definitions

Constructs	Definitions	Major references
Front-line management and gig workers' engagement	The leadership and managerial approaches have been majorly impacted by the emergence of the gig economy and the gig workers in the UK restaurant sector due to the nature of the employees that require a better understanding of their needs and motives to develop the most efficient approach by the front-line management.	Sarangal et al. (2020); Majid et al. (2019); Mueller-Hanson & Pulakos (2018); Meijerink & Keegan (2019); Myung et al. (2020).
Leadership functions and gig workers' engagement	Leadership functions are the functions that leaders conduct while managing the employees, there are a variety of drivers that enhance the gig workers' engagement and a long list of them come under the functions conducted by leaders and managers in the UK restaurant sector.	Vogler et al. (2018); Iqbal et al. (2017); Jha & Kumar (2016); Gupta et al. (2017); Osabiya(2015); Myung et al. (2020); Ab-Latif et al. (2020).
Challenges of gig workers' engagement	Engaging a gig worker comes with a variety of challenges due to the nature of the gig workers as well as the employment concept that is making it even more challenging to engage them.	Suharno & Despinur (2017); Davis et al. (2020); Chaand Seo (2020); Kuhn et al. (2021); Rofcanin et al. (2017).

The gig economy in the restaurant sector	The gig economy has developed a new era in the restaurant industry where it has reshaped every single part of the industry including the labour market which has been affected by the delivery and hiring agencies apps which have directly and indirectly impacted the leadership and the engagement of employees.	Shin et al (2021); Chen et al (2019); Watson et al. (2021); Hyers & Kovacova (2018); Mahato et al. (2021); van der Burg et al. (2019); Ostoj (2019); Vyas (2021); Wilson (2017); Waring (2018).
Front-line management and gig workers in the UK restaurant sector	The leadership and managerial approaches have been majorly impacted by the emergence of the gig economy and the gig workers in the UK restaurant sector due to the nature of the employees that require a better understanding of their needs and motives to develop the most efficient approach by the front-line management.	Jha & Kumar (2016); Guay et al (2020); Werdhiastutie et al. (2020); Pereira et al (2022); Victor & Hoole (2017); Duggan et al. (2020).
Hiring and delivery apps and the labour market in the restaurant sector	The emergence of food delivery apps and hiring agencies has developed a new employment concept where employees are a single click from their next position which has created challenges for the management to keep their employees and engage them.	EY (2020); Suciu et al. (2019); Sibanda et al. (2021); Cha & Seo (2020); Laitinen (2021); Goods et al. (2019); Anwar & Graham (2021); Horney (2016); Kaine & Josserand (2019).
Engagement from a gig worker's perspective	Gig workers are mostly individuals who have chosen flexibility over the traditional secure position; this could show that gig workers are more into getting the job done and may not be into engagement. This has to be understood by the management to achieve the absolute engagement of the gig workers	Mousa & Chaouali (2022); Rothmann (2016); Davis et al (2020); Chandani et al. (2016); Gupta (2015); Bhuvanaiah & Raya (2015); Rucket al. (2017).
The gig workers' engagement development	The management needs to determine the drivers of the gig workers' engagement while efficiently using their functions to drive the gig workers' engagement.	Victor & Hoole (2017); Davis et al. (2020); Meijerink & Keegan (2019); Iqbal et al. (2017); Karanges et al. (2015); Xiong & Wen (2020); Nunkoo (2016).

Source: developed for the current study by the researcher

This study will examine the impact of the leadership functions on enhancing gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector. Thus, the literature review includes the gig economy, leadership, gig workers' engagement and the labour market in the restaurant sector.

The scales determined will be related to the items, domains as well as literature generated from journal articles and previous research that have directly and indirectly influenced the development of a conceptual framework for this research.

3.7.3 The development of item measurement

The paradigm of Churchill (1979) includes the generation of item measurement as a second step. Several criteria need to be considered in the scale development procedures, such as the level of readability of items, length, double-barrelled items and the negative and positively worded items (DeVillis, 2003). Relying on the literature and qualitative research, the constructs were developed representing a multi-item scale; each item was unique with a low correlation with the measured attributes, which prevents the passive attitude toward the object. In addition, according to Churchill (1979), single items have shown significant measurement errors. The items were generated mainly from the literature developing measures that were used in questionnaires. The researcher has developed some scales showing extensive reliability and validity based on previous studies. At an early stage of item generation, the research came up with 62 items. Table 9 demonstrates the research constructs with the initial items.

Table 11: The constructs of the initial items

Constructs	Total no. of initial items
Front-line management and gig workers' engagement	12
Leadership functions and gig workers' engagement	9
Challenges of gig workers' engagement	9
The gig economy in the restaurant sector	8
Front-line management and gig workers in the UK restaurant sector.	6
Hiring and delivery apps and the labour market in the restaurant sector	5
Engagement from a gig worker's perspective	7
The gig workers' engagement development	6

Source: The researcher

It is more efficient to use pilot testing in the process of questionnaire development, as it will allow participants to answer questions more easily. The pre-test study was utilised by the researcher to

gather reliable and valid measures. The 7-point Likert-type scale was used throughout the questionnaire moving from the very strongly agree interval to the very strongly disagree, which was given to gig workers to show the level of their agreement with a statement concerning the gig workers' engagement.

Table 12: The codes for items

Constructs	Items wording	Codes of items
Front-line management and gig workers' engagement		
	You will be more engaged if you are satisfied with the front-line management strategies.	FLMGE_1
	The collaboration approach from the front-line management influences your engagement.	FLMGE_2
	The learning and development approach from the front-line management including training influences your engagement.	FLMGE_3
	The management of performance access adopted by the front-line management influences your engagement.	FLMGE_4
	Being treated equally with the in-house workers by the management will enhance your engagement.	FLMGE_5
	Integration platforms can help increase your involvement which will eventually boost your engagement.	FLMGE_6
	The two-way feedback with the front-line management will enhance your engagement.	FLMGE_7
	A structured team approach with full-time employees if opted for by the front-line management can help influence your engagement.	FLMGE_8
	Efficient communication with the front-line management can boost your engagement.	FLMGE_9
Leadership functions and gig workers' engagement		
	The leadership functions can enhance gig workers' engagement if they are mastered by the management.	LFGE_1
	Being valued and involved can increase the willingness of engagement among gig workers.	LFGE_2
	Being treated equally with the permanent employees enhances your engagement.	LFGE_3
	Motivation is a very important driver for gig workers' engagement.	LFGE_4
	Efficient communication is considered a strong driver for the engagement of gig workers.	LFGE_5
	Teaming up with the in-house employees boosts gig workers' engagement.	LFGE_6

	Delegating some of the tasks to the gig workers enhances their engagement.	LFGE_7
Challenges of gig workers' engagement		
	The nature of the gig workers' employment system prevents them from being part of the team.	CGWE_1
	Effective communication cannot be achieved with gig workers.	CGWE_2
	Gig workers' motivations are different from full-time employees who are harder to define by the management due to the short term of gig employment.	CGWE_3
	Gig workers do not care much about the business value and reputation.	CGWE_4
	The management does not waste time briefing and training gig workers as they expect them to be ready to work.	CGWE_5
	It is hard for management to treat the gig workers equally with full-time employees.	CGWE_6
	The management is finding it hard to keep in-house employees from moving to the gig era.	CGWE_7
	The lack of comprehension of the engagement from the gig workers may prevent them from being fully engaged.	CGWE_8
	Not having a clear approach from the management to help engage you may affect your willingness to engage.	CGWE_9
	The hiring and food delivery apps are tempting traditional employees to move to the gig model and increase restaurant turnover.	CGWE_10
The gig economy in the restaurant sector		
	The gig economy has reshaped the labour market in the UK restaurant sector.	GIRS_1
	The gig economy is winning over traditional jobs in the UK restaurant sector.	GIRS_2
	The pandemic has enhanced the gig economy popularisation in the UK restaurant sector.	GIRS_3
	The gig economy has become a necessity for restaurants to sustain themselves in the market.	GIRS_4
	The gig economy has become the main source of income for many employees.	GIRS_5
	Flexibility and life balance are the two major reasons behind the shift of employees to the gig economy.	GIRS_6
	The gig economy has made leaving a job easier than ever for employees.	GIRS_7
	The gig economy has reshaped the labour market in the UK restaurant sector.	GIRS_8
Front-line management and gig workers in the UK restaurant sector.		

	Communication	FLMG_1
	Motivation	FLMG_2
	Training	FLMG_3
	Valuing and involving	FLMG_4
	Delegating tasks	FLMG_5
	Teamworking with in-house workers	FLMG_6
Hiring and food delivery apps and the labour market in the restaurant sector		
	Food delivery apps have revolutionised the employment market in the UK restaurant sector.	HFALM_1
	The flexibility offered by the gig economy is attracting employees from all industries to the UK restaurant sector.	HFALM_2
	Food delivery and hiring apps are increasing employee turnover in the UK restaurant sector.	HFALM_3
	Gig workers consider previous workers' reviews and rating of employers before accepting the offer.	HFALM_4
	Hiring and food delivery apps offer better pay and flexibility than traditional job positions.	HFALM_5
	Employees are relying on hiring apps and food delivery apps as their main source of income.	HFALM_6
	Gig workers repeat the experience with the same restaurant if they are happy with the front-line management.	HFALM_7
	Food delivery apps have revolutionised the employment market in the UK restaurant sector.	HFALM_8
Engagement from a gig worker's perspective		
	Gig workers go the extra mile if they are engaged.	EGWP_1
	Gig workers are always willing to be engaged.	EGWP_2
	Gig workers perform better if they are engaged.	EGWP_3
	Gig workers do not feel that are part of the restaurant.	EGWP_4
	Gig workers always seek permanent positions with the restaurants they are gigging for.	EGWP_5
	Gig workers do not care much about being valued and motivated by the management.	EGWP_6
	The gig workers will be more productive if they are engaged.	EGWP_7
The gig workers' engagement development		
	Communicating efficiently with gig workers will enhance their engagement.	GED_1
	Discovering what motivates gig workers and using it can boost the gig workers' engagement.	GED_2
	Relationships between full-time and gig workers can boost their engagement.	GED_3
	Delegating some tasks to gig workers improves their engagement.	GED_4

	Requesting the services of the gig workers all the time from the agency or the app will enhance their engagement.	GED _5
	Rating and valuing the gig workers' performance will encourage them to repeat the experience and increase their engagement.	GED _6
	Involving the gig workers in business events could enhance their involvement and appreciation level and encourage their engagement.	GED _7
	The more the gig workers are engaged, the better restaurant operations are performed.	GED _8
	Engaging employees will enhance their involvement in all parts of operations and allow them to run more smoothly.	GED _9

Source: developed for the current study by the researcher

3.7.4 Purifying the measurement scales

The third stage in Churchill's (1979) paradigm involves purifying the measurement scales to enhance progress. The computation of purifying measures is deemed roughly relevant to the chosen measurement paradigm. Hair et al. (2016) define validity as "the degree to which what the researcher was trying to measure was measured". In the initial phase, before commencing the main questionnaires, the researcher conducted two types of validity assessments: content validity and face validity. These subjective forms of 'validity' assist in determining the suitability of the survey. Furthermore, according to DeVellis (2003), content validity, which is judgmental in origin, is based on "the extent to which a specific set of items reflects a content domain." Five individuals in various managerial positions collaborated with the researcher to review the initial draft of the research survey and evaluate its credibility. These individuals have expertise in the gig workers domain within the restaurant sector, rendering them qualified to assess the questionnaire's content (Wieland et al., 2017). Their input was sought to verify the clarity of the wording and offer feedback on the appropriateness of the items; recommendations were highly valued. Furthermore, the individual participants discussed the significance of each statement and suggested which elements should be excluded. Subsequently, an evaluation was conducted to ensure that the items included in the tool adequately conveyed the main findings of the study. This process follows a precedent where experts evaluated a scale's field, providing informed opinions from experts in the field of study (Wieland et al., 2018)

The themes, issues and material associated with the measurement tool are deemed pertinent to the feature being tested (Wieland et al., 2018). After revisions, two individuals in very high managerial positions at big chains in the UK reviewed the survey to assess its face credibility and its suitability

as an item measure for the study's issue. The two managers were invited to respond to the survey and share their feedback on whether or not the questions demonstrated the purposeful phrasing, construct, layout and ease of completion. The items derived from the literature were scrutinised alongside the responses gathered from interviews with managers. Participants suggested some questions to be removed and others to be adjusted for clarity reasons. The leading research on employee engagement, such as Kahn (1992, as cited in Bakker et al., 2014) and Saks (2006, as cited in Rai and Maheshwari, 2020), acknowledged the significance of leadership and its roles and functions in aiding front-line management to enhance gig workers engagement in the UK restaurant sector. The majority of the research focused on communication, motivation and collaboration alongside many drivers that show a positive impact on the engagement of gig workers (Srivastava and Dhar, 2016). Furthermore, some of the drivers that were argued not to come under the leadership function were eliminated based on the opinions of managers. Before the pilot test of the survey, two managers assessed the lexical accuracy, and four managers verified the appearance of the pre-test component (Kramer et al., 2019).

3.8 Quantitative evaluation

The questionnaire was reviewed throughout the qualitative study to evaluate the themes. The participants proposed several changes regarding the survey of this research based on conducting a pilot study to check the validity of the constructs together with assessing the reliability of the scale's measurement (Malhotra et al., 2017).

3.8.1 Pilot study

In the process of developing the measurement instrument and completing the questionnaire, a pilot study needs to be conducted in the primary survey. The pilot study is about evaluating the core requirements such as layout and form, sequence test, questions' wording, response rate, difficulty and instruction of the questions, and the questionnaire completion time in the purifying procedures. Thus, the pre-test purpose is to clarify the questionnaire and exclude ambiguous items in the pilot study (Saunders et al., 2007). The questionnaire testing was conducted for two weeks, including 50 participants with 12 questionnaires showing low-quality responses, which qualified 38 questionnaires to be tested. The number of respondents was within the range scales that allowed the process of testing the survey to be efficient. The 38 participants were gig workers in different

positions throughout the UK restaurant sector. Those participants will be part of the final study due to their likeliness to be influenced by the pilot study responses.

The researcher gathered a total of 38 respondents in the instrument purifying process to assess the validity and reliability. Using Cronbach's alpha is ideal for evaluating and measuring the consistency of variables while reaching reliability. Developing and investigating the reliability is the stage before conducting the primary survey Melewar (2001, p. 39). In addition, exploratory factor analysis will be utilised to determine the data patterns and minimise the items (Bryman & Bell 2007). The scale has shown high reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of all constructs scaling between .932 and .959; according to Hair et al. (1998), all coefficient alpha above 0.70 are ideal for research.

3.8 Data analysis

The constant comparative method is adopted alongside theoretical sampling by the researcher to efficiently oversee the qualitative analysis (Boeije, 2002). Yet, qualitative research relies on comparison as the dominant principle of the analysis procedures. The researcher utilises the constant comparative method to analyse the participants' responses effectively. This method is used alongside the NVivo software to analyse the qualitative data (Bryman and Bell, 2007). Evidently, the development of the theoretical framework is subsequently conducted with the data collection, which has allowed the researcher to explain the building approach for the qualitative analysis (Hounslow, 2018). The researcher used the themes and the literature as a starting point for the collection and the analysis. This helped the researcher gather ideas from interviews and questionnaires and compare them with the ideas generated from the conceptual framework and the literature review (Irwin, 2008). The data analysis procedure includes first disaggregating the qualitative data gathered into meaningful and accompanying groups through open coding. Classification is coded where each particular code will represent a specific element of the phenomenon under research (Horsburgh, 2003). The reorganisation and the synthesis of the coded divisions drive the creation of themes and patterns that can be utilised to confront the current theories. Then, the research utilised selective coding to designate the connection among the constructs (Collis & Hussey, 2003). The researcher efficiently interprets the review to discover the impact of the gig economy on the restaurant sector in general and how the leadership functions can drive gig workers' engagement in particular (Patton, 2005). Quantitative studies mainly depend on reliability and validity measures to evaluate the results' quality. The qualitative outcomes' quality is measured through an important criterion called trustworthiness, which can be

accomplished through the efficient utilisation of the thematic sample that will permit the researcher to cover every single element of the study questions (Grolemond & Wickhman, 2014). Moreover, the trustworthiness of the findings can be enhanced through the repeated usage of the coding procedure throughout the research by the same researcher (Ngulube, 2015). The researcher has gone through three stages in analysing the data for this study: the scaling and refining of qualitative and quantitative data content, the scale validations reflection of those contents and, finally, testing the final model. The researcher has used the multi-scale development on all constructs to minimise measurement error and maximise reliability. The three approaches opted by the researcher were: exploratory factor analysis (EFA), which covered the coefficient alpha to evaluate the quality of instruments and the reliability of the scales; confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to evaluate the properties measurement of the existing scales' validity; and structural equation modelling (SEM) to examine the research themes. SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) was used in the initial stage of the data analysis to help the researcher to edit and review the missing data and the assumptions of normality, linearity, outliers and multi-collinearity. In addition, the software helped the researcher to determine the focal tendency and the dispersions of the variables, mean, calculation of the standard deviation and analysis of frequencies. EFA can be one of the reasons for using the software, together with reliability and validity analysis, among several other benefits.

3.9 Data analysis and Statistical techniques

The data analysis in this research unfolds in three phases. The initial phase involves refining the scales and content based on the data obtained from both quantitative and qualitative sources. The second phase entails the validation of scales, aligning with survey responses and quantitative data. The third phase involves examining the completed paradigm (Luo et al., 2019). It is essential to emphasise that multiscale development should be applied to all constructs to maximise measurement error and enhance dependability. Following Churchill's (1979) recommendation of utilising multi-item scales over single-item measures, this study employed three distinct methods for data analysis. The initial approach, EFA, was utilised in the pilot project to reduce the items and identify potential data trends before proceeding to the main investigation (Watkins, 2018). Coefficient alpha was employed in a qualitative data analysis to evaluate the instrument's quality and the credibility of the scales, following the guidelines of Churchill (1979) and Hair et al. (2016). To assess the measurement qualities associated with the validity of the current scales. Field (2009) utilised the second method, CFA, on the principal questionnaire data. This method is valuable

when scales need reconstruction for further examination in structural modelling and is employed to verify the variables'. To investigate each construct and prevent potential connections between measurements and structural models, the third strategy – SEM – was implemented, as recommended by Williams et al. (2010).

Several researchers have confirmed the use of SPSS software in their studies, including Hair et al. (2016) and Tabachnick and Fidell (2007). The use of SPSS as the first step in data analysis is justified due to the diverse goals it serves. The initial goal involves coding, amending and checking missing data. The second goal is to examine the assumptions related to multicollinearity, linearity and outliers concerning normality. The third goal of using SPSS is to demonstrate the computation of analysis frequencies, including the standard deviation, variables and mean dispersions. Reliability analysis was also employed to assess the validity of the data and the instrument's reliability, considering that refinement depended on reliability and dimensionality (Luo et al., 2019). This examination aims to assess the scales used in evaluating the constructs and refining measurements. The researcher utilised Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) due to its distinctive graphical user interface to evaluate the quality of the provided measurement paradigm and structural model. As suggested by Hair et al. (2016), AMOS was implemented by advancing with the structural model and CFA. The detailed features of these techniques, along with the rationale for choosing them, are explained in the following sections (Watkins, 2018).

3.9.1 Coefficient alpha and exploratory factor analysis

EFA plays a crucial role in the initial phases of scale validation (Netemeyer et al., 2003). This method is instrumental in reducing the number of observed variables (indicator variables) making them more manageable through an exploratory, data-driven approach (Hair et al., 2016). According to Hair (2013), EFA ensures that any individual factor should account for the difference of at least one single variable. This aspect is vital for understanding the independent aspects and identifying the structure of a specific field (Field, 2009). By using EFA, the study can identify the data and determine the number of likely factors that accurately reflect the data. The initial EFA method helps prepare data for SEM (Hair et al., 2016). The principal components approach was employed for factor extraction (Effendi et al., 2019). This technique estimates the minimum number of significant variables needed to display the largest amount of variance encompassing unique, common and error variance. To condense the number of variables into a more manageable set of independent variables, this study utilises the orthogonal Varimax rotation method. As stated by Hooper (2012) an efficient predictive method involves using the retained variables.

Eigenvalues, guided by the latent root criterion (eigenvalue >1.00), were employed to determine the number of variables to extract (Malhotra et al., 2017).

3.9.2 Structural equation modelling (SEM)

In this study, the Amos software package is utilised to facilitate the application of structural equation modelling (SEM), offering insight into the diverse interactions and impacts of each dependent variable (Field, 2013). The proposed conceptual framework underwent testing through a literature review, and constructs were assessed using a structural equation model. As per Thakkar (2020), SEM encompasses various statistical methods that enable the testing of multiple connections between discrete or continuous independent factors and discrete or continuous dependent variables. Structure equation modelling is associated with robust explanatory power, where factors or variables under evaluation can be considered either exogenous or endogenous. The terms 'causal modelling, causal analysis, simultaneous equation modelling, analysis of covariance structures, path analysis, or confirmatory factor analysis' are also employed to refer to SEM, as indicated by Barrett (2007). The SEM data in this study will be analysed in two steps. First, CFA will be employed to support all constructs, examining the measurement characteristics of the key latent variables in the paradigm. According to the premise of Unidimensionality, the measurement model elucidates the relationships between the corresponding latent and observed indicators' constructs (Hair et al., 2016). Unidimensionality is characterized by multiple indicators reflecting a single fundamental concept (Thakkar, 2020). CFA initially examined the Unidimensionality of scale and EFA further refined it (Streiner, 2006). This phase, crucial for ensuring the standardised factor loading values are 0.6 or higher, involves the confirmatory measurement model, establishing a robust linkage between respective constructs and observed variables (Barrett, 2007). The analysis was conducted to verify the internal consistency of each group of items. The validity and reliability of the construct are pivotal for exploring potential theories. CFA, following EFA, facilitates the computation of additional estimates for construct reliability, or composite reliability (Field, 2013).

3.9.3 The Unidimensionality

Uni-dimensionality provides robust support for the measurements, but it alone is insufficient for establishing construct validity. According to Cronbach's (1984) definition of Unidimensionality, A set of items is 'Unidimensional' if the sequence of difficulty is similar across all individuals in a

population of interest. In this context of unidimensional items, there exists only one fundamental construct (Ziegler & Hagemann, 2015). To distinguish measurement concerns from structural problems in the model, Uni-dimensionality is often assessed using estimated model specifications and structural equation analysis. Lumsden (1961) defined operationalising Uni-dimensionality as employing structural equation analysis for both interior and exterior consistency. Consistency has been modelled as a structural equation model to align with the data (Ziegler & Hagemann, 2015). By Anderson and Gerbing's (1982) definition, X, X1, and X2 represent indicators of consistency. They are internally consistent if the correlation among them equals the correlation of their respective X constructs. Similarly, external consistency is achieved if the relationship within z and x is analogous to the three correlations (X with Z, Z with its construct Z, and with its construct) for two distinct indices of X and Z, X and Z are consistent (Ziegler & Hagemann, 2015). External consistency is considered optimal when objects "cluster together in a matrix of sorted or ordered similarity coefficients" (Hair et al., 2016). There is a subtle but potential difference between the latent variable reliability (ρ) and coefficient alpha (α) for unidimensional constructs that have sufficient information. The use of coefficient alpha involves evaluating reliability as an initial measure (Ziegler & Hagemann, 2015).

3.9.4 Composite reliability assessment

CFA enables the assessment of more intricate reliability, specifically construct reliability (Field, 2013). Composite reliability, according to Field (2013), assesses the consistency of the internally measured variables and reflects the reliability of the latent construct. Raykov (1997) emphasises that composite reliability is a crucial metric for evaluating the overall dependability of the measurement model for each latent component (Peterson & Kim, 2013). A minimum composite reliability value of 0.7 is required to demonstrate that the aggregate measures consistently capture the same latent construct (He, 2009). According to Hair et al. (2016), the Uni-dimensionality indices, denoted by inter-correlation with their latent constructs, are measured by the reliability of contracts, as illustrated by Cronbach's alpha.

3.9.5 Average variance extracted (AVE)

The average variance extracted (AVE), as indicated by Diamantopoulos et al. (2012), quantifies the reciprocal variance in a latent variable (LV), representing the amount of variance that the LV displays about the variance due to arbitrary measurement error. In other words, AVE measures the error-free variance of multiple elements. Dos Santos and Cirillo (2023) suggest that, unlike

composite reliability, AVE serves as an indicator of effective construct reliability. AVE is a measure of the total variance captured by the relevant indicators, accounting for measurement error; it should be 0.50 or higher to ensure the validity of the scale under examination and to support the use of a concept (Field, 2013). According to Dos Santos (2022), "the validity of the construct is doubtful if it is below 0.50, as the variance due to measurement error is greater than the variance captured by the construct"

3.9.6 Strategies for structural equation modelling (SEM)

The SEM data in this study will be analysed in two steps. First, the confirmatory factor analysis will be employed to support all constructs, examining the measurement characteristics of the key latent variables in the paradigm. According to the premise of unidimensionality, the measurement model elucidates the relationships between the corresponding latent and observed indicators' constructs (Hair et al., 2010). in unidimensionality is characterized by multiple indicators reflecting a single fundamental concept (Field, 2009). Confirmatory factor analysis initially examined the unidimensionality of scale and exploratory factor analysis further refined it (Steenkamp and Baumgartner, 2000). This phase, crucial for ensuring the standardized factor loading values are 0.6 or higher, involves the confirmatory measurement model, establishing a robust linkage between respective constructs and observed variables (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012). The analysis was conducted to verify whether the internal consistency of each group of items. Validity and reliability of the construct are pivotal for exploring potential theories. Confirmatory factor analysis CFA, following exploratory factor analysis (EFA), facilitate the computation of additional estimates for construct reliability, or composite reliability (Handerson and Gerbing, 1982, Field, 2013).

The second phase involves a structural model analysis to confirm the causal relationship between latent constructs and the measurement development, establishing the relationships between constructs and their indicators (Hair et al., 2010). All constructs can be measured by latent variables, observable variables, or both.

3.9.7 Evaluating the model suitability

Confirmatory factor analysis facilitates the confirmatory phase by allowing a statistical analysis of dimensionality and goodness-of-fit for a specific measurement model. This analysis is based on the overall control of the characterization of constructs' indicators (Field, 2013).

The aim of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is to Confirm and validate the measurement elements associated with various variables in the theoretical model (Field, 2013). The Bollen (1989) method, which considers unidimensional measurements, is often employed to evaluate reliability of multidimensional measures. As per Novick and Lewis (1967), effective use of coefficient alpha requires Unidimensionality. And the assessment of the goodness-of-fit assessment of any model takes into account theoretical, statistical, and practical considerations.

This section delineates the implementation of methodological literature recommendations for confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) , which encompass model parsimony indices, absolute fit indices, and incremental fit indices within the framework of this research.

First, this investigation employs both incremental fit indicators and absolute fit indices. Absolute fit indices, as advocate by Field (2013), are utilised to test both the measurement models and the overall structural model. These indices signify the extent to which the proposed model replicates the sample data. Unlike incremental fit indices, absolute fit indices do not necessitate the use of alternative models for differentiation. Goodness-of-fit indicators are employed to assess the nomological validity of the measurement models. The specific fit indicators utilised in this study are elaborated upon the following section

The chi-square (χ^2) statistic is a widely used method to asses goodness-of-fit. This metric is considered a fundamental fit measure incorporated in AMOS.. According to Hair et al. (2012), a non-significant result suggests no significant difference between the observed and expected matrices, while a small χ^2 value , indicating lack of significance, would suggest a good fit. The purpose of the chi-square analysis is to evaluate the congruence between the observed and expected matrices

P-values are utilized to determine whether the goodness-of-fit model significantly differs from the null model, where "0" represents the null in statistics. Applying the null construct to a substantial probability would be inappropriate if the p-value exceeds 0 (MacLean and Gray, 1998). A low or nearly zero p-value suggests rejecting the null construct with a low probability of making an incorrect decision to arrive at the correct conclusion. The discrepancies between Both matrices must be statistically comparable ($p > .05$). criticism has been directed at relying heavily on χ^2 to assess the goodness-of-fit for the entire model, as it is highly sensitive to sample size (Qu et al., 2013, Tabachnick and Fidell 2007).

MacLean and Gray (1998) suggested that a model with a $\chi^2/d.f.$ ratio of three or less fits the data reasonably. The chi-square is significantly influenced by the sample size, especially when the number of observations exceeds 200. If data deviates from normalcy, the χ^2 value exceeds the

expected error in the model. The genuine fit measure for structural models, the lowest passable norm chi-square (also known as T. Chi-square), lacks set guidelines and needs to be considered alongside additional indicators (Field, 2013). χ^2 is considered the genuine fit index and is typically reported in SEM outcomes.

The goodness-of-fit index (GFI), introduced by Jorgeskog and Sorbom in 1982, is the primary metric for the main model, providing a fit statistic with minimal dependence on sample size. It measures the degree of variance and covariance close to sample covariance matrix, reflecting in the population covariance matrix. values close to 1 indicate a good fit, with the GFI range between 0 and 1. It is set to 1 when the index is above 1 and to 0 when below 1. The GFI is expected to fall between 0.90 and 1.00 for a satisfactory match, between 0.80 and 0.89 for an acceptable match, and values below 0.8 are considered inadequate (Qu et al., 2013). Variance is a fundamental concept guiding assessments of the model's goodness-of-fit.

The Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index (AGFI), utilised to asses rival models, considers the model's degree of freedom the null model, is useful for quickly assessing rival models (Field, 2013). The AGFI like GFI, incorporate χ^2 in its calculation, but it adjust GFI for the degree of freedom, resulting in a smaller value for models with numerous parameters. AGFI and GFI concur in terms of altering the range of general squares through the addition of main squares. An appropriate fit is indicated by an AGFI greater than 0.90(Zhang et al., 2020).

As suggested by Byrne (2001), Field (2013), Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), Teo (2011), and other references, AGFI values range from 0 to 1, with good values falling within 0.9 and 1. Values in the range of 0.80 and 0.89 are considered a reasonable fit (Qu et al., 2013).

When assessing model fit, the root-mean-square error of approximation (RMSEA) is a highly useful criterion. This index is considers the number of parameters (MacLean and Gray, 1998) and evaluate the discrepancy between the sample and fitted covariance matrices relative to the degree of freedom (Steiger, 1990). The root-mean-square error of approximation measures discrepancies in the population not the sample, indicates how well a model fits a given population (Field, 2013). A good fit is indicated by a value less than 0.05, while a reasonable fit is suggested by a value between 0.08 and 0.10. A poor fit is indicated by values exceeding 0.08 (Byrne, 2001; Field, 2013; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Teo, 2011).

Secondly, as per Hair et al. (2012), the incremental fit indices assess the extent to which the proposed models align with a specific null model. The present study elaborated on several incremental fit metrics. According to Hair et al. (2012), the normed fit index (NFI) is designed to compare hierarchical models. disregarding the degree of freedom, the comparison procedure is

linked to the proposed model. Additionally, it calculates the ratio that improved the model's fit when compared to the original model (Field, 2013). NFI compares the model's chi-square value to the independence model's chi-square value (Byrne, 2001; Field, 2013; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). According to Teo (2011), the normed fit index (NFI) measure is criticized for ignoring fit in small samples and lacking control over the degrees of freedom. In response to these limitations, an upgraded version known as the comparative fit index (CFI) has been introduced (Byrne, 2001; Field, 2013; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Teo, 2011).

The comparative fit index CFI is based on the metrics of non-centrality, with a representation of 1 indicating a strong fit when it is above 1 and 0 when it is below 0. A CFI near 1 is considered indicative of a strong fit, and it is dependent on the average size of the correlations in the data (field, 2013). Additionally, a low CFI suggests a low average linkage among the variables regarding Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) or non-normed fit index (NNFI), it involves comparing the chi-square value of the model to the independence, Taking into account the degree of freedom in both models. Field, 2013; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Teo, 2011). LTI is based on the average size of correlations in the data and makes a mathematical comparison between the baseline null model and various theoretical measurement models (Field, 2013). Anderson and Gerbing (1982) defined acceptable as values as falling within 0.8 and 0.89 and good as values as 0.9 and above. while not its primary goal, this index (TLI) has been parsimoniously adjusted.

3.9.8 Nomological validity

Nomological validity is a critical aspect of achieving construct validity in theory construction and testing (Hair et al., 2016). It involves assessing the linkages among multiple constructs and experimental link within multiple constructs' measurements.(Peter and Churchill, 1986). Nomological validity examines whether the behaviour of constructs is consistent with what was predicted in both empirical and theoretical terms, including the predicted measure's behaviour in the manner advised by Peter and Churchill (1986). Goodness-of-fit indicators must be used to assess the nomological validity of the measurement models (Hair et al., 2016).

3.9.9 Convergent validity

Convergent validity refers to the homogeneity of the concept and the degree to which independent measures of one construct converge or exhibit positive correlations with various measures of the same construct (Malhotra et al., 2017). According to Diamantopoulos et al. (2012), convergent validity can be assessed in connection to concept credibility. Each construct item's internal

consistent validity (low or high correlation) is related to convergent validity (Fornell and Larckers 1981). Convergent validity can also be expressed in terms of average variance obtained, composite reliability, and item credibility. Additionally, assessing the t-values and the significance level of the factor is crucial. Each construct shows excellent inter-item correlations, suggesting convergent (Shiu et al., 2009). Accordingly, measures with credibility greater than 0.85 indicate an error variance of over 50%, and reliability with a value of 0.7 and above indicates convergent validity (Field, 2009).

3.9.10 Discriminant validity

According to Malhotra et al (2017) discriminant validity refers to the degree to which one construct's measures are not highly linked with the measures of other constructs. Therefore, it is valid provided that there is a negative correlation between the experimental measure and the measurements of every construct (Shiu et al., 2009). Accordingly, discriminant validity is established if the association between two constructs is less than 1.00 (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012). Anderson and Gerbing (1982) suggest that discriminant validity "The evaluation of two estimated constructs can involve conducting a chi-square difference test on the values obtained for the constrained and unconstrained model. This process includes constraining the estimated correlation parameter between them to 1.00." .There is evidence of discriminant validity when the constrained model shows a worse fit than the unconstrained model. The square correlation for each construct and the average variance extracted (AVE) can be used to quantify discriminant validity (Malhotra et al., 2017). It is suggested that each concept possesses more error-free variance (either internal or extracted) than variance shared with other constructs when the squared correlation between two latent variables is less than all of their individual AVEs (r^2). Additionally, they should exhibit higher internal correlation than they do with other constructs, as demonstrated by Fornell and Larker (1981), this observation implies discriminant, indicating the successful extraction of targeted variance. In summary, the construct's unidimensionality (Hair et al., 2016), nomological validity, discriminant validity, convergent validity, and credibility as advocated by Peter and Churchill (1986) are all crucial aspects of validity that play a significant role in reinforcing the investigation for execution of structural model analysis is this research

3.10 Ethical considerations

According to Saunders et al. (2010), ethics refers to the set of behaviours which secure the rights and the privacy of the authors. Sauder et al. (2010) stated that ethics can be defined as the behaviour that guarantees the rights of those implicated and influenced by the research. In this study, the research will use secondary data to gather data that is unlikely to cause some ethical issues in its process (Connelly, 2014). Honesty in using, analysing and providing data is one of the ethical issues that the researcher should consider due to its impact on the analysis of the case study. Moreover, the outcomes and the objectivity in analysing the findings required the researcher to analyse the gathered data (Cacciattolo, 2015). Academic research must adhere to relevant ethical guidelines governing investigative activities. This adherence encompasses ethical standards outlined by organisations such as the British Educational Research Association and the West of Scotland Business School. Observing the fundamentals of ethical research and understanding its impact on the conducted work is paramount. Numerous ethical issues are common to all social and business scholars (Valentine et al., 2014). It is the duty of each researcher to conduct studies appropriately, considering a specific and relevant topic. In this work, every fundamental ethical factor is carefully considered. First and foremost, participants have the right to protect the statutory rights of the social research group by avoiding unnecessary disruption, obtaining participants' consent and ensuring their privacy. Second, it is imperative to clearly articulate the purpose of the study's enquiries to adhere to research ethics. Third, the researcher should consider cultural and social distinctions. Fourth, the public is more likely to trust an approach that yields satisfactory information. The cover letter in this study explicitly communicates these points and the survey is designed to respect people's privacy. The researcher has considered extra precautions to avoid bias with the interview due to his prior direct and indirect knowledge of some of the interviewees; this was addressed through clear communication that the process should be approached professionally as it is part of research and that their responses would be treated confidentially. In addition, the researcher developed well-defined questions that were used for all participants using neutral language and allowed the participants to express their views independently to avoid leading them toward a particular response. Furthermore, the researcher focuses on the research topic and avoids discussing personal matters to keep the interview on the professional path. The anonymity of the responses helped the interview to be conducted professionally. All these have helped the researcher to avoid biases in the research interviews.

3.11 Summary

This chapter of the research aims to illustrate and discuss the methodology utilised to examine the conceptual mode employed by the researcher and the philosophy. This study addressed the data collection process's significant issues, including the quantitative and qualitative phases (Saris & Gallhofer, 2014). The researcher illustrated the analysis unit, the survey instrument choice and the targeted participants of this study. Moreover, the researcher explained the techniques used in the data analysis process (Taguchi, 2009). The methodology employed to conduct this research was deeply discussed, moving from the chosen philosophy. The research methodology is one of the essential parts of any research due to its role in the process of gathering the necessary data as well as selecting the most efficient tools to analyse the data and interpret it in analysing applicable theories and ideas that can enable the research to investigate effectively and answer the research questions.

Chapter 4: Qualitative data

(Management aspects)

4.1. Introduction

Qualitative research is based on utilising unstructured methods, encouraging interviewees to utilise their unique interpretations, which will come up with fresh insights. The chapter above covered the usefulness of the methodology adopted in this research. The researcher will present the interviews and questionnaire outcomes in this chapter.

The researcher aims to collect further comprehensive information to enhance understanding of the gig economy and the leadership functions as drivers of gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector. The qualitative findings gathered in this research are based on over 22 interviews with individuals at different managerial levels, including big chains and corner shops. Furthermore, questionnaires were utilised in this thesis to understand gig workers' engagement in the restaurant sector and the influence of management roles in enhancing and driving their engagement. This study's findings will be presented in a thematic way that was developed regarding the interview questions and answers.

4. 2 Qualitative study: results

Drilling down to the research topic is one of the qualitative study's core objectives for efficiently comprehending and testing surface features. This part of the research will present a report of the data and findings that contributed to the theme's development of this study on how leadership functions can enhance gig workers' engagement. The research analysis in this part of the study has identified the elements that encourage gig workers to emerge together with understanding the relation of their engagement with the front-line management and how the leadership functions can be utilised to enhance gig worker engagement.

4.3 Gig workers' engagement

4.3.1 Front-line management and gig workers' engagement

Most participants confirmed the importance of gig workers' engagement for businesses aiming to achieve high productivity and performance within restaurants to provide better food and services

for consumers, increasing sales. This is coherent with the prior research, which has shown a compelling relationship between front-line management and employee engagement (Sharma et al., 2016). Furthermore, the interviewees acknowledged the benefits and the importance of engaging employees in the smooth running of their business to developing a collaborative atmosphere allowing better communication among employees and management, in line with Paulas and Kenworthy's (2019) findings, which argued that collaboration could develop efficient communication that can lead to engaged employees. Front-line management appears to admit the importance of engaging gig workers, as pointed out by the quotes below:

"Employee engagement is very important for restaurants to perform better and to increase their productivity in addition to that he stated that engaging employees in the restaurant will allow operations to run more efficiently and smoothly which enhances customer service and increase customer satisfaction." (Supervisor 1)

Similarly, another participant added:

"I always tell my managers to focus on engaging their employees including the gig workers due to their importance in increasing the employee's productivity allowing better communication that will lead to better gig workers satisfaction and better customer satisfaction." (Owner 1)

It is clear from the views stated above that the front-line management is fully aware of the importance of their role in engaging gig workers' engagement alongside their acknowledgement of the importance of gig workers' engagement in enhancing productivity together with consumer satisfaction.

In the same line with the interviewees suggesting the importance of equal treatment, feedback as a motivator and efficient communication, the literature has highlighted other front-line management roles that seem to trigger engagement among gig workers covering two-way feedback, learning and development, efficient communication and treating employees equally. According to Guay et al. (2020), Ryan and Deci (2020) and Tucker (2017), various front-line management roles were argued to help engage the gig worker, including efficient communication, collaboration and motivation. The interviewees agreed with some of the statements mentioned above; this will be illustrated in the quotes below:

"I always rely on my roles and functions to efficiently deal with employees and make them more productive and engaged to allow the business to run in a better way. Employee engagement is one other part of the business that can be influenced by the

roles and the functions of the management for this can include communication, feedback and motivation" (Head Chef 1)

In the same line, this shop owner added:

"Engaging employees does not have single approaches and steps to be achieved as they vary from one manager to another and from one business to another and from one employee to another." (Owner 2)

However, [...] he always feels that with the appropriate use of his roles and functions can understand those differences and determine the right approach to help employees to engage and that he sees the equal treatment between gig workers and in-house employees can motivate the gig worker to be engaged and facilitate communication among all individuals in the restaurant.

The interviews have shown evidence in acknowledging the importance of engaging gig workers for both employees and businesses, as well as the role of the front-line management to help the gig workers to engage through collaboration, equal treatment and efficient communication. Most of it was in line with the literature that suggested that motivation, communication and collaboration as core roles that can efficiently be adopted by front-line management to engage gig workers (Guay et al., 2020; Ryan and Deci, 2020; Tucker, 2017).

4.3.2 Leadership functions and gig workers' engagement

The participants agreed that the leadership functions could enhance gig workers' engagement if the management efficiently utilised them. In addition, the interviewees say that there is a set of leadership functions that enhance gig workers' engagement, which is the reward, value, communication and motivation and include them in the team, while less important other participants have chosen training and delegating tasks.

All interviewees strongly agreed on the importance of the leadership functions in engaging gig workers if they were efficiently employed by the front-line management. This is consistent with the findings of Gupta et al. (2017), which indicated leadership functions are important factors that can enhance gig workers' engagement. Thus, it is no surprise that participants had different views regarding different functions. In the same line, prior studies have highlighted various functions, including reward and value, communication, motivation and teamwork and training and delegating tasks (Gupta et al., 2017; Saks, 2017; Al Maktoum, 2015). Participants have shown various views regarding leadership functions in engaging gig workers, as proven by the quotes below:

"Despite seeing gig workers as members of the team it is too risky to delegate significant jobs to them." (Owner 8)

[...] not delegating important tasks to gig workers is not a sort of underestimation, but it is more related to their lack of information regarding circumstances surrounding the workplace.

In the same line, another participant asserted that:

"The delegation of important tasks to giggers can affect the operation of services massively due to their lack of knowledge regarding how things are done in-house [...] gig workers can follow but not lead, though, delegating core tasks are meant to be given to permanent workers that are more knowledgeable regarding work environment and can accomplish the task more efficiently." (Owner 5)

These statements demonstrate that front-line managers are aware that the delegation of tasks to gig workers is not an efficient function when it comes to the engagement of gig workers, and it may have negative outcomes on the overall operation of services and the in-house employees.

On the other hand, another interviewee asserted that:

"I see delegating some of the tasks to gig workers as a great way of motivating them. [...] I delegate secondary tasks to gig workers as a way to make them feel more valuable and they are part of the team as delegating some tasks to gig workers will encourage them to be more efficient and feel more comfortable with team members." (Owner 4)

This interviewee quote is consistent with Jha and Kumar's (2016) findings that stressed delegation as a leadership function that can enhance gig workers' engagement alongside other functions. Research indicates that the development of teamwork spirit among employees can positively influence gig workers' engagement (Al Maktoum, 2015; Truss et al., 2013). It is foreseeable that interviewees agreed on the efficiency of development of teamwork among gig workers and in-house employees concerning engagement. The participant quotes will be illustrated below:

"I always work on developing teamwork among the gig and in-house workers as I see it as the best approach to motivate the gig workers to engage as well as to let the in-house workers be part of the engagement process. [...] alongside allowing the gig workers to be part of the team, relied on communication and appreciation as efficient methods that can help gig workers to engage." (Manager 6)

Along the same line, another interviewee commented:

"Teaming up my gig workers and full-time employees can be very challenging for me. Yet if it is done efficiently, most of the time I get the best results that can ever be achieved and both permanent employees and gig workers are more engaged and involved in all business operations". (Owner 2)

Both interviewee statements illustrated above suggested that the efficient development of teamwork among all employees is important for the enhancement of the gig workers' engagement.

In the same vein, another restaurant owner stated that:

"I focus heavily on developing teamwork between my full-time employees and gig workers and in my experience, it can help the integration and involvement of the gig workers, increase the knowledge and the awareness of the gig workers on how things are done in-house which will eventually enhance their engagement" (Owner 7)

Efficient communication is believed by many studies to be among the most effective leadership function that can significantly enhance gig workers' engagement (Al Maktoum, 2015; Gupta et al., 2017). Furthermore, the literature has argued all the leadership functions are important while different managers rely more on different functions. This is noted in the quotation below:

"I see communication as the key to engaging employees including gig workers as it allows everyone to see where they are standing in the company. In addition to that, he said that motivation can play a huge role in engaging gig workers [...] the leadership functions can be used to motivate gig workers including including them in the team, rewarding them, valuing and appreciating them." (Owner 6)

In the same line, another participant affirmed that:

"I use the same functions with all employees. Although I focused on communication, motivation and teamwork as the main approaches to drive the engagement of the gig workers, I also relied less importantly on other functions whenever they were needed such as delegating tasks, rewarding and inviting the gig workers to the in-house events." (Owner 3)

Despite this, training employees has been mentioned in the literature by various studies (Gupta, 2015; Jha & Kumar, 2016; Mishra & Mohanty, 2016; Dessler, 2013; Simha & Vardhan, 2015). As a driver that can enhance employee engagement, most interviewees showed less interest in training gig workers as well as including them in the process of decision making due to a variety of reasons.

This is supported by the quote below:

"I expect gig workers to be experts at what they are doing, and the training is not something that will make a difference to them besides the time and cost consuming of the operation. Including the gig workers in the decision-making process will not be a good idea [...] [I] never allow the gig workers to make any decision unless there is no one to do so due to their lack of knowledge of the circumstances." (Supervisor 1)

Accordingly, another restaurant manager asserted that:

"I do not train the gig workers apart from some guidance to help them run the shift efficiently [...] most gig workers are good at what they are doing, and they were hired for their expertise [...] the decisions are made based on the knowledge of the surrounding business factor which is something that the gig workers lack and in-house employees seems to master better" (Manager 10).

Motivation has been mentioned in various research as a significant driver that can engage employees efficiently. It is no wonder that all participants agreed on the importance of this function in efficiently driving gig workers' engagement.

"All employees need to be motivated to perform better including to be engaged, I motivate my gig workers and permanent employees equally through various methods which help them to be engaged and involved. Throughout my long experience, I learned that while the employees are motivated, they will be physically and emotionally involved and engaged in the business." (Owner 8)

Therefore, in general, it can be summed up that leadership functions play a crucial role in engaging gig workers. However, the importance and the frequent adoption of the functions vary from one manager to another depending on the need and ability to apply them.

4.4 Challenges of gig workers' engagement

This study's findings support studies that indicate the unwillingness to engage is among the well-known challenges to management (Aslam et al., 2018; Allam, 2017). The outcome of the qualitative research argues that the engagement plans conducted by the management may impact the level of gig workers' willingness to engage. However, this may require more effort to be accomplished which according to most interviewees this cannot possibly be achieved due to the nature of gig workers' jobs that is based on spending limited time with the management preventing them from being adopted the management plans.

Along the same line, the quotes of participants will be illustrated below:

"I rely heavily on gig workers, throughout my long experience with gig workers I could not define a standard approach to manage or engage gig workers due to the nature of their positions which is mostly short for managers to efficiently understand the gig workers including the level of willingness to engage, the best way to communicate with them and motivate them" (Manager 5).

In the same vein, another owner asserted that:

"With no doubt, the engagement of the gig workers is very crucial to the management and the businesses. Yet, it requires a little effort and time to be fully understood which in most cases is not available due to the gig workers' nature of jobs and positions [...] the usage of the same approaches and methods with all workers will encourage the gig workers to be part of it and engage. On the other hand, this can shortly and efficiently allow me to define the ones that are ready to engage and the ones that are interested in the engagement." (Owner 6).

While some managers associated the challenges with the unwillingness of gig workers to engage, others suggested practical managerial solutions that can be used by the front-line management to overcome the lack of willingness to engage by gig workers. The quotes of the interviewees are stated below:

"In my opinion, the only way for managers to engage gig workers is to treat them equally with the full-time employees which will help to easily determine the willingness of the gig workers to be engaged and encourage the management to go the extra mile if it is needed to determine what motivates them and how they can efficiently be communicated with and motivated." (Manager 9)

Similarly, another owner commented:

"The bakery manager in Walthamstow has said that it is easy for him to treat the gig workers as the in-house employees while allowing the first move to happen from the gig workers which will show him how much are willing to be involved and engaged which will help him to help the ones that are interested in engaging and do not waste time with the ones that are not willing to engage." (Manager 11).

The qualitative study showed that the management does not find it hard to treat gig workers and in-house employees equally. Most interviewees agreed that it is easier and more efficient for them to treat all employees the same allowing the gig workers to feel that they are as valuable as full-time employees which can enhance their involvement making it easy for the management to determine the best way to communicate and motivate the gig workers.

"Treating the gig workers and full-time employees is the safest way to engage and manage both employees under one roof as the gig workers will be more involved, motivated and engaged without risking that full-time employees will not be appreciated treated as gig workers which will increase the risk of turnover." (Owner 1).

The equal treatment of all employees seems to be acknowledged by all participants as the best way that helps management tackle the unwillingness to engage, which has been defined by interviewees as a motivator that can enhance gig workers' engagement. The quote below evidences the statement and the quotes noted above:

"Treating all employees, the same can help gig workers feel valued which facilitates the management job in engaging them as well as in determining what motivates them the most and the best way to communicate with them. This can show the management how much they are willing to engage and allow them to draw the best approach to engage gig workers." (Manager 5).

Another head chef and shop owner believe that this method is important. Yet, the final call for the engagement has to come from the gig workers. This point of view was supported by the following quote:

"Pizza head chef in Walthamstow has said that it is easy for him to treat the gig workers as the in-house employees while allowing the first move to happen from the gig workers which will show him how much they are willing to be involved and engaged which will help him to help the ones that are interested in engaging and not waste time with the ones that are not willing to engage". (Head Chef 1)

Accordingly, a shop owner added:

"I treat all employees the same, but he expects the gig workers to earn that position and he cannot see how gig workers can do the same job as full-time and employees that are aware of every single thing about how operations are done in the restaurant." (Owner 5)

On the contrary, two interviewees affirmed the opposite point of view regarding the equal treatment of gig workers, which they believe is not effective and it may even worsen the relationship with the in-house employees. The quotes supporting this point of view will be illustrated below:

"It is not my job to engage employees and employees cannot be treated as in-house workers due to different job and personal related causes. Yet, that does not mean I treat the gig workers badly, but I expect them to be engaged and involved and always make the first move." (Manager 1)

In the same line, one interviewee stated that:

"I can never risk treating the gig workers as the full-time employees. Believing that this action can encourage the in-house employees to be tempted to move to the gig option" (Owner 7)

"I treat all employees the same, but I expects the gig workers to earn that position and I cannot see how gig workers can do the same job as full-time and employees that are aware of every single thing about how operations are done in the restaurant." (Owner 9).

The literature highlighted the defective managerial strategy and the lack of understanding of engagement as challenges that prevent the front-line management from engaging gig workers (McManus & Mosca, 2015). This was supported by the qualitative interviewees who see the efficient strategy employed by the management as the key to an efficient engagement alongside the full comprehension of the engagement by the management that will allow the managers to develop the right approach and strategies to engage gig workers. The quotes of the interviewees will be shown below:

"In the challenging management world, it is becoming a necessity for the management to comprehend all managerial functions including the employee engagement to allow an efficient strategy to be developed and enhance gig workers' engagement" (Owner 4)

In the same line, another manager stated:

"I feel like the right way to engage gig workers is to fully understand the engagement. Understanding the engagement will allow me to create the right method to approach the gig worker and boost their engagement" (Manager 10)

On the whole, the outcomes of the interviewees stressed significantly the challenges faced by the front-line management that could result in negative consequences on the gig workers' engagement. The challenges derived from the qualitative interviews can be summarised in an efficient understanding of the engagement, unclear strategy and approach from the management and the unwillingness to engage.

4.5 Gig economy

4.5.1 The gig economy in the restaurant sector

This study literature has agreed that the gig economy is inevitable concept in the restaurant industry, developing efficient solutions for both individuals and businesses (Khan, 2020; Gupta, 2019). Along the same line, the qualitative study findings strongly agree with the literature, suggesting that the gig economy has become a large part of restaurants and it should be largely considered by the management while operating and managing their businesses and employees. Accordingly, the interviewees' textual input reveals that businesses should be run around the gig economy and businesses' success is becoming strongly related to the understanding of the gig economy aspects. This matched what was mentioned in the literature review (Khan, 2020; Gupta, 2019). The comments illustrating the interviewees' appraisals will be stated below

"The gig economy in recent years has affected every single aspect of how businesses are operating as well as how leaders and managers are functioning [...] the gig economy is reshaping the traditional concept of the restaurant sector. businesses need to be part of the gig economy if they want to sustain" (Manager 1)

In the same vein, another supervisor stated that:

"The gig economy could be the only way to reach consumers and sell ready-to-eat food shortly. In addition, technically the gig economy has developed a new era where restaurants can reach unreachable consumers with an easy click on their smartphones" (Supervisor 1)

It is acknowledged by all participants that the gig economy is the future and there is no way for businesses aiming to sustain themselves to avoid being part of it. The gig economy has brought various benefits for both employees and employers.

Various studies have covered how the gig economy has revolutionized and reshaped the restaurant industry introducing new ways of purchasing ready-to-eat food and changing the traditional employment model (Hyers & Kovacova, 2018; Shin et al., 2021). Unsurprisingly, the qualitative interviews agreed with the literature highlighting the importance of food delivery and hiring apps in changing how business functions are conducted in the restaurant industry. The quotes below will demonstrate their point of view:

"The business operations have massively changed with the introduction of Deliveroo to the company and most sales are done through the app while fewer people are visiting the premises to get their food. The restaurant can seem very quiet, but employees are very busy serving consumers who have ordered from their homes and waiting for their food to be delivered by our delivery partner to their doorstep. [...] the delivery apps have developed new sources of income for businesses and have brought large benefits for both consumers and restaurants". (Manager 2)

In the same line, another owner asserted that:

"The management of business operations is being set around the figures gathered from the sales done through the apps as over half of several shops' sales are done through the app-based companies. Partnering with the delivery apps is becoming a necessity as consumers' concept of eating out has changed recently due to several reasons and ordering through the apps is becoming the new norm." (Owner 1)

After acknowledging the fact that the restaurant sector has been impacted by the so-called gig economy, changing the old traditional concept of the restaurant industry, it is important to comprehend how and what has caused these major changes. The suggestions gathered from participants will be illustrated below:

"I think it is necessary for managers nowadays to be aware of the gig economy and its aspects due to the rapid emergence of the phenomena that is reshaping the restaurant sector at a very rapid pace. Being able to master the gig economy is the key for businesses to succeed and sustain themselves in the new business environment" (Manager 3)

Accordingly, another owner agreed with the previous interviewee stating that:

"Not using delivery apps can cause businesses to lose a large stake of consumers due to the large shift to the app ordering concept. Introducing delivery apps to shops has developed a new source of income and the number of customers ordering through apps is increasing continuously. When I first looked at the margin taken by the apps, it took a long time to make up my mind and adopt them. However, after a year of using the apps, I can tell that it was one of the best decisions I have ever made" (Owner 2)

While the front-line management affirmed the importance for restaurants to be on board with the new concept developed by the gig economy, the management stressed how the gig economy has enhanced the sales for restaurants. The following quotes support the statement asserted above:

"The sales have increased dramatically since adopting the app-based delivery companies and it seems that it has brought new consumption [...] when the pandemic hit, the number of walk-in consumers decreased remarkably, and the use of the delivery apps was the rescuers as the sales have picked up and new consumers are ordering regularly. Delivery apps are seen by many consumers as the ideal way to order food, particularly with the introduction of the pandemic restriction, which has caused the sales to increase through the delivery apps due to facilities and services they provide"
(Manager 6)

Supporting the quotes stated above, another owner affirmed that:

"Giving away more than a third of sales to the delivery apps sounds a lot. However, the benefits accompanied by the Use of those apps are far more valuable than the shares given. The delivery apps have brought new customers and increased restaurant sales which have set themselves among managers' strategies to sustain and develop businesses." (Owner 3)

The above quotes set the delivery apps to be among the significant changes that help reshape the restaurant industry alongside the sales and eating-out concept. The employment system is one of the areas that was hardly hit by the gig economy. This was supported by the findings of the qualitative study that is becoming inevitable for restaurant management to avoid being part of the gig economy, either by adopting food delivery apps to increase sales or by hiring agency apps that allow the smooth running of businesses filling the vacant position with experts in an artistic method. Participants statements will be illustrated below:

"I used to be known for not supporting the employment of gig workers, in recent years, I had to change my mind occasionally to allow my restaurant to run smoothly. I rely heavily on gig workers as they can be a very last-minute replacement or an addition to the team when needed, this hiring system allows me to always be ready and flexible while running my business." (Manager 9)

Agreeing with the quotes motioned above, another owner stated that:

"Since I started using agencies to hire gig workers, I have never been short-staffed due to the on-demand hiring flexibility offered by agencies. Gig workers can be last-minute rescuers that managers can hire to operate their businesses efficiently. [...] using the app-based hiring agencies provides employers with real-time employees' rate and availability which allows managers to run their operations smoothly." (Owner 6)

On the whole, the outcomes of the interviews approved widely the impact of the gig economy in the restaurant sector including many business functions such as sales and employment which were mainly caused by the emergence of food delivery and hiring apps.

4.5.2 Front-line management and gig workers in the UK restaurant sector

The literature has agreed on the importance of front-line management in adopting compelling approaches to manage employees efficiently. Furthermore, various studies suggest that the gig economy has reshaped the employment market, enhancing the emergence of gig workers (Hyers & Kovacova, 2018; Shin et al., 2021; Lobel, 2017). In the same vein, the findings from the qualitative study have agreed that the traditional approaches that the front-line management used to adopt should be updated to cope with the gig workers. The quotes generated from interviews will be stated below:

"Looking at how the employment system has changed as well as the large shortage of employees in the UK restaurant sector, the old traditional ways of leading and managing seem to be unfruitful and could leave employers without workers for ages which may lead to a disastrous operation of business". (Manager 5)

In the same line, another restaurant owner stated that:

"I have been known and considered an autocratic leader and that was the key to my success for many years, despite not being my employees' favourite manager in the company. However, in the very few last years, with the emergence of the gig economy that has reshaped the job market, I had to change my leadership and move toward being more flexible" (Owner 6)

The findings mentioned above supported the literature by agreeing that the significant changes occurring in the restaurant industry require the management to adopt a new approach to manage and lead gig workers. In addition to that, the findings suggest that the gig economy is taking over the traditional employment system due to the large pool of benefits offered by the gig economy to businesses and management. This was evident by participants' quotes:

"The vacant positions have not become an issue in recent years while the right alternative is just a few clicks away, Thanks to the app-based hiring agencies. I had never thought that getting a last-minute worker could be as easy as a few touches on my mobile screen as back in the day, I used to struggle to find a replacement for sick employees and could take me days to get hold on the replacement." (Manager 11)

In support of that, another owner stated other benefits of adopting the gig economy:

"Running special events and occasions used to consume a lot of time and money to prepare employees. The emergence of gig workers has helped me massively to get the right people at the right times with a simple process and that saves the training cost, time and the commitment accompanied by employing permanent workers. Bringing employees only when they are needed has saved me a fortune as I used to find it hard to balance the employee's shifts in the quiet periods while trying to keep them for the busiest time, using the gig workers has allowed me to hire employees only when they are needed." (Owner 7)

While the statement above asserted agreement among all participants regarding the benefit associated with employing gig workers, other various studies suggested the roles that can be used by front-line management to effectively manage gig workers (Ryan & Deci, 2020; Ab-Latif et al., 2020; Vogler et al., 2018; Li, 2020). A list of approaches was suggested by the literature showing various reactions to various approaches in the qualitative findings, which have highlighted teamwork development, delegation, communication and motivation as the ideal approaches that the front-line management can adopt to deal with gig workers. The quotes of the interviewees are stated below. Participants asserted that teamwork development is an efficient approach to managing gig workers. The quotes evident in this statement will be affirmed below:

"The gig workers who are hired for a longer time have a higher willingness to be part of the team and enhance the in-house employees to welcome them to the team and work on developing their professional relationship [...] as for the management, it is very important for managers to work on developing this teamwork due to its importance in running the business more efficiently." (Owner 9).

Along the same line, another interviewee agreed that motivation is an efficient approach that can be used by front-line management to manage and lead gig workers. His quote is stated below:

"Motivation and communication are the two most important activities that managers should focus on to attract and keep all employees connected and satisfied. [...] I always put communication at the top of my priorities due to its importance in allowing all the managerial functions to be done as efficiently as they can be. Also, regarding motivation [...] motivating gig workers can allow them to go the extra mile adding that motivations can be the same for the in-house employees including free meals while working, half-price when they are not working, an employee of the week and many other motivation methods." (Manager 8)

In the same vein, agreeing with the quote mentioning communication as an approach, another owner stressed this approach:

"Communication is one of the most important managerial functions as it helps the management to understand gig workers as well as to give instructions which will facilitate the business operations to run more efficiently. Regarding motivation, [...] gig workers have to be motivated as full-time employees [...] motivations can come in different forms which can be emotional or physical." (Owner 8)

While motivation and communication were derived from the qualitative findings, delegation is among the approaches that were highlighted by the literature. The quotes below will discuss the participant's point of view regarding delegation:

"Delegating varies from one gig worker to another as well as from one task to another. [...] some gig workers are just ready to be delegated some tasks and participate in making decisions while others are not. In addition, some tasks can be risky to delegate to gig workers while others are just not ready." (Owner 2)

Another participant agreed on the importance of delegation as an approach. Yet not all tasks can be delegated. His quote is stated below:

"Due to the way my restaurant operates, some tasks have to be delegated to gig workers and some decisions need to be taken by them which I find helpful in boosting their involvement and satisfaction [...] management needs to work on finding a way to allow gig workers to be part of the decision-making process as well as to delegate some tasks to them." (Manager 7).

On the contrary, another manager denied his ability to delegate tasks to gig workers due to his point of view that he saw no benefit in delegating while he added that it can be harmful to business. The quote is stated below:

"I rely heavily on gig workers to run my business. However, I do not delegate nor allow gig workers to decide unless it is extremely necessary believing that the in-house employees are more aware regarding the job circumstances which are more suitable to make decisions and to be delegated." (Owner 5)

The findings of the qualitative interviews listed various approaches for the front-line management to adopt while leading and managing the gig worker. One interviewee highlighted the importance of understanding the gig workers to be able to implement those approaches effectively. His quote is noted below:

"I Believe that managing gig workers needs time and practice to be efficient due to their position that limits the contact leaving small space for the managers to know more about the gig workers which may prevent managers from developing the best approach regarding motivation, communication and many other managerial approaches".
(Manager 8)

4.5.3 Hiring and food delivery apps and the labour market in the restaurant sector

The literature of various studies suggests that food delivery and recruiting apps are the two major developments of the gig economy in the restaurant employment concept. The two methods have attracted employees from different sectors as well as from full-time employees in the restaurant industry itself (Bi et al., 2021; Tepayakul and Rinthaisong, 2018; Duggan et al., 2021; Barratt et

al., 2020; Finn, 2020). Along the same line, the qualitative study findings show that hiring and food delivery apps have developed a new era of employment where employees are one click away from finding or switching to a new position. The interviewee's quotes supporting the literature are noted below:

"Since the emergence of the gig opportunities employees are not thinking twice before leaving their jobs. [...] I am finding it hard to engage in-house employees particularly the millennium generation let alone the gig workers that are used to securing their living through gigging all year long." (Supervisor 1)

In the same vein, those apps have increased employee turnover; one owner stated that:

"Since the increase in the app popularity, it seems that the engagement of the gig workers varies from one individual to another [...] it is hard to tell if the gig worker is fully engaged [...] employee turnover has increased because of the flexibility offered by the hiring and food delivery apps" (Owner 2) Alongside, those statements mentioned above highlight the benefits alongside the challenges noted by the qualitative findings. Another interviewee pointed the gig economy is a cost-efficient way for business:

"Relying on gig workers is becoming a necessity for businesses aiming to reduce their cost of operations due to the large accompanying financial benefits such as the training cost, holiday pay, sick pay and many others." (Manager 7)

In the same line as the benefits brought by the hiring apps, one participant stated that:

"It has never been easy to find a last-minute replacement for vacant positions. Yet, with the emergence of the app-based companies, it can happen with just a few clicks on the phone allowing the positions to be filled by individuals who are mostly experts in their jobs and with just a little guidance they will fit in the team." (Manager 1)

Another owner sees the employment of gig workers as a temporary solution that can be used occasionally. His quote is stated below:

"The restaurant sector always has a peak period such as charismas; preparing employees for that period used to start as early as August to get the stuff ready by

Christmas, now with the flexibility accompanied with employing gig workers, all the worries have gone as hiring the needed employees with specific expertise can happen instantly which can save me a lot of time and efforts. Employing gig workers has helped employers to reduce their employment costs as well as run their businesses more efficiently. Not to mention that gig workers are seen by employers as an effective alternative that can be relied on whenever are needed" (Owner 8)

Based on the outcomes of the interviewees, it could be said that the hiring and delivery apps have reshaped the labour market in the restaurant sector. permitting employees to gig flexibility and allowing the restaurant to fill their vacant positions at a cost-efficient method. This is the same in the research by Bi et al. (2021) and Finn (2020).

4.6 Engagement from a gig worker's perspective

The findings of this research alongside the literature lend support to the gig workers' engagement studies that suggest that gig workers are different from permanent employees and management needs to efficiently comprehend the gig workers as they are giggers for a reason (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018; Maslach & Leiter, 2017; Leiter & Maslach, 2016). The qualitative interviews' outcomes argue that gig workers as permanent employees have different needs and wants which may impact their gig experience with various restaurants. Thus, the data shows that the willingness to engage can vary from one gig worker to another. The evidence of this statement is illustrated below:

"Throughout my long experience with gig workers in the restaurant sector, I realised that gig workers' interest in engagement can never be measured till it is tested which has pushed me to focus more on putting the right measures and not waste time and effort to deal with gig workers with different approaches. Particularly with easiness to secure another gigger as well as the consequences accompanied with a focus on engaging one gig worker." (Owner 6)

On the contrary, another head chef believes that the same approach that is used for permanent employees can be used for gig workers. His quote is stated below:

"In my experience, I always use the same methods and approaches to engage all employees equally and I believe it is up to the gig employees to make an effort and find a way to adjust to those measures to make their experience more enjoyable, extend their experience and secure good feedback for the upcoming experiences." (Owner 3)

The above-mentioned statements have suggested that the management looks at gig workers' engagement approaches differently. While some believe that the same approach can be used efficiently to engage all employees, others believe that the management should opt for different approaches for gig workers and permanent employees.

Along the same line, gig workers look at gig positions differently; some see it as a temporary situation, while others see it as their main source of income and are looking at positive feedback. On the other hand, some are looking at it to secure a permanent position in the places that they are gigging for. The findings from the qualitative study affirmed that gig workers are expected to enhance their willingness to engage. The quote will be illustrated below:

"The engagement is a long process that can be used by the management to allow a better performance. On the other hand, the gig workers are called to assist an existing team. From this perspective, I always expect the gig workers to go the extra mile and adjust to the measures put in place and increase their willingness to be involved and engaged in the team and business. In addition to that, I believe that the engagement benefits the gig workers and the business equally" (Owner 10).

In the same line but from a different point of view, one manager believes that for efficient engagement to happen, it has to be accepted by the management and the gig workers equally. His note is stated below:

"Gig workers' engagement is a two-way process; the management puts the measures and the gig workers are part of it. If any of the parts has not done their job, the procedure will not succeed. For that reason, I cannot see why any of the parts will not participate, particularly with the benefits that the process can bring for both the gig workers and management." (Manager 2)

This study literature shows that the more the employees are engaged, the easier they are managed. This was explained by the literature by demonstrating the benefits of having engaged employees, including having more productive and involved employees in the workplace (Iqbal et al., 2017; Chandani et al., 2016; Saks, 2019). The findings from the qualitative interview show that engaging gig workers is very beneficial for restaurant management. The quote of the interviewee is shown below:

"I believe that engaging gig workers is beneficial for restaurant management and for the gig workers themselves. Enhanced productivity is without a doubt one of the many benefits of gig workers' engagement. Also, from the gig worker perspective, there are

several benefits for the gig workers if they are engaged including being rewarded, increasing their contribution and involvement in the business." (Owner 2)

In the same vein, managers need to understand gig worker engagement to accomplish it efficiently.

The quote is presented below:

"I look at the gig workers as workers that like to be more flexible so I make sure whenever I deal with them to leave them some space where they can enjoy their flexibility. This includes leaving them the choice to be engaged and to what extent they want to be engaged while at the same time, if the extent of their engagement is less than what I am expecting, I will make sure to make their experience as short as it can be in the restaurant as honestly, I feel that if I treat them differently I risk losing my full-time employees and developing instability in the workplace." (Manager 7)

The above statements demonstrate that it is very beneficial for gig workers to be engaged and most importantly, the management needs to be fully aware of the gig workers to accomplish the beneficial engagement. The quotes presented below show more benefits of having engaged employees:

"From my experience, the more gig workers are engaged the more they are ready to participate in the business permitting the management to spend less effort to manage them. Also, engaged employees are valued and rewarded more by the management allowing a strong relationship to be developed that can bring more benefits for both the management and the gig workers." (Manager 6)

Along the same line, businesses and management are better off with gig workers if they are engaged. This was supported by a quote from a head chef:

"I look at employee engagement as an equation, in which the business and the gig workers are the main part of it. The more gig workers are engaged the more they will be involved in the businesses, rewarded and valued by the business management. This will allow the business to perform better." (Head Chef 1)

4.7 Gig workers' engagement development

The literature review suggested that there are various methods, drivers and approaches that need to be employed effectively by the management to engage employees, bringing a set of benefits for both the management and the businesses (Rothmann, 2016; Mousa & Chaouali, 2022; Bakker & Leiter, 2017). The findings from this study showed that engaged employees bring several benefits to the business table including better customer service, smooth running of operations, fewer

conflicts, a better work environment and satisfied employees. In addition to that, the gig workers' engagement helps reduce the in-house employee turnover and encourages gig workers to repeat the experience, encourages better business performance and increases gig workers' productivity. The evident statements are quoted below:

"I always try to engage my gig workers as they allow my restaurant to run smoothly and efficiently allowing the food to be delivered in conditions that enhance the customer services. Also, this will help to develop a very positive environment that will reduce the in-house employee turnover and encourage the gig workers to make a repeatable experience." (Manager 8)

In the same line, another participant pointed out what benefits he believes gig engagement brings to businesses.

"The engagement of the employees including gig workers is the key to my restaurant's success as engaged employees always care and go the extra mile which will end up in improving the customer service attracting new customers and developing repeatable customers allowing the business to grow and succeed." (Owner 3)

Alongside those benefits, there are various other benefits, which this owner identified:

"I see the gig workers' engagement as the key to the restaurant's success as throughout my very long experience in the restaurant industry, the more the gig workers are engaged, the better the business environment it will be. I always rely on engaging the in-house employees as they will help me massively in engaging gig workers. Engaged employees always be more productive, reduce mistakes, reduce employee turnover and work deliberately toward satisfying customers." (Owner 8)

There is no doubt that the gig workers' engagement as well as the permanent employees' engagement bring various benefits to businesses and management, as was proven by the findings and the literature. This can happen efficiently under the condition of applying the right approach for the right gig workers.

This study's findings showed that different gig workers reflect differently on different functions; motivation and communication are set to be the most two important functions that the management can use and that the gig workers accept. In addition to that, the study showed that other factors help engage gig workers, such as being part of the team, delegating, valuing and rewarding but those are defined by the management as motivational methods that can drive the gig workers' engagement. The evident quote is stated below:

"I use efficient communication as a magical tool to achieve a better performance in all his business operations including engaging the gig workers [...] gig workers react positively to effective communication and end up engaging [...] gig workers or even in-house employees may require different approaches to be engaged. Yet, the communication, the motivation, the valuation and the reward seem to be accepted and efficient with all employees." (Head Chef 1)

In the same line, another owner asserted the importance of the communication:

"I use communication throughout the business operations and with all the stakeholders as that, in my point of view, is the only way that allows the information and the instructions to flow smoothly allowing positive outcomes to be developed including engaged employees. In addition, there are a variety of drivers that I rely on while engaging employees, such as integrating gig workers into the team, delegating some tasks and allowing the gig workers to be part of the decision-making; those will motivate the employees as well as the gig worker to be engaged." (Owner 4)

While the above-mentioned functions have proven efficient in the literature and the findings, there are other drivers that shown positive impact on the engagement of gig workers while employed such the equal treatment of the gig workers and full-time employees was one of the approaches that enhanced gig worker engagement. The interviewee's quote is stated below:

"My best approach to engage gig workers is to treat them equally with in-house employees. This has shown positive results from gig workers. I also use the appreciation and valuation of the gig workers' efforts by leaving good feedback and requesting their services for future jobs. Those methods usually motivate gig workers to be involved and engaged in the restaurant." (Manager 2).

Another participant stressed the importance of understanding the gig worker in defining the efficient approach to management. His quote is stated below:

"I always say that employees are different, and managers need to put some time and effort into finding what triggers the involvement and the engagement of the gig workers through using efficient communication and teamwork to gather enough data; the process itself can help engage gig workers as they feel that they are valued, treated equally, needed and part of the business. This will eventually enhance their engagement." (Owner 2)

Alongside the literature and prior findings, this participant illustrated the importance of developing teamwork in enhancing engagement among gig workers. His quote is stated below.

"I do engage my gig workers through focusing on the engagement of the in-house employees and work on developing teamwork between the two parts; this usually automatically develops the urge of engagement among the gig workers as they are mostly there to get the job done through following the culture and the process that is used by permanent employees as they are more aware of how things are done" (Owner 6).

The above-mentioned approaches, methods and drivers showed no surprise to what the literature covered as well as to prior findings throughout this research. Yet, the willingness of the gig workers to engage alongside the efficient comprehension from the management allows the management to be developed efficiently.

4.8 Conclusion

This part of the study has presented the qualitative empirical findings gathered from the interviews conducted on the leadership function and gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant industry. Front-line management, including managers and owners, were interviewed, enabling the researcher to comprehend the various perspectives of engagement. The findings outcomes suggested that the gig economy is taking over the traditional concept of the restaurant industry, reshaping various parts of the business, including employment and the labour market. Furthermore, the findings emphasise the importance of the gig economy to the restaurant alongside the importance of engagement to the restaurants and the gig workers. The findings suggested various leadership functions that can be adopted by the front-line management as drivers to engage the gig worker, highlighting communication, motivation, collaboration, the equal treatment as significant drivers to engage gig workers. This was accomplished through the efficient understanding of engagement and the willingness to engage by the gig workers. The next chapter will cover the quantitative data analysis.

CHAPTER 5: Quantitative aspects

(Gig workers' perspective)

5.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to accomplish the objectives of this research by detecting and analysing the associated links between the independent and the dependent variables. The planned steps to achieve this thesis were mentioned in detail in the research methodology chapter. This chapter is focused on the experimental analysis supporting the study and presenting the research results relying on the previous chapters. Also, this chapter will cover the steps that the collected data went through, including preparing, coding, editing and screening. In addition, this chapter will cover outliers, multicollinearity and normality and interpret the data's linearity. Moving forward, the illustration of the non-response biases will be included in this chapter, together with re-assessing the resulting solutions through the utilisation of the confirmatory analysis.

5.2 Preparing data

5.2.1 The coding and editing of data

Missing data is one of the prevalent issues when it comes to the analysis of the data, despite the importance of how much data is missing; the real issue is the missing data pattern. According to Kumar (2019), the data editing process needs to happen just after the data is gathered to ensure data completeness and consistency. Therefore, the collected data were examined, followed by coding all items before importing them into the SPSS software (Field, 2013). The data editing was administrated to ensure the coding process was accomplished accordingly. Moreover, all-out ranged detected values were double-checked.

5.2.2 The sample's data screening and characteristics

Accurate data is fundamental in the process of analysing the responses of participants. The researcher tested the pre-analysis data screening to allow the impartialness of the fundamental analysis and the production of efficient results from the collected data (Malhotra, 2017). The researcher utilised SPSS 25 to test the gathered data together with multivariate analysis to secure the accuracy of the data entry. The researcher included inconsistency checks and missing responses through the data screening and cleaning procedures. Field (2013) stated, according to his four

fundamental purposes, that the multivariate analysis should be conducted after data screening. The accuracy of the gathered data and factor consideration could cause disfigured correlations. In addition, screening the missing data can be utilised to deal with and assess the incomplete data. Before conducting the analysis, the gathered data was checked to disqualify questions with poor responses of substantive missing values and data. Moreover, the extreme effects of values on the analysis will be assessed together with the evaluation of the fit between the assumptions and the data gathered.

5.2.3. Missing data analysis

The initial stage of missing data analysis was to look for missing values in the data acquired from the main questionnaire. The outcomes of data analysis might be impacted by missing data, which can be troublesome (Field, 2013). Any trends in the missing data should be recognised to avoid any bias. The intensity of missing data is determined by data patterns such as the amount of data missing and the causes of missing data (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). As Field (2013) stated, there are two categories of missing data: ignorable and non-ignorable. The data regarded as ignorable missing data (the missing data process works randomly) is when the detected values are formed of a random selection from the overall values' pool, realised as missing or incorporated in the implemented technique, whereas missing data that cannot be perceived ignorable, returns for various reasons in various scenarios (Field, 2013). According to Field (2013), the missing data is divided into known and unknown processes.

The researcher is aware of the procedures of missing data, which occur as a result of assessment equipment failure, topics missing some questions and errors in the data entry procedure, resulting in pointless codes. As a result, the research can only exert restricted control over the missing data procedures; nonetheless, missing data can be managed in some circumstances when it is random. It is challenging to discover and handle unknown missing data processes. These situations usually involve participants who want to avoid answering specific questions owing to the delicate nature of the topic or when they have no answer to the enquiry. The difficulties were foreseen by the researcher, who attempted to mitigate them during earlier rounds of the study. Consequently, the researcher must cope with missing data by devising solutions to minimise the detrimental consequences of missing data that occur in a random sequence (Field, 2013).

Two approaches are discussed by Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) for evaluating missing data in questionnaires that have one or many missing responses. Discarding incomplete surveys with some missing data is not essential (Field, 2013; Hair et al., 2009) and the research should move on to

the next level of the procedure by determining the impact and scope of the missing data (Field, 2013; Hair et al., 2009). The first method of calculating the total amount of missing data is based on 'Missing Completely at Random (MCAR),' missing at random' or 'know ignorable' (MAR) and 'not-ignorable' (MNAR), which stands for missing not at random.

Missing values randomly distributed via data matrix cause fewer issues than missing values spread non-randomly. Non-randomly missing values, on the other side, have an impact on the generalisability of the outcomes (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). The prior trial shows a significant difference between non-missing and missing values, indicating that non-random missing data.(Field, 2013). Field (2013) proclaims that the missing data plot is random because there are no possible biases in the layout of missing data and numerous imputation procedures can be applied for missing values. The second method is concerned with the amount of missing data. Following Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), the amount of missing data has a lesser validity than the form of missing data.

5.2.3.1 Determining the degree and patterns of missing data

The above examination of the importance of missing data encourages the application of the SPSS missing value analysis procedure using Expectation-Maximisation approaches (EM). As an outcome, the results indicate no missing data at the item or build levels. subsequently, there was no necessity to examine any pattern or treatments to overcome the problem of missing data in this study. This fact highlights the questionnaire's efficacy, i.e. it was well understood by participants and compatible with their work circumstances.

5.3 The evaluation of normality, outliers, linearity and multi-collinearity

5.3.1 Normality assumption examination

On the constructs and items of the research, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk (k-s) statistics were employed. The k-s test's supposition reveals that the results were unreliable at both stages (item and construct). In a vast sample of data, the K-S test's fluctuation is broadly shared (Shiu et al., 2009).

Table 13: The normality test

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov(a)			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
FLMGE_TOTAL	.349	336	.000	.624	336	.000
LFGE_TOTAL	.363	336	.000	.608	336	.000
CGWE_TOTAL	.370	336	.000	.583	336	.000
GIRS_TOTAL	.344	336	.000	.620	336	.000
FLMG_TOTAL	.333	336	.000	.642	336	.000
HFALM_TOTAL	.374	336	.000	.595	336	.000
EGWP_TOTAL	.354	336	.000	.614	336	.000
GED_TOTAL	.384	336	.000	.581	336	.000

Another approach used as a vital normality portion is Jarque-Bera (skewness and kurtosis). Skewness measures the asymmetry of a real-valued random variable's probability distribution. A skewed variable signifies a variable not in the distribution hub (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). Skewness is utilised to distribute balance and to identify how unbalanced data is spread, with the majority of scores piling on the part of the distribution whereas few dropouts off in the distribution tail (Hair et al., 2016). Kurtosis discusses how 'flat' or 'peaked' a distribution is (if too flat with a long distribution, the tails are thin; if too peaked with a short distribution, the tails are thick) (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). The normal distribution is represented by a zero skewness and kurtosis value (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). The skewness is negative when examples stack up to the right with a lengthy left tail (Hair et al., 2016). Kurtosis values less than zero reflect a too-flat distribution (in many cases in the tails), whereas values more than zero suggest a peaked distribution with short and thick tails. Non-normal kurtosis results in a variance undervalue of the variable. However, positive or negative kurtosis and skewness pose no issue unless and until they are in the normal spectrum. Similarly, kurtosis and skewness values, whether positive or negative, reflect the fundamental nature of the gauged constructs (Shiu et al., 2009). Variables fulfilled the optimum values (i.e., $< \pm 3$) of kurtosis and skewness at this phase of the study (Hair et al., 2016).

5.3.2 Outliers: univariate and multivariate testing

An outlier is an insight that stands out from the rest, highlighting the disparity in viewpoints. According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), an outlier is "a case with such an immense value on one variable (univariate outlier) or such a peculiar combo of scores on two or more variables (multivariable outlier)" (p.72). Furthermore, because outliers are substantial, the data findings can be altered (Hair et al., 1998). They are sensors of observations that reflect a section of participants; they can be eliminated from the investigation.

The outlier is a remark with a considerable differentiation between its projected and actual reliant variable values or between its variable values and those of other remarks. Outliers can be spotted through persistent data scrutiny, which aids statisticians in acquiring helpful data-related information. In addition, statisticians must proceed with considerable caution while spotting outliers (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007).

The evaluation of constructs reveals multivariate and univariate outliers in this study. Outliers' scores might be highly elevated or extremely low (extreme value), impacting non-normality data and warped statistics (Zhang et al., 2020). A univariate outlier is relevant to a crucial value in one variable, whereas multivariate outliers indicate an unusual set of remarkable values in two variables or more. The researcher determined univariate outliers by converting all variables' outputs to basic outputs. In terms of univariate outliers, the rule of thumb proposes that a case is deemed as an outlier when the sample size is bigger than 80 cases (336) and the outlier is recognised with a standard score of 3.0 or above (Hair et al., 2016). The rule of thumb applies to ordinal and interval level variables handled as a metric, but not nominal level variables.

During the research analysis, numerous univariate outliers were discovered. As a result, throughout the subsequent analysis, the researcher discarded outliers. Univariate outliers were found by combining components into a single construct. The data values for each observation were translated into a standardised score (z-scores) using SPSS's descriptive statistics function (Hair et al., 2016). Plenty of outliers will be displayed based on the dataset used in this study. **CGWE** and **GED** constructions have the most outliers (three each), whereas **GIRS** and **FLMG** have the least (one for each).

Table 14: Univariate outliers

S.NO	Variable	Case of outlier	Standardised values i.e., z-scores > ± 3.0
1	FLMGE	31	-3.14111
		334	-3.05992
2	CGWE	307	-3.17864
		322	-3.00159
		309	-3.00159
	GIRS	237	-3.35861
	FLMG	256	-3.10734
	GED	167	-3.23674
		169	-3.23674
158		-3.07046	

Source: DATA ANALYSIS (SPSS file)

The Mahalanobis D2 measure is a multidimensional copy of the z-score that reveals multivariate outliers (Hair et al., 2016). The Mahalanobis D2 assesses the dimension of a case employing the

6	239	48.41259	4.841259	.00000	26	304	41.52058	4.152058	.00000
7	237	48.15073	4.815073	.00000	27	249	41.30659	4.130659	.00000
8	322	47.48276	4.748276	.00000	28	252	40.23957	4.023957	.00000
9	241	47.39880	4.739880	.00000	29	178	39.48469	3.948469	.00000
10	284	46.93755	4.693755	.00000	30	236	38.74851	3.874851	.00000
11	170	46.35435	4.635435	.00000	31	229	37.98073	3.798073	.00000
12	190	46.02429	4.602429	.00000	32	230	37.88084	3.788084	.00000
13	309	45.79992	4.579992	.00000	33	217	36.83677	3.683677	.00000
14	181	45.45379	4.545379	.00000	34	282	36.81262	3.681262	.00000
15	246	45.11070	4.511070	.00000	35	227	35.38875	3.538875	.00000
16	208	45.10174	4.510174	.00000	36	199	35.06951	3.506951	.00000
17	154	45.01860	4.501860	.00000	37	205	33.77795	3.377795	.00000
18	319	44.08073	4.408073	.00000	38	36	29.34888	2.934888	.00000
19	233	43.83908	4.383908	.00000	39	24	29.15708	2.915708	.00000
20	224	43.59119	4.359119	.00000					

Source: data analysis (SPSS file)

5.3.3 Multi-collinearity and linearity

The ongoing dissertation is based on survey questions and investigates the degree of relevant variables (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). Linearity assumes a straight-line link between two variables. Exploring the relationship between variables is necessary to account for any deviations that could affect the correlation (Hair et al., 2016). "Linearity is crucial in a concrete sense since Pearson's r solely catches linear interactions between variables; if there are large nonlinear relationships among variables, they are disregarded," Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) explain (p. 84). "Linearity between latent variables is hard to measure," say authors, "but linear connections among pairs of measurable variables can be evaluated by observation of scatter plots" (p. 682).

Pearson's correlation matrix was utilised in this analysis at the 2-tailed (0.01 significance scale) to describe the multi-collinearity and linearity of leadership functions and the gig workers' engagement, where correlations between independent variables and dependent variables were significantly positive. The test observations reveal that variables are linearly related to one another. The bivariate correlation matrix was created using Pearson's association. The correlation matrix

findings are presented in Table 15 and they reveal that the variate correlations are not significantly correlated (i.e., = or > 0.90) to one another (Hair et al., 2016), thereby satisfying the multi-collinearity requirement. The tolerance impact and scores of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) can be exploited to verify multi-collinearity. Multiple-collinearity is noted whenever the value is higher than 10 and the tolerance is less than 0.1.

Table 16: Correlation matrix and descriptive statistics for every construct

	FLMGE	LFGE	CGWE	GIRS	FLMG	HFALM	EGWP	GED
FLMGE	1							
LFGE	.760**	1						
CGWE	.804**	.817**	1					
GIRS	.763**	.756**	.779**	1				
FLMG	.739**	.728**	.744**	.732**	1			
HFALM	.795**	.791**	.805**	.788**	.731**	1		
EGWP	.806**	.800**	.810**	.777**	.756**	.804**	1	
GED	.787**	.776**	.793**	.789**	.735**	.799**	.807**	1

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (Pearson correlation sig. (2-tailed))

Figure 3: Gig workers engagement constructs scatter matrix plot

To compute the VIF and tolerance impacts, the investigator employed a multiple regression approach and the collinearity diagnostic feature. No construct violates the tolerance or multi-collinearity assumptions. hence, no variables should be deleted at this point.

Table 17: Regression to observe tolerance and VIF effect.

	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	-.705	1.694		-.416	.677		
GIRSTOTAL	.177	.076	.122	2.320	.021	.279	3.584
FLMGTOTAL	.232	.077	.141	3.003	.003	.353	2.832
HFALMTOTAL	.308	.073	.232	4.232	.000	.256	3.899
EGWPTOTAL	.362	.075	.270	4.819	.000	.246	4.061
GEDTOTAL	.188	.057	.184	3.314	.001	.252	3.974

Dependent Variable: GIRSTOTAL

	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	-.882	1.598		-.552	.581		
GIRSTOTAL	.163	.072	.123	2.265	.024	.279	3.584
FLMGTOTAL	.196	.073	.129	2.683	.008	.353	2.832
HFALMTOTAL	.302	.069	.248	4.387	.000	.256	3.899
EGWPTOTAL	.339	.071	.276	4.784	.000	.246	4.061
GEDTOTAL	.153	.054	.163	2.861	.004	.252	3.974

Dependent Variable: LFGETOTAL

	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	2.807	1.718		1.634	.103		
GIRSTOTAL	.237	.077	.157	3.071	.002	.279	3.584
FLMGTOTAL	.229	.078	.133	2.915	.004	.353	2.832
HFALMTOTAL	.336	.074	.242	4.541	.000	.256	3.899
EGWPTOTAL	.354	.076	.253	4.648	.000	.246	4.061
GEDTOTAL	.185	.058	.173	3.209	.001	.252	3.974

Dependent Variable: CGWETOTAL

5.3.4 Homoscedasticity/homogeneity

Homoscedasticity, or uneven variances, indicates an analysis suggestion based on ungrouped univariate data. The variables are homoscedastic if the variability of scores for a single continuous

variable is the same as the variability of all values for another constant variable. For multivariate analysis, homoscedasticity might cause issues (Hair et al., 2012). The lack of homoscedasticity is exacerbated by the non-normality of a variable, which is also true if one of the variables is correlated to a transformation of another. The location of data collection is reflected in the homogeneity of variance (homoscedasticity) (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007, p. 86). Levene's test of variance equality is a prominent approach to determining homoscedasticity (Field, 2009). At $p \leq .05$, Levene's test is significant, indicating that the variance heterogeneity is immensely conservative (Hair et al., 2016). The researcher employed Levene's test to calculate the variance of metric variables, which is deemed equivalent across non-metric variables. Levene's test is not significant (above 0.05), which shows that there is no difference in variances. Levene's test, like the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests, is considered sensitive to sample size and thus may be significant in extensive samples (Hair et al., 2016). The homogeneity of Levene's test, therefore, stated the consequences of the heterogeneity amongst independent and dependent variables in this research, which included a sample of 336 participants.

Table 18: Test of homogeneity of variance (Levene's test)

	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
FLMGE	2.834	11	324	.001
LFGE	3.493	11	324	.000
CGWE	4.558	11	324	.000
GIRS	3.101	11	324	.001
FLMG	2.056	11	324	.023
HFALM	6.988	11	324	.000
EGWP	4.742	11	324	.000
GED	5.358	11	324	.000

Source: Data analysis (SPSS file)

5.4 Non-response biases

The gathered sample must reflect the total population throughout the data collection process. The reluctance of possible respondents to participate in the study or to answer specific questions has been highlighted as one of the most important reasons to reveal the entire targeted sample of a study (Silverman, 2015). If respondents reckon that the survey would treat their data with the utmost confidentiality, the non-response rate may be lowered (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012). The survey technique of research has the most significant issues with non-response bias since

responders differ in meaning from non-respondents (Churchill, 1979). The non-response bias probability was computed by assessing how the Mann-Whitney U-test between late and early respondents varies from the means of all variables (Silverman, 2015). The surveys were submitted in the following sequence: the first 50 observations were deemed early respondents, while the last 50 were designated late respondents. All variables have a significant value greater than 0.5 probability value, indicating no significant statistical difference between early and late respondents. As a result, this study has no disquiet about non-response bias.

Table 19: Observing non-response bias through Mann-Whitney U-test

	FLMGE_TOTAL	LFGE_TOTAL	CGWE_TOTAL	GIRS_TOTAL
Mann-Whitney U	557.000	647.500	710.000	778.000
Wilcoxon W	857.000	947.500	1010.000	078.000
Z	-2.152	-1.328	-.752	-.129
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.031	.184	.452	.898
	FLMG_TOTAL	HLME_TOTAL	EGWP_TOTAL	GED_TOTAL
Mann-Whitney U	764.000	705.000	776.000	677.500
Wilcoxon W	1064.000	1005.000	2987.000	977.500
Z	-.257	-.800	-.147	-1.053
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.797	.424	.883	.292

Source: Analysis of Survey data

5.5 Factor loading and data analysis

The factors or underlying variables were determined by employing the statistical method of factor analysis, which was used to determine the pattern of association between a set of variables. This approach is frequently utilised to decrease data and identify several components that demonstrate the noticed variances in manifest variables with considerably higher quantities (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). As per Field (2009), factor analysis has three main applications: "understanding the structure of a band of variables; building a survey to assess any underlying variables; and reducing a dataset to a more controllable size while maintaining as much of the original information as feasible". As stated by Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka (2010), "EFA is an exploratory study because no prior constraints are laid on the pattern of associations between the observed measures and the implicit variables," whereas "with CFA, the researcher must outline various essential facets of the factor model in advance, like the number of factors and patterns of indicator-factor loadings". Because EFA is exploratory in nature and hence has the potential to be undependable, CFA may

be able to aid in avoiding errors. The validity of the constructs and the scales' convergence will be evaluated in the ensuing section. The factor analyses amid various factors are performed through a scope of specified factors that are not vigorously associated (negatively or positively) in the assessment of covariance (pattern of correlations) (Hair et al., 2016). Confirmatory and exploratory factor analysis are forms of factor analysis; their application aids in data reduction and variance grouping. The EFA's job is to identify the nature of the constructs that impact an array of answers, whereas the CFA determines whether a given range of constructs affects responses. The exploratory factor analysis techniques were utilized to form group data. The exploratory factor analysis was performed by SPSS 25 (Field, 2013).

5.5.1 Exploratory factor analysis

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) evaluates internal reliability, recognises measure factor structure and identifies the underlying structure for the relatively severe variables (Hair et al., 2016). SPSS 25 provides a plethora of operations for factor extraction and rotation. The EFA solution was formed via principal component analysis (PCA), one of the extraction methods used. By augmenting the number of variances relying on their component scores, PCA illustrates the linear combination of measured variables from unassociated topics. PCA pinpoints and reduces a vast group of variables into a smaller number of components by turning interlinked variables into new unconnected linear composite variables. PCA also assesses the extraction of maximum variance (where the first component constructs the highest variance and the last component generates the lowest variance) according to the dataset (Field, 2009). Defining those packed variables on each factor is essential after extracting the factors and checking the rotated stacking matrix. The extraction technique was merged by rotation to enhance the scientific value and exegesis of the solution. The two primary types of rotation are orthogonal and oblique (Field, 2013). The orthogonal factor rotation approach is useful if each factor is independent (orthogonal) of the others. Orthogonal provides simple tools for interpreting, characterising and informing outcomes (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). The oblique factor rotation is efficacious if the extracted factors are linked among themselves, and the amount of linkage is realised. The researcher employed Varimax, the most often used approach of orthogonal rotation, to enhance the loading variance for each factor (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). Varimax additionally tries to construct variance between components to make them comparable in importance by removing variance from the first-extracted factors and disseminating it among the last-extracted factors. Compared to the

oblique methodology, the use of orthogonal rotation to explain the findings is more favourable depending on unrelated elements. Rotation was employed to promote strong correlation and reduce low correlation within variables and factors (Shiu et al., 2009).

Throughout the factor extraction in this study, three criteria were counted 'scree test criteria,' 'percentage of variance criteria,' and 'latent root criteria'. Calculating the fluctuation in the variance for all variables is essential before removing components (Field, 2013). "As part of an initial run using main component extraction," eigenvalues are considered (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007, p. 644). A variable with random or imprecise variation can have a commonality of one, whereas a variable that does not share anything can have a commonality of zero (Field, 2013). When the model is made up of numerous constructs, factor loading aids in calculating communality. The communality value must be greater than 0.5, otherwise, the study will require a large sample size. According to Hair et al. (2012), the sample size must be greater than 200 when the model has less than three elements or the commonality is between 0.45 and 0.55. When the commonality is less than 0.45, the minimum sample size must be 300 or greater. To acquire accurate factor analysis results, Bartlett's test of sphericity (BTS) and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling adequacy measuring) are helpful. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin statistic identifies variation attribution within variables that new factors can generate. When the measurement of KMO for sampling adequacy is more than 0.6, the relationship among items is appropriate for EFA to give a limited range of parameters and is statistically significant (Malhotra et al., 2017). The correlation between the measured items is over 0.3, making EFA suitable, according to Bartlett's test of sphericity (BTS) and following recommendations of Hair et al. (2013). After conducting an EFA for items derived from the literature, the researcher did a qualitative study (interviews). Initially, EFA was used to look at 58 factors related to leadership functions and gig workers' engagement to classify them into eight constructs. KMO has a value of 0.982, as seen in Table 18 (above 0.6 is considered acceptable sampling adequacy). It is significant if BTS meets the necessary conditions ($BTS \leq 0.001$) (Malhotra et al., 2017). The eigenvalue or latent root expresses the number of variances considered for a variable. According to Malhotra et al. (2017), every variable from the component analysis variability that participates in a principal factor extraction (one or above) is significant and then excluded (Hair et al., 2013, p. 120). The results show five factors with an eigenvalue greater than one and that item loading is processed separately in different components. LFGE 3, CGWE 8, FLMG 4, EGWP 3 and GED 2 were all deleted from the second part of EFA with cross-loaded.

Table 20: KMO and Bartlett's test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy. .982		
	Approx. chi-square	17890.283
	df	1596
	Sig.	.000

Source: Analysis of data (SPSS file)

All of the maintained variables in the factor loading attained a communality value of greater than 0.6 indicating a lot of variation across the variables (from 0.662 to 0.778). As a result, all items have communalities above 0.6 with their components, showing that the items' fit is good compared to the rest of the items from the same constituents. Only relevant elements with an eigenvalue more significant than one were considered, with the rest being ignored (Hair et al., 2012). The principal component analysis identified eight components with eigenvalues greater than one. The greatest variance attained was 58.010 per cent (identified in GIRS), while the lowest variance extracted by elements into a construct attained 1.726 per cent (identified in EGWP). As seen in the column 'Cumulative %', a set of eight components reflects a total variation of 72.9 per cent, which is higher than the guidelines (Hair et al., 2016).

Table 21: Explanation of total variance

Component	Initial eigen values			Extraction sums of squared loadings			Rotation sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	32.870	57.667	57.667	6.982	12.248	12.248	32.870	57.667	57.667
2	1.517	2.662	60.329	6.049	10.612	22.861	1.517	2.662	60.329
3	1.490	2.615	62.944	6.049	10.612	33.472	1.490	2.615	62.944
4	1.309	2.296	65.240	5.348	9.383	42.855	1.309	2.296	65.240
5	1.189	2.086	67.326	4.940	8.667	51.522	1.189	2.086	67.326
6	1.131	1.983	69.309	4.306	7.555	59.076	1.131	1.983	69.309
7	1.016	1.782	71.092	4.055	7.113	66.190	1.016	1.782	71.092
8	1.001	1.756	72.848	3.795	6.658	72.848	1.001	1.756	72.848
9	.647	1.135	73.983						
10	.606	1.062	75.045						
11	.588	1.031	76.076						
12	.575	1.010	77.085						
13	.562	.985	78.071						

Extraction method: Principal component analysis (13 observations).

"Starting with the first factor, the plot slopes steeply downward at first and then gradually becomes an approximately horizontal line" (Hair et al., 2012). The greatest number of components to extract

is thought to be the point where the curve first begins to smooth out" (p. 121). The scree plot test validates the extracted factors using eigenvalues and the extracted number of factors is validated using KMO's latent root criteria. The curve in the scree plot breaks down between components seven and nine, with the curve explaining much more variance from components one to eight than the remaining components.

It is necessary to determine the adequate loading for each variable about each factor (Hair et al., 2016). The efficient factor loading was 0.5 and more at the significant level of 0.05 to ensure an efficacious factor loading, in which the sample size of the study was 336 (n=33 gig workers at various positions in the UK restaurant sector) (Hair et al., 2016). Items having factor loadings less than 0.4, following Churchill's 1979 proposal, should be eliminated. The outputs and rotated component matrix of scale show that the loading of items on eight factors varies between 0.543 to 0.96, satisfying the lowest factor loading criteria (Shiu et al., 2009). Cronbach's alpha is also computed for all components correlated with their pertinent items (Cronbach, 1951).

Two distinct groups were used to test structures in a theatrical setting. The first group assessed the gig economy and its components (front-line management and gig workers' engagement, leadership functions and gig workers' engagement, and challenges of gig workers' engagement), depending on Crowe and Sheppard's (2010) proposal that when testing several constructs, the evaluation of a compact measurement model gives highly dependable results. The main advantage of gig workers' engagement is the second group. Cronbach's alpha was used to assess the consistency of the internal factors that emerged. Five items were removed from various builds due to cross-loading or a low factor, whereas most of the objects were loaded in their respective constructs. The EFA aids researchers in determining whether the items fit within theoretical factor structures. Cronbach's alpha was applied to ensure the inner consistency of items in each factor (Cronbach, 1986).

Table 22: Factor loadings

Items	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
FLMGE_1	.660							
FLMGE_2	.656							
FLMGE_3	.604							
FLMGE_4	.657							
FLMGE_5	.676							
FLMGE_6	.657							
FLMGE_7	.650							
FLMGE_8	.645							
FLMGE_9	.662							
LFGE_1				.645				
LFGE_2				.610				
LFGE_3				.629				
LFGE_4				.636				
LFGE_6				.608				
LFGE_7				.643				
LFGE_8				.668				
CGWE_1			.607					
CGWE_2			.579					
CGWE_3			.602					
CGWE_4			.583					
CGWE_5			.575					
CGWE_6			.623					
CGWE_7			.604					
CGWE_9			.591					
CGWE_10			.633					
GIRS_1					.667			
GIRS_3					.594			
GIRS_4					.597			
GIRS_5					.588			
GIRS_6					.631			
GIRS_7					.623			
GIRS_8					.548			
FLMG_1						.674		
FLMG_2						.679		
FLMG_3						.605		
FLMG_5						.700		
FLMG_6						.668		
HFALM_1							.637	
HFALM_2							.546	
HFALM_4							.591	
HFALM_6							.659	
HFALM_7							.570	
HFALM_8							.566	
EGWP_1								.617
EGWP_2								.554
EGWP_3								.547
EGWP_5								.578
EGWP_6								.570
EGWP_7								.579
GED_1		.643						
GED_2		.610						
GED_3		.626						
GED_4		.612						
GED_5		.617						
GED_6		.602						
GED_7		.681						

GED_9								
Cronbach's a	.954	.946	.945	.941	.924	.907	.930	.926

5.6 The assessment of the model's structure

5.6.1 Structural equation modelling: essential concepts

5.6.1.1 The structural equation modelling notion

Structural equation modelling (SEM) aids the merging of fundamental theory and data by enabling statistical methodologies (Zhang et al., 2020). SEM tools allow you to respond to questions about numerous regression analyses of factors (factor analysis, linear regression, analysis of variance, principal component analysis and multivariate analysis of variance). Employing SEM, the researcher can simulate several layer linkages among various dependent and independent variables at the same time (Martinez-Lopez et al., 2013). The answer variable inside a single regression equation can be used as a prognosticator in different equations in SEM. In a structural equation model, variables can impact one another directly or indirectly through distinct variables (intermediaries). The structural equations represent the causal relationships between variables in a model. The structural equation model is similar to causal links with informal thinking, which is prominent in social science theory. As a result, the researcher discovered that SEM helped translate current theories into data analysis.

5.6.1.2 Types of models in structural equation modelling

SEM contains two interconnected models: structural and measuring models (Hair et al., 2016). The measurement model, also known as confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), is the component that connects the measured variables to the factors. CFA is a problematic approach used in the early stages of research to test theories based on the relationship between various measuring items and their factors (Martinez-Lopez et al., 2013). The two-step approach in SEM allows for the examination of the importance of each pattern coefficient before providing a practical framework for comparing the investigated substantive model with prospective theoretical alternatives (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012). The goal of employing AMOS 25 was to figure out what caused the observed variables (items) to influence the unobserved constructs. CFA was used to test the construct validity at this level (Hair et al., 2016). On the other hand, the structural model testing clarifies the causal relationships between all the analysed constructs. The analysis and outcomes of both models are explained in the following section.

5.6.1.3 Practical consideration for structural equation modelling

Before using SEM approaches, some practical concerns must be considered (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007).

5.6.1.3.1 The sample sizes

When the sample is tiny, SEM, like correlations, is based on low constant covariances (Martinez-Lopez et al., 2013). The sample size impacts the estimation of sample error and the model's capacity to be appropriately estimated (Hair et al., 2016). SEM requires a large sample size. However, there is no absolute or exact sample size restriction in the literature (Hair et al., 2016). A sample size of 100 to 150 (small sample) is consistent with a model with five or fewer constructs with three items or more (for each construct) and communality over 0.6 (Hair et al., 2016). The sample size must be greater than 200 when the commonality is between 0.45 and 0.55. Models with more than six constructs and a commonality of less than 0.45 require a sample size of over 500 (Hair et al., 2016). This study encloses a sample size of 336 participants and a commonality of more than 0.5, indicating no significant concerns.

5.6.2 One-step vs. two-step procedure

Researchers such as Diamantopoulos et al. (2012) and Hair et al. (2016) prefer the two-step method over the single-step method because of its benefits and it is extremely suitable for this analysis. The two-step method includes an estimate of the measurement model (authorises the model's validity, reliability and unidimensionality assessments) and the structural model simultaneously (where the path significance among the observed theoretically latent constructs is verifying the causal relationships). This method distinguishes between the suggested model and other options (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012, p. 423). The 'one-step approach' considers the structural model and the measurement simultaneously (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012). According to Hair et al. (2012), the efficiency of the one-step approach resides in how the method of measuring the overall fit of a model neglects structural models and independent measurement. In situations when the models depend on firm theoretical arguments and measurement items previously established in current research, the one-step strategy, according to Hair et al. (2012) and Fornell and Lacker (1981), is more effective than the two-step approach. From another point of view, the one-step strategy is not optimal because it is difficult to establish good model fitting (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012). As a result of the preceding clarifications, this study utilised a two-step method.

5.6.3 Basic model evaluation

The two-stage approach in structural equations aids in examining the effectiveness of each pattern coefficient and provides a valuable framework for explicitly comparing the interest of the substantive model with the following possible theoretical alternatives (Byrne, 2001). AMOS 25 was used to test the measurement model in the first stage and assess the link between the variables (observed items) and the unobserved (latent) construct in the second stage. CFA was employed to test the construct's validity at this level (Hair et al., 2016). The second stage involves putting the structural model to the test to determine the relationships between the observed constructs (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012).

5.6.3.1 First step: Measurement model results

The initial level of model evaluation is the measurement model, which uses CFE to test the model's dependability and validity. The AMOS (full measurement model and modification indices) assists in determining the multiple loading item, followed by a suitable external consistency. This can also be accomplished by omitting objects that cluster together and belong to the same construct. The measurement model uses factor loading to determine the level at which the measured variables are gathered inside their construct (Teo, 2011). The CFA, or measurement model, affirms the link between the observable variables and the hidden factors (Hair et al., 2016).

The CFA assessment of the measurement model checks the model's complete validity (e.g., nomological validity). The optimal fit indices determine how well the estimated model can replicate the observed data. The fit indices evaluate the total disparity between the implied and observed covariance matrices. Unidimensionality and goodness-of-fit were used to ensure the model's applicability (Hair et al., 2016). The construct's unidimensionality must first be established to validate that the mutual feature reflects a multitude of indicators via a reliability test plus factor loading for all constructs. The complexity of determining model fit necessitates the development of various goodness-of-fit criteria for assessing SEM for several constructs (Teo, 2011). For overall fitness, the measurement model was examined through the fit indices suggested by various researchers (Hair et al., 2016). The fit indices represented in this study were model absolute fit, parsimony fit and incremental fit. The absolute fit indices represent the level at which the measurement and structural model (overall model) accurately predict the evaluated correlation or covariance matrix (Hair et al., 1998). The structural equation model with absolute fit indices can

be perceived as a satisfying fit of a distinct model from others (Hair et al., 2012). Absolute fit indices have criteria such as normed fit Chi-square CMIN/DF (2 /df), Chi-square (2), adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI) and goodness-of-fit index (GFI) and root mean square error of approximation residual (RMSEA).

The targeted model's fit is compared to a null model using incremental fit indices, where the variables are uncorrelated (Hair et al., 2012). The incremental fit indices were used to test the extent to which the model fits close to some alternative baseline models. The non-normed fit index (NNFI), normed fit index (NFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) and normed comparative fit index (NCFI) are all incremental fit indices (CFI). The result of absolute fit indices without including the fit of substantive models near incremental fit indices is the model fit measurement (null model). Quantitative measures employing the CFA (Hair et al., 2016) likelihood estimation method in the measurement model are used to determine the constructs' reliability and validity. Parsimony fit indices are used to ensure that a model has a good fit (Hair et al., 2012). The parsimony normed fit index (PNFI) and the parsimony goodness-fit index are two parsimony fit indices' criteria (PGFI). The following is a stepwise analysis based on the measurement model criteria.

5.6.3.1.1 The dependability measurement (items level)

The primary measurement model evaluation is reliability, which assesses the internal consistency of the measured items to perform a latent construct and prevent more dimensions from emerging through component analysis due to incorrect items (Hair et al., 2016). Internal consistency dependability shows item uniformity across the scale. The part of an item's variance explained by the principal latent variable is illustrated by item dependability. Due to the popularity of Cronbach's alpha as an internal consistency method that helps how the range of items encourages to evaluation of a construct from multiple perspectives, the coefficient alpha method was employed to examine the internal consistency reliability (rather than the split-half methodology) (DeVellis, 2003). The factor loading was found to be reliable, ranging from 0.781 (**GIRS_1** <-- **GIRS**) to 0.869 (**GIRS_6** <-- **GIRS**). The correlation between factor loading and its construct was higher than the minimum allowed value of 0.4.

5.6.3.1.2 Measurement of reliability (constructs level)

The composite reliability, also known as construct-level dependability, confirmed that the components of each construct had a strong relationship with one another. The composite reliability

calculation and testing of the statistical significance of all component loading are both parts of the model suitability evaluation. Internal indicator consistency is measured by construct or composite reliability, which explains the degree to which they point to the mutual latent construct. It is suggested that the composite reliability be greater than 0.7 (Hair et al., 1998). Composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha were calculated to determine the construct's level of dependability. As shown in the Tables below, Cronbach's alpha is higher than the recommended range of 0.864 to 0.925 (>0.70), which passed the psychometric reliability requirements (Hair et al., 2016). The internal consistency of the unidimensionality of the multi-item scale is measured through Cronbach's alpha. On the other hand, the construct reliability will be adopted to measure the efficiency of the construct based on its assigned item. In this experiment, squared multiple correlations (SMC) were used to evaluate construct dependability. The SMC equals the square of the indicator's standardised loading for an observed variable. The SMC for an observed variable is the square of the indicator's standardised loading. In this investigation, the SMC was higher than the suggested value (>0.5), corresponding to a standardised loading of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2016).

Table 23: Front-line management and gig workers engagement construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .925				Composite reliability = 0.93				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Front-line management and gig workers' engagement Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.712
FLMGE_1	<---	FLMGE	.858	1				0.736	
FLMGE_2	<---	FLMGE	.883	1.034	0.048	21.758	***	0.780	
FLMGE_5	<---	FLMGE	.848	0.950	0.047	20.115	***	0.719	
FLMGE_7	<---	FLMGE	.811	0.883	0.047	18.645	***	0.658	
FLMGE_9	<---	FLMGE	.818	0.948	0.050	19.049	***	0.669	

Table 24: Leadership functions and gig workers' engagement construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .882				Composite reliability = 0.88				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Leadership functions and gig workers engagement (LFGE) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.712
LFGE_1	<-- -	LFGE	.840	1				0.706	
LFGE_4	<-- -	LFGE	.838	0.974	0.053	18.351	***	0.702	
LFGE_7	<-- -	LFGE	.854	1.005	0.053	18.798	***	0.729	

Table 25: Challenges of gig workers' engagement

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .893				Composite reliability = 0.89				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Challenges of gig workers engagement (CGWE)				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.678
Standard factor loading									
CGWE_3	<---	CGWE	.842	1				0.709	
CGWE_6	<---	CGWE	.824	0.920	0.050	18.330	***	0.679	
CGWE_7	<---	CGWE	.792	0.871	0.051	17.181	***	0.627	
CGWE_11	<---	CGWE	.835	.928	0.050	18.614	***	0.697	

Table 26: Front-line management and gig workers' engagement

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .864				Composite reliability = 0.87				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Front-line management and gig workers engagement (FLMGE)				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.682
Standard factor loading									
(FLMGE)_1	<---	(FLMGE)	.781	1.000				0.610	
(FLMGE)_3	<---	(FLMGE)	.836	1.198	0.074	16.251	***	0.699	
(FLMGE)_7	<---	(FLMGE)	.859	1.213	0.071	17.036	***	0.738	

Table 27: Front-line management and gig workers

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .907				Composite reliability = 0.91				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Front-line management and gig workers (FLMG)				Estimate/B-value	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.662
Standard factor loading									
FLMG_1	<---	FLMG	.819	1.000				0.671	
FLMG_2	<---	FLMG	.785	0.936	0.057	16.361	***	0.616	
FLMG_3	<---	FLMG	.812	1.002	0.058	17.181	***	0.659	
FLMG_5	<---	FLMG	.796	0.969	0.058	16.768	***	0.634	
FLMG_6	<---	FLMG	.853	1.056	0.057	18.592	***	0.728	

Table 28: Hiring and food delivery apps and the labour market

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .884				Composite reliability = 0.88				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Hiring & food delivery apps and labour market (HFALM)				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.717
Standard factor loading									
HFALM_1	<---	HFALM	.841	1.000				0.707	
HFALM_6	<---	HFALM	.830	0.961	0.052	18.387	***	0.689	
HFALM_8	<---	HFALM	.869	0.992	0.051	19.437	***	0.755	

Table 29: Engagement from a gig worker's perspective

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .875				Composite reliability = 0.88				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Engagement from gig workers' perspective (EGWP)				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.703
Standard factor loading									
EGWP_2	<---	EGWP	.859	1				0.738	
EGWP_5	<---	EGWP	.816	0.994	0.054	18.298	***	0.666	
EGWP_7	<---	EGWP	.839	1.021	0.053	19.373	***	0.704	

Table 30: Gig workers' engagement development

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .904				Composite reliability = 0.90				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Gig workers engagement development (GED)				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.704
Standard factor loading									
GED_1	<---	GED	.841	1				0.707	
GED_5	<---	GED	.855	0.981	0.051	19.409	***	0.731	
GED_7	<---	GED	.816	0.953	0.053	17.961	***	0.666	
GED_9	<---	GED	.843	0.971	0.051	18.991	***	0.711	

5.6.3.1.3 Validity evaluation (convergent validity)

Internal consistent validity is related to convergent validity, which is evaluated by determining whether the factor loading of items belonging to constructs is equal to or greater than 0.5 and statistically significant (Hair et al., 2016). Convergent validity is linked to construct homogeneity, which describes how indicators of a given construct share or converge a significant portion of their variance. Furthermore, the average variance extracted (AVE) for the components in this investigation ranged from 0.662 to 0.717. When the AVE is 0.5 or greater, satisfactory convergent validity is reached, according to the excellent rule of thumb.

Table 31: Inter-construct correlation and AVE (for basic model)

	AVE	$\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$	FLMGE	LFGE	CGWE	GRIS	FLMG	HFALM	EGWP	GED
FLMGE	0.712	0.844	1							
LFGE	0.712	0.844	0.59	1.00						
CGWE	0.678	0.823	0.67	0.68	1.00					
GRIS	0.682	0.826	0.61	0.62	0.66	1.00				
FLMG	0.662	0.813	0.57	0.54	0.63	0.60	1.00			
HFALM	0.717	0.847	0.66	0.61	0.67	0.64	0.58	1.00		
EGWP	0.703	0.838	0.68	0.66	0.67	0.68	0.61	0.70	1.00	
GED	0.704	0.839	0.62	0.62	0.63	0.65	0.59	0.64	0.62	1.00

5.6.3.1.4 Measurement of validity (discriminant validity)

As a complement to convergency validity, discriminant validity shows how measurements diverge when compared to other conceptualisations when the construct differs from other constructs. Hair et al. (2016) found that the average variance extracted (AVE) findings are greater than the squared correlation estimations. Calculating the AVE for all constructs and comparing it to the square correlation among them is another way to verify discriminant validity. The discriminant validity in this study is supported by the fact that the AVE is higher than the squared correlations of the latent variables (LV) of the factor to which they belong (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). As a result, the improved measurement model displays discriminant validity with no cross-loading within evaluated variables.

Table 30: The correlation matrix for all the constructs

Construct	FLMGE	LFGE	CGWE	GIRS	FLMG	HFALM	EGWP	GED
FLMGE	0.844							
LFGE	0.765	0.844						
CGWE	0.817	0.822	0.823					
GIRS	0.779	0.790	0.811	0.826				
FLMG	0.756	0.736	0.782	0.773	0.813			
HFALM	0.812	0.780	0.819	0.797	0.762	0.847		
EGWP	0.825	0.811	0.816	0.824	0.782	0.834	0.838	
GED	0.786	0.785	0.795	0.806	0.770	0.797	0.787	0.839

5.6.3.1.5 Measurement of validity (nomological validity)

Nomological validity is concerned with the overall fit of a model, as it relates to how the scale predicts data based on theory and the entire model validity (Hair et al., 2016). The model's overall fit within CFA is used as a sufficient and appropriate provision for analysing nomological validity (Steenkamp & Baumgartner, 2000). The goodness-of-fit measure proposed by Eriksson and Sharma (1998) is used to examine the nomological validity. The construct correlation matrix elements must be related to establish nomological validity. All measurement model evaluations used maximum likelihood (ML) to estimate factor loading within CFA. Because of the usage of ML, the model validation is supported by model fit indicators, which helps to resolve the issue of standard errors and an inaccurate Chi-square (χ^2) statistic (Hu & Bentler, 1999).

Model fit indicators were used in model validation to resolve the possibility of a standard error and unreliable Chi-square static as a result of the usage of ML (Hu & Bentler, 1999). In this study, both absolute and incremental fit indices were used. An examination of the measurement model and structural model was conducted using the absolute fit indices to predict the correlation matrix or observed covariance.

Table 32: The model modification's goodness-of-fit indices

Model fit indicators								
Chi-square/ X^2	Df	RMSEA	GFI ¹	NFI	CFI	AGFI ¹	IFI	TLI
420.178	377	.018	.924	.952	.995	.907	.995	.994
X^2 – Chi-square; Df – degree of freedom; RMSEA – Root mean square error of approximation; GFI – Goodness-of-fit index; NFI – Normed fit index; CFI – Comparative fit index; AGFI – Adjusted goodness-of-fit index; and TLI – Tucker-Lewis Index								

The root mean square approximation of error (RMSEA) and the comparative fit index (CFI) give information that is unique in evaluating a model (Hair et al., 2016). A RMSEA less than 0.08 indicates a good match (RMSEA = 0.0180.08). A CFI of more than 0.90 signifies a satisfactory fit, while 0.995 is an incremental index that evaluates a model's fit with the basic model (Hair et al., 2016). The comparative fit index (CFI) is an evolved version of the normed fit index (NFI), which evaluates the attribution by which a model is generated. As recommended by Hair et al.

(2012), an accepted NFI must be greater than 0.08. Hence the result of NFI (0.952>0.08) is acceptable. The goodness-of-fit index (GFI) is a measure of model fitness in comparison to other models; it is deemed a good fit when it is greater than 0.95 and acceptable when 0.95>GFI>0.90 (GFI=0.924), while the adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI) amends the model complexity which is accepted as well (0.995>AGFI=0.907>0.90) (Hair et al., 2012). The Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), which is as popular as the non-normed fit index (NNFI), compares the model's χ^2 value to one of the independence models while considering the model's freedom degrees. Consequently, the measuring model for these factors was nomologically acceptable. Additionally, the Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) and the incremental fit index (IFI) (0.994 and 0.995, respectively) were above the 0.90 requirements (Hair et al., 2012). As a result, all the fit criteria show that the model fit is satisfactory in this research. After that, the measurement models' discriminant, nomological and convergent validity assessments yielded theoretically and statically affective constructs.

The important re-specifications were applied to gig worker engagement using the leadership functions, front-line management and gig workers' engagement (FLMGE), leadership functions and gig workers' engagement (LFGE), challenges of gig workers' engagement (CGWE), gig economy in the restaurant sector (GRIS) front-line management and gig workers (FLMG), hiring and food delivery apps and the labour market (HFALM), engagement from gig workers' perspective (EGWP) and gig workers' engagement development (GED). Twenty-seven items were removed from the CFA models (FLMGE_3, FLMGE_4, FLMGE_6, FLMGE_8, LFGE_2, LFGE_3, LFGE_6, LFGE_8, CGWE_1, CGWE_2, CGWE_4, CGWE_5, CGWE_9, GIRS_4, GIRS_5, GIRS_6, GIRS_8, HFALM_2, HFALM_4, HFALM_7, EGWP_1, EGWP_3, EGWP_6 and GED_2, GED_3, GED_4, GED_6).

5.7 Second step: testing constructs through structural model evaluation

In the second step of the analysis, the presumed linear relationships, both causal and covariance, between the endogenous (dependent) and exogenous (independent) latent variables are estimated. The structural model then facilitates an evaluation of the path model or inner model. illustrates the operational model for the gig workers engagement . The structural model elucidates the rationale behind the relationships among theoretical constructs.

(Hair et al., 2012)

As an example, this study posited a question suggesting that the leadership functions can be employed by the frontline management as drivers to engage the gig workers in the UK restaurant

sector. Using the structural model, this study tested its constructs utilizing the t-value and standardized estimate. The SEM model was executed, and construct were examined using AMOS 25.0. The Chi-square, an original fit index for structural models, was employed, as it directly reflects the fit function.

At this stage, the chi-square was 520.639, the comparative fit index (CFI) was 0.984, indicating an improvement in the model fit compared to the baseline model (Hair et al., 2016). The incremental fit index (IFI) and normed fit index (NFI) scores of 0.984 and 0.940, respectively, surpass the recommended threshold of 0.9 (Byrne, 2001; Hair et al., 2016). Hence, there is additional support for the satisfactory fit of the constructed model based on the experimental data in this research.

Table 33: The model modification's Goodness-of-fit indices

Model fit indicators								
Chi-square/X ²	Df	RMSEA	GFI ²	NFI	CFI	AGFI ²	IFI	TLI
520.639	387	.032	.907	.940	.984	.888	.984	.982
X ² – Chi-square; Df – degree of freedom; RMSEA – Root mean square error of approximation; GFI – Goodness-of-fit index; NFI – Normed fit index; CFI – Comparative fit index; AGFI – Adjusted goodness-of-fit index; and TLI – Tucker-Lewis' index								

The total model-fit indices meet the criteria for validity levels, indicating that the model achieves a good fit based on the collected data (Hair et al., 2016) (Table 6.25). Additionally, the goodness-of-fit index (GFI), as another comprehensive fit measure, indicates an acceptable fit at 0.907. The GFI index is complemented by the adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI) of 0.888, suggesting that the model fit is ultimately marginal. For evaluating the model fit, the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) at 0.032, below 0.08, ensures an acceptable level (Zhang et al., 2020). Since there is no common agreement among researchers on the ideal goodness-of-fit index, and due to the sensitivity of some indices to sample size, adopting different goodness-of-fit indices is considered the best strategy (Anderson and Gerbing, 1982).

The proposed structural model fit according to the criteria for adequate fit was satisfactory, as the accepted limits were achieved through all the fit indices of this research (Hair et al., 2016; Martinez-Lopez et al., 2013; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). The researcher faced a major problem in the stage of confirmatory factor analysis due to the absence of a common agreement on what is

considered as a good fit (Hair et al., 2016) Therefore, there is room for argument about the interpretation of AMOS analysis results. To conclude, based on the observed data the proposed model contains a good fit.

The proposed structural model exhibited a satisfactory fit according to the criteria for adequacy, as it met the accepted limits for all the fit indices in this research (Hair et al., 2016) The researcher encountered a significant challenge in the confirmatory factor analysis stage, primarily due to the lack of a common agreement on what constitutes a good fit (Martinez-Lopez et al., 2013) Consequently, there is room for debate regarding the interpretation of AMOS analysis results. In conclusion, based on the observed data, the proposed model demonstrates a good fit.

The implications of these results will be discussed in the following chapter. Path coefficients represent the standardized regression coefficients. Structure equation modelling, where the data collected from validated measures test the relationships among constructs, reflects the assumed linearity. In structural equations index, the square multiple correlation indicates the highest variance between independent variables and dependent variables, with **EGWP** (i.e., $R^2 = 79\%$) and **CGWE** (i.e., $R^2 = 80\%$).

The standardised regression path among the Gig economy in the restaurant sector **GIRS** and front-line management and gig workers **FLMGE**; leadership functions and gig workers' engagement **LFGE**; and challenges of gig workers' engagement **CGWE** is statistically significant ($\gamma=0.406$, t -value=4.171; $\gamma=0.556$, t -value=5.513; $\gamma=0.457$, t -value=4.744 respectively). This illustrates the significant relation among front-line management and gig workers (**FLMG**) with **FLMGE**, **LFGE**, and **CGWE** ($\gamma=0.183$, t -value=1.879; $\gamma=0.134$, t -value=1.238; $\gamma=0.245$, t -value=2.552 respectively). The results for hiring and food delivery apps and the labour market (**HFALM**) with **FLMGE**, **LFGE**, and **CGWE** were statistically significant ($\gamma = 0.489$, t -value = 6.289; $\gamma = 0.422$, t -value = 5.077; $\gamma = 0.421$, t -value = 5.608 respectively).

The paths from front-line management and gig workers' engagement (**FLMGE**), leadership functions and gig workers' engagement (**LFGE**), and challenges of gig workers' engagement (**CGWE**) to engagement from gig workers' perspective (**EGWP**) were statistically significant ($\gamma=0.328$, t -value=4.947; $\gamma=0.299$, t -value=4.265; $\gamma=0.259$, t -value=3.320, respectively). Showing a strong connection among **LFGE**, **LFGE**, and **CGWE** and gig workers' engagement development (**GED**), achieved the constructed direction of significance ($\gamma=0.262$, t -value=3.334; $\gamma=0.286$, t -value=3.445; $\gamma=0.291$, t -value=3.285, respectively). While the relation between **EGWP** and **GED**, was not found to be significant within the constructed path ($\gamma=0.072$, t -value=.658).

5.8 Summary

This analysis aimed to investigate the constructs quantitatively and answer the research questions. These goals were met by analyzing the data in three phases, each of which comprised multiple steps. The first phase clarified the information and included a sample descriptive analysis. Data were screened by highlighting missing data and identifying responses with low kurtoses and skewness to obtain effective results from acquired data; normality, linearity, non-response bias tests and homoscedasticity were studied. The data correctness was examined using normality, linearity, non-response bias tests and homoscedasticity to obtain effective results from the collected data. The data was suggested to be normal at a univariate scale because of some skewness and kurtosis in the responses. Based on Mahalanobis D^2 (d-squared) analysis, there were 39 multivariate outliers displayed. There is no difference or significance between the variances when the homogeneity (Levene's test) is non-significant (i.e., >0.05). The r and value of VIF were both within range, indicating that multi-collinearity was not present, as determined by bivariate Pearson correlation. The Mann-Whitney-U results, which looked at non-response errors from respondents, were insignificant (no distinction among the late and early respondents).

In this study, the two-step process was used to demonstrate the relationship between variables and factors using the exploratory factor analysis technique. The scree plot and eigenvalues aid in factor extraction. The employment of the orthogonal approach (Varimax) in the primary component contributed to determining the greatest variance of factor loading based on the rotated factor. **HFALM** 5 Hiring and food delivery apps and labour market, **FLMG** 8 from front-line management and gig workers, **LFGE** 4 from leadership functions and gig workers engagement, **CGWE** 5 from challenges of gig workers' engagement, **EGWP** 4 engagement from gig workers' perspective and **GED** 8 from gig workers' engagement development were excluded from the six constructs after reliability and EFA testing. The components derived based on EFA were analysed using scree charting. All variables, including discriminant validity and appropriate convergence for the measurements, had an AVE value of more than 0.5. The correlation matrix of the constructs was used in the nomological validity analysis. As a result, the potential of multi-collinearity was tested using correlation analysis on the interrelations among research variables.

CFA is the second step in the goodness-of-fit study of various measurement models. AMOS 25 was used to analyse confirmatory analyses of multiple measurement models and structural models of the proposed gig workers' engagement and leadership functions model in 336 cases. In terms of goodness-of-fit analysis, CFA reveals that all indicators had high values within their specific factors and overall goodness-of-fit indices, indicating that the model was accepted. Cronbach's

alpha, reliability and validity, composite reliability and average variance were all assessed for each construct. The instrument has a high level of reliability and validity, according to the outcomes. In addition, all constructs were found to have discriminant, convergent and nomological validity. Based on the review of this study's measurement model fit and psychometric qualities, the CFA provided significant evidence for the construct's validity. This investigation's structural equation model (SEM) was evaluated and developed in the next stage. The researcher used overall model fit to determine the SEM, where the pathway coefficient was linked to the causal effects. The SEM used a two-step technique to carry out the proposed model. The measurement model was examined in the first step to determine construct and item reliability and convergent and discriminant validity.

Chapter 6: Discussion

(Qualitative and quantitative data)

6.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to discuss the outcome in detail and conclude the objectives of this study by examining the relation between the conceptual framework and answering the questions of this research. The researcher utilised a mix of quantitative and qualitative research methods to promote the scale of measurements as well as to test the focal constructs developed to respond to the research questions (Paris & Winn, 2013).

6.2 Findings conclusion

This research aimed to investigate gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector. The relevant literature proposed several research objectives to be accomplished: (1) to understand how the gig economy has reshaped the labour market in the UK restaurant sector; (2) to define the front-line management roles in gig workers' engagement; (3) to identify the leadership functions that can drive gig workers' engagement; (4) to determine the challenges faced by management while engaging gig workers; (5) to recommend the most efficient leadership functions that can be utilised by the front-line management to engage gig workers.

This research has adopted a holistic approach to the gig workers' engagement concept incorporating both gig workers and front-line management in the UK restaurant sector, the gig economy, leadership function and employee engagement literature to develop the focal constructs and the conceptual framework. This study aims to determine the research questions. This part will discuss the empirical findings of the qualitative and quantitative phases and connect the findings to the research questions and the constructs developed.

6.3 The gig economy reshaping the labour market in the restaurant sector (R1)

This section will integrate the findings from the interview analysis and the literature to answer the research question below.

To what extent has the gig economy reshaped the labour market in the UK restaurant sector?

The gig economy has reshaped the labour market in the restaurant industry, particularly with the emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic. Adopting the gig economy has become a necessity for businesses allowing the management to secure last-minute employees for their vacant positions in just a few clicks on their phones selecting talented workers to be employed at their chosen time and place. This was supported by the literature stating that the emergence of the gig economy has drastically transformed the labour market in the restaurant sector by introducing a new concept that allows restaurants to hire talented and trained employees whenever they are needed (Chen et al., 2019). Furthermore, the benefits offered by the gig economy have attracted gig workers from different sectors as well as the restaurant industry, so that according to Lobel (2017) the gig economy is attracting new employees from various sectors due to the flexibility it offers, particularly in the restaurant sector, which according to (Sun et al) 2020 is the highest industry when it comes to the lack of life balance. This has allowed the gig economy to win over traditional jobs.

In the same line, the qualitative findings have backed the concept mentioned above, the qualitative quote is stated below:

"Replacing a sick employee or an employee going on holiday used to be a nightmare for me causing me a stressful and costly process that needed to bever a long time. This caused me to employ extra workers just to be on the safe side if an employee leaves, getse sick or goes holiday. The emergence of the gig apps has given me the freedom to hire last minute workers with an easy process that a few years back used to sound like a miracle if it happened" (Manager 11)

The literature supported that gig workers are relying on the gig option as their main or as an extra source of income. In addition to that, the ease of securing jobs has enhanced the migration of in-house employees to the gig economy (Wood et al., 2019). Also, Kost et al. (2020) stated that the high level of flexibility alongside many other benefits offered in the gig era has attracted employees from different sectors specifically when the pandemic hit hard causing many employees to lose their jobs (Cherry & Rutschman, 2020).

The data collected from the qualitative research support the statement mentioned above; the quote from qualitative research is stated below:

"The labour market has changed drastically since the introduction of the gig economy. This has made securing jobs easy for employees and securing employees easy for employers. Also, the flexibility offered by the gig economy has encouraged employees from all sectors as well as the restaurant traditional employees to migrate to the gig economy" (Owner 7)

In the same direction, the literature has shown that hiring and food delivery apps have transformed the labour market in the restaurant sector, where more flexible and life balance jobs are offered, enticing more employees to be part of the gig economy. According to Adams (2018), hiring apps have attracted many in-house employees to the gig economy, where better flexibility, pay and life balance are accomplished with just a few clicks on their phones. In addition, this study's literature discussed the benefits offered by the hiring apps that facilitate the process for restaurants to fill their vacant positions with an easy process reducing the cost of hiring and employing permanent workers (Kuhn & Galloway, 2019). On the contrary, Ahmad (2020) stated that mapping the gig economy as a main source of employees to occupy vacant positions in the restaurant sector can bring various challenges to restaurants and management, such as a lack of productivity, involvement and engagement that have an impact on operating the business effectively. This was supported by the findings generated from the qualitative study. The quotes are stated below:

"It has never been easier to secure a last-minute replacement for my vacant position than in the hiring apps era where real-time availability of gig workers can be seen, allowing me to select the best talented individuals at the most needed time. Yet, I believe that no matter how talented the gig workers are, they can never replace the full-time employees. However, gig workers can still be very efficient if they work alongside the in-house employees." (Manager 1)

Previous research highlighted the role of food delivery apps in decreasing employees' retention in the restaurant sector due to the benefits offered by such apps that provide employees with more flexibility and better pay (Duggan et al., 2020). Furthermore, Van Doorn et al. (2020) stated that the food delivery apps enhanced the migration of permanent employees, increasing the need for gig workers to cope with turnover of full-time employees. This has boosted the urge for businesses to rely on gig workers to run their business and cope with the shift of in-house employees to food delivery apps (Cho et al., 2019). Accordingly, the study results showed support for the reviewed literature. The quote of the qualitative study is stated below:

"Many of my employees have left for the food delivery apps, left me no choice but to employ gig workers. He added, I used to be known for not supporting the employment of gig workers. In recent years, I had to change my mind occasionally in order to allow my restaurant to run smoothly. I rely heavily on gig workers as they can be a very last-minute replacement or an addition to the team when needed; this hiring system allows me to always be ready and flexible while running my business." (Manager 4)

The quotation above agreed with the literature in this study, arising from the role played by the food delivery apps in reshaping the labour market by attracting traditional employees to the gig economy where better flexibility and pay are offered. This has enhanced the need for restaurants to employ gig workers to allow a smooth running to their businesses.

6.4. Gig workers' engagement

This research was conducted based on the urge to develop ideal visibility in the conceptualisation and the measurement of the front-line management role in engaging gig workers focusing on the leadership functions. Despite the gig economy and the importance of gig workers, the literature lacks a hefty definition of gig workers' engagement and how the leadership functions can be used to influence it in the restaurant sector. Prior definitions regarding gig workers' engagement and leadership functions were given in the literature review chapter, followed by a conceptualisations analysis developed in Chapter 6. While the employee engagement drivers were targeted in previous studies, gig workers were not put into studies in the same way as for the leadership functions. Yet, relating the two was not put into studies. Thus, this study attempts to establish an exploratory comprehension of gig workers' engagement construct.

The researcher relied on interviews to gather qualitative data to address the research problems from the management point of view and develop the measurement scale for gig workers' engagement. In addition to that, the quantitative research was conducted to address gig workers' engagement from gig workers' perspective. The researcher has customised the related items scale for the gig workers' engagement. The researcher has built and tested the related items scale of the gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector; the outcomes have enabled the scale of gig workers' engagement to be facilitated and adjusted.

6.4.1 Front-line management roles enhancing gig workers' engagement (RQ 2)

This section will aim to answer the research questions mentioned below by using the outcomes from both the quantitative and the qualitative findings.

Which core responsibilities are employed by the frontline management within the restaurant sector?

Both practitioners and academics have agreed that various roles of front-line management have been associated with employee engagement, playing significant roles in enhancing gig workers' engagement in the restaurant industry (Elikwu, 2019; Morrison-Smith and Ruiz, 2020; Lie et al., 2019). However, few studies have related those roles to gig workers' engagement. Prior research has studied the drivers of engagement, including leadership, communication and many others. However, this study focuses on the front-line management and which day-to-day roles can enhance gig workers' engagement. The findings from both the qualitative and quantitative research have agreed with the literature study that stressed the importance of front-line management itself in engaging gig workers, the collaboration, the feedback and the equal treatment for all employees as roles that can positively affect gig workers' engagement if they were implemented effectively by the front-line management and be utilised to discuss this concept (Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020).

The quantitative data outcomes confirm that gig workers are more engaged if they are satisfied with the front-line management. Furthermore, several roles are highlighted by the quantitative study, such as collaboration, equal treatment of all employees, efficient communication and two-way feedback between the gig workers and the front-line management (Lie et al., 2019).

The quantitative findings have agreed with the literature identifying various front-line management roles that can be considered as drivers of engagement by the gig workers. Those findings will be discussed below.

You will be more engaged if you are satisfied with the front-line management (FLMGE _1). The collaboration approach from the front-line management influences your engagement (FLMGE _2). Being treated equally with the in-house workers by the management will enhance your engagement

(FLMGE _5). The two-way feedback with the front-line management will enhance your engagement. (FLMGE _7). Efficient communication with the front-line management can boost your engagement. (FLMGE _9). The range of the factor loading is between 0.811 (FLMGE _7 <- - FLMGE) and 0.883 (FLMGE _2 <-- FLMGE) where the requirements of reliability were accomplished (Hen et al., 2016). The reliability of Cronbach's alpha (α) was set at 0.925 according to the findings, which has gone beyond Cronbach's alpha appropriate value and the requirements are positively satisfied by the psychometric reliability test based on the outcomes (Hair et al., 2016).

The quantitative findings are clearly supporting the literature, pointing out the satisfaction with front-line management, the collaboration approach, the efficient communication and the equal treatment of the employees as a significance role that can positively influence gig workers' engagement if well employed by the front-line management.

This part of the research will clear up the significance of the relation between gig workers' engagement items that have been boosted over the qualitative research and the constructs of gig workers' engagement generated from the outcomes of the qualitative study. It is no surprise that the qualitative findings have set in line with the literature to highlight the satisfaction with the front-line management as an important concept that can enhance the engagement of the gig worker.

The next quotation gathered from the interview findings shows that the front-line management approach can play a significant role in enhancing gig workers' engagement "You will be more engaged if you are satisfied with the front-line management". This agrees with the outcomes (FLMGE _1 <--- FLMGE).

"Throughout my long career in the restaurant industry, the most valuable lesson that I have learned is that all employees including gig workers reflect positively on the management approach. For that reason, I believe that the more employees are satisfied with the management, the more they are involved and engaged in the work and vice versa" (Owner 6).

Therefore, according to the statement above, the front-line management approach is crucial to the gig workers, particularly with the nature of jobs that limit the contact and the knowledge with the business which allow the front-line management to play a significant role in interacting positively with the gig workers to enhance their involvement and engagement. Accordingly, the literature has shown that the front-line management can play huge role in involving gig workers in the

restaurant. Lam et al. (2017) stated that the gig workers have limited time to spend, in particular in jobs with limited contacts which usually start with the front-line management; this increases the importance of the front-line management in the process of engaging gig workers.

The quantitative findings have highlighted that another component of the front-line management and gig workers' engagement is "The collaboration approach from the front-line management influences your engagement" (FLMGE _2). As stated in prior studies, the collaboration with gig workers is a very strong driver that can boost the engagement dramatically alongside the increment of the involvement among the gig workers (Busse & Weidner, 2020). The qualitative study has validated this concept as well as validating the outcomes (FLMGE _2 <-- FLMGE). The statement is quoted below:

"Collaborating with the gig workers is a very efficient approach that allows gig workers to feel that they are valued by the management and that they are an essential part of the success. Also, collaborating makes the gig worker contribute to the overall success of the of the restaurant which will allow them to improve their performance and be more engaged." (Owner 2)

The quote above assists with the concept that collaboration is a dynamic approach that allows the creation of structured teamwork which boosts a company's production, making collaboration between full-time employees and gig workers a critical aspect in its success. It permits all members of the team to generate ideas and ask questions in order to increase efficient communication and allow restaurants to run more efficiently.

Various research has brought attention to the urge of developing a collaboration approach in the workplace including all employees in increasing the feeling among all employees that they are treated equally and that their contribution matters to the management and the business (Paulas & Kenworthy, 2019). The outcomes illustrated that working as a team enhances gig workers' perception that they are treated equally, which will in turn enhance involvement, valuation and thus boost their engagement. This statement was proved by the quotation from the interview stated below:

"Collaboration is my ideal approach due to its importance in accomplishing the job efficiently as well as enhancing the gig workers' roles in being part of that success coming from their appreciation of being treated as an in-house employee and that their part in the team is valued and appreciated." (Owner 3)

This delineates a consistent finding with prior research regarding the importance of teamwork creation in developing the feeling of being treated equally among gig workers, which can play a consequential role in engaging them. Therefore, being treated equally with the in-house workers by the management will enhance your engagement (FLMGE _5) and is a crucial factor of the front-line management and gig workers' engagement (FLMGE _2 <--- FLMGE).

In the same line, this has been the interest of various research highlighting the legal requirement of treating gig workers and permanent employees equally (Tan et al., 2021). Yet, this research focuses on this concept from a managerial perspective. The findings from this research showed the importance of treating gig workers and permanent employees equally in enhancing engagement among gig workers.

Another determination of the front-line management and gig workers' engagement is "The two-way feedback with the front-line management will enhance your engagement." (FLMGE _7) FLMGE _7 <-- FLMGE, which according to the literature is proven to be noteworthy for the construct, the qualitative research and the qualitative outcomes. Consequently, it supported this critical role to be among the roles that gig workers see as a driver that can enhance their engagement in the restaurant sector due to its role in alerting the management about what needs to be changed in their approaches, which will enhance their comprehension and knowledge regarding gig workers.

Alongside the above-mentioned roles, the quantitative findings have pointed out that efficient communication is a core role that can be used by the front-line management to engage gig workers.

The qualitative research inspected the claim that "efficient communication with the front-line management can boost your engagement." (FLMGE _9), which was approved from the literature review as well as the quantitative study (FLMGE _9<-- FLMGE). Thus, the appropriate scales demonstrate that the items' range connected to the front-line management and gig workers is well known for managers. This outcome meets those accomplished by the academics that support theories of gig workers' engagement.

Overall, the qualitative and the quantitative findings have supported the literature review by pointing out that collaboration, the equal treatment of employees, satisfaction with the front-line management and efficient communication as core roles that can enhance gig workers' engagement

if it is well performed by the front-line management. Therefore, the findings accordingly respond to research question 2 of this research.

6.4.3 Leadership function related drivers responsible for gig workers' engagement (RQ3)

This part attempts to respond to the study question below by combining both the qualitative and the quantitative outcomes.

What specific leadership functions serve as critical drivers for employee engagement?

Both practitioners and academic communities have asserted that there are various employee engagement drivers which include leadership and several of its functions as drivers (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018; Tayama et al., 2019; Bliese et al., 2017). However, different management employ different drivers or combination of drivers to engage the gig worker. Accordingly, this research has examined the mentioned drivers in the literature to develop the most efficient drivers that are related to the leadership functions that can be used by the management to enhance gig workers' engagement. The quantitative findings of this study suggested the development of teamwork, efficient communication and motivation as the core drivers that can be employed by the management to boost gig workers' engagement; the findings outcomes will be illustrated below.

Teaming up with in-house employees boost gig workers' engagement (LFGE _1). Efficient communication is considered as a strong driver for engagement by the gig workers (LFGE _4). Motivation is a very important driver for gig workers' engagement (LFGE _7). The range of the factor loading was between 0.838 (LFGE _4 <-- LFGE) and 0.854 (LFGE _7 <-- LFGE) where the requirement of the reliability was accomplished. The reliability of Cronbach's alpha (α) is 0.882 which eclipses the acknowledged rate of psychometric reliability test and Cronbach's alpha.

Accordingly, the qualitative findings were not surprising in supporting the quantitative data and the literature review that identified collaboration between gig workers and full-time employees as an efficient approach that can be used by the management to efficiently enhance gig workers' engagement.

This is evident from the quotations from the interviews presented below, given that gig workers' engagement can be achieved through the fact that "Teaming up with the in-house employees boosts

gig workers' engagement" (LFGE _1) which was also supported by the findings (LFGE _1 <--- LFGE). The managers provided some information.

"Teaming up my gig workers and full-time employees can be very challenging for me. Yet if it is done efficiently, most of the time I get the best results that could ever be achieved and both permanent employees and gig workers are more engaged and involved in all business operations." (Owner 2)

In the same line, another owner agrees on the importance and the efficiency of teamwork development among all employees in enhancing gig workers' engagement.

"I focus heavily on developing teamwork between my full-time employees and gig workers and in my experience, it can help the integration and involvement of the gig workers, and increase the knowledge and the awareness of the gig workers on how things are done in-house, which will eventually enhance their engagement" (Owner 7)

This appraisal illustrates the point of view that team development is one of major leadership functions, and that if it is opted by the management efficiently, it can enhance gig workers' engagement due the relationship developed between gig workers' and employees' engagement that allows gig workers to feel more valued and appreciated by the management and more involved in the operation, which will ultimately end up boosting their engagement. Therefore, "teaming up with the in-house employees boosts gig workers' engagement" (LFGE _1) is accepted as a measurement item to the leadership function and the gig workers' engagement construct.

The literature, the qualitative and the quantitative drivers agree one more time in this piece of work on the efficiency of communication in boosting gig workers' engagement. According to Ruck et al. (2017), gig workers' engagement can be significantly influenced by communication. In the same vein, the quantitative findings highlighted communication as an efficient approach that can lead the gig worker to engage. Communication is considered as a strong driver for engagement by gig workers (LFGE _4); this is another element of the leadership function and gig workers' engagement in this research. The literature review shows that the communication has shown efficiency in facilitating the process of engaging employees, which can be achieved through management communication of the operational and the strategic procedures with employees and can encourage employees to communicate back with their managers (Bailey et al., 2017).

Participants in the qualitative study highlighted the importance of communication in engaging gig workers in the restaurant sector. As evidence from the quantitative findings and the literature, a head chef interviewed in this study statement is quoted below:

"I use efficient communication as a magical tool to achieve a better performance in all business operations including engaging the gig workers. [...] gig workers react positively to effective communication and end up by being engaged [...] gig workers or even in-house employees may require different approaches to be engaged. Yet, communication, motivation, valuation and the reward seem to be accepted and efficient with all employees." (Head Chef 1)

The quotation above is coherent with research conducted on communication and engagement literature together, with the importance of efficient communication in operating every single part of the business which allows all operations to run better and in a more efficient way as well as enhancing the engagement among gig workers (Karanges et al., 2015). Thus, communication is considered as a strong driver for engagement by gig workers (LFGE _4) and is a substantial factor of the leadership functions and gig workers' engagement (LFGE _4 <--- LFGE).

Accordingly, this study has pointed to motivation as among the drivers that the quantitative findings and the qualitative findings supported, and which prior research has affirmed. According to Suharno and Despinur (2017), motivation is a core approach that can help the management to engage gig workers. The evidence from the quantitative research is stated below.

Another significant aspect of leadership function and gig workers engagement is that "motivation is a very important driver for gig workers' engagement" (LFGE _7) (LFGE _7 <--- LFGE). This aspect was taken from the literature and interpreted in the interviews and corroborated in the quantitative research. In the same line, the qualitative findings supported both the literature and the quantitative outcomes claiming the motivation enhances the involvement and the engagement of gig workers. The quotation of the interviewee is stated below:

"All employees need to be motivated to perform better including to be engaged. I motivate my gig workers and permanent employees equally through various methods which help them to be engaged and involved. Throughout my long experience, I learned that while the employees are motivated, they will be physically and emotionally involved and engaged in the business." (Owner 8)

Therefore, the apt scales demonstrate that the items' range connected to the leadership functions and gig workers' engagement is mundane for participants. The academics' accomplished perspective is compatible with the outcomes that support the leadership functions as drivers of gig workers' engagement.

Overall, the outcomes suggested that communication, motivation and teamwork development among gig workers are drivers that can accomplish engagement if employed efficiently by the management. The three drivers derived from this research, which are also leadership functions, can positively influence gig workers' engagement. Consequently, the findings have responded to the third research question of this study.

6.5 Gig workers' engagement challenges (Q4)

This section will use the both the quantitative and the qualitative findings to answer the research question below.

What challenges do management encounter when engaging gig workers in the UK restaurant sector?

The literature has highlighted the difference between the gig workers and permanent employees, stressing that this can bring the management several challenges that need to be understood and addressed for them to be able to engage the gig workers efficiently. There are various challenges developed through the literature, such as the lack of definition of motivators of the gig workers by the front-line management and the inability to treat gig workers the same as in-house employees. Furthermore, there is the risk of losing in-house employees to the gig economy, particularly with the increased temptations and benefits offered by the gig economy (Kuhn et al., 2021; Roy & Shrivastava, 2020; Dey et al., 2022).

In the same line, the quantitative findings have agreed with the literature highlighting various challenges that can be faced by the management while engaging gig workers as discussed below. Gig workers' motivations are different from full-time employees which are harder to define for the management due to the short-term nature of gig employment (CGWE _3). It is hard for management to treat gig workers equally with full-time employees (CGWE _6). The management are finding it hard to keep in-house employees from moving to gig work (CGWE _7). Hiring and food delivery apps are tempting traditional employees to move to the gig model and increasing

restaurant turnover (CGWE _10). The factor loading set to be between 0.792 (CGWE _7 <-- CGWE) and 0.842 (CGWE _3 <-- CGWE) where the requirements of reliability were accomplished. The Cronbach's alpha (α) reliability is 0.893 according to the findings which surpass Cronbach alpha acknowledged value. Also, the requirements are satisfied based on the outcomes of the psychometric reliability test. This section interprets the emphasis of relation amid the challenges of gig workers' engagement items and their constructs from the qualitative research. There are four aspects of the challenges of gig workers' engagement indicated from the quantitative research outcomes.

The quotations gathered from the qualitative research implied that the challenges of gig workers' engagement is compelling: "Gig workers motivations are different from full time employees which are harder to be defined by the management due to the short term of gig employment (CGWE _3); the results are backed by (CGWE _3 <--- CGWE). It is no surprise that this agrees with the literature and the quantitative findings setting the difference nature of the gig workers and the full-time employees and making it, challenging for the management to define the gig workers' motivators given that they have limited contact with them. That this is evident from the qualitative findings is illustrated below:

"With no doubt the engagement of gig workers is crucial to the management and the businesses. Yet, it requires a little effort and time to be fully understood which in most cases are not available due to the nature of gig workers' jobs and positions [...] the usage of the same approaches and methods with all workers will encourage the gig workers to be part of it and engage. On the other hand, this can shortly and efficiently allow me to define the ones that are ready to engage and the ones that they are interested in the engagement" (Manager 8)

Another gig worker engagement challenge faced by the management highlighted in this research is that it "is hard for management to treat the gig workers equally with full-time employees" (CGWE _6). Prior studies confirmed that managers have limited contact with gig workers, which prevents them from being treated the same as in-house employees that are permanently in the workplace and can be relied on to get the job done as efficiently as it can be done. The outcomes and the qualitative research can prove the concept mentioned earlier (CGWE _6 <--- CGWE).

Treating gig workers and full-time employees equally was stressed throughout the research and in prior studies as a significant driver that can positively influence gig workers' engagement. Several participants in the quantitative study referred to treating full-time employees and gig workers

equally as the optimal method, and that if it is mastered by the management, it can efficiently motivate gig workers to be engaged in the restaurant and allow the management to open dynamic channels to communicate with the gig workers in a way that helps them determine what motivates gig workers to be fully engaged. The quotation of the interviewee supporting the statement above is listed below:

"In my opinion, the only way for managers to engage gig workers is treat them equally with the full-time employees, which will help to easily determine the willingness of the gig workers to be engaged and encourage the management to go the extra mile if it is needed to determine what motivates them and how they can efficiently be communicated with and motivated." (Manager 11)

In the same line, another finding suggests that treating all employees equally can be beneficial for both businesses and employees which can be put the list of the challenges that the management need to consider in developing an artful solution to overcome it and enhance gig workers' engagement. This was supported by the interviewee quote stated below:

"Treating gig workers and full-time employees equally is the safest way to engage and manage both employees under one roof as the gig workers will be more involved, motivated and engaged without risking that full-time employees will not appreciate being treated as gig workers, which will increase the risk of turnover." (Owner 1)

Another challenge of gig workers' engagement is "The management are finding it hard to keep in-house employees from moving to gig work" (CGWE _7) (CGWE _7 <--- CGWE). The literature has significantly backed this construct together with the quantitative outcomes and the qualitative data. The qualitative research has examined also "the hiring and food delivery apps are tempting traditional employees to move to the gig model and increase restaurant turnover" (CGWE _10). This was concluded in the literature review and confirmed by the quantitative study (CGWE _10<-- CGWE).

Looking at both the quantitative and the qualitative findings, the risk of losing permanent employees to the gig economy has increased dramatically in recent years, particularly with the benefits offered by the gig economy, according to the literature. This has developed a significant challenge for the front-line management to keep their employees away for leaving the company. This can develop a barrier for the management to treat all employees equally as it can encourage the in-house employees to leave the restaurant if they can enjoy both world: the flexibility and the

premium treatment from the management. The evidence from the qualitative study is illustrated below:

"I can never risk treating the gig workers as full-time employees [...] this can encourage the in-house employees to be tempted to move to the gig option" (Owner 7).

In the same line, the ease of securing jobs is a challenge for the management as it is a benefit that can make keeping the full-time employees a hard mission to be achieved which can develop instability that can prevent the engagement from happening. The qualitative finding stated below supports this statement:

"Jobs have never been as easy to secure as in the apps era where employees are just few clicks away from their next position. This has allowed full time employees to never think twice before quitting their jobs. This has developed a challenge for me to keep my regular employees let alone engage them." (Owner 5)

In this matter, the apt scales demonstrate that the items range related to the challenges of gig workers' engagement is intimate for participants. This outcome agrees with the ones defined by the academics.

Overall, the quantitative and qualitative findings have aligned with the literature in pointing out the lack of understanding of the gig workers as a significant challenge alongside the risk of losing the in-house employees which focus on engaging gig workers; this is another challenge that was stressed in both the qualitative and the quantitative findings. Therefore, the findings have answered research question 4 of this study.

6.6 Gig workers' engagement development (Q5)

This section will answer the research question below.

How can frontline management leverage their core functions to enhance gig workers' engagement and efficiently address their challenges?

The literature review alongside both qualitative and quantitative findings has pointed out various drivers throughout the research. However, the front-line management's efficient understanding of the gig economy and engagement is the key for gig workers' engagement to be accomplished. The literature has pointed out the importance of gig workers' engagement alongside the necessity for

the management to employ gig workers (Iddagoda & Opatha, 2017; Shuck et al., 2017; Mencl et al., 2016). This has made it important to understand gig workers' engagement aspects including the gig economy, gig workers' engagement and the drivers that has shown efficiency in engaging the gig workers.

In addition to that, there are various challenges that were highlighted in the findings as well as literature enhancing the importance of understanding those challenges. One of the core challenges highlighted in this study is the lack of understanding of gig workers and their engagement (Kuhn et al., 2021; Roy & Shrivastava, 2020; Dey et al., 2022). Therefore, understanding is the key for the front-line management to cope with challenges of gig workers' engagement as well as to achieve gig workers' engagement. The qualitative findings have supported the statement mentioned by highlighting the importance of understanding and highlighting the risks that can be faced if there is a lack of understanding. According to the qualitative findings, understanding is the key for engagement to be achieved and its importance has been stressed throughout the qualitative study. Yet, it has been highlighted in the research that the nature of the gig workers can be an obstacle for various drivers to be implemented on gig workers to be engaged. This was evident from the interviewee statement quoted below:

"With no doubt the engagement of the gig workers is crucial to the management and the businesses. Yet, it requires a little effort and time to be fully understood which in most cases are not available due to the nature of the gig workers' jobs and positions [...] the usage of the same approaches and methods with all workers will encourage the gig workers to be part of it and engage. On the other hand, this can shortly and efficiently allow me to define the ones that are ready to engage and the ones that they are interested in the engagement." (Owner 6)

While the nature of employees was pointed out throughout the qualitative findings as a key challenge for gig workers' engagement, it has been made clear that it is not easy for the management to determine the drivers and identify their willingness to engage. A quote from the qualitative research shows support for the statement mentioned above alongside a protentional solution:

"In my opinion the only way for managers to engage gig worker is to treat them equally with the full-time employees which will help to easily determine the willingness of the gig workers to be engaged and encourage the management to go the extra mile if it is

needed to determine what motivates them and how they can efficiently be communicated with and motivated." (Manager 11)

Both quantitative and qualitative findings supported the literature by providing a set of drivers that are highly recommended for the front-line management to engage gig workers. The literature has suggested a long list of drivers which have been narrowed throughout the research to relate them to the leadership function. The qualitative study has been made even narrower by pointing out communication, equal treatment and teamwork development between gig workers and in-house employee as efficient drivers that can be considered as motivators for the gig workers to be engaged. The evidence for those statements is quoted below:

"Motivation and communication are the two most important activities that managers should focus on in order to attract and keep all employees connected and satisfied [...] [I] always put communication at the top of [my] priorities due to its importance in allowing all the managerial functions to be done as efficiently as they can be [...] regarding motivation [...] motivating gig workers can allow one to go the extra mile [...] motivations can be same to the in-house employees including free meals while working, half price when they are not working, employee of the week and many other motivation methods." (Manager 8)

In the same line, another interviewee highlighted other drivers that have agreed with the literature and been highly stressed in the qualitative study:

"I always work on developing teamwork among the gig and in-house workers as [it is] the best approach to motivate the gig workers to engage as well as to let the in-house workers to be part of the engagement process. [...] alongside allowing the gig workers to be part of the team, [I] rely on communication and appreciation as efficient methods that can help gig workers to engage." (Manager 6).

Overall, going through the literature alongside the qualitative and the quantitative findings, it can be said that gig workers' engagement is critical for front-line management due to various challenges that were highlighted throughout this piece of work. Yet, there are various drivers that are part of the front-line management that can be used to enhance gig workers' engagement, such as communication, motivation, equal treatment of all employees alongside teamwork

development. However, the condition for the engagement to happen is awareness and comprehension of the engagement from the management and the willingness from the gig workers. If that happened, the gig workers would be efficiently engaged.

6.7 Conclusion

This part of the research identified the empirical findings of both the qualitative and quantitative methods employed in this research. Various gig workers' engagement perspectives were identified throughout this chapter. This happened by mixing the discussion of research questions and the interpretation of the findings. The qualitative interviews were thematically analysed, producing strong comprehension regarding how the gig economy has reshaped the labour market in the UK restaurant sector, increasing the need for employing gig workers in restaurants. Similarly, on the other hand, the findings from the quantitative study were mixed with those gathered from the qualitative findings to highlight the significance of leadership functions that have shown positive outcomes when employed by the front-line management as drivers of gig workers' engagement. This chapter showed the efficiency of employing a mixed-method approach to understand gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector. Similarly, this was used to discuss how the front-line management has an impact on the engagement of the gig workers, together with the challenges that can be faced by restaurants while engaging gig workers. The next chapter will present the research contributions, limitations, implications and reflections.

Chapter 7: Conclusions and recommendations

7.1 Introduction

The previous chapter has discussed the findings about the research questions and the focal constructs developed throughout this research regarding gig workers' engagement. This has included the antecedents that have developed the gig workers moving toward how the management can enhance their engagement by relying on the leadership functions covering the challenges that can be faced and suggesting how the engagement can efficiently be achieved. The researcher utilised qualitative and quantitative methods in this process, which enabled him to utilise the triangulation logic to interpret the outcomes to address the research objectives.

This chapter will present a summary of the preeminent findings concerning the questions of the research. Afterwards, a discussion of the contribution of the research will be presented together with the practical and the research implications. Finally, the researcher's reflections will be discussed. Subsequently, the limitations of the research will be covered alongside the suggestions for future research.

7.2 conclusion

This researcher has explored gig workers' engagement along with its antecedents and how it can be achieved using leadership functions in the UK restaurant sector. The researcher opted for both quantitative and qualitative methods in the process of interpreting and analysing the outcomes of the research. The core findings respond to the research questions, as illustrated below.

First, the study findings indicate that the gig economy has become a necessity more than a privilege and restaurants are moving toward the gig era either by opting for food delivery apps or hiring apps due to the benefits associated with the employment of gig workers. On the other hand, the employment of gig workers has brought new challenges to management due to the different nature of gig workers, including how they can efficiently engage them. The emergence of the gig economy has attracted many employees to move to gig work due to the flexibility offered by the gig option, which was far from being achieved in the restaurant industry, known as it was for its lack of life balance (Watson et al., 2021). In addition, the pandemic has encouraged employees to move to the gig economy. This has shaken the labour market and employee behaviour in the UK restaurant sector, encouraging more employers to rely on gig workers to fill vacant positions and allow their restaurants to run smoothly (Shawl, 2021). According to the findings, this has

developed another challenge for the management: keeping the in-house employees away from moving to the gig working option, seeking more flexible options to secure their source of income. Secondly, the findings point out that gig workers are becoming more than a last-minute solution for many managers in the restaurant industry due to the cost-efficiency in hiring gig workers, reducing the cost of training, holiday pay, sick pay and many other charges. On the other hand, this same beneficial method of employment has brought various challenges to the management, including the risk of losing permanent employees to the gig option and efficiently managing the gig workers and helping them to fit into the team. Various managerial functions have shown a positive response from gig workers, such as efficient communication and delegation of few tasks; those functions tend to help gig workers to team up adequately with the in-house employees, which will motivate them to be involved and engaged in all business operations.

Third, the findings suggest that gig workers are more engaged if front-line managers are treating full-time employees equally with them and listen to the gig workers' voices through a constructive feedback approach as well as a collaborative approach, which shows a positive impact on the engagement of the gig workers due to its contribution in efficiently circulating information which allows them to perform their jobs in a better way. Learning and developing is another approach that showed great outcomes and appreciation from the gig workers by helping in increasing their self-confidence and improving the overall engagement of the gig workers.

Fourth, front-line management is facing several challenges with the gig option. The research findings show that the management employs a more flexible approach to keep their full-time employees from moving toward the gig choice. On the other hand, there are various challenges highlighted throughout the research, which are the difficulty of defining what motivates gig workers, the best way to communicate with them, developing teamwork and many other functions due to the short and objective nature of the gig workers employment system which may develop a lack of willingness of engagement among the gig workers.

Fifth, this research explored the core leadership functions that can drive gig workers' engagement. According to the findings, several drivers have shown efficiency in driving gig workers, which are efficient communication, motivation, treating them equally with the in-house employees and involving them in the team.

Sixth, this study explored the mediating effect of engagement between the antecedents and consequences. Findings suggest that engagement mediated the link between relations. Treating gig workers and permanent employees equally strengthens the relationship between the management and their gig worker subordinates. Similarly, gig workers working alongside the in-house

employees in accomplishing jobs will make them feel valued and appreciated, motivating them to be more involved and engaged.

Seventh, the data collected for this research suggest that looking at engagement from the gig workers' point of view has shown that gig workers' willingness to engage varies from one individual to another and that needs to be determined by the management before engaging gig workers. Yet, that requires time for the management to define those who are willing to engage and those who are not, and that is where the issue stands: the nature of the gig workers has limited time and contact with the management. Moreover, the equal treatment of gig workers and in-house employees seem to be key for engagement among gig workers as that makes them feel as valuable as employees to the company, which allows them to enjoy both worlds, the gig flexibility and full-time treatment in the workplace. On the other hand, this can help to reduce permanent employees' intention to leave.

Eighth, this study's findings agree that there is a set of functions that helps with engagement of the gig workers in the restaurant sector, such as efficient communication, a delegation of some of the tasks, collaboration among the management, permanent and gig employees as well as spending some time and effort on discovering what motivates gig workers to be engaged, not to mention the importance of treating all employees equally.

7.3 How the research aims, objectives, and questions were addressed.

The aim and objectives of this study were meticulously addressed through extensive methodology that included both quantitative and qualitative data collections methods. The first objective of this research was fulfilled by conducting an extensive review of the literature on the gig economy, employee engagement, gig workers, leadership, and frontline management functions in the UK restaurant sector. This was achieved through a comprehensive analysis of various academic publications, books, scholarly articles, and industry reports. This in-depth qualitative review laid the groundwork for subsequent research, establishing a thorough understanding of the existing knowledge landscape.

The second objective of this research aimed to identify the core functions and responsibilities exercised by the frontline management in the UK restaurant industry. This was addressed through the application of both qualitative and quantitative data collection methods. In-depth interviews were employed to gather qualitative data from frontline managers, providing a rich insight of their day-to-day functions, responsibilities and challenges. Additionally, the quantitative data were collected through a structured questionnaire distributed among gig workers in various positions

and locations with direct contact with the frontline management. This approach allowed for a comprehensive insight into the frontline management functions from the gig workers perspective, enabling a rich broader understanding on the frontline management roles and responsibilities with the gig economy in the UK restaurant sector.

For the third objective of this research, the researcher aims to explore the drivers related to the leadership functions that can enhance the engagement of gig workers in the UK restaurant sector. Both qualitative and quantitative were instrumental in achieving this objective. In-depth interviews were conducted with various frontline management personnel, including head chefs, supervisors, managers, and restaurant owners. Additionally, structured questionnaires were administered with gig workers across different positions and locations within the UK restaurant sector. This dual approach facilitated a comprehensive examination of the leadership functions that have emphatically impact gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant industry. The qualitative insights obtained from the front-line management were complemented by the quantitative survey data from the gig workers, providing a well-rounded perspective on the prevalence and impact of these drivers.

For the fourth objective of this research, the researcher was dedicated to understanding the challenges encountered by the management in engaging gig workers in the UK restaurant sector. The objective was thoroughly addressed through a qualitative approach. Both interviews and questionnaires were employed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the perspective of both front-line managers and gig workers regarding the challenges experienced throughout the engagement process. Thematic analysis was applied to identify themes and recurring patterns within the qualitative data, enabling a detailed exploration of all the intricacies involved.

In addressing the final objective of this study, which involved providing recommendations to the restaurant sector on achieving gig worker engagement by relying on appropriate leadership functions and addressing associated challenges, a synthesis of data from both quantitative and qualitative approaches was employed. The qualitative insights derived from interviews facilitated the development of valuable recommendations by fostering a contextual understanding of the most effective leadership functions that front-line management can adopt to enhance gig worker engagement and addressing industry-specific challenges. Conversely, the quantitative findings from questionnaires offered a broader perspective on gig workers' viewpoints, shedding light on the factors that enhance their engagement, as well as the challenges that may impede and influence their engagement within the industry.

In this study, a comprehensive approach was taken, utilizing both quantitative and qualitative analyses to systematically address the research questions. The exploration of sector practices and trends through qualitative review was employed by the researcher to delve into the extent to which the gig economy has reshaped the UK restaurant sector's labour market. Additionally, a combined methodology involving quantitative questionnaires and qualitative interviews was adopted by the researcher to identify the specific core responsibilities exercised by frontline management in the UK restaurant sector. This dual-method approach allowed for a more holistic and nuanced understanding of the research objectives. Furthermore, the researcher conducted an in-depth investigation into the specific leadership functions that can serve as key drivers for employee engagement in the UK restaurant industry, employing both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Moreover, the challenges encountered by management in engaging gig workers were thoroughly explored, drawing insights from both gig workers through questionnaires and management through interviews. This approach aimed to provide a detailed comprehension of the obstacles faced in the engagement process.

Aligned with the research aim to identify the core leadership functions that front-line management can use as drivers to engage gig workers in the UK restaurant industry, the study successfully revealed these functions through a combination of quantitative and qualitative findings. The triangulation of these sources enhanced the reliability and robustness of the data.

In conclusion, this study embraced a multi-faceted and comprehensive approach by utilizing both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods to systematically address the research objectives and aim. The integration of questionnaires and interviews contributed to the establishment of a holistic exploration of the impact of the gig economy on the UK restaurant industry, providing relevant insights for both practitioners and academia. The broader perspective offered by the qualitative analysis complemented the understanding derived from the quantitative data, illuminating the overall study findings. Beyond achieving its aim and objectives, this research has made a significant contribution to the methodological discourse on investigating intricate phenomena within the context of the gig economy. The research methodology employed in this study will be discussed in detail in the next chapter, covering the rationale, procedures, and ethical considerations.

7.4 The research contributions

Theoretical evaluation is one of the primary objectives of pure research, including knowledge and understanding advancement. On the other hand, the practical implications are considered a secondary focus approach. Spotting solutions for issues is the applied study's primary focus. Moreover, the motivation behind the applied business study is the aspiration to clarify the specific organisational issue (Jha & Kumar, 2016). Despite the likeness of the implication of the theory in the applied research, its utilisation in a practical setting is crucial. The research in social science combines both applied and theoretical approaches. In this study, the researcher applied the approaches due to the necessity to comprehend gig workers' engagement and its connection to other core constructs, such as the gig economy, hiring and food delivery apps, front-line management, leadership function, gig workers' drivers from a theoretical point of view, before utilising this knowledge to explore gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector from an empirical angle. This research covered applied and theoretical contributions, which are reviewed below.

7.4.1 Theoretical contributions

The theoretical contributions consist of three possible forms: invention, discovery and reflection. Each form has a different application in the research. Invention tends to create new techniques and methods to cope with a specific issue. Discovery deals with creating new ideas about an empirical study. Lastly, reflection is focused on re-checking the ideas, techniques and methods that already exist and applying them in a different context; this theoretical research contribution is based on reflection as it is applying existing theories regarding the leadership function, employee engagement drivers in a new setting such as gig workers and the gig economy in the restaurant sector. Employee engagement is a well-researched area. However, previous research does not focus on the new system of employees, gig workers in the restaurant industry (Fest et al., 2021). In addition, despite the drivers highlighted throughout the previous research, which consisted of several pure leadership functions, none of the studies has studied them as drivers related directly to leadership functions. The researcher will identify and discuss their core reflective contributions in this part of the research.

This thesis enhances the understanding of the gig economy in the restaurant sector besides the existing knowledge of how restaurants have moved toward employing food delivery apps in recent years. Hiring agency apps seem to have become more popular after the pandemic, attracting employees from all industries as well as restaurant employees who are moving toward the gig option, which tends to offer more flexibility in an industry that was known for its unsociable working conditions. On the other hand, gig workers seem cost-efficient for businesses to fill their vacant positions while minimising the accompanying cost and finding a solution to the employee turnover which has affected the industry for so long, particularly after Brexit. This research contributes to the emerging area of the gig economy and benefits the restaurant industry.

This research contributes to the employee engagement literature by covering a new form of employee, i.e. gig workers. However, the literature lacks knowledge on how those employees should be managed, including how they can be more involved and engaged in restaurant operations. This study has focused on gig workers, who have a different nature of employment and, to some extent, are different from traditional employees. While the reliance on gig workers is increasing drastically, huge roles are played in restaurants. This study contributes by highlighting the impact of the gig workers, including how they are taking a large part in the restaurant industry and the importance of focusing on those employees and their engagement.

This research has covered employee engagement from various literatures, in which a variety of those drivers have been studied under the leadership functions literature. This research has highlighted the efficiency of focusing on the drivers related to the leadership functions and how management in the restaurant industry can effectively rely on those drivers to enhance the gig workers' engagement. This research contributes to connecting the literature on the employee engagement drivers and the literature on leadership functions to develop drivers that can be utilised by restaurant management in enhancing gig workers' engagement.

This study suggests that various challenges were highlighted. However, the lack of willingness to engage from the gig workers and the nature of their jobs while the limited contact with the management is set to be the most critical challenge that needs to be addressed by the front-line management. The literature highlighted communication, motivation and teamwork development as strengthening gig workers' engagement. This study's findings show that none of the above-mentioned drivers can be adopted by the management unless the gig workers are willing to engage. In addition, the nature of gig workers can develop an obstacle to their engagement as it limits the

connection with the front-line management, which prevents them from developing proper communication and motivation approaches to engage employees.

This study contributes to gig workers' engagement drivers by highlighting the importance of leadership and its functions in the process of gig workers' engagement evolution, covering the core functions that can be highly recommended for the front-line managers willing to efficiently engage their gig workers, such as efficient communication, the equal treatment of gig workers and permanent employees, delegating few tasks and enhancing the team development, which will motivate the gig workers to be engaged.

The theoretical contributions of this research emerge from a reflective approach, wherein established theories on factors influencing employee engagement and leadership roles are employed in a unique context—the gig economy within the restaurant sector. The contributions are categorized as follows:

Reflection on existing knowledge

- Given the extensive examination of employee engagement, this study provides a critical assessment of prevailing theories regarding leadership functions and engagement.
- The reflective contribution lies in the application of these theories to a novel context, specifically focusing on gig workers in the restaurant industry.

Addressing gaps in literature

- Despite the abundance of research on employee engagement, limited knowledge exists regarding the engagement of gig workers in the restaurant sector.
- The study identifies and fills this gap, introducing a novel perspective to our understanding of employee engagement concerning gig workers.

Connecting literature stands

- The study adeptly establishes connections across various strands of literature, particularly bridging the gap between research on the factors influencing employee engagement and that on leadership functions.
- By highlighting leadership functions as key drivers for gig workers' engagement, the research provides a comprehensive approach that intertwines and extends existing literature.

Enhancing understanding of the gig economy

- The study surpasses current knowledge by shedding light on the rise and impacts of the gig economy within the restaurant industry.

- The reflective contribution involves documenting the sector's dynamic shifts, including the post-pandemic surge in the adoption of employment agency apps.

Highlighting gig workers' significance

- Significantly contributing to the understanding of the gig economy, the study emphasizes the pivotal roles played by gig workers in the restaurant sector.
- By stressing the importance of comprehending and effectively managing gig workers, particularly in the face of evolving dynamics and challenges within the sector, the study provides valuable insights.

Efficient use of leadership functions

- Building on the existing literature on leadership functions, the study identifies and recommends crucial functions specifically relevant for front-line managers to enhance engagement with gig workers.
- The study's practical recommendations, which centre around task delegation, equal treatment, effective communication, and team development as influential factors in gig workers' engagement, offer valuable contributions to the field.

Identification of critical challenges

- The research addresses critical challenges faced by front-line managers, including gig workers' reluctance to engage and the associated limitations.
- Through the identification of these challenges, the study provides valuable insights for developing strategies to overcome engagement hurdles.

In conclusion, this study enriches the existing knowledge base by employing a reflective approach, applying established theories to a new context, addressing literature gaps, connecting diverse strands, enhancing our understanding of the gig economy, emphasizing the importance of gig workers, and proposing effective utilization of leadership functions. Collectively, these contributions extend the theoretical foundation for employee engagement, particularly in light of the unique dynamics of the gig economy within the restaurant industry (Fest et al., 2021).

7.4.2 Empirical contributions

The empirical contributions of this research lie in its inclusion of various types of data analyses and sample sizes in the methodological approach. Furthermore, the study developed constructs regarding gig workers' engagement that have covered all the research objectives intending to respond to the study questions. The employee engagement concept has been a topic of interest for

both practitioners and researchers in the last couple of decades, making it an organisational first concern. On the other hand, the gig economy is growing drastically, as many businesses become part of it including gig workers (Meyerand Schneider, 2021). This has developed a gap in the academic literature where gig workers' engagement development is not covered sufficiently. The research addresses this gap by employing quantitative and qualitative data collection methods, allowing the management and the gig workers' point of view to be gathered to give a clear overview of gig workers' engagement in the restaurant sector.

Another empirical contribution of this research is studying the interference, impact and importance of the gig economy in the restaurant sector, which is one of the industries most impacted by the gig economy and one of the sectors of highest employee turnover, which has made gig workers a large part of this industry. This has allowed the researcher to be supported by the most valuable data regarding gig workers, including their engagement. Thus, this study is the first to cover gig workers' engagement in the restaurant industry.

Employee engagement was globally presented and studies as a monologue in prior literature, Yet this research focused on exploring the lived experience of gig workers and front-line management, finding out the management approaches employed to engage the gig worker while asking gig workers how the adopted approaches tend to help them engage.

This study has an empirical strength over the previous research demonstrated in its reliance on both the quantitative and the qualitative data gathered from front-line managers and gig workers in the restaurant industry. Their integration allows a more profound comprehension to be developed concerning the engagement of gig workers. Furthermore, the mixed method adopted in this research allowed an original empirical contribution to emerge.

Despite the large number of literatures covering gig workers' engagement and leadership functions, this study has taken the lead in studying the leadership functions as drivers that can be adopted by front-line management while enhancing their gig workers' functions in the UK restaurant sector. The research contributes empirically to relating the various gig workers' engagement drivers that can be categorised under the leadership functions to allow the front-line management to utilise their traits in enhancing gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector. A large number of sample sizes of this study has added an empirical strength to this study giving the findings more authority in representing gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector. credence

7.4.3 Practical contributions

The applied study mainly focuses on providing pure solutions to the highlighted issues. In this research, the issue is that the engagement of gig workers in the UK restaurant sector lacked empirical comprehension of the role of front-line management in using their position to enhance the engagement of gig workers. The research findings, including the qualitative and the quantitative, have answered the research questions. This part covers the practical contributions aiming to implement good practice in gig workers' engagement relating to the front-line management in terms of reliance on the leadership functions. These research findings provide further support to front-line management to maintain a healthy relationship with the in-house and the gig employees in order to create a positive environment where a spirit of teamwork can be efficiently developed between permanent and gig workers, which can enhance the gig workers' willingness to engage. This collaboration allows gig workers to feel valued and be treated fairly by the management, boosting their involvement and engagement in the restaurant operations. The study showed that collaboration among all employees in the work environment encouraged a positive response from the gig workers and enhanced their engagement in the business operations. While the literature has covered the constructs related to gig workers' engagement, the research findings are developing practical results on the most efficient drivers for gig workers' engagement that can be adopted efficiently by the front-line managers to clearly determine the most effective actions that can practically boost the engagement among gig workers. These research findings have distinguishing associations for restaurant managers and owners regarding the most valuable drivers that can boost gig workers' engagement. Treating the permanent and gig employees equally seems to evoke positive gig workers' attitudes and enhance their involvement in the business operations. While several practitioners showed no interest in setting separate procedures and policies for the gig workers, employing the same approaches for all employees seems to be the most efficient path for managers as no time or effort is wasted in developing a specific approach for the gig workers, assuming that there are already policies for the in-house employees in place which can be employed for the gig workers. These research findings suggest that the practitioners can rely on efficient communication to accomplish a high level of commitment among gig workers allowing them to share their expertise and ideas. Also, this helps build trust between the managers and the gig workers that can develop communication channels to enhance their satisfaction and engagement within the workplace. The management can use well-established communication between the gig workers and the management findings in various other sectors to engage the former.

The findings highlighted another leadership function that restaurant owners and managers can utilise to engage gig workers, despite the qualitative findings suggesting that motivation may differ between gig workers and permanent employees. However, the discussion of the findings suggested that the practitioner can utilise the same motivation approach for all the workforces. Also, most of the leadership functions are considered as tools that motivate gig workers, such as collaboration, communication, equal treatment with full-time employees; if they are efficiently adopted, they will make the gig workers valued and appreciated, which will enhance their involvement and engagement in workplace operations.

Regarding gig workers, their willingness to be engaged can develop a real challenge for the restaurant owners and managers. No matter how hard the front-line managers try, if the gig workers are unwilling to engage, it will not be accomplished – it should be added that due to the nature of gig work, based mainly on short-term employment, this limits the contact with workplace individuals. This study's findings encourage the management to maintain a positive relationship between all permanent employees and gig workers and with the management.

Restaurant owners and managers who are willing to implement engagement in their restaurants need to start engaging their in-house employees as they can be critical for the success of gig workers' engagement. Having the permanent employees engaged and successfully developing teamwork collaboration between the gig workers and full-time employees will help the management determine the gig workers' willingness to engage and enhance their engagement.

Defining the applied Study

The primary focus of this research is to offer tangible solutions to identified challenges within the United Kingdom restaurant industry. More precisely, the study aims to bridge a critical gap in understanding—the empirical comprehension of how leadership functions can be strategically utilized by frontline management to enhance gig workers' engagement. The research findings, a culmination of both quantitative and qualitative insights, effectively address the identified research questions, laying the groundwork for practical recommendations.

Understanding front-line management roles

This research serves as a practical model for frontline management, offering insights into the intricacies of engaging gig workers in the restaurant industry. Through a combination of questionnaires and interviews, the study provides a meticulous understanding of the roles played by front-line managers in fostering a positive work environment. The practical insights derived from the research can aid front-line management in addressing challenges associated with

managing a gig-based workforce. Additionally, it offers valuable guidance in navigating daily activities, responsibilities, and decision-making processes within the restaurant sector.

Defining leadership functions as drivers

This research makes a practical contribution by delineating specific leadership functions that can serve as drivers to engage gig workers in the UK restaurant industry. A combination of interviews and questionnaires was employed to identify actionable procedures for restaurant management. Emphasis is placed on leadership functions such as communication, motivation, collaboration, and equal treatment for both gig workers and in-house employees. These functions are deemed practical tools that can effectively make gig workers feel more valued, consequently enhancing their involvement and commitment to restaurant operations.

Understanding the challenges faced by the management

This research offers practical insights into exploring the challenges faced by management in engaging gig workers in the restaurant industry. Qualitative interviews were conducted to identify and categorize recurring challenges, and these challenges were then validated through questionnaire responses from gig workers. This approach provides management with a comprehensive understanding of the obstacles inherent in engaging gig workers in the UK restaurant sector. The challenges identified, ranging from limited interaction with gig workers to the short-term nature of their employment, lay the foundation for developing tailored solutions.

Development of an efficient approach:

Building on the identified frontline management roles, leadership functions, and challenges, this research contributes to the development of an effective approach for engaging gig workers in the UK restaurant industry. The practical approach advocates for treating gig workers and in-house employees equally. It proposes a unified strategy, leveraging existing policies for in-house workers, with the understanding that gig workers respond positively to a communicative and collaborative work environment, as well as when they are motivated. This comprehensive approach aims to enhance gig workers' willingness to engage by fostering a positive and inclusive workplace culture.

Collaboration and positive environment

The research underscores the significance of promoting collaboration among all staff members to cultivate a positive environment conducive to teamwork. Managers are provided with practical recommendations on fostering a culture where gig workers feel valued and treated equitably. The study offers actionable insights for managers aiming to enhance gig workers' engagement through

positive workplace connections and a collaborative approach, considering the distinctive dynamics of the gig economy.

Communication as a Key Driver

Effective communication emerges as a crucial catalyst for heightened dedication among gig workers. The practical aspect of the research lies in furnishing actionable communication strategies that empower gig workers to share expertise and ideas. Establishing trust through well-established communication channels is identified as one of the most significant contributors to enhancing employee satisfaction and engagement in the workplace.

Motivation and equal treatment

The study underscores the pivotal role of motivation as a leadership function in fostering engagement among gig workers. It also acknowledges potential disparities in motivation between gig and permanent employees, proposing a unified motivational approach for practitioners. Alongside equal treatment for full-time employees, the research identifies collaboration and communication as instrumental components of various leadership functions that form a practical toolkit for managers in engaging gig workers.

Overcoming challenges and building positive relationships

Despite the challenges associated with the readiness of gig workers' engagement, the study advocates for maintaining positive relationships among all employees, both permanent and gig workers. The practical suggestions highlight the significance of involving in-house employees as crucial contributors to the success of gig workers' engagement. Managers can overcome challenges and foster positive relationships by implementing these suggestions, promoting teamwork, collaboration, and overall engagement in restaurant operations. In essence, the applied research serves as a valuable resource, offering actionable strategies and a concrete roadmap for managers in the restaurant industry to effectively engage gig workers and establish a collaborative and positive work environment. Grounded in an empirical understanding of the gig economy dynamics, this comprehensive approach sets the stage for improved practices and increased engagement from gig workers in the restaurant sector.

7.5 Research limitations

Despite the fruitful insight in this study covering the gig economy, gig workers' engagement drivers and leadership functions, the research has applied various paths to enhance the trustworthiness of the findings and the study outcomes, such as reliability and the credibility of the

quantitative data, alongside extra analysis for the qualitative data. Some limitations may interfere with the efficient interpretation of some of the findings. This research has been focused on the restaurant sector in the United Kingdom. Hence, the findings can be argued to be unique to the United Kingdom and therefore may not be able to be generalised. In addition, since restaurant jobs require physical labour and are considered low-level jobs, this can trigger doubt about employing the findings in remote jobs and high-skilled workers. Despite this limitation, this research has been conducted in one of the countries where gig workers are taking a significant portion of the labour market and the restaurant sector is the most critical sector for gig workers' employment.

Adopting a mixed methodology throughout this study has significantly helped the data analysis and interpretation. However, there were some limitations that can be highlighted in the qualitative phase, where participants were interviewed privately, which increased the risk of non-self-disclosure through the selection of responses by the managers. The researcher limited that by not disclosing the questions beforehand, which enhanced the spontaneous responses ensuring a better reliability and reality representation. On the other hand, despite the researcher insisting on applying simple, understandable English, some participants had limited knowledge of the English language, which may have forced them to choose randomly. The researcher asked the participant to ask for any help needed during the research.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Questionnaire form

Examining the influence of the leadership functions on gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector

My name is Ahmed Kerdali. I am a doctorate candidate in Business Administration at the University of the West of Scotland. The core theme of this research is analysing the impact of the leadership and its core functions on driving employee engagement in the gig era in the United Kingdom restaurant sector. This questionnaire targets gig workers who are currently working or have worked in the restaurant industry. This questionnaire aims to gather data regarding the experience of gig workers with their leaders, full-time employees and the operations restaurants and how as gig workers they feel toward the effort of the front-line leaders and managers in enhancing their engagement.

Your answers will help the researcher to evaluate your experience as a gig worker with the leadership core functions in enhancing their engagement. The gathered data will be confidentially, privately and strictly utilised for the purpose of understanding and analysing this study only and not be disclosed under any circumstances.

Please choose the option that best describe your opinion. If none of the options are applicable to you, select the "Not applicable "option. Note that the questions have no wrong or right answer. Your opinion is crucial to this research to understand gig workers' engagement in the UK restaurant sector.

This questionnaire is designed to not take more than 10 minutes of your time to answer.

Section 1 – Introductory questions

1a. How long have been working as a gig worker? (Please select ONE box only)

- More than 5 years
- Less than 5 years
- After Covid-19

1b. What benefits made you choose the gig economy?

- Flexibility
- Pay
- Lack of life balance in permanent positions
- Other benefits in the gig economy

Other drawbacks in permanent positions

1d. How many hours do you work per week?

- 40 hours or over
- Less than 40 hours
- Around 30 hours
- Around 16 hours

Section 2 – Gig workers' engagement

2a. Front-line management and gig workers' engagement

Review the statements listed below and define the extent to which you agree based on the scores from 1 to 7, going from 1, very strongly disagree, to 7, very strongly agree; 4 represents neither agree nor disagree.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
You will be more engaged if you are satisfied with the front-line management strategies	<input type="radio"/>						
The collaboration approach from the front-line management influences your engagement	<input type="radio"/>						
The learning and development approach from the front-line management including training influences your engagement.	<input type="radio"/>						
The management of performance access adopted by the front-line management influences your engagement	<input type="radio"/>						
Being treated equally with the in-house workers by the management will enhance your engagement	<input type="radio"/>						
Integrations platforms can help increase your involvement which will eventually boost your engagement	<input type="radio"/>						
The two-way feedback with the front-line management will enhance your engagement	<input type="radio"/>						
A structured team approach with the full-time employees, if adopted by the front-line management, can help influence your engagement	<input type="radio"/>						
Efficient communication with the front-line management can boost your engagement.	<input type="radio"/>						

2b. Leadership functions and gig workers' engagement

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
The leadership functions can enhance gig workers' engagement if they are mastered by the management	<input type="radio"/>						
Being valued and involved can increase the willingness of engagement among the gig workers	<input type="radio"/>						
Being treated equally with the permanent employees enhances your engagement	<input type="radio"/>						
Motivation is a very important driver for gig workers' engagement	<input type="radio"/>						
Efficient communication is considered as a strong driver for engagement by the gig workers	<input type="radio"/>						
Teaming up with in-house employees boosts gig workers' engagement	<input type="radio"/>						
Delegating some of the tasks to the gig workers enhance their engagement	<input type="radio"/>						
Involving gig workers in the training and development schemes by the management will increase their engagement.	<input type="radio"/>						

2c. Challenges of gig workers engagement

Please define to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements based on scores from -1- to -7-? (1 = Very Strongly Disagree, 4 = Neither Disagree or Agree and 7 = Very Agree)
Which of the statement below you consider them challenges for the management to engage gig workers?

Section 3 – Gig economy

Going through the following statement. To what extent do you agree or disagree based on scores from 1 to 7 (1 = strongly disagree, 4 = neither agree nor disagree and 7 = very strongly agree).

3a. Gig economy in the restaurant sector

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
The gig economy has reshaped the labour market in the UK restaurant sector.	<input type="radio"/>						
The gig economy is winning over the traditional jobs in the UK restaurant sector.	<input type="radio"/>						
The pandemic has enhanced the gig economy popularisation in the UK restaurant sector.	<input type="radio"/>						
The gig economy has become a necessity for restaurants to sustain in the market	<input type="radio"/>						
The gig economy has become the main source of income for many employees	<input type="radio"/>						
Flexibility and life balance are the two major reasons behind the shift of the employee to the gig economy	<input type="radio"/>						
The gig economy has made the decision of leaving a job easy then ever for employees	<input type="radio"/>						

3b. Front-line management and gig workers in the UK restaurant sector.

Which of the following functions encourage gig workers to make a repeatable experience if they are performed efficiently by the front-line managers?

- Efficient communication
- Motivation
- Creating teamwork
- Delegating work

Does the front-line management approach affect the experience of gig workers and encourage them to be more engaged and repeat the experience?

- Yes
- No

Evaluating the following leadership functions, which of the functions do you think are the most valuable and important for gig workers and highly expected from the front-line management, from 1 to 7? (1 being extremely unimportant, 4 moderately important and 7 extremely important).

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Communication	<input type="radio"/>						
Motivation	<input type="radio"/>						
Training	<input type="radio"/>						
Valuing and involving	<input type="radio"/>						
Delegating tasks	<input type="radio"/>						
Teamworking with in-house workers	<input type="radio"/>						

3c. Hiring and food delivery apps and labour market in the restaurant sector

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
The food delivery apps have revolutionised the employment market in the UK restaurant sector	<input type="radio"/>						
The flexibility offered by the gig economy is attracting employees from all industries to the UK restaurant sector	<input type="radio"/>						
Food delivery and hiring apps are increasing the employees' turnover in the UK restaurant sector	<input type="radio"/>						
Gig workers consider previous workers' review and rating of employers before accepting the offer	<input type="radio"/>						
Hiring and food delivery apps offer better pay and flexibility than traditional job positions	<input type="radio"/>						
Employees are relying on hiring and food delivery apps as their main source of income	<input type="radio"/>						
Gig workers repeat the experience with the same restaurant if they are happy with the front-line management	<input type="radio"/>						

Section 4 – Engagement from gig workers' perspective

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the statement below referring to the extent of the engagement of gig workers, from '1' to '7'? (1 = Very strongly disagree, 4 = Neither disagree nor agree, and 7 = very strongly agree).

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Gig workers go the extra mile if they are engaged	<input type="radio"/>
Gig workers are always willing to be engaged	<input type="radio"/>
Gig workers perform better if they are engaged	<input type="radio"/>
Gig workers do not feel that are part of the restaurant	<input type="radio"/>
Gig workers always seek permanent positions with the restaurant they are gigging for	<input type="radio"/>
Gig workers do not care much about being valued and motivated by the management	<input type="radio"/>
Gig workers will be more productive if they are engaged	<input type="radio"/>

Section 5 – Gig workers' engagement development

5a. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statement suggesting action of the improvement of the gig worker engagement 1- to -7-? (1 = extremely very low, 4 = moderate and 7 = extremely very high).

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Communicating efficiently with gig workers will enhance their engagement	<input type="radio"/>
Discovering what motivate gig workers and use it can boost gig workers' engagement	<input type="radio"/>
Relationship between full time and gig workers can boost their engagement	<input type="radio"/>
Delegating some tasks to gig workers improve their engagement	<input type="radio"/>
Requesting the services of the gig workers all the time from the agency Or the app will enhance their engagement	<input type="radio"/>
Rating and valuing the gig workers performance will encourage them to repeat the experience and increase their engagement.	<input type="radio"/>

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Involving gig workers in business events could enhance their involvement and appreciation level and encourage their engagement

5b. How do you evaluate the level of engagement in improving the overall business operation -1- to -7-? (1 = does not impact it and 7 = majorly improve it)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

The more the gig workers are engaged, the better restaurant operations are performed

Engaging employees will enhance their involvement in all parts of operations and allow them to run more smoothly

Section 6 - Additional enquiries

Answering the following will give an overview regarding your input to this research.

15. What is your position?

16. How long you have been working as a gig worker?

17. Is the gig position your main source of income?

18. Do you use delivery apps or just agencies?

Appendix 2: Interview

My name is Ahmed Kerdali. I am a doctorate candidate in Business Administration at the University of the West of Scotland. The core theme of this research is analysing the impact of leadership and its core functions on driving employee engagement in the gig era in the United Kingdom restaurant sector. This interview aims to gather data regarding the experience of business front-line managers, leaders and owners with the gig economy and gig workers and how their core functions have influenced the engagement of gig workers. The gathered data will be confidentially,

privately and strictly utilised for the purpose of understanding and analysing this study only and not be disclosed under any circumstances.

Introductory Questions

-Do you use food delivery apps? If so, for how long have you used them? Did the sales increase after using them?

-Do you employ gig workers in your company? If so, for what tasks?

-Do you use traditional agencies and app-based agencies to hire gig workers?

-What made you hire and employ gig workers?

Main Questions

-How do you describe the role of front-line management toward the gig workers?

-What are the most important benefits of employing gig workers?

-Do you tend to work on creating teamwork between full-time and gig employees?

-Do you allow gig workers to be part of the decision-making process?

-Do you feel confident to delegate tasks to gig workers?

-Do you motivate gig workers? How important it is to you? What are the best approaches to motivating gig workers?

-How important is communication with the gig workers to you? How often you communicate with the gig workers?

-How important is employee engagement to you?

-How does employee engagement contribute toward the success of the restaurant?

-To what extent do you consider the importance of your roles toward engaging gig workers?

-Do you think that gig workers' engagement affects the way you manage and lead the restaurant?

And do you ever think of adjusting your approach to efficiently engage employees?

- In your opinion, what are the core leadership functions that can enhance gig workers' engagement?

-Do you think that leadership functions can influence gig workers' engagement?

-How important are the motivation and the communication to you in boosting the gig workers engagement?

-Do you think delegating jobs and training giggers enhance gig workers' engagement?

-Do you allow gig workers to be part of the decision-making process?

- To what extent do you believe that the hiring and food delivery apps are influencing gig workers' engagement?
- How do the food delivery and hiring apps increase the employees' turnover in the UK restaurant sector?
- Do you think that the easiness of securing jobs offered by the apps is challenging the stability of the labour market in the UK restaurant sector?
- The model of employment developed by the hiring and food delivery apps is influencing gig workers' engagement?
- From your experience how likely are gig workers willing to engage?
- How important is the engagement to the gig workers?
- Are engaged gig workers more productive and easier to manage?
- How will the gig workers benefit from their engagement?
- From your experience how likely are gig workers willing to engage?
- How important is the engagement to the gig workers?
- Are engaged gig workers more productive and easier to manage?
- How will the gig workers benefit from their engagement?
- How will the business benefit from gig workers' engagement?
- For what functions do you rely on engaging gig workers?
- What are the functions that show more acceptance from the gig workers?
- What are the functions that show efficiency in engaging gig workers?

Final Questions

- Can leadership functions enhance gig workers' engagement?
- Do you think that leadership functions can influence gig workers' engagement?
- Do you think that gig workers' engagement affects the way you manage and lead the restaurant?
- What are the challenges that can be faced by front-line managers while engaging gig workers?
- How can gig workers' engagement be improved in the UK restaurant sector?

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Question 1 (Introductory question): To what extent has the gig economy reshaped the labour market in the UK restaurant sector? 	
<p><u>Gig economy in the restaurant sector</u></p> <p>Definition: The gig economy has developed new era in the restaurant industry where it has reshaped every single part of the industry including the labor market that has been affected by the delivery and hiring agencies apps which has directly and indirectly impacted the leadership and the engagement of employees</p>	
<p>Questions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Do you use food delivery Apps? For How long? Did the sales increase after using it? -Do you employ gig workers in your company? For what tasks? -Do you use traditional agencies and app-based agencies to hire gig workers? -What made you hire and employ gig workers?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research question 2 (Main questions): Which core responsibilities are employed by the frontline management within the restaurant sector? 	
<p><u>Front line management and gig workers in the UK restaurant sector.</u></p> <p>The leadership and managerial approaches have been majorly impacted by the emerge of the gig economy and the gig workers in the UK restaurant sector due the nature of the employees that require better understanding of their needs and motives to develop the most efficient approach by the front-line management</p>	
<p>Questions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do you describe the role of front-line management toward the gig workers? - What are the most important benefits of employing gig workers? - Do you tend to work on creating teamwork between full-time and gig employees? - Do you allow gig workers to be part of the decision-making process? - Do you feel confident to delegate tasks to gig workers? - Do you motivate gig workers? How important it is to you? What are the best approaches to motivating gig workers? - How important is communication with gig worker is to you? How often you communicate with the gig workers?
<p><u>Front line management and gig workers engagement</u></p> <p>Definition: front line management can refer to the leaders and managers that have played role in engaging gig workers through performing their managerial roles in the UK restaurant sector</p>	
<p>Questions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -How important is the employee engagement to you? -How the employee engagement contributes toward the success of the restaurant? -To what extent you consider the importance of your roles toward engaging gig workers? - Do you think that gig workers engagement affects the way you manage and lead the restaurant? And do ever think of adjusting your approach to efficiently engage employees?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research question 3 (Main questions): What specific leadership functions serve as critical drivers for employee engagement? 	
<p><u>leadership functions and gig workers engagement</u></p> <p>Definition: leadership functions are the functions that leadership conduct while managing the employees, there are a variety of drivers that enhance the gig workers engagement which a long list of them come under the functions conducted by leaders and managers in the UK restaurant sector.</p>	

Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -What are in your opinion the core leadership functions that can enhance the gig workers engagement? -Do you think that leadership functions can influence the gig workers engagement? -How important are the motivation and the communication to you in boosting the gig workers engagement? -Do you think delegating jobs and training giggers enhance the gig workers engagement? -Do you allow gig workers to be part of the decision-making process?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Question 4 (Main question): What challenges do management encounter when engaging gig workers in the UK restaurant sector? 	
<p><u>Challenges of gig workers engagement</u></p>	
<p>Definition: engaging a gig worker comes with a variety of challenges due to the nature of the gig workers as well as the employment concept that are making it even more challengeable to engage them.</p>	
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent the gig workers are willing to engage? - What are the challenges that can be faced by front line managers while engaging gig workers? - Do you find it hard to treat the gig workers equally with Full time employees? - can you perform your functions efficiently due to the nature of gig workers? And do you describe the
<p><u>Hiring and food delivery apps and labour market in the restaurant sector</u></p>	
<p>Definition: The emerge of the food delivery apps and hiring agencies has developed new employment concept where employees are a single click from their next position that has created challenges for the management to keep their employees and engage them</p>	
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -To what extent you believe that the hiring and food delivery apps are influencing the gig workers engagement? -How the food delivery and hiring apps are increasing the employees' turnover in the UK restaurant sector? -Do you think that the easiness of securing jobs offered by the apps are challenging stability of the labour market in the UK restaurant sector? -The module of employment developed by the hiring and food delivery apps are influencing the gig workers engagement?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Question 5 (Main question): How can frontline management leverage their core functions to enhance gig workers' engagement and efficiently address their challenges? 	
<p><u>The engagement from gig workers perspective</u></p>	
<p>Definition: The gig workers are mostly individual that have chosen the flexibility over the traditional secure position, this could show that gig workers are more into getting the job done and may not be into engagement. This has to be understood by the management in order to achieve the absolute engagement of the gig workers</p>	
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From your experience how likely are gig workers willing to engage? - How important is the engagement to the gig workers? - Are engaged gig workers more productive and easier to manage? - How will the gig workers benefit from their engagement?
<p><u>The gig workers engagement development</u></p>	
<p>Definition: The management needs to determine the drivers of the gig workers engagement while efficiently using their functions to drive the gig workers engagement.</p>	
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How will the business benefit from the gig workers engagement? - what functions do you rely on engaging gig workers?

	<p>- what are the functions that shows more acceptance from the gig workers?</p> <p>-what are the functions that show efficiency in engaging gig workers?</p>
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Appendix 4: The domain and items of constructs in the existing literature

Construct	Measurement items	Major references
Front line management and gig workers engagement		
	You will be more engaged if you are satisfied with the front-line management strategies	Savarimuthu and Rachel (2017); Agarwal and Gupta (2018); Liu et al. (2020); Sharma et al. (2016); EY (2020); Morrison-Smith and Ruiz (2020).
	The collaboration approach from the front-line management influences your engagement	Paulas and Kenworthy (2019); Elikwu (2019); Ruggieri et al. (2016); Anderson and Sanga (2019); Brown and Poortman (2018).
	The learning and development approach from the front-line management including training influence your engagement.	Lives (2017); McGuinness and Ortiz(2015); Wilkie (2013); Fiscor (2018); Kulkarni (2019); Tucker (2017).
	The management of performance access opted by the front-line management influence your engagement	Sarangal et al.(2020); Majid et al.(2019) ; Mueller-Hanson and Pulakos (2018) ; Myung et al.(2020); Meijerink and Keegan (2019).
	Being treated equally with the in-house workers by the management will enhance your engagement	Biermannand Kalfagianni (2020); Osabiya(2015); Lee and Raschke(2016); Myung et al.(2020).
	Integrations platforms can help increasing your involvement which will eventually boost your engagement	Suciu et al.(2019); Williams et al.(2021) ; Gross et al.(2018) ; Meyerand Schneider(2021); Sanford(2017).
	The two-way feedback with the front-line management will enhance your engagement.	Meijerink and Keegan (2019); Myung et al.(2020); Majid et al (2019); Sarangal

<p>Structured team approach with the full-time employees if opted by the front-line management can help influence your engagement</p>	<p>et al.(2020);Mueller-Hanson and Pulakos(2018).</p> <p>Guchait et al.(2016); Senani (2016); Sulistiyaniand Ferdinand(2018) ; Vogler et al.(2018) ; Vanikjand Zendeli(2019) ; Ab-Latif et al.(2020).</p>
<p>The efficient communication with the front-line management can boost your engagement.</p>	<p>Osborne and Hammoud (2017); Kang and Sung (2017); Adiarani(2019); Decuypere and Schaufeli(2020); Soares and Mosquera(2019); Moletsane et al.(2019).</p>

leadership functions and gig workers engagement

<p>The leadership functions can enhance the gig workers engagement if they are mastered by the management.</p>	<p>Gupta et al.(2017); Smith(2021); Breevaart et al.(2016) ; Baoand Zhao(2018); Carasco et al.(2015) ; Prochazka et al.(2017).</p>
<p>Being valued and involved can increase the willingness of engagement among the gig workers</p>	<p>Iddagodaand Opatha (2017);Ruck et al.(2017); Mmako and Schultz (2016);Chandani et al.(2016); Al Senani (2016); Iqbal et al.(2017).</p>
<p>Bering treated equally with the permanent employees enhance your engagement</p>	<p>Lee and Raschke(2016); Osabiya(2015);Myung et al.(2020); Biermannand Kalfagianni (2020)</p>
<p>Motivation is a very important driver for the gig workers engagement</p>	<p>Ryan and Deci (2020); Jabagi et al.(2019); Pereira et al.(2022) ; Guay et al.(2020) ; Butschek et al.(2022) ; Prabowo et al.(2019).</p>
<p>The efficient communication is considered as a strong driver for the engagement by the gig workers</p>	<p>Mone and London(2018); Ruck et al.(2017); Iqbal et al.(2017) ;Megha(2016);</p>

<p>Teaming up with the in-house employees boost the gig workers engagement</p>	<p>Bailey et al.(2017); Adiarani(2019).</p> <p>Hanners, and Malvini (2021);Paulas and Kenworthy (2019); Guchait et al. (2016); Ab-Latif et al. (2020) ;Vogler et al. (2018) .</p>
<p>Delegating some of the tasks to the gig workers enhance their engagement</p>	<p>Jha & Kumar (2016); Andres et al. (2015); Robbins & Judge (2015) ; Hidayat et al.(2021); Al Maktoum (2015).</p>
<p>Involving gig workers in the training and development schemes by the management will increase their engagement.</p>	<p>Ryan and Deci(2020); Gupta (2015); Jha & Kumar (2016); Mishra & Mohanty (2016); Simha& Vardhan (2015).</p>
<p>Challenges of gig workers engagement</p>	
<p>The nature of the gig workers employment system prevents Them to be part of the team.</p>	<p>Dey et al.(2022); Kuhn et al.(2021) ; Royand Shrivastava(2020) ; Allam (2017) ; Lemon and Palenchar(2018) ; Rofcanin et al.(2017).</p>
<p>Effective communication cannot be achieved with gig workers.</p>	<p>Simonsson(2018); Moletsane et al.(2019); Karanges et al.(2015) ; Okpuand Kpakol(2018) ; Rofcanin et al.(2017) ; Kulachai et al.(2018).</p>
<p>Gig workers motivations are different from full time Employees which are harder to be defined by the management Due to the short term of gig employment.</p>	<p>Suharno and Despinur(2017); Sanford (2017); Abah and Nwokwu(2016); Davis et al.(2020); Anthony-McMann et al.(2017).</p>
<p>Gig workers does not care much about the business value and reputation.</p>	<p>Myung et al.(2020); Stallkampand Schotter(2021); Suharno and Despinur(2017).</p>

The management does not waste time briefing and training gig workers as they expect them to be ready to work	Collier et al.(2017); Shin et al (2021) ; Williams et al. (2021) ; Umar et al (2021).
It is hard for management to treat the gig workers equally with Full time employees	Balaram et al.(2017); Chen et al.(2019); Karlsson and Wranne(2019) ; Schweltnus et al (2019) ; Broughton et al.(2018).
The management are finding it hard to keep in house employees from moving to the gig era	Shin et al.(2021); Xiong and Wen(2020); Chaand Seo(2020);Altenried(2021).
The lack of comprehension of the engagement from the gig workers my prevent them from being fully engaged.	Huo et al.(2020); Rockmann et al.(2018); Kuhn et al.(2021).
Not having a clear approach from the management to help engaging you may affect your willingness to the engagement	Jha and Kumar (2016); Andres et al.(2015); Saks (2017); Robbins and Judge (2015) ;Anitha (2014); Al Maktoum (2015).
The hiring and food delivery apps are tempting traditional employees to move to gig model and increase restaurant turnover.	Chaand Seo(2020); Laitinen(2021); Altenried (2021); Chaand Seo(2020); Gandhi et al.(2018).

Gig economy in the restaurant sector

The gig economy has reshaped the labour market in the UK restaurant sector.	Hyersand Kovacova(2018); Shin et al (2021); Broderick (2018); (Lobel, 2017); Vallasand Schor(2020); Watson et al.(2021).
The gig economy is winning over the traditional jobs in the UK restaurant sector.	Shin et al (2021);Hyersand Kovacova(2018); Mahato et al.(2021).
The pandemic has enhanced the gig economy popularisation in the UK restaurant sector.	Mahato et al.(2021); Jooand Shawl(2021); Nkengasong and Mankoula(2020); Jooand Shawl (2021); Umar et al (2021); Healy et al. (2017); Stewart and Stanford(2017).

The gig economy has become a necessity for restaurants to sustain in the market.	Ostoj(2019); Chen et al (2019); Zaman(2019) ; Mulcahy (2016) .
The gig economy has become the main source of income for many employees.	Croxson et al.(2021) ;Grahamand Anwar(2019) ; Chen et al.(2019) ; van der Burg et al.(2019) ; Donovan et al. (2016).
The flexibility and life balance are the two major reasons behind the shift of the employee to the gig economy.	Vyas(2021);Waring(2018); Wilson(2017); Kitching et al.(2019) ;van der Burg et al.(2019); Ostoj(2019); Ly (2020);
The gig economy has made the decision of leaving a job easy then ever for employees	Wilson(2017); Waring (2018); MacDonaldand Giazitzoglu(2019); Vyas(2021); Donovan et al. (2016); Schiekand Gideon (2018).
The gig economy has reshaped the labour market in the UK restaurant sector.	Vallasand Schor(2020); Watson et al.(2021); Broderick (2018); (Lobel, 2017); Hyersand Kovacova(2018); Shin et al (2021).

Front line management and gig workers in the UK restaurant sector.

Important functions to gig workers	
Communication	Guay et al (2020); Duggan et al.(2020); Li(2020) ; Kaineand Josserand (2019) ; Smith(2021); Carasco et al.(2015).
Motivation	Werdhiastutie et al.(2020); Suharno and Despinur (2017); Jabagi et al.(2019) ; Anthony-McMann et al (2017) ; Ye(2018) ; Pereira et al (2022).

Training	McGuinness and Ortiz(2015); Ryan and Deci(2020); Gupta (2015); Jha and Kumar (2016); Mishra & Mohanty (2016) .
Valuing and involving	Larteyand Randall(2021); Victor and Hoole(2017); Jha & Kumar (2016); Andres et al. (2015); Park et al.(2020) ; Rothmann(2016).
Delegating tasks	Al Maktoum (2015); Robbins & Judge (2015) ; Jha & Kumar (2016); Hidayat et al.(2021); Andres et al. (2015).

Hiring and food delivery apps in the restaurant sector

The food delivery apps have revolutionised the employment market in the UK restaurant sector	Sibanda et al.(2021); Suciu et al.(2019) ; Williams et al.(2021).
The flexibility offered by the gig economy is attracting employees from all industries to the UK restaurant sector.	Anwar and Graham(2021); Horney(2016); Vallasand Schor(2020); Watson et al.(2021); Lehdonvirta (2018).
The food delivery and hiring apps are increasing the employees' turnover in the UK restaurant sector	EY(2020); Gross et al, 2018) ;Kaineand Josserand(2019); Sibanda et al.(2021).
Gig workers consider the previous workers review and rating of employers before accepting the offer.	Duggan et al.(2021); EY (2020); Myung et al.(2020) ; Meijerink and Keegan(2019).
Hiring and food delivery apps offer better pay and flexibility than the traditional job positions.	Bryant(2020); Sibanda et al.(2021); Wu et al.(2019).
Employees are relying on the hiring apps and food delivery apps as their main a source of income	EY(2020); Gross et al, 2018) ;Kaineand Josserand(2019); Sibanda et al.(2021); Suciu et al.(2019) .
Gig workers repeat the experience with the same restaurant if they are happy with the front-line management.	EY(2020);Huo et al.(2020); Engen and

<p>The food delivery apps have revolutionised the employment market in the UK restaurant sector</p>	<p>Magnusson(2015); Vogler et al.(2018)</p> <p>Goods et al.(2019); Laitinen(2021) ;Chetan et al.(2019) ; Chaand Seo(2020).</p>
<p>The flexibility offered by the gig economy is attracting employees from all industries to the UK restaurant sector.</p>	<p>Horney(2016); Schor(2020); Anwar and Graham(2021); Vallasand Watson et al.(2021); Lehdonvirta (2018).</p>
<p>The food delivery and hiring apps are increasing the employees' turnover in the UK restaurant sector</p>	<p>Hyersand Kovacova(2018); Altenried(2021); Chaand Seo(2020); Laitinen(2021).</p>
<p>The engagement from gig workers perspective</p>	
<p>Gig workers go the extra mile if they are engaged</p>	<p>Aslam et al. (2018); Abah and Nwokwu(2016); Rofcanin et al.(2017).</p>
<p>Gig workers are always willing to be engaged</p>	<p>Chandani et al.(2016); Mmako and Schultz (2016); Iddagodaand Opatha (2017); Al Senani (2016); Ruck et al.(2017); Iqbal et al.(2017).</p>
<p>Gig workers perform better if they are engaged</p>	<p>Bhuvanaiah and Raya (2015); Gupta (2015);Davis et al (2020); Mousa and Chaouali(2022); Rucket al.(2017); Rothmann(2016)</p>
<p>Gig workers does not feel that are part of the restaurant.</p>	<p>McManus and Mosca(2015); Park et al(2020); Rothmann(2016); Chandani et al.(2016)</p>
<p>Gig workers always seek permanent position with the restaurant Gigging for Gig workers does not care much about being valued and motivated by</p>	<p>Jabagi et al.(2019); Shambi(2021); Kuhn et al.(2021) ; Latta and Fait(2016).</p>
<p>Gig workers does not care much about being valued and motivated by the management</p>	<p>Larteyand Randall(2021); Al Maktoum (2015); Rogers(2018); Larteyand Randall(2021).</p>
<p>The gig workers will be more productive if they are engaged</p>	<p>Mousa and Chaouali(2022); Davis et al (2020);</p>

	Bhuvanaiah and Raya (2015); Gupta (2015); Rothmann(2016);Rucket al.(2017).
Gig workers engagement development	
Communicating efficiently with gig workers will enhance their engagement	Karanges et al.(2015); Kulachai et al.(2018) ; Lemon and Palenchar(2018) ; McManus and Mosca (2015).
Discovering what motivate gig workers and use it can boost the gig workers engagement	Hailat et al. (2019); Chung (2012); Ryan and Deci (2020); Sanford(2017); Suharno and Despinur(2017).
Relationship between full time and gig workers can boost their engagement	Okpuand Kpakol(2018); Broughton et al.(2018); Anitha (2014); Al Maktoum (2015).
Delegating some tasks to gig workers improve their engagement	Hidayat et al.(2021); Jha and Kumar (2016); Andres et al. (2015); Robbins and Judge (2015).
Requesting the services of the gig workers all the time from the agency or the app will enhance their engagement	Victor and Hoole(2017); Nunkoo(2016); waring (2018); Davis et al.(2020).
Rating and valuing the gig workers performance will encourage them to repeat the experience and increase their engagement.	Meijerink and Keegan(2019); Iqbal et al. (2017); Al Mehrzi and Singh(2016); Sexton et al.(2018).
Involving the gig workers in the business events could enhance their involvement and appreciation level and encourage their engagement	Bhuvanaiah and Raya (2015); Gupta (2015);Mishra et al.(2014); Truss et al. (2013);Gopinath(2020).
The more the gig workers are engaged the better restaurant operations are performed	Xiong and Wen(2020);Dazzi (2019); Davis et al.(2020); Abah and Nwokwu(2016);
Engaging employees will enhance their involvement in all part of operations and allow them to run more smoothly	Victor and Hoole (2017); Nimri et al.(2015); Dey et

Source: Developed for the current study by the researcher

Appendix 5: Univariate variables

Tests of Normality

	Std.			Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Mean	n	Missin g	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statisti c	df	Sig.
FLMGE_1	5.36	1.617	.0	.259	336	.000	.824	336	.000
FLMGE_2	5.38	1.625	.0	.260	336	.000	.811	336	.000
FLMGE_3	5.23	1.593	.0	.243	336	.000	.831	336	.000
FLMGE_4	5.53	1.625	.0	.222	336	.000	.804	336	.000
FLMGE_5	5.37	1.578	.0	.248	336	.000	.831	336	.000
FLMGE_6	5.50	1.667	.0	.222	336	.000	.804	336	.000
FLMGE_7	5.34	1.667	.0	.251	336	.000	.847	336	.000
FLMGE_8	5.42	1.541	.0	.246	336	.000	.830	336	.000
FLMGE_9	5.35	1.607	.0	.260	336	.000	.825	336	.000
LFGE_1	5.41	1.674	.0	.251	336	.000	.810	336	.000
LFGE_2	5.48	1.622	.0	.236	336	.000	.811	336	.000
LFGE_3	5.53	1.665	.0	.226	336	.000	.797	336	.000
LFGE_4	5.43	1.633	.0	.256	336	.000	.806	336	.000
LFGE_5	5.51	1.699	.0	.223	336	.000	.796	336	.000
LFGE_6	5.50	1.594	.0	.224	336	.000	.818	336	.000
LFGE_7	5.48	1.655	.0	.236	336	.000	.805	336	.000
LFGE_8	5.53	1.674	.0	.216	336	.000	.796	336	.000
CGWE_1	5.51	1.484	.0	.233	336	.000	.823	336	.000
CGWE_2	5.52	1.537	.0	.233	336	.000	.816	336	.000
CGWE_3	5.41	1.637	.0	.269	336	.000	.799	336	.000
CGWE_4	5.55	1.558	.0	.228	336	.000	.810	336	.000
CGWE_5	5.44	1.588	.0	.261	336	.000	.807	336	.000
CGWE_6	5.50	1.540	.0	.239	336	.000	.817	336	.000
CGWE_7	5.47	1.516	.0	.248	336	.000	.823	336	.000
CGWE_8	5.49	1.568	.0	.248	336	.000	.811	336	.000
CGWE_9	5.60	1.483	.0	.213	336	.000	.819	336	.000
CGWE_10	5.52	1.532	.0	.236	336	.000	.816	336	.000
GIRS_1	5.49	1.397	.0	.236	336	.000	.837	336	.000
GIRS_3	5.50	1.564	.0	.253	336	.000	.797	336	.000
GIRS_4	5.5	1.428	.0	.241	336	.000	.831	336	.000
GIRS_5	5.49	1.461	.0	.242	336	.000	.823	336	.000
GIRS_6	5.46	1.481	.0	.255	336	.000	.820	336	.000
GIRS_7	5.59	1.540	.0	.228	336	.000	.797	336	.000

GIRS_8	5.52	1.377	.0	.228	336	.000	.843	336	.000
FLMG_1	5.48	1.472	.0	.239	336	.000	.830	336	.000
FLMG_2	5.44	1.436	.0	.245	336	.000	.841	336	.000
FLMG_3	5.58	1.480	.0	.219	336	.000	.812	336	.000
FLMG_4	5.60	1.486	.0	.215	336	.000	.816	336	.000
FLMG_5	5.50	1.466	.0	.233	336	.000	.829	336	.000
FLMG_6	5.54	1.491	.0	.230	336	.000	.816	336	.000
HFALM_1	5.32	1.600	.0	.267	336	.000	.827	336	.000
HFALM_2	5.482	1.498	.0	.222	336	.000	.838	336	.000
HFALM_3	5.464	1.542	.0	.233	336	.000	.829	336	.000
HFALM_4	5.44	1.604	.0	.239	336	.000	.821	336	.000
HFALM_5	5.44	1.544	.0	.238	336	.000	.832	336	.000
HFALM_6	5.59	1.550	.0	.202	336	.000	.814	336	.000
HFALM_7	5.45	1.501	.0	.229	336	.000	.827	336	.000
EGWP_1	5.37	1.512	.0	.253	336	.000	.841	336	.000
EGWP_2	5.34	1.518	.0	.263	336	.000	.835	336	.000
EGWP_3	5.52	1.558	.0	.223	336	.000	.816	336	.000
EGWP_4	5.50	1.486	.0	.234	336	.000	.826	336	.000
EGWP_5	5.62	1.553	.0	.226	336	.000	.801	336	.000
EGWP_6	5.42	1.537	.0	.242	336	.000	.832	336	.000
EGWP_7	5.50	1.551	.0	.226	336	.000	.822	336	.000
GED_1	5.37	1.597	.0	.261	336	.000	.823	336	.000
GED_2	5.44	1.538	.0	.239	336	.000	.831	336	.000
GED_3	5.44	1.647	.0	.244	336	.000	.811	336	.000
GED_4	5.41	1.690	.0	.255	336	.000	.802	336	.000
GED_5	5.42	1.541	.0	.245	336	.000	.827	336	.000
GED_6	5.56	1.512	.0	.211	336	.000	.822	336	.000
GED_7	5.45	1.569	.0	.238	336	.000	.827	336	.000
GED_8	5.36	1.528	.0	.259	336	.000	.832	336	.000
GED_9	5.42	1.547	.0	.242	336	.000	.832	336	.000

Source: Analysis of survey data

Appendix 6: Multivariate normality

Items	Mean	SD	Skewness		Kurtosis	
			Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Front line management and gig workers engagement						
FLMGE_1	5.36	1.617	-1.118	.133	.719	.265
FLMGE_2	5.38	1.625	-1.25	.133	.917	.265
FLMGE_3	5.23	1.593	-1.064	.133	.647	.265
FLMGE_4	5.53	1.625	-1.261	.133	.948	.265
FLMGE_5	5.37	1.578	-1.157	.133	.867	.265

FLMGE_6	5.50	1.667	-1.239	.133	.818	.265
FLMGE_7	5.34	1.667	-.920	.133	.426	.265
FLMGE_8	5.42	1.541	-1.160	.133	.937	.265
FLMGE_9	5.35	1.607	-1.055	.133	.591	.265
Leadership functions and gig workers engagement						
LFGE_1	5.41	1.674	-1.154	.133	.707	.265
LFGE_2	5.48	1.622	-1.170	.133	.800	.265
LFGE_3	5.53	1.665	-1.209	.133	.761	.265
LFGE_4	5.43	1.633	-1.116	.133	.696	.265
LFGE_5	5.51	1.699	-1.249	.133	.808	.265
LFGE_6	5.50	1.594	-1.120	.133	.712	.265
LFGE_7	5.48	1.655	-1.175	.133	.764	.265
LFGE_8	5.53	1.674	-1.284	.133	.929	.265
Challenges of the workers engagement						
CGWE_1	5.51	1.484	-0.924	.133	.46	.265
CGWE_2	5.52	1.537	-1.081	.133	.742	.265
CGWE_3	5.41	1.637	-1.169	.133	.872	.265
CGWE_4	5.55	1.558	-1.198	.133	.961	.265
CGWE_5	5.44	1.588	-1.152	.133	1.005	.265
CGWE_6	5.50	1.540	-1.054	.133	.572	.265
CGWE_7	5.47	1.516	-1.088	.133	.859	.265
CGWE_8	5.49	1.568	-1.164	.133	.882	.265
CGWE_9	5.60	1.483	-1.059	.133	.647	.265
CGWE_10	5.52	1.532	-1.125	.133	.771	.265
Gig workers in the restaurant sector						
GIRS_1	5.49	1.397	-.876	.133	.491	.265
GIRS_2	5.50	1.564	-1.374	.133	1.557	.265
GIRS_3	5.5	1.428	-1.075	.133	.898	.265
GIRS_4	5.49	1.461	-.963	.133	.649	.265
GIRS_6	5.46	1.481	-1.076	.133	.855	.265
GIRS_7	5.59	1.540	-1.371	.133	1.57	.265
GIRS_8	5.52	1.377	-.953	.133	.641	.265
Front line management and gig workers						
FLMG_1	5.48	1.472	-1.154	.133	1.047	.265
FLMG_2	5.44	1.436	-1.011	.133	.715	.265
FLMG_3	5.58	1.480	-1.274	.133	1.176	.265
FLMG_4	5.60	1.486	-1.207	.133	1.033	.265
FLMG_5	5.50	1.466	-1.161	.133	1.014	.265
FLMG_6	5.54	1.491	-1.289	.133	1.369	.265
Hiring and food delivery apps and the labour market						
HFALM_1	5.32	1.600	-1.134	.133	.760	.265
HFALM_2	5.482	1.498	-1.021	.133	.419	.265
HFALM_3	5.464	1.542	-1.078	.133	.513	.265
HFALM_4	5.44	1.604	-1.139	.133	.619	.265
HFALM_5	5.44	1.544	-1.092	.133	.669	.265
HFALM_6	5.59	1.550	-1.117	.133	.507	.265

HFALM_7_	5.45	1.501	-1.127	.133	.560	.265
Engagement from gig workers perspectives						
EGWP_1	5.37	1.512	-.977	.133	.594	.265
EGWP_2	5.34	1.518	-1.098	.133	.782	.265
EGWP_3	5.52	1.558	-1.231	.133	.930	.265
EGWP_4	5.50	1.486	-1.165	.133	.696	.265
EGWP_5	5.62	1.553	-1.251	.133	.819	.265
EGWP_6	5.42	1.537	-1.105	.133	.679	.265
EGWP_7	5.50	1.551	-1.173	.133	.794	.265
Gig workers engagement development						
GED_1	5.37	1.597	-1.12	.133	.831	.265
GED_2	5.44	1.538	-1.005	.133	.474	.265
GED_3	5.44	1.647	-1.166	.133	.773	.265
GED_4	5.41	1.690	-1.245	.133	.852	.265
GED_5	5.42	1.541	-1.008	.133	.355	.265
GED_6	5.56	1.512	-1.099	.133	.555	.265
GED_7	5.45	1.569	-1.079	.133	.587	.265
GED_8	5.36	1.528	-1.007	.133	.461	.265
GED_9	5.42	1.547	-.993	.133	.384	.265

Source: Analysis of survey data

Appendix7 : Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
FLMGE_1	.646							
FLMGE_2	.638							
FLMGE_3	.604							
FLMGE_4	.649							
FLMGE_5	.661							
FLMGE_7	.635							
FLMGE_6	.644							
FLMGE_8	.640							
FLMGE_9	.656							
LFGE_1				.659				
LFGE_2				.625				
LFGE_3			.304	.625				
LFGE_4				.623				
LFGE_5				.577				
LFGE_6				.610				
LFGE_7				.646				
LFGE_8				.666				
CGWE_1			.606					

CGWE_2			.588					
CGWE_3			.617					
CGWE_4			.588					
CGWE_5			.576					
CGWE_6			.621					
CGWE_7			.593					
CGWE_8	.318	.301	.558					
CGWE_9			.586					
CGWE_10			.635					
GIRS_1						.653		
GIRS_2						.586		
GIRS_3						.596		
GIRS_4		.345				.570		
GIRS_5						.621		
GIRS_6						.627		
GIRS_7			.321			.552		
FLMG_1					.690			
FLMG_2					.677			
FLMG_3					.598			
FLMG_4	.325				.571			
FLMG_5					.700			
FLMG_6					.674			
HFALM_1				.307			.640	
HFALM_2							.536	
HFALM_3							.578	
HFALM_4		.323					.519	
HFALM_5	.313						.656	
HFALM_6							.579	
HFALM_7		.315					.564	
EGWP_1				.319				.583
EGWP_2							.315	.561
EGWP_3		.357		.318				.505
EGWP_4								.517
EGWP_5								.562
EGWP_6	.311		.303					.581
EGWP_7								.591
GED_1		.647						
GED_2	.338	.601						
GED_3		.623						
GED_4		.611						

GED_5		.624						
GED_6		.604						
GED_7		.669						
GED_8		.593						
GED_9		.670						

Source: Analysis of survey data

Appendix 7: Normal probability Q-Q plots

